

**The International Rice Research Institute
Annual Report for 1971**

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The International Rice Research Institute Annual Report for 1971

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*Left during year.

About this report

This is the tenth annual report to be published by the International Rice Research Institute since it was founded in 1960 by The Rockefeller Foundation and the Ford Foundation in cooperation with the Republic of the Philippines.

A limited subject index has been added to this year's report to help the reader locate common subjects discussed in several sections.

The thumb index on the back cover provides quick access to any research section. To use it, bend the book in half and follow the margin index to the page with the black edge marker.

Data in the report are given in metric units, e.g., "t/ha" means metric tons per hectare. Unless otherwise stated, *control* means untreated control, *grain yield* is calculated as rough rice at 14 percent moisture, and *protein content* is calculated as a percentage of brown rice at 14 percent moisture. A single asterisk (*) means significant at the 5 percent level, a double asterisk (**) means significant at the 1 percent level.

The report frequently mentions three fundamental types of rice culture. *Upland* culture means rice grown without irrigation in fields without bunds. *Rainfed paddy* culture means rice grown without irrigation but in fields that are banded to impound rainfall. *Irrigated* or *flooded* culture means rice grown with irrigation in banded fields.

Director's introduction

The 1971 crop year was marked by heavier than normal rainfall in March and again in November and December. Furthermore rice in the Philippines suffered the most serious outbreak of the tungro virus disease in history. The combination of rainy weather and disease incidence reduced crop yields on the Institute experimental farm. It provided useful information about varietal resistance to adverse environmental conditions however.

On May 24, 1971 the Institute announced the naming of IR24. This is the fifth variety to be named by the Institute. It is a selection from a cross between IR8 and one of the progeny of the cross [(Century Patna 231 x SLO 17) x Sigadis]. Its previous designation was IR661-1-140-3-117. The advantages of this variety are its resistance to the green leafhopper, which is the vector of the tungro virus; moderate resistance to the tungro disease itself; resistance to bacterial leaf streak; excellent grain shape and appearance; favorable cooking and eating quality; and, of course, good plant type and high yield potential. In yield trials conducted during the past 2 years in South and Southeast Asian countries, IR24 has usually been among the top three or four varieties. Its defects include susceptibility to some races of the blast disease occurring in the Los Baños area, and to the grassy stunt virus disease and its vector, the brown planthopper. Also it has moderate susceptibility to bacterial leaf blight, and has been reported to be susceptible to sheath blight in Indonesia.

In areas of the Philippines where the tungro disease epidemic is serious, it has become clear that IR20 has true field resistance to the disease. To our knowledge, no farmer's field of IR20 has become seriously affected with the disease. IR5, IR8, and IR22 are sometimes heavily damaged, however. IRRI scientists have come to the view that, although resistance to the insect vector is an asset, it is more important for a rice variety to have resistance to the disease itself. Naturally, the ideal variety will have resistance to the virus and to its vector. Such varieties are now being developed by IRRI scientists. In fact, genetic lines emerging from the Institute's breeding program have resistance to several major insects and diseases. By combining the best of these through further crossing, it seems certain that during the next few years varieties will be created that have resistance to most of the important insects and diseases of rice. Many of the crosses have been made, and it only remains to make the selections. The list of insects for which known resistance exists includes the green leafhopper, the brown planthopper, the rice gall midge, and the rice stem borers. Among diseases, sources of resistance exist for tungro and grassy stunt viruses, the rice blast disease, bacterial streak, and bacterial blight. There are several other diseases against which strong resistance may be found, but further work is needed to establish the pest-host relationships.

The resistance factors, of course, are being introduced into the short, stiff-strawed, high-yielding varieties with good grain quality. Once the further-improved varieties have been created, the small and the large farmer alike will benefit from their use because the need for pesticides will be greatly reduced, and, often, entirely eliminated.

Program highlights

The success of IR667-98 in Korea is an outstanding achievement. This line has now been named officially by the Koreans and is called Tongil. It has a japonica-type grain, but outyields commonly grown Korean varieties by 20 to 30 percent. In 1971, 2,700 hectares of this line were grown for seed in Korea. This area will furnish enough seed to plant one-fourth of Korea's rice land in 1972, if the country chooses to do so. As is true for all varieties, improvements are needed in Tongil. New crosses have been made to incorporate into this variety such traits as increased cold resistance, earlier maturity, improved resistance to diseases and insects, tougher leaves, slower leaf senescence, and improved grain quality.

Ten genetic lines developed at IRRI, but not named by the Institute, have proved so successful that other countries have released them. This brings to 15 the number of varieties being used in the world that had their origin at IRRI. At least 15 other short, stiff-strawed varieties have been released that resulted from crosses between varieties or lines developed or distributed by IRRI (including Taichung Native 1 from Taiwan which was introduced into the breeding programs of tropical Asia mostly by IRRI).

Although marked progress is being made in developing insect-resistant varieties, it is still necessary to use chemical insecticides for the control of the major pests of rice. Carbofuran has proved to be an excellent systemic insecticide. When applied in granular form every 3 weeks, it provides good control of rice stem borers, green leafhoppers, and brown planthoppers, as well as several less important insects. Its cost in the Philippines however, is too high for economic use on the rice crop if more than one application is made at the rate of 2 kg/ha of active ingredient. The entomologists have shown that if rice seeds are soaked in a carbofuran solution, and then the seedlings are dipped in the solution at a concentration of 1,500 ppm of active ingredient just before transplanting, good protection against both the green leafhoppers and the brown planthoppers is obtained for as much as 60 days. The amount of the chemical needed to treat enough seedlings to plant 1 hectare of ground is 0.25 kg of active ingredient costing P25.00 (about US\$4.00).

Another compound made in Japan, called Knockbal, is proving to be as satisfactory as carbofuran as a seedling dip. It is so new that it is not yet on the market. Its mammalian toxicity is lower than that of carbofuran so it will be further tested with the hope that its price will be within the range of small farmers. IRRI scientists now feel that if the seed soaking and seedling dip treatments are administered to resistant varieties, farmers need not fear the tungro virus disease.

Although the exact cause of the rise and fall in the incidence of the tungro virus disease is not known, it appears to be related to the changes in the population density of its vector, the green leafhopper. Institute entomologists are now attempting to study the population dynamics of this insect in relation to variations in weather and other environmental factors.

A finding of the soil microbiology department which may prove to have great significance is that nitrogen fixation by soil microorganisms is much higher in a soil planted to rice than in the same soil that remains unplanted. It needs to be determined whether air, which is transmitted from the atmosphere to the roots through leaf and stem channels, is supplying needed nitrogen to the nitrogen-fixing bacteria in the rhizosphere or whether root exudates simply

provide an energy source for the bacteria and allow them to be more active in nitrogen fixation. Such possibilities are being explored.

The soil chemistry department emphasized the reaction of different varieties and genetic lines of rice to adverse soil conditions. Among 52 varieties or lines studied, IR20 consistently showed the widest adaptability to unfavorable soil conditions such as iron toxicity, phosphorus and zinc deficiency, and high soil moisture tension.

The plant pathology department screened thousands of rice varieties and genetic lines in search of broad-spectrum resistance to the many physiologic races of the rice blast disease. Two varieties, Tetep and Carreon, proved to be highly resistant to most of the known races of the disease, and these varieties are now being used extensively in the breeding program to introduce this quality into high-yielding varieties.

The plant physiology department is intensifying its studies of the differences in photosynthetic efficiency of rice varieties under field conditions in an effort to determine the impact of this quality on yield potential. Early evidence indicates that it is possible to further increase yields by imparting higher photosynthetic efficiency into the varieties that have improved plant type, but it will take several years to develop appropriate isogenic lines to prove this point.

The agricultural engineering department continued to develop simple agricultural equipment for use and manufacture in the less-developed regions. A 4- to 6-hp power tiller, a manually operated low-lift pump, a six-row multi-hopper seeder, and a test-tube rice miller for laboratory use were developed this year. During the year, over 600 single-hopper seeders and 3,000 power weeders, which were originally designed and developed by the department, were commercially produced in Asia. Local manufacture of the table thresher and grain cleaner was begun and field evaluation and extension activities were substantially increased. Work continues on the development of a stripper harvester and a high-capacity, multi-crop thresher. Increased emphasis was placed on the development of rice processing equipment. Work is continuing on the development of the rice hull furnace and new systems for rapid drying and parboiling of paddy.

The agronomy department studied the interaction between water management, nitrogen application, and variety, and, as might be expected, showed that the negative response of the tall, traditional rice varieties to nitrogen was removed when the level of water management was poor. This appeared to be due to the slower absorption of nitrogen by the plant under adverse soil moisture conditions which prevented lodging at high nitrogen levels. The highest yields were obtained with improved varieties under good management. The agronomy department also developed a method for measuring evapotranspiration instantaneously and a simple device to supply water to greenhouse pots at predetermined soil moisture tensions. These two developments appear to be significant advances in the methodology of studies of relations between soil, plants, and water.

The agricultural economics department continued to obtain input-output data from 152 farms in Laguna province that have been under study since 1966. Although yield levels were depressed by unfavorable weather conditions and increased disease incidence, farmers still preferred the improved varieties.

The intensity of labor use continued to be higher for the high yielding varieties than for the traditional ones.

Yield increases on farmers' fields in the Philippines as a result of changing from the traditional to the high yielding varieties, have not been as great as would be expected from the well-established fact that the yield potential has been doubled. To gain more information on factors limiting grain yield, a project was started this year to study the possibilities for increasing yields under non-irrigated conditions. About 150 field experiments were placed on farmers' fields in the provinces of Bulacan and Nueva Ecija in the Philippines. Two kinds of rice culture were involved. One was the so-called rainfed paddy which is banded and flooded (when enough rainfall occurs), and the other was strictly upland rice culture with no bunding and no flooding. This project, conducted jointly by the Institute and the Philippine Agricultural Productivity Commission, under a 3-year grant from The Rockefeller Foundation, involved 22 permanent professional field workers and about 100 cooperating farmers. The results of the first year show that in the absence of any irrigation system, yields of 4 to 6 t/ha are possible in the monsoon season with relatively simple management systems involving fertilizers, and insect and weed control.

The "country" programs in India, Ceylon, and Indonesia are progressing well. The Pakistan program was slowed down by the political disturbance but will be reactivated in early 1972. A small cooperative program with the USAID got under way in late 1971 in South Vietnam, with the main objective of studying varietal adaptation and cultural practices suitable for Vietnam.

Staff changes Dr. Richard Bradfield, who has been assigned to the Institute by The Rockefeller Foundation for the past 6 years to handle our multiple cropping research program, retired on July 1, 1971 at the age of 75. His replacement, Dr. Richard R. Harwood, now an agronomist in The Rockefeller Foundation program in Thailand, is expected to move to the Institute in 1972.

Dr. W. Ronnie Coffman, joined the Institute in November 1971 as an associate plant breeder. His addition is in anticipation of the retirement of Mr. Henry M. Beachell in 1972.

Dr. A. Colin McClung, associate director, left the Institute at the end of 1971 to accept the post of deputy director-general of Centro Internacional de Agricultura Tropical in Cali, Colombia. Dr. McClung still continues on assignment by The Rockefeller Foundation.

In September 1971, the Board of Trustees announced that they had selected Dr. Ralph W. Cummings as the next director of the Institute to replace Dr. Robert F. Chandler, Jr., who will retire in mid-1972.

Trustees Dr. Clarence C. Gray III was designated as The Rockefeller Foundation representative on the Board. He replaced Dr. L. Sterling Wortman, who served until February 10, 1971.

Finances During 1971 the Institute received cash grants amounting to US\$3,210,850. *Ford Foundation* gave \$1,359,340. Of this amount \$750,000 was toward the operating and capital expenditures of the Institute. The remainder was in support of the rice research and development programs in five countries: Bangla Desh—\$260,000 which is part of a 6-year grant of \$996,000; Ceylon—\$167,090 which is part of a 6-year grant of \$819,000; Indonesia—\$64,250 which

is part of a 2-year grant of \$257,000; Pakistan—\$53,000 which is part of a 4-year grant of \$550,000; Philippines—\$65,000 which is part of a 32-month grant of \$226,000.

The *Rockefeller Foundation* granted the Institute \$598,670 during 1971. Its contribution toward the operating and capital expenditure needs of the Institute amounted to \$750,000 of which \$521,000 was received in cash. The balance represented the value of the foundation's manpower contribution to the Institute. The Rockefeller Foundation also supported the Institute's accelerated research and training program on cropping systems for tropical areas. For this purpose, a grant of \$182,500 over a 3-year period was made in 1968, of which \$25,320 was released in 1971. Furthermore, The Rockefeller Foundation made a grant to the Institute toward the costs of research on nutrition and growth of upland rice under the direction of Dr. Gary M. Paulsen. For this purpose \$10,000 was released during the year. The Rockefeller Foundation also supported an experimental program to identify and demonstrate techniques for increasing the productivity of disadvantaged Asian rice farmers. For this purpose \$42,350 was released during 1971.

From various grants, the *U. S. Agency for International Development* released a total of \$1,162,210 to the Institute during 1971. In 1970, USAID made grants totalling \$1,100,000 toward the operating and capital expenditures of the Institute for a 2-year period. During 1971, the Institute had been reimbursed in the amount of \$872,290. USAID renewed a project entitled "Research on Farm and Equipment Power Requirement for Production of Rice and Associated Food Crops in the Far East and South Asia" in 1970 for a 2-year period with a budget of \$404,600. In 1971, the Institute was paid \$174,230. Since 1967 a contract between the Institute and USAID has supported a project for the acceleration of rice research and training programs in India. For 1971 it had a budget of \$153,810 which is in addition to an Indian rupee budget managed by the USAID mission in India. During the year, \$90,000 was released to the Institute. USAID contributed toward the training program of the Institute by supporting scholars from various countries where USAID has an active program. The Institute received \$25,700 for this purpose in 1971.

In 1967, the Institute entered into a contract with the U.S. National Institutes of Health, to study ways to increase the protein and essential amino acids of the rice grain through plant breeding. During 1971, \$26,360 was released by NIH to the Institute.

In October 1971, the *Netherlands Government* made a 5-year grant of \$500,000 for the Institute's rice research project in Indonesia. This year \$44,350 was released.

Stauffer Chemical Co. provided the sum of \$2,000 to partially support the Institute's weed control research program.

The sum of \$2,193 was received from the *International Potash Institute* toward the soil fertility research of the Institute.

Imperial Chemical Industries gave \$5,000 to support research on weed control.

Bayer Philippines, Inc. gave \$1,000 to the Institute in support of the herbicide research work.

Monsanto Co. gave \$750 as a grant-in-aid for herbicide research work.

Occidental Chemical Co. gave \$500 as a grant-in-aid for research work.

The *Japanese Government* gave \$8,480 as a contribution toward the Institute's training program.

Crop weather

Rainfall during 1971 was higher than the average of the previous 5 years. The total amount in 1971 was 2,316 mm compared with a 5 year average of 1,811 mm. Unusually heavy rains associated with a tropical depression, occurred in March (fig. 1). The wet season rains began earlier in 1971 than in the previous years and were heavier than usual until the end of July. This delayed the planting of much of the upland rice crop. Relatively dry periods occurred from August to September and in early November. These dry periods did not seriously interfere with rainfed rice experiments. Heavy rains

resumed in late November and continued until the end of the year.

The solar radiation values were lower than normal in 1971 (fig. 1). These lower solar radiation values are associated with the higher rainfall amounts obtained throughout the year. The grain yields of crops in the wet season were reduced because of the low solar radiation from October through December.

No damaging tropical storms or typhoons occurred at Los Baños in 1971. The maximum wind velocity observed was 48 kph on May 26.

1. Solar radiation and rainfall (three-point moving weekly average) at IRRI, 1971 and 1966-70. Shaded area shows standard deviation of the 5-year rainfall average.

Chemistry

Protein distribution in the grain, determined by Kjeldahl protein content of brown rice, was a better index of milled rice protein than histological examination of individual grains. The constant lysine content of rice protein at high protein levels in the grain was due in part to simultaneous increases in the albumin and prolamin fractions with an increase in protein content. High protein milled rice tended to have a higher thiamine content, but the same protein digestibility as samples with normal protein content.

Screening the lysine content of 10,493 varieties from the world collection led to the identification of five higher lysine varieties. But the varieties represented a possible improvement in lysine content of only 0.5 percentage point.

Rice with high yield of grain protein per panicle had high levels of leaf protein at booting and flowering and a greater drop in leaf protein during grain development than lines with low grain protein. Factors affecting assimilation of soil nitrogen were studied at the seedling and booting stages.

A simplified amylose assay was developed that was rapid and accurate. A resurvey of world rice was undertaken to determine any change in quality preferences since the introduction of the IRRI varieties. The water content of steeped rice and of grain at high relative humidities was negatively correlated with amylose content. Waxy rices differing in cake quality differed also in gelatinization temperature and molecular size of amylopectin.

The production of protease in the embryo-less seed-half incubated in gibberellin A₃ was faster and less inhibited by actinomycin D than that of α -amylase.

Properties of grain protein

IRRI plant breeders are developing lines with improved protein content. As part of a cooperative program, we studied the properties of grain protein of promising lines using better methods of amino acid analysis and of histological screening for protein bodies.

Grain properties and nutrient distribution. We studied the grain properties and nutrient distribution of samples from the same line but differing in protein content. Twenty-one samples from seven varieties and lines were used. We found that the brown rice of samples that had over 10 percent protein were harder (Kiya tester) than samples of the same line with less protein. The head-rice yield of high protein samples was the same as or higher than that of low protein samples. The fat content of high protein samples was higher than that of low protein samples in only two of the seven lines.

1. Cross-sectional view of destarched brown rice. Stain: mercuric chloride-Bromphenol blue. Top, 6.6% protein; bottom, 9.2% protein.

This observation verified our previous findings that fat content is not always higher in higher protein samples of the same variety.

The protein distribution was assessed both histologically and by protein analysis of bran-polish and milled rice. Brown-rice samples were fixed with a mixture of formalin, acetic acid, and ethanol, and then dehydrated, embedded in methacrylate, and sectioned with a rotary microtome. Sections 3 μ thick were destarched with α-amylase and stained for protein. Fixing was required to insure the integrity of adjacent protein bodies during sectioning. Protein distribution became more even and the stained area became larger as the protein content of the grain increased in all seven lines (fig. 1). But the extent of the total area that stained for protein varied among grains of the same sample, reflecting the variation in protein content that occurs among grains even within the same panicle. The increase in protein content resulted mainly from an increase in the number of protein bodies although a slight increase in their size also occurred.

At 10 percent (by weight) milling of brown rice, traces of the aleurone layer were still observed in grain sections of the milled rice. Presumably not more than one cell layer of the endosperm is, on the average, removed during normal milling. Protein analysis of bran-polish and milled rice at the same degree of milling showed that the fraction of grain protein that is retained in the milled rice fraction increases as protein content increases (fig. 2). Since a smooth curve was obtained for all the samples tested, protein distribution presumably is mainly a function of the protein content of brown rice. Deviation from the protein curve was chiefly due to the deviation from 90-percent milling. Kjeldahl analysis, therefore, is a more reliable index of protein distribution than the more tedious histological technique. In addition, a mean value of 10 or 20 grains is obtained in the chemical analysis, but several grains must be individually screened by the histological method. Since protein distribution is affected by protein content, varieties cannot justifiably be classified histologically for differences in protein distribution unless they have comparable protein content.

Milled rice that has more than 8 percent protein tended to have a higher content of thiamine (vitamin B₁) than samples of the same variety or line with lower protein content (Table 1).

Lysine and protein content. The correlation between the lysine content of protein and the protein content of brown and milled rices was studied with the promising high protein lines. Better data than in our previous studies were obtained by more efficiently removing oxygen from the hydrolysis tube and by using internal standards—norleucine and *S*-β-(4-pyridylethyl) L-cysteine. The negative correlation between the lysine level in protein and the protein content of the grain was verified to be absent above 10 percent protein in brown rice and above 9.5 percent protein in milled rice (fig. 3). For example, three samples of IR22 brown rice with 10.3, 11.8, and 16.2 percent protein had corresponding lysine contents of 3.73, 3.61, and 3.82 g/16.8 g N.

The protein of milled rice had a slightly lower lysine content than protein of brown rice because the protein fraction with the highest lysine content, albumin, is more concentrated in the bran layers. The lysine content was more variable in milled rice than in brown rice. For IR8, the tryptophan content of milled rice protein was 1.2%; of albumin, 1.9%; of globulin, 1.3%; of prolamin, 0.9%; and of glutelin, 1.2%. These values are less variable than the ones for lysine content that we reported last year.

The constancy of lysine content at high protein levels is important since the proportion of the low-lysine fraction, prolamin, increases with protein content. The major fraction, glutelin, accounts for most of the increase in protein, but it has little effect on lysine since it has an aminogram similar to that of milled-rice protein. Since only albumin can offset the negative effect of prolamin on lysine content, we examined the water-soluble nitrogen content of the 21 samples of brown rice and found that as protein content increased water-soluble nitrogen content increased as a percentage of brown rice ($r = 0.710^{**}$) (fig. 4), but decreased as a percentage of protein ($r = -0.755^{**}$). Such an increase in albumin may contribute to the stability of lysine content of rice protein at high levels of grain protein.

2. Fraction of brown-rice protein retained in milled rice increased with an increase in protein content (milled rice yield $90 \pm 1\%$ of brown rice).

Protein digestibility. Cooperative studies on protein digestibility were conducted in Latin America, USA, and Denmark. Studies on nitrogen balance in Peru and Guatemala with dogs and humans show that the digestibility of protein in cooked rice is slightly inferior to that of wheat flour, although rice protein has a better nutritional quality. Dr. Helen Clark (Purdue Univ., USA), however, reported that human digestibility of protein in cooked milled rice from raw grain with 7.9 and 14.5 percent protein was similar (77 to 78%). Dr. B. O. Eggum (Agricultural Research Laboratory, Copenhagen) determined the digestibility of all amino acids (except tryptophan) of milled rice in rats using a sample of BPI-76-1 (14.5%

Table 1. Protein and thiamine contents of milled rices (at 14% moisture).

Variety or line	Protein (%)	Thiamine ($\mu\text{g/g}$)
IR8	4.9	0.63
	8.0	0.70
IR480-5-9	7.0	0.81
	10.7	1.33
IR1100-89-2	5.9	0.95
	10.1	1.83
IR1103-15-8	7.0	0.98
	11.2	2.55
LSD (5%)		0.32

3. Relationship between lysine content of protein and protein level of brown and milled rices (HP = high protein; DS = dry season).

protein) and a sample of IR8 (7.3% protein). He reported identical high availabilities (94.1 to 100%) for all amino acids in the two samples. Apparently, protein digestibility data in white rats are not applicable to humans. But protein digestibility did not change with protein content of milled rice. Thus the poorer digestibility of rice protein relative to wheat protein deserves verification in traditional rice-eating subjects.

Screening for lysine content. We screened 10,493 entries in the world rice collection by the dye-binding technique and found a change in

4. Water-soluble nitrogen increases with an increase in protein content of brown rice.

the slope of the regression curve above 10 percent protein (fig. 5). The lower slope at high protein levels reflects the lower constant lysine content of brown-rice protein above 10 percent protein. Only 38 entries showed higher dye-binding values than the regression equation. These entries were further analyzed for lysine content. Only five had a lysine content 0.5 percentage point higher than the mean value for brown rice (fig. 3). Only three retained their higher lysine content after milling. Milling resulted in a mean drop of 0.19 percentage point in the lysine content of protein for the five entries.

Although these five entries had higher than average lysine content, some of the promising semidwarf lines also had similar lysine levels (fig. 3). Hence, there is no advantage in using these entries in a breeding program. In addition, feeding trials with preschool children in Vellore, India, in which milled rice contributed 80 percent of calories and protein, showed that fortification for 6 months with lysine and threonine did not improve the height of the children over those given the same rice diet without fortification. Food consumption surveys also indicate that lysine is not the first limiting amino acid in rice diets. Thus improving lysine content of rice protein is less important than improving protein level without sacrificing lysine content in a breeding program to improve the nutritional value of rice.

The size of protein bodies in rice endosperm was determined in the five higher lysine entries. Protein bodies varied in size from 1.1 to 3.4 μ . ARC 10525 had smaller protein bodies than the other four samples or IR8 and BPI-76-1 (Table 2). It had the highest lysine content, 4.6 percent, but it had a normal level of water-soluble nitrogen, 0.13 percent of brown rice. The lysine content of the wet season crop of these five lines, however, was average (3.7 to 4.3%) for their protein content (8.0 to 9.7%). The mean size of endosperm protein bodies of ARC 10525 in this crop was 2.0 μ and smaller than that of the other varieties (2.4 to 2.8 μ).

The size of protein bodies of three IRB100 high protein mutants from γ -irradiation of Norin 8 at the Institute of Radiation Breeding, Ohmiya, Japan was similar to that of ordinary rice (Table 2). The data indicate that size of protein bodies is not simply related to protein content or to lysine content of protein.

Aminogram of rice byproducts and corn. Samples of rice byproducts and corn, which are being assessed for their feed value by the animal husbandry department, University of the Philippines College of Agriculture, were analyzed for amino acid content. Rice bran had the best amino acid pattern, followed, in order, by whole *opaque-2* corn, broken rice, rice middlings (brewers' rice), and normal corn, based on content of lysine—their first limiting essential amino acid (Table 3). The aminograms of broken rice and middlings were similar to the aminogram of milled rice. They were characterized by lower levels of basic amino acids (lysine, arginine, and histidine) than bran. The protein of rice byproducts had a higher level of arginine than whole corn protein but a lower level of proline. Normal corn, however, had a lower lysine content than *opaque-2* corn, but a higher leucine content.

Protein metabolism

In contrast to carbohydrates in the rice grain, which result mainly from photosynthesis after flowering, protein nitrogen in the grain is considered by physiologists to be derived mainly from the nitrogen present in the vegetative tissues of the tiller at flowering. Our previous

5. Dye-binding capacity as an index of the lysine content of brown rice protein.

studies showed that the developing grain of high protein lines had higher levels of free amino acids than their low protein counterparts. The sap entering the panicle in the high protein lines generally contained higher levels of free amino acids than the sap in low protein lines, indicating a faster senescence of tissues or a more efficient translocation of free amino acids into the developing grain in high protein lines. A study of five varieties and lines indicated that mean protease activity was also higher in leaf blades of high protein rices during grain development.

Protein metabolism in leaves. This year we studied the changes in nitrogen metabolism in

Table 2. Mean size of endosperm protein bodies of rice samples differing in lysine content.

Variety or mutant	Brown rice protein (%)	Lysine (% of protein)	Size of protein bodies ^a (μ)
IR8	8.2	4.0	2.5
BPI-76-1	9.2	3.7	2.5
Wu-chiang-tsao-lu-hsien	9.8	4.2	2.3
Pulut Nangka 016	9.9	4.0	2.7
Kalajira (Aman)	10.3	4.1	2.6
Kalijira (Aman)	10.1	4.2	2.1
ARC 10525	8.4	4.6	1.7
IRB100-4	13.4	3.8	2.5
IRB100-5	13.4	3.8	2.3
IRB100-177	14.8	3.7	2.4
LSD (5%)		0.3	0.2

^aMean of 40 measurements.

Table 3. Amino acid content of defatted rice byproducts and whole corn grain.

Feed sample	Protein ^a (%)	Amino acid content ^b (% of protein)				
		Lysine	Histidine	Arginine	Leucine	Proline
<i>Rice byproducts</i>						
Bran A	13.8	5.5	3.2	9.4	7.9	5.6
Bran B	14.4	5.8	3.3	9.1	8.3	5.0
Broken rice	6.6	4.4	2.5	8.0	8.7	5.3
Middlings	8.1	3.7	2.4	7.8	8.4	4.7
<i>Corn grain samples</i>						
Yellow, normal	7.4	3.2	3.5	5.9	12.5	9.7
Yellow, <i>opaque-2</i>	8.8	4.6	3.5	6.4	8.8	8.8
White, <i>opaque-2</i>	8.2	5.1	3.8	6.5	8.5	10.0

^aBased on N x 5.95 for rice and N x 6.25 for corn. ^bBased on g/16.8 g N for rice and g/16.0 g N for corn.

individual leaf blades of IR8 and IR22 plants grown in the greenhouse. The levels of total and soluble protein, free amino acids, chlorophyll, and the activities of amino-acid incorporation, protease, ribulose 1,5-diphosphate (RuDP) carboxylase, and peroxidase were assayed at each developmental stage from transplanting to harvest.

In both varieties, all properties of leaf blades reached maximum values after full exertion and decreased during senescence, with the older leaves attaining peak levels earlier than the younger leaves (fig. 6 and 7). The flag leaf and the next two uppermost leaves tended to undergo senescence at the same time rather than sequentially as in older leaves. Peak levels occurred close to booting except the peak for protease, which occurred about 10 days earlier, and those for chlorophyll and peroxidase, which occurred at heading. Protease, chlorophyll, and RuDP carboxylase levels were generally correlated with the total and soluble protein in all leaf blades except the flag leaf. The decrease in leaf nitrogen during senescence coincided with a drop in the rate of protein synthesis rather than with an increase in protease activity.

Grinding fresh leaf blades in a mortar and pestle with sand gave better extraction of protein than mechanical homogenization. The latter procedure did not completely break up the chloroplasts. For freeze-dried, 40-mesh powder of the leaf blades, stirring with a cold buffer for 30 minutes extracted protein more efficiently than homogenization. Freezing the leaf samples

at -50 C during freeze-drying presumably disrupts the chloroplast membranes.

Varietal differences in N translocation. Nitrogen translocation was studied in 12 varieties and lines grown in the greenhouse. Leaf 2 (next to flag leaf) and leaf 4 were used for the enzymic assays. High yield of grain (brown rice) protein per tiller was associated with high protein levels in the leaf blades, particularly in leaf 2, at booting ($r = 0.892^{**}$) and flowering ($r = 0.813^{**}$). This association was confirmed in eight of the samples grown in the field at 20 x 20 cm spacing with 0 or 120 kg/ha N. The high nitrogen content of the leaves in the high protein samples reflected a more efficient rate of absorption of soil nitrogen than that of normal protein samples. A high level of leaf protein did not always result in high yield of grain protein because of the effect of other factors on grain protein yield.

Regardless of whether the high leaf protein resulted from genetic or from environmental factors, or from both, this property was positively correlated with a greater decrease in amount of leaf nitrogen during grain development and with high levels of soluble protein and protease in leaf 2 at booting. The RuDP carboxylase activity was correlated positively with the amount of soluble protein but not with the amount of total protein of the leaf blade.

Varietal differences in N absorption. The low concentration of nitrate that we found in rice leaves reflected the relatively minor role of nitrate reductase in flooded rice. Nitrate reductase is an enzyme that is induced by its

substrate and is suppressed by ammonium ion. Physiologists believe that the rice plant absorbs soil nitrogen from flooded soils in the ammonium form which is toxic to plants. Since glutamate dehydrogenase is the main enzyme involved in detoxifying ammonium by converting it into amino acid, we made a study in the wet season to determine the level of nitrate reductase and glutamate dehydrogenase in field samples of six varieties and lines at the panicle initiation stage.

The roots had negligible nitrate reductase activity, but they approached the leaf blades in glutamate dehydrogenase activity per gram of fresh tissue. The percentage of leaf protein was positively correlated with glutamate dehydrogenase activity per gram of roots ($r = 0.700^{**}$) and of leaf blades ($r = 0.597^{**}$) and with leaf nitrate reductase activity per gram ($r = 0.586^{**}$) and per leaf ($r = 0.590^{**}$). Basal application of nitrogen fertilizer at 90 kg/ha N increased only the amount of leaf protein and the specific activity of root glutamate dehydrogenase.

We also studied glutamate dehydrogenase and nitrate reductase in leaf blades and roots of 4-week-old seedlings of low-protein and high-protein seeds of six varieties and lines. The seedlings were grown in seedbeds kept moist, but not submerged. Greater varietal differences in dry weight of roots were observed than in dry weight of tops. The roots had a low content of soluble protein and little nitrate reductase activity, and both were less than the corresponding values for the three upper fully expanded leaf blades. Presumably nitrate reduction was already principally in the leaves rather than

6. Changes in dry weight and nitrogenous fractions of flag leaf, leaf 2, and leaf 4 of two rice varieties.

7. Changes in enzymic properties of flag leaf, leaf 2, and leaf 4 of two rice varieties.

in the roots in these seedlings. By contrast, the total activity of glutamate dehydrogenase was equally distributed between the roots and the leaf blades.

Grain protein level had, in general, no effect on dry weight of tops and roots of the seedlings whether or not fertilizer was applied. Only in two lines was the amount of leaf protein consistently higher in the seedlings from high protein grain, whether fertilized or not. But, the amount of leaf protein was correlated with total nitrate reductase activity ($r = 0.674^{**}$) and glutamate dehydrogenase activity ($r = 0.505^*$) in the three uppermost fully exerted leaf blades. Total glutamate dehydrogenase activity of leaves and that of roots were correlated ($r = 0.540^*$). The amount of protein and total glutamate dehydrogenase activity of roots also were correlated ($r = 0.627^{**}$).

Free amino acids and leaf nitrogen. Wheat workers have shown that glutamate increases more than other amino acids with an increase

in level of free amino acids in the leaf blades. We studied whether all amino acids increase proportionally with an increase in free amino acids in the leaf blades of rice. A twofold difference in the amount of free amino acids in leaf blades of 45-day-old seedlings of two varieties, caused by basal nitrogen fertilization, corresponded to proportionally more arginine, asparagine, glutamine, pipercolate, and serine, and to proportionally less isoleucine, leucine, lysine, ornithine, phenylalanine, threonine, and tryptophan. Glutamate remained the major amino acid.

Grain quality

Simplified amylose assay. Four samples differing in amylose content were sent to 10 individuals in eight laboratories for analysis with the simplified amylose assay at 590, 620, and 650 nm and the standard iodine colorimetric assay at 590 nm. Milled rice flour was gelatinized with

sodium hydroxide solution at 100 C for 10 minutes without prior defatting; iodine was added and the starch dispersion was neutralized with acetic acid to provide a final pH of 4.5 to 4.7. Absorbance readings at 620 nm by this method gave values comparable to amylose data by the standard method for samples with low and intermediate amylose contents, but gave slightly lower values for samples with high amylose and slightly higher values for samples with very low amylose (Table 4). The new method is simpler, more rapid, and more reproducible than the standard method. The modified method showed lower variation (0.33) in amylose content than the standard method (9.96) while interaction between samples and analysts were of the same magnitude. In the tests, an important variable was the colorimeter because three out of the eight laboratories reported a maximum absorption at wavelengths other than 650 nm for the amylose standard.

The method was satisfactorily adapted to the AutoAnalyzer with a 608 nm filter for screening breeders' selections (100-mg sample), including single grains (10 mg) at the rate of 70 samples an hour. The only manual steps that were retained were weighing and dispersion of starch.

Survey of world rices. Our previous survey of the amylose content of rices from different countries was done before the introduction of the IRRI varieties. To keep abreast of changing tastes we rechecked the amylose content of important varieties of known quality sent to us by breeders in various countries.

Varieties preferred in Indonesia, Pakistan, and the Philippines had 22 to 26 percent amylose. Japonica rices from Taiwan had 20 to 21 percent

amylose, while the native varieties had high (28%) amylose. In Malaysia, Thailand, and Colombia, rices with 25 to 27 percent amylose were preferred to those with higher amylose content. All the samples from Ceylon and India had high amylose (27 to 30%). The preference in Ceylon for the short-grained "samba" varieties may be due in part to their resistance to splitting during cooking.

The results indicate that high amylose rices (>25%) can be grouped into two distinct types. Rices with 25 to 27 percent amylose, when cooked, have the flaky texture of rices with over 27 percent amylose, but not the extreme hardness. We propose calling this amylose class "moderately high" to distinguish it from the "high" amylose class (27 to 33%). Single-sample analysis for amylose is not reliable because the environment affects amylose content by as much as 6 percentage points. We found that the starch-iodine blue value at 100 C is a more reliable varietal indicator. The procedure was modified so that amylose of the supernatant liquid of the heated mixture (25 mg/10 ml water) was determined with an AutoAnalyzer and expressed as percentage of amylose. Varieties with moderately high amylose gave the highest values (13 to 15%) for water-soluble amylose, while the high amylose varieties gave values that were at least 1 percentage point lower and those values overlapped the values for intermediate amylose varieties (20 to 25%) (fig. 8). The starch-iodine blue test may be used instead of amylose content to identify lines that have low amylose (<20%) or moderately high amylose (25 to 27%). Among the IRRI varieties, only IR20 may be classified as moderately high

Table 4. Mean apparent amylose content (dry basis) determined by the standard and simplified methods of four samples of milled-rice flour in a cooperative test by five selected analysts^a.

Method	pH	Amylose content (%) ^b			
		IR35-23-2	IR24	BPI-121-407	IR22
Standard					
590 nm	10	12.4 c	15.8 b	21.0 b	26.8 b
Simplified					
590 nm	4.5 to 4.7	16.2 a	19.6 a	24.6 a	29.3 a
620 nm	4.5 to 4.7	13.3 b	15.9 b	20.9 b	25.2 c
650 nm	4.5 to 4.7	10.3 d	13.6 c	18.4 c	22.9 d

^aSelected from data of 10 analysts based on normal amylose values by the standard method and with lowest conversion factor at 650 nm. ^bAny two-method means within each sample followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Amylose soluble in 100 C water
(% of milled rice)

8. Water-soluble amylose in the starch-iodine blue test may be used to identify rices with 25 to 27 percent amylose.

in amylose content. The low and intermediate types have negative setback values in the amylograph, the moderately high type has setback values between 0 and 300 Brabender units (B.U.), and the high type has values exceeding 300 B.U.

Properties of starch and grain. The interaction between differences in grain properties and amylose content or gelatinization temperature of the starch was studied in two crops of nine selected IR841 lines (IR262-43-8 x Khao Dawk Mali 3-2-105). The amylose content of grain of the two crops was positively correlated with the residual protein content of the purified starch ($r = 0.904^{**}$ and 0.966^{**}). The correlation between bound protein and amylose content of the rice starch supported a previously reported positive correlation between activity of ADP glucose-starch synthetase which is bound to the starch granule and amylose content.

The amylose content was negatively correlated with the water content of steeped brown rice in both crops ($r = -0.975^{**}$ and -0.940^{**}) and with the equilibrium moisture content of purified starch at 96 percent relative humidity in one crop. These results support the high moisture content we have observed in waxy grain above 75 percent relative humidity, which contributes to the more rapid loss of viability in seeds of waxy varieties during storage at high humidity than in nonwaxy rices. The low density of waxy

starch may explain the greater capacity of waxy and low amylose grain to hold water.

Gelatinization temperature was verified to be negatively correlated with alkali digestibility values of milled rice and with the extent of acid corrosion of starch granules in both crops. The grain of a line with a low gelatinization temperature (68 C) liberated twice as much reducing sugar after 4 days germination than the grain of a line with a high gelatinization temperature (75 C). Molecular weights were indexed from 0.6 percent starch dispersions in dimethylsulfoxide centrifuged at 15,000 rpm for amylopectin, and then at 39,460 rpm for amylose. The molecular size of amylopectin was positively correlated with gelatinization temperature in both crops although the correlation was significant in the first crop ($r = 0.834^{**}$) but not in the second crop ($r = 0.619$). Hence, no correlation between the molecular sizes of the starch fraction may be expected among varieties that differ in both amylose content and gelatinization temperature. Consistent differences in the molecular size of starch fractions were observed previously in lines (from the same cross) differing in either amylose content or gelatinization temperature. Grain characteristics, such as hardness, protein and amylose content, and gelatinization temperature, and the molecular size of amylopectin differed in the two crops in many of the lines.

Cooking properties of low amylose rices. Preliminary studies were made on cooking properties of 12 indica, japonica, and indica x japonica rices of similar amylose content (18 to 21%) and low or high gelatinization temperature. The samples showed overlapping scores for cohesiveness and gloss of cooked rice, for splitting after overnight soaking of cooked grain, and for cooking time, probably because of the similar amylose contents of the samples. Parboiling had little effect on the amylograph values for peak viscosity in two of the three samples tested. These results indicated the similarity in cooking properties of rices that have similar amylose content.

Environmental effect on Basmati quality. We verified that gelatinization temperature is more important than amylose content in the extreme elongation of Basmati-type rices during cooking.

Table 5. Physicochemical properties of two samples of Basmati rices from Pakistan differing in elongation ratio.

Variety	Quality rating ^a	Elongation ratio ^b	Protein content (%)	Amylose content ^c (%)	Final gelatinization temperature (C)
Basmati 6129	good	2.09	9.0	23.6	66
	poor	1.68	7.8	21.4	76
Basmati 370	good	1.79	7.5	23.4	72
	poor	1.61	7.6	22.2	75
Palman 246	poor	1.14	9.4	28.6	73

^aAssessed by Dr. G. McLean. ^bLength of cooked grain to length of raw grain. Mean of 10 grains. ^cDry basis.

Ambient temperature during grain development affects the aroma and elongation of Basmati rice. Grain from a Basmati crop grown at Dokri, Pakistan, was more chalky, had a lower elongation ratio, had a much higher gelatinization temperature, and had a slightly lower amylose content than a good-quality Basmati crop grown at Punjab (Table 5). The environmental effect was more evident in Basmati 6129 than in Basmati 370. The differences in elongation ratio were more proportional to the differences in gelatinization temperature than to the differences in amylose content due to location. Palman, a poor quality variety, had a higher gelatinization temperature and amylose content. Its grains split when cooked. Previous studies elsewhere have shown that ambient temperature during grain development is directly correlated with gelatinization temperature, and independently, inversely affects the amylose content of rice starch.

Waxy rice and cake quality. Waxy rices differ in cake quality in Japan, although they all have about 100 percent amylopectin content. Our studies on two sets of waxy rices showed that preferred varieties had higher gelatinization temperatures, but lower sedimentation con-

stants than the poor-quality varieties (Table 6). The lower molecular size of amylopectin in these preferred waxy rices probably contributes to a more sticky rice cake. The alkali digestibility test using 1.3 percent potassium hydroxide solution can readily distinguish between these two types of waxy rices.

Carbohydrate metabolism

Soluble starch synthetases. A study was begun in cooperation with Dr. E. del Rosario of the University of the Philippines College of Agriculture to isolate and characterize starch synthetases. Leaves of 2-week-old IR8 seedlings were ground in the presence of dry ice and extracted with buffer containing dithiothreitol. The extract of soluble starch synthetase was purified by fractionation with ammonium sulfate and sequential chromatography through diethylaminoethyl cellulose and amylopectin-cellulose in the presence of phosphate buffer. Three active fractions were obtained from the column chromatography and also by disc electrophoresis in polyacrylamide gel. Molecular-weight fractionation by gel electrophoresis in the presence of sodium dodecyl sulfate

Table 6. Physicochemical properties of two sets of Japanese waxy varieties differing in cake quality.

Variety	Cake quality	Final gelatinization temperature (C)	Amylopectin		Protein (%)
			S _{20,w} (Svedbergs)	Mean chain length (glucose units)	
Koganemochi ^a	good	67.5	78	25.8	6.5
Hatsunemochi ^a	upper interm.	66.0	60	25.1	7.6
Nakatamochi ^a	poor	63.0	114	26.0	7.0
Hatsunemochi ^b	good	68.5	84	25.0	6.5
Norin 1 ^b	poor	58.5	144	26.6	9.6
LSD (5%)		2.7	8.4	n.s.	0.3

^aObtained from and assessed for cake quality by Dr. H. Kurasawa, Niigata Univ. ^bObtained from and assessed for cake quality by Dr. S. Saito, Niigata Prefectural Food Res. Inst.

Table 7. Effect of leaf age (position) on the levels of ribulose 1,5-diphosphate and phosphoenol pyruvate carboxylases and photorespiration of rice at the booting stage (mean of IR8 and IR22).

Leaf no.	RuDP carboxylase ($\mu\text{mole}/\text{min CO}_2$)	PEP carboxylase ($\mu\text{mole}/\text{min CO}_2$)	Photorespiration (nmole/min CO_2)
1 (flag leaf)	10.4	0.46	0.087
2	23.5	1.01	0.216
3	21.6	1.34	0.190
4	15.5	1.34	0.223
LSD (5%)	4.1	0.24	0.090

resolved all the fractions into the same three bands. The fractions showed higher enzyme activity with adenosine diphosphate glucose as substrate in the absence of added primer (amylopectin) than in its presence, even in the absence of albumin. Similar results have been reported elsewhere for the major fraction of soluble starch synthetase of spinach leaves.

By contrast, soluble starch synthetase from developing IR8 grains at the midmilky stage showed no activity in the absence of amylopec-

9. Densitogram of thin-layer gel filtration of soluble leaf protein on Sephadex G-200. Stain: Coomassie blue. The fastest peak is Fraction I protein.

tin primer. These starch synthetases are being characterized together with synthetase bound to the starch granules of IR8 grain. Most preparations of rice starch, however, contain more than 10 percent protein which is presumably adsorbed mainly on the surface of the starch granule since it is dispersed by detergents and sulfhydryl reagents.

Photosynthetic enzymes and photorespiration.

Two pathways of carbon dioxide fixation during photosynthesis are known—ribulose diphosphate (RuDP) carboxylase in the classical Calvin cycle and phosphoenol pyruvate (PEP) carboxylase in the C₄ dicarboxylic acid cycle. The Calvin cycle predominates in plants that exhibit photorespiration such as rice. Studies in the 1971 dry season showed that at flowering, the upper three leaves contributed 86 percent of total leaf RuDP carboxylase activity in IR8 and 85 percent of the total leaf activity in IR22.

The effect of leaf age on the activity of these two carboxylases and on photorespiration rate was determined in IR8 and IR22 plants at the booting stage in the wet season. RuDP carboxylase was confirmed to be the major enzyme for photosynthetic fixation of carbon dioxide in rice. Mean RuDP carboxylase activity was highest in leaf 2 and leaf 3, and least in the flag leaf (Table 7). PEP carboxylase activity was less than 9 percent that of RuDP carboxylase and was highest in leaf 3 and leaf 4, and least in the flag leaf. Photorespiration rate was lower in the flag leaf than in other large leaves.

Fraction I protein is the principal protein of chloroplasts. It possesses RuDP carboxylase activity and is reported to have a high molecular weight, about 5×10^5 . By using thin-layer gel filtration on Sephadex G-200 we separated soluble leaf proteins into a major fraction with high molecular weight at the solvent front (Fraction I protein) and two other minor fractions with lower molecular weight (fig. 9). This technique may be used instead of ultracentrifugation for determining Fraction I protein.

Biochemistry of insect resistance

Polyphenols are important because of their reported role in disease infection and in seed

dormancy. In cooperation with Dr. S. Rodolfo of the University of the Philippines College of Agriculture, a method was developed for extracting polyphenols from freeze-dried, ground rice seedlings using 90 percent methanol in a carbon dioxide atmosphere. Two-dimensional paper chromatography of methanol extracts from plants of varieties ASD 7, Mudgo, Pankhari 203, and Taichung Native 1 showed qualitative and quantitative differences in the chromatographic pattern of phenols among the varieties.

Since the planthoppers and leafhoppers are sap feeders, and since water and 90 percent methanol in water extracted similar amounts of phenols from the plant samples, we made additional studies with water extracts of the rice plant.

Susceptible and resistant varieties had similar levels of total phenols (Folin-Denis) in 1-month-old seedlings (Table 8). ASD 7 had higher levels of *ortho*-diphenols than the other varieties however. But the aqueous extracts from which protein had been removed by acetone precipitation had similar contents of *ortho*-diphenols. Among the subfractions of the aqueous extract from IR8 and Mudgo plants, total phenol content was highest in the protein and in the amino-acid and amine fractions, followed in order by the carboxylic acid fraction and the neutral fraction.

Biochemistry of leaf damage

Knowledge of normal nitrogen metabolism in the rice plant is invaluable in studying the effect on nitrogen metabolism of external factors, such as pests, viruses, and diseases. Preliminary studies were undertaken to compare the effect of these factors with normal leaf senescence.

Hopperburn. Preliminary studies were made on plants subjected to hopperburn (damage caused by heavy feeding by brown planthopper) in cooperative work with the entomologists. After 1 week of feeding by 80 or more brown planthoppers per plant, 50-day-old seedlings of Taichung Native 1 had a threefold to fourfold increase in free amino acids in the leaf blades, a twofold increase in free amino acids in the leaf sheaths plus culm, and a drop in chlorophyll

Table 8. Content of phenols in aqueous extracts of 1-month-old rice plants.

Variety or line	Reaction ^a to		Phenol content (% dry basis)	
	Green leaf-hopper	Brown plant-hopper		
			Total ^b	<i>Ortho</i> -diphenols ^c
Taichung Native 1	S	S	0.44	0.08
IR22	S	S	0.38	0.08
Pankhari 203	R	S	0.40	0.08
IR8	R	S	0.44	0.09
Mudgo	S	R	0.39	0.10
CO 22	S	R	0.46	0.13
TN1 x ASD 7	S	R	0.47	0.12
ASD 7	R	R	0.45	0.17
Ptb 18	R	R	0.46	0.11
LSD (5%)			0.05	0.05

^aS = susceptible; R = resistant. ^bAs vanillin. ^cAs chlorogenic acid.

content of leaf blades to one-third the level present in plants with 40 or less insects. The free amino acids of leaf blades infested with 160 insects had proportionally more glutamine, isoleucine, leucine, phenylalanine, pipecolate, proline, taurine, threonine, tyrosine, and tryptophan than the acids of leaf blades infested with 40 insects and had proportionally less aspartate, glutamate, histidine, and serine. Asparagine and glutamate were the major free amino acids in the leaves with 40 insects per plant while glutamine and asparagine were the major acids in the heavily infested leaves. These changes contrasted with the increase due to nitrogen fertilization in normal leaves in which glutamate remained as the major free amino acid.

In another study we examined the biochemical changes that occur during the course of infestation of Taichung Native 1 seedlings by brown planthoppers with uninfested plants as control. The results indicated a reduction in translocation rate between the leaf sheaths and the leaf blades, as evidenced by the dehydration (below 70% moisture) of the leaf blades, but not of the leaf sheaths, and a greater decrease in the amounts of dry matter, total and soluble protein, starch, and sugars in the leaf sheaths than in the leaf blades. The drop in the chlorophyll content of the leaf blades and leaf sheaths of infested plants preceded the dehydration of the leaf blades. The infested plants had higher levels of free amino acids than healthy plants but

lower protein levels during the start of hopperburn. Specific protease activities were similar in infested and healthy plants and were essentially a function of the protein content of the leaves. In contrast, blades of infested plants showed a greater capacity for protein synthesis during the start of hopperburn. The reduction in translocation rate between the sheaths and blades may have resulted from lower osmotic pressure caused by insect punctures on the vascular bundles or from plugging of the vessels by salivary secretion of the insects during feeding or from insect toxins.

Blast disease. In cooperative work with the pathologists, the leaf blades of blast-inoculated

plants were found to have higher levels of protein and specific activities of protease and peroxidase than the leaves of the control plants in both resistant and susceptible rices during the appearance of lesions 4 days after inoculation. Disc electrophoresis at pH 8.2 revealed six peroxidase isozymes whose major bands were the fastest and the third fastest in migrating. In diseased plants, only the third fastest peroxidase band increased in activity during infestation, in contrast to normally aging leaves in which both major bands increase in activity.

Seed germination

Enzyme production. Embryo-less IR8 seed-halves incubated in 1.2×10^{-7} M gibberellin A_3 showed a peak production for protease which coincided with the peak level of soluble protein and occurred earlier than the peak for α -amylase (fig. 10).

The addition of actinomycin D partly inhibited the production of α -amylase and R-enzyme but did not affect protease. Cycloheximide, an inhibitor of protein synthesis, inhibited all three enzymes even in intact germinating seeds, however. Since protease was synthesized earlier than α -amylase, messenger ribonucleic acid (mRNA) for protease apparently was already present in the mature grain, which explains the lack of inhibition by actinomycin D, an inhibitor of RNA synthesis, on protease. Similar results have been reported for cottonseed protease. In contrast, mRNA and protein synthesis for α -amylase probably occurred during germination. Although α -amylase was not completely inhibited by EDTA in the colorimetric R-enzyme assay using amylopectin β -limit dextrin, the increase in R-enzyme was verified using pullulan as substrate. Presumably rice R-enzyme, like α -amylase, was also resynthesized from amino acids during germination, rather than being derived from inactive forms of the enzyme.

Seed dormancy. Freshly harvested seeds of most rice varieties lose their dormancy during storage at room temperature for 4 to 6 weeks. A survey was made of factors reported to be related to seed dormancy using dormant (stored at 0 C) and nondormant seeds of the same

10. Changes in protease, α -amylase, and soluble protein in embryo-less half-seed of IR8 rice incubated at 1.2×10^{-7} M gibberellin A_3 .

varieties. Dormant and nondormant grains of variety H 6 steeped for less than 24 hours had similar capacity for synthesis of protein and ethylene, activities of maltase and 3'-nucleotidase, and content of total phenols.

Dormant seeds had slightly higher respiration rates only during the first 6 hours of steeping

and had higher peroxidase activity than nondormant seeds. The drop in peroxidase activity was verified in two other varieties tested. Pricking the aleurone layers and seed coat over the embryo, but not elsewhere, broke dormancy. Presumably, the seed coat and aleurone layers act as a barrier to oxygen diffusion to the embryo.

Soil microbiology

Submergence maintains the nitrogen fertility of soil. The fixation of atmospheric nitrogen was more active in flooded fields than in upland fields during the rice-growing season. The rhizosphere of the rice plant in a submerged field seems to be a favorable environment for nitrogen fixation. Less fertilizer nitrogen was lost and more was recovered by variety IR5 in submerged soil than in upland conditions or under alternate drying and flooding.

Microorganisms in submerged soils play a major role in iron reduction. A decline in root activity appears to enhance microbial iron-reduction in rice rhizosphere. The application of organic materials to submerged soil accentuates sulfur or zinc deficiency in some soils through microbial immobilization of the element.

Fermentation of organic materials in submerged soils severely affects the growth of rice seedlings. Organic acids in the soil accumulated to levels toxic to rice seedlings within 2 weeks after flooding. The application of ammonium sulfate seems to change the pattern of the organic acid fermentation in submerged soils to favor rice growth.

A bacterium isolated from paddy water degraded diazinon and parathion. Parathion was degraded rapidly in submerged soil but not in upland soil.

Atmospheric nitrogen fixation

Nitrogen-fixing activity in rice fields. We previously reported (1970 Annual Report) that, measured by the acetylene-reduction method, submerged soils have a greater capacity to fix atmospheric nitrogen than non-submerged soils during the wet season. We conducted the same experiment in the 1971 dry season and found that, as in the wet season, submerged soil has a greater capacity to fix atmospheric nitrogen than upland soil and that soils planted with rice have more nitrogen-fixing activity than unplanted soils (fig. 1). The nitrogen-fixing activity of submerged soil planted to IR20 started to increase about 7 to 9 weeks after transplanting and continued to increase until harvest through the ripening phase. Nitrogen-fixing activity was less in unplanted submerged soil than in the planted soil, particularly during the later stages of rice growth. Similarly, in the upland soil the nitrogen-fixing activity in soil planted to IR20 was higher than in the unplanted soil by 7 to 9 weeks after transplanting. It increased during the rest of the crop's growth. Nitrogen-fixing activity in the planted, upland soil, however, was about one-tenth less than that in the planted, submerged soil.

1. N₂-fixing activity, measured by C₂H₂-C₂H₄ assay in planted (rice variety IR20) and unplanted upland and submerged soils. IRRRI, 1971 dry season.

Nitrogen-fixing activity in washed roots was higher on a weight basis than that of soil or water (fig. 2). It was much higher in rice roots grown in submerged soil than in roots grown in upland soil conditions. From the fifth week after transplanting the nitrogen-fixing activity of the roots increased as the plants grew older.

Surface water may be an important site for nitrogen fixation in the field because it is directly in contact with the atmosphere and with sunlight which is necessary for photosynthetic nitrogen-fixing algae and bacteria. The nitrogen-fixing activity in the paddy water from an unplanted field did not differ much from that in the paddy water from a planted field during the dry season (fig. 3). Generally, nitrogen-fixing activity was higher for the submerged soil and paddy water during the dry season than in the wet season.

The amounts of nitrogen fixed in 1 hectare, estimated by using the theoretical conversion factor (C₂H₄:N₂ = 3:1), during the dry season are 79.8 kg/ha in planted, submerged fields; 42.5 kg/ha in unplanted, submerged fields; 5.4 kg/ha in the planted, upland fields; and 2.7 kg/ha in unplanted, upland fields. In the field, most nitrogen is fixed in soils during the reproductive and the ripening phases of rice growth.

2. N₂-fixing activity, measured by C₂H₂-C₂H₄ assay, in washed rice roots (rice variety IR20) grown in upland and submerged soils. IRRRI, 1971 dry season.

Soil samples taken from a planted field when the rice was at the reproductive phase were occupied by developed roots. At 50 days, or at about the tillering stage of rice, the rice roots showed the rhizosphere effect through the brown coloring around the roots which markedly contrasted with the black color of the surrounding soil (fig. 4). At this stage of growth the areas showing the rhizosphere effect were not yet large, however. Most of the soil areas became rhizosphere soil by 80 days after transplanting. Small blackish areas indicated that the soil remained reduced. Most of the soil samples which we took at the reproductive phase of rice (80 days after transplanting) can be considered as rhizosphere soil. We isolated bacteria from the rice rhizosphere on a nitrogen-free sucrose agar medium. All were positive in the $C_2H_2-C_2H_4$ assay, fixed atmosphere nitrogen, and grew in the nitrogen-free liquid medium.

The nitrogen-fixing activity of rice roots in association with soil bacteria in the rice rhizosphere was compared with three rice varieties, IR5, Peta, and M1-48, planted in fields under different water regimes. Nitrogen-fixing activity differed among the three varieties in submerged fields, but not in upland fields. In the paddy water, nitrogen-fixing activity was low, probably because of the small algal population in the newly reclaimed plots.

Measuring nitrogen fixation in the rhizosphere.

An experiment was performed to study the acetylene-reduction method for assaying nitrogen fixation in the rice rhizosphere. Since the nitrogen-fixing enzyme (nitrogenase) is sensitive to molecular oxygen, values derived from aerobic $C_2H_2-C_2H_4$ assay for the nitrogen-fixing activity of rice roots should give lower values than the real ones. To examine the effect of O_2 on the assay in the rice rhizosphere, 20 g of flooded Maahas clay soil were placed in a test tube (19.5 x 2.3 cm) with a pre-germinated IR20 seed. Three weeks later the surface water was poured out and the tubes were tightly closed with needle-puncture stoppers. The atmosphere in the tubes was adjusted to three different conditions: anaerobic ($P_{O_2} = 0.0$ atm), partially anaerobic ($P_{O_2} = 0.03$ atm), and aerobic ($P_{O_2} = 0.2$ atm). The rest of the atmosphere in the tubes was filled with argon and

3. N_2 -fixing activity, measured by $C_2H_2-C_2H_4$ assay, in paddy water of cropped (rice variety IR20) and uncropped fields. IRR1, 1971 dry season.

acetylene ($P_{C_2H_2} = 0.3$ atm). The samples were incubated at 30°C in the dark.

With oxygen in the intact soil-plant system, the acetylene reduction was almost linearly related to time during the first 7 hours of the assay. In the absence of O_2 , acetylene reduction showed a lag period, but became remarkably high after 7 hours. Whether the high ethylene production in the anaerobic $C_2H_2-C_2H_4$ assay was due to the nitrogen-fixing activity or to some factor not related to nitrogen-fixation is under investigation.

Nitrogen transformation

We previously showed by use of ^{15}N that nitrification and subsequent denitrification take place in the oxidized soil layer. The loss of fertilizer nitrogen was high in laboratory conditions. This year we conducted a greenhouse experiment to trace the fate of fertilizer nitrogen

4. Root development of rice and its influence on submerged soil at 50 days (left) and 80 days after transplanting. The rhizosphere effect is demonstrated by the different color (brown) development around the roots in the soil media (black).

under three water regimes: submerged, upland, and alternating upland and submerged.

Ten kilograms of Maahas clay soil were placed in glazed porcelain pots and subjected to different water management treatments. Nitrogen was added as ammonium sulfate (125 ppm N) and two pots of each treatment received ^{15}N -tagged fertilizer. Organic matter (rice straw) was added to half of the pots at the rate of 0.5 percent. The other pots were used as controls. All treatments were replicated three times. To determine the effect of nitrification on nitrogen transformation and the growth of rice, another set of pots was treated with the nitrogen fertilizer coated with N-Serve, a nitrification inhibitor.

For upland conditions the fertilizer and rice straw were mixed thoroughly with dry soil and then water was added until the soil reached field capacity. Two germinated IR5 seeds were planted in each pot. The soil was maintained at field capacity throughout the growth of the rice crop. For submerged conditions, the soil was puddled with fertilizer and rice straw, then two 14-day-old IR5 seedlings were transplanted into each pot. The soil was kept submerged throughout the growth of the plants. The pots for the alternating conditions were prepared similarly except that the soil was flooded for 1 week, then

the soil was drained and held at field capacity for 3 weeks. This pattern was repeated four times throughout the growth of the rice crop. Two 14-day-old IR5 seedlings were transplanted into each pot. Soil samples were taken every 4 weeks from all pots and were analyzed for exchangeable ammonium, nitrate, and organic nitrogen.

By a month after planting, most of the fertilizer nitrogen had converted to nitrate in the upland soil, but remained as ammonia in the submerged soil (fig. 5). The loss of nitrogen was highest in the alternating conditions. The immobilization of nitrogen increased steadily during the season in upland soil, but in submerged soil, immobilization reached a maximum 8 months after planting. Adding rice straw to the soils increased the microbial immobilization of nitrogen under all three soil conditions (fig. 6).

At harvest we found that in submerged soil the plant absorbed 51.7 percent of the tagged fertilizer nitrogen — 41.9 percent went to the panicles and 9.8 percent remained in the straw. The plants took up 37.0 percent of the fertilizer nitrogen when rice straw was added — 27.9 percent went to the panicles and 9.1 percent remained in the straw. The uptake of fertilizer nitrogen was much less under upland and

5. Tagged fertilizer N recovered from soil planted to rice without addition of rice straw under different water regimes.

alternating conditions — 26.1 percent of fertilizer nitrogen was taken up by rice plant under the upland soil condition and 28.3 percent under the alternating conditions. When rice straw was added to the soil, 16.1 percent of the fertilizer nitrogen was taken up by plants under the upland condition and 13.5 percent by plants under the alternating conditions. Much less fertilizer nitrogen was recovered in the panicles

of the rice plant under both these conditions than under the submerged conditions.

At harvest, the largest amounts of fertilizer were recovered from the soil and rice plants in submerged soil — 72 percent in the unamended soil and 82 percent in the soil amended with rice straw (Table 1). In the upland conditions 62 percent of fertilizer nitrogen was recovered in the unamended soil and 68 percent in the soil

6. Tagged fertilizer N recovered from soils planted to rice and amended with rice straw under different water regimes.

Table 1. Balance sheet of tagged fertilizer nitrogen in rice plants and soils at harvest under different water regimes and with and without application of rice straw in the greenhouse.

Water regime	Tagged N recovered (mg/pot)					Total	N recovery ^b (%)
	Plant		Soil				
	Straw	Panicles	Ammonium	Nitrate	Organic		
				<i>Control</i>			
Submerged	117	500	3.3	0.9	233	854	71.6
Upland	158	167	1.8	6.9	439	773	62.2
Alternating ^a	109	226	4.6	1.2	318	659	55.8
				<i>Rice straw added</i>			
Submerged	105	321	9.3	0.0	502	937	81.6
Upland	82	119	2.8	24.4	651	879	70.5
Alternating ^a	51	116	4.9	5.2	596	773	62.6

^a1 week submerged, then drained and maintained at field capacity for 3 weeks. ^bBased on the amount of tagged nitrogen measured in each pot at the start of the experiment.

amended with rice straw. Under the alternating conditions 56 percent was recovered in the amended soil and 66 percent in the soil amended with rice straw. A large amount of fertilizer nitrogen was immobilized in soils at harvest: 20 percent in the submerged conditions, 35 percent in the upland conditions, and 27 percent in the alternating conditions. When rice straw was added to the soil, more nitrogen was immobilized: 44 percent in the submerged conditions, 52 percent in the upland conditions, and 48 percent in the alternating soil conditions. The nitrogen usually is immobilized within a month after transplanting and remains in the organic fraction until harvest.

The total dry matter of IR5 in the experiment was highest in the submerged conditions. When rice straw was added to the submerged soil the growth of rice was greatly retarded. Application of ammonium sulfate, however, largely prevented the growth retardation. The amount of fertilizer nitrogen in the grain of rice plants grown in the flooded soil was remarkably high compared with the amount in the grain of rice grown in the upland or the alternating conditions. The ratio of fertilizer nitrogen to soil nitrogen found in straw and grain was highest in the upland conditions and lowest in the submerged conditions. The nitrogen ratio in the plant decreased when rice straw was added to the soil probably because nitrogen was released from rice straw during decomposition.

During the first 2 months after planting, N-Serve inhibited nitrification in upland conditions but had only a slight effect on the other

two soil conditions (fig. 7). The nitrogen content and dry-matter weight of rice plants grown in upland soils with fertilizers coated with N-Serve were higher than those of plants grown in soils with ordinary fertilizers. N-Serve did not affect plant growth and yield in the other two soil conditions, however.

Mineral transformation

Iron-reducing bacteria. To examine the role of bacteria in reducing iron in the rice rhizosphere, we tested germ-free rice roots grown in sterile mineral solutions and natural roots grown in submerged soils for iron-reducing activity. Twenty seeds of IR5 were dehulled and surface-sterilized. They were germinated in a Petri dish containing a solidified culture solution and placed in sterile test tubes. The germ-free seedlings were grown aseptically for 2 weeks under light in an incubation room. Nonsterile seedlings were prepared by broadcasting IR5 seeds on presubmerged Maahas clay in a pot. Two-week-old seedlings were washed with tap water to remove the soil from the roots. The roots of six seedlings each of sterile and nonsterile plants were submerged in a glucose-peptone solution containing hematite, incubated for 4 days, and analyzed for ferrous iron. The solution with the roots grown in soil had 1.5 mg ferrous iron per seedling while the solution with the germ-free roots had none. This result suggests that iron reduction in rice rhizosphere is mostly due to the activity of bacteria.

To examine the effect of above-ground plant

parts on the iron-reducing activity of roots, roots of 9-day-old rice seedlings grown in culture solution were immersed in the assay solution in a test tube and compared with roots detached from seedlings. The amount of reduced iron, per gram of fresh roots, after 5 days incubation at 30 C was 4.4 mg with attached roots and 21.9 mg with detached roots. Another experiment with seedlings grown in submerged soils also showed that more iron was reduced with detached roots than with attached roots. Thus the rice plants seemed to retard iron reduction in the rhizosphere.

The same method was used to test the iron-reducing activity of the soil. A soil suspension of one-tenth dilution was added to the assay solution and the amount of reduced iron was measured during incubation at 30 C for 7 days. The activity showed a 48-hour lag phase and reached a maximum in 5 days of incubation. To investigate the iron-reducing activity of submerged soils and the rice rhizosphere, 10 kg of Maahas clay soil (pH 6.4; organic matter, 2.6%; total nitrogen, 0.12%; active Fe, 2.91%; active Mn, 0.21%) and of Louisiana clay soil (pH 4.5; organic matter, 3.7%; total nitrogen, 0.17%; active Fe, 3.64%; active Mn, 0.17%) were mixed with fertilizers in pots and then submerged. Half the pots were planted with 2-week-old IR5 seedlings after 1 day of submergence. The iron-reducing activity of soil and

rhizosphere during the 6 weeks after flooding was tested by the method described above. Iron-reducing activity in the soil and roots was highest 2 weeks after submergence although the amount of ferrous iron in soil increased during the 6-week period. There was not much difference in the activity among treatments. The amount of ferrous iron in soil leachates increased continually after submergence for 6 weeks and was much larger in soils with rice straw than in the controls and in Louisiana soil than in Maahas soil. When Louisiana soil was planted to rice plants less ferrous iron accumulated than when it was unplanted.

Sulfur transformation. Soil microorganisms require sulfur for growth and they sometimes compete with higher plants for the element. The transformation of sulfur resembles the transformation of nitrogen: both elements are constituents of cell materials mostly as proteins. The concentrations of inorganic sulfur in soil are usually lower than those of organic sulfur, which is the major form of the element in soil. To study the effect of organic material on the transformation of sulfur in rice soil, 10 g of Maahas clay soil was mixed in flasks with 1 percent green manure or with green manure plus ammonium sulfate or ammonium chloride at 100 ppm N. The soil was submerged in distilled water. The flasks were covered with black cloth and incubated at 30 C. The depth

7. Effect of N-Serve on nitrogen transformations in soils planted to rice under different water regimes.

of the water was maintained by adding distilled water. Periodically up to 21 days after incubation, the samples were analyzed for acetate-soluble sulfate and organic sulfur.

After 21 days of incubation, 8 ppm of inorganic sulfur was present in soil with green manure, 9 ppm in soil with green manure plus ammonium chloride, and 11 ppm in soil with green manure plus ammonium sulfate, but soil without green manure had 63 ppm, soil with ammonium chloride had 62 ppm, and soil with ammonium sulfate had 166 ppm. The green manure application rapidly decreased the amount of inorganic sulfur in soil. But most converted to the organic form and the rest possibly to sulfides (Table 2).

Microbial influence on zinc availability. Several causes of zinc deficiency in the rice plant have been suggested by workers at IRRI (1970 Annual Report). Some of these, such as organic acid, bicarbonate, and P_{CO_2} are indirectly related to microbiological activity in the soil. In addition, bacteria in soil may compete with higher plants for zinc during their growth. We investigated the possibility of zinc immobilization by soil bacteria in a problem soil located in Bicol, Philippines.

Indigenous or applied organic matter in soil may be a major cause of zinc deficiency in rice. Organic materials in soil favor microbial growth. In the greenhouse, application of organic materials decreases the amount of available zinc in the soil and aggravates zinc deficiency in rice. We found that even glucose, which is a unit molecule of most carbohydrates and is commonly used for bacterial cultures, aggravated zinc deficiency in rice when applied to the submerged soil.

The effect of organic materials on the availability of zinc in flooded Libon soil (pH 6.5; organic matter, 8.9%; total nitrogen,

0.38%) was examined by using ^{65}Zn . Organic material was added at 0.5 percent as glucose, lactose, cellulose, green manure, or rice straw. The soil was anaerobically incubated and analyzed for available zinc. When glucose or lactose, which decompose easily, were applied, the available zinc in soil decreased rapidly within a day. Available zinc in soils with organic materials continued to decrease for at least 2 weeks after incubation. The amounts of available zinc in the soils compared with the control soil 2 weeks after incubation were 69.3% with glucose, 71.0% with lactose, 73.5% with green manure, 74.3% with rice straw, and 78.2% with cellulose. When nitrogen was added to the soil, the values decreased to 49.5% with lactose, 57.5% with glucose, 64.4% with rice straw, 66.6% with cellulose, and 66.7% with green manure. The data suggest that applying organic materials to soil causes immobilization of zinc by bacteria or by the chelation of zinc with metabolites produced by bacteria during degradation of the organic materials. The results also suggest that nitrogen application in addition to organic materials may increase the microbial immobilization of zinc.

Organic matter transformations

Formation of organic acids in submerged soil treated with green manure was investigated with two Mindanao soils by the gas chromatographic method. Clay soils collected from Mabini (pH 6.5; organic matter, 4.0%; total nitrogen, 0.2%) and Ampayon (pH 6.7; organic matter, 6.1%; total nitrogen, 0.32%) in Agusan province, Mindanao, were used in a laboratory experiment with Maahas clay soil as a control. Acetic, propionic, butyric, and iso-butyric acids formed in the three soils after anaerobic incubation with 5 percent fresh green manure at 30 C (Table 3). The acids attained peak levels between the fifth and seventh day of incubation. Acetic acid, the most dominant of the four acids, reached its peak level, more than 6 mmole/100 g soil, in the three soils within 3 to 5 days of incubation. Propionic, butyric, and iso-butyric acids attained their peaks by the seventh day of incubation. Propionic and butyric acids were present in smaller amounts than acetic acid but at their

Table 2. Changes in amount of sulfate S and organic sulfur in soil with green manure and inorganic nitrogen during 21 days of incubation at 30 C.

Soil treatment	Change in amt (ppm) of S in	
	Sulfate	Organic sulfur
Green manure	- 51	+ 36
Green manure + NH_4Cl	- 50	+ 39
Green manure + $(NH_4)_2SO_4$	-153	+112

Table 3. Accumulation of acetic, propionic, iso-butyric, and butyric acids in three submerged soils amended with green manure in N₂ atmosphere.

Incubation period (days)	Amt of organic acids (mmole/100 g soil)			
	Ac	Pr	iso-Bu	Bu
<i>Maahas clay</i>				
0	^a	0.00	0.00	0.00
3	4.66	0.28	0.12	0.65
5	6.20	0.54	0.20	0.18
7	3.78	1.37	0.24	1.32
9	0.29	0.88	0.10	0.14
13	0.08	0.77	^a	^a
<i>Mabini clay</i>				
0	^a	0.00	0.00	0.00
3	6.06	0.46	0.16	1.10
5	5.88	0.64	0.23	0.16
7	0.63	0.85	0.27	0.66
9	^a	^a	^a	^a
13	^a	^a	^a	^a
<i>Ampayon clay</i>				
0	^a	0.00	0.00	0.00
3	5.32	0.32	0.17	0.90
5	8.28	0.83	0.29	0.29
7	2.82	1.09	0.32	1.28
9	0.08	0.78	^a	^a
13	0.11	0.64	^a	^a

^aLess than 0.02 mmole.

Table 4. Accumulation of acetic (Ac), propionic (Pr), iso-butyric (iso-Bu), and butyric (Bu) acids in three submerged soils amended with green manure.

Incubation period (days)	Amt of organic acids (mmole/100 g soil)			
	Ac	Pr	iso-Bu	Bu
<i>Maahas clay</i>				
0	^a	0.00	0.00	0.00
3	2.00	0.20	^a	0.30
5	2.73	0.48	^a	0.30
7	2.21	0.55	^a	0.33
9	1.87	0.35	^a	0.17
13	0.11	0.38	^a	^a
<i>Mabini clay</i>				
0	^a	0.00	0.00	0.00
3	2.40	0.20	^a	0.44
5	2.40	0.58	^a	0.31
7	1.96	0.62	^a	0.13
9	1.40	0.40	^a	0.13
13	0.06	0.38	^a	^a
<i>Ampayon clay</i>				
0	^a	0.00	0.00	0.00
3	2.02	0.20	^a	0.38
5	2.43	0.45	^a	0.22
7	1.34	0.56	^a	0.16
9	0.56	0.40	^a	0.07
13	0.10	0.29	^a	^a

^aLess than 0.02 mmole.

peaks the levels were phytotoxic. Propionic acid was present until the 13th day of incubation. The levels of the acids generally were lower in the submerged soil (Table 4) than in the anaerobic soil (Table 3). The accumulation of isobutyric acid was negligible in the submerged soil.

In the greenhouse we attempted to determine if soil amended with fresh green manure produces toxic levels of organic acids in submerged soil as well as in anaerobic soil and to determine if applying ammonium sulfate with green manure retards the accumulation of the organic acids. We found that when fresh green manure was applied to Maahas soil at 2.5 percent, organic acid production reached a toxic level (Table 5). A small amount of butyric acid was found, but no iso-butyric acid was detected. The lower volatile fatty acids are toxic to rice seedlings even in neutral soils at 0.5 mmole/100 g soil in greenhouse conditions (1970 Annual Report). Thus, the soil amended with green manure had high amounts of acid for 19 days. Adding ammonium sulfate and green manure to the soil retarded the production of all the

acids. Ammonium chloride did not cause much change in the pattern of acid formation resulting from application of green manure. We found that the application of ammonium sulfate re-

Table 5. Amount of acetic, propionic, and butyric acids in submerged Maahas clay soil amended with fresh green manure (2.5%) with and without ammonium sulfate under greenhouse conditions.

Days after transplanting	Amt of organic acids (mmole/100 g soil)		
	Ac	Pr	Bu
<i>Green manure</i>			
0	^a	0.00	0.00
2	0.63	0.06	0.09
5	0.78	0.06	^a
8	0.54	0.04	^a
12	0.15	0.02	^a
19	0.26	0.01	^a
26	0.04	^a	^a
<i>Green manure + (NH₄)₂SO₄</i>			
0	^a	0.00	0.00
2	0.10	^a	^a
5	0.46	0.03	^a
8	0.18	^a	^a
12	0.21	^a	^a
19	0.21	^a	^a
26	0.04	^a	^a

^aLess than 0.02 mmole.

8. Growth of rice plant in submerged soils treated with various inorganic chemicals and organic materials.

duced the injurious effect of the organic acids. The grain and straw yields were highest with ammonium sulfate, followed in descending order by yields from green manure plus ammonium sulfate, control, and green manure.

To study the cause of the beneficial effect of ammonium sulfate on rice growth in submerged soils amended with green manure and cellulose, we added various inorganic chemicals to Maahas clay soils amended with the organic materials. Figure 8 shows the growth of IR8 at 55 days after transplanting. The injurious effect on rice growth of applying powder of 1.0 percent green manure or 0.5 percent cellulose to soil was decreased if ammonium sulfate, potassium

sulfate, sulfur, or potassium nitrate was applied with the organic materials. The application of organic matter and a sulfur compound increases the number of sulfate-reducing bacteria in submerged soil. The change in bacterial population in submerged soil caused by adding the sulfur compound may change the fermentation pattern of the organic substrate which favors the growth of the rice plant. The anaerobic degradation of organic substrate by *Desulfovibrio*, a group of sulfate-reducing bacteria, leads to the production of acetic acid as an end-product. The sulfate-reducing bacteria may compete with propionic- and butyric-acid-producing bacteria for carbohydrates in the

soil. The addition of nitrate to submerged soil probably kept the soil's oxidation-reduction potential higher in the early days after submergence during which the fermentation of organic materials was retarded. Or, denitrifying bacteria used organic acids produced in soils as a substrate.

Microflora in submerged soil

The number of aerobic bacteria, anaerobic bacteria, denitrifiers, and fungi in the rice rhizosphere was determined at 2, 11, 17, and 40 days after transplanting in Maahas clay in the greenhouse. The number of fungi decreased within 2 days after the soil was submerged. Afterwards no significant change in population occurred, suggesting that the fungi were mostly inactive in the soil. Glass slides buried in the submerged soil for 10 days showed no hyphal growth of fungi. But the thin hyphal structure of actinomycetes was observed on the slides under the microscope. Other slides buried in soil in which several seedlings of rice were transplanted showed traces of root growth, but only a negligible amount of hyphal growth.

The population of aerobic bacteria, including facultatively anaerobic bacteria, in the rhizosphere soil markedly increased 2 days after transplanting. In soils treated with green manure or cellulose, the population of aerobic bacteria in the rhizosphere soil was several thousand times greater than that in the initial soil samples. The nonrhizosphere soil had 200 times more aerobic bacteria than the initial soil samples. The number of aerobic bacteria decreased, however, to 10^6 /g soil by 11 days after transplanting and remained at that level thereafter.

In contrast to the total aerobic bacteria, the number of anaerobic bacteria did not increase rapidly during the early growth stages of the plant. But it increased gradually until 40 days after transplanting. Green-manure treatment resulted in a significantly higher number of anaerobic bacteria in the rhizosphere soil than did the cellulose treatment. The number of denitrifiers in the rhizosphere soil also increased soon after transplanting, then gradually decreased. Adding ammonium sulfate did not significantly increase any of the microbial

populations. The soil with green manure and ammonium sulfate had the highest population of sulfate-reducers, however.

Insecticide degradation

Bacterium that degrades parathion and diazinon.

A bacterium that degrades diazinon and parathion was isolated from paddy water. The bacterium is a gram-negative flagellate, and facultative anaerobe (fig. 9). The bacterium was identified as *Flavobacterium* sp. based on morphological and biochemical characteristics. One-tenth milliliter of cell suspension was added to 4 ml of mineral solution containing ^{14}C -diazinon. The inoculation mixture was held at 30 C in a test tube. At the start of the experiment and at 24 and at 72 hours after incubation, the incubation mixture was extracted twice with chloroform-diethyl ether and analyzed for metabolites by thinlayer chromatography. In a separate experiment, the $^{14}\text{CO}_2$ evolved from

9. Diazinon-degrading bacteria, *Flavobacterium* sp. (x 50,000). (Courtesy of Dr. S. Tsuru).

the inoculation mixture was trapped in sodium hydroxide solution.

We found that the bacterium degraded most of the diazinon within 24 hours of incubation; 66 percent of the added radioactivity was recovered as 2-isopropyl-6-methyl-4-hydroxypyrimidine (IMHP), a hydrolysis product of diazinon (Table 6). IMHP could not be detected at 72 hours after incubation, however. More than 30 percent of the total radioactivity was recovered as $^{14}\text{CO}_2$, which indicates the cleavage of the pyrimidine ring. The ring cleavage was confirmed by the spectrographic analysis of the solutions: the ultraviolet absorption at 229 $\text{m}\mu$ was lost after 72 hours of incubation. The bacterium decomposed diazinon under both aerobic and anaerobic conditions but more rapidly under aerobic conditions than under anaerobic conditions. The pyrimidine ring of IMHP was disrupted only under aerobic conditions.

We also tested the ability of the bacterium to decompose parathion, an organophosphorus insecticide related to diazinon. We inoculated a cell suspension of the bacterium into a mineral solution containing parathion. At 1 and 24 hours of incubation the solution was analyzed for parathion and intermediate compounds by thin-layer and gas-liquid chromatography. Chloroform-diethyl extracts were spotted on silica-gel plates alongside authentic *p*-nitrophenol and parathion. Analysis of the incubation mixture by gas-liquid chromatography showed that parathion was completely lost from the incubation mixture within 1 hour of its incubation with living cells. This loss was accompanied by the formation of *p*-nitrophenol, as determined by thin-layer chromatography.

Table 6. Metabolism of ^{14}C -diazinon by *Flavobacterium* sp. in a mineral solution.

Incubation time (hr)	Recovery of ^{14}C (1×10^3 count/min)			
	Diazinon		IMHP ^a	
	Inoculated	Uninoculated	Inoculated	Uninoculated
0	40.8	43.0	1.7	1.9
24	2.3	41.3	27.2	1.7
72	0.1	39.7	0.0	1.7

^aHydrolysis product of diazinon, 2-isopropyl-6-methyl-4-hydroxypyrimidine.

Both the metabolite and authentic *p*-nitrophenol had identical R_f values, 0.67, in analysis by thin-layer chromatography, and showed the maximum absorption at 400 $\text{m}\mu$ in the spectrographic analysis. By 1 hour of incubation with living cells, most of the parathion converted to *p*-nitrophenol. Thus the parathion was readily cleaved at P-O-C bond and formed *p*-nitrophenol and, probably, diethylthiophosphoric acid. At 24 hours after incubation, the amount of *p*-nitrophenol in the medium decreased. The results indicate that the diazinon-degrading bacterium degrades parathion primarily through a hydrolytic pathway with the formation of *p*-nitrophenol as a major metabolite, and not through nitro-reduction.

To determine whether the enzyme involved in the biodegradation of diazinon and parathion is constitutive or adaptive, the bacterium was grown in a mineral solution containing 0.5 percent yeast extract with 10 ppm diazinon or without diazinon. Fifty milliliters of the medium in flasks were inoculated with the bacteria and incubated. The cells grown in diazinon and the cells grown on a medium without diazinon readily decomposed both diazinon and parathion without a lag phase, indicating that the enzyme involved in the degradation is constitutive. Cell-free extracts of the bacteria degraded diazinon, parathion, and dursban, but not malathion.

Parathion degradation in submerged soils.

Parathion is persistent in aerobic soils. Its persistence in four soils of the Philippines was investigated in upland and submerged conditions. Air-dried Maahas clay, Luisiana clay, Casiguran sandy loam (pH 4.8; organic matter, 4.4%; total nitrogen, 0.2%), and Pila clay loam (pH 7.6; organic matter, 1.5%; total nitrogen, 0.09%) were used. At the start of the experiment and at 7 and 14 days after incubation, the soil samples in three replications were extracted with hexane-acetone solution. Parathion extracted by the solvent was quantitatively analyzed by gas-liquid chromatography. During the 2 weeks of incubation, no appreciable degradation of parathion occurred in the soils under upland conditions (fig. 10). In contrast, most of the insecticide added to submerged soil was rapidly decomposed. The insecticide de-

10. Degradation of parathion in four Philippine soils under upland and submerged conditions.

graded faster in submerged Casiguran and Maahas soil than in submerged Pila and Luisiana soil. By 14 days of incubation, however, most of the insecticide had disappeared from all four submerged soils. This result indicates that parathion is less persistent in submerged soils than in upland soils. The degradation of parathion was mostly the result of bacterial activity since parathion disappeared more rapidly from nonautoclaved submerged soil samples than from autoclaved submerged soil samples.

Gas chromatograms of hexane extracts revealed that aminoparathion was formed during the degradation of parathion in submerged soils. Submerging soils may accelerate the formation of aminoparathion since the anaerobic conditions may favor the reduction of nitro-nitrogen in parathion to amino-nitrogen.

Organochlorine insecticide residues. To assess the possible accumulation of the insecticides lindane, Dol granule, and DDT in rice soils, lindane or Dol granules was broadcast at 6 kg/ha a.i. 10, 40, and 70 days after transplanting IR20 in field plots. A DDT suspension containing 0.2 percent active ingredient was sprayed at the rate of 1,900 liter/ha (500 gal/ha) with a commercial sticker at the same time as lindane and Dol granules. At harvest, samples of paddy water, soil, and plants were analyzed for insecticide residues.

Paddy water in lindane-treated plots contained an average of 2 ppb γ -BHC while the

plots treated with Dol granule contained an average of 2.7 ppb γ -BHC. More of the other BHC isomers were found in the plots treated with Dol granule than in the lindane-treated plots.

In the soil, γ -BHC ranged from 2 to 87 ppb (36 ppb, average) in the lindane-treated plots. The amount of γ -BHC in the plots treated with Dol granules, ranged from 8 to 180 ppb (80 ppb average); the amount of α -BHC averaged 615 ppb; β -BHC, 262 ppb; δ -BHC, 202 ppb.

The concentrations of BHC were much higher in rice straw and roots than in soils. Rice straw in lindane-treated plots averaged 1.2 ppm γ -BHC and plots treated with Dol granule averaged 1.5 ppm. Rice straw harvested in the plots treated with Dol granule contained levels of other isomers of BHC about 5 to 10 times as high as those of γ -BHC. The amount of γ -BHC varied from 2 to 101 ppb (31 ppb, average) in milled grains from lindane-treated plots and 9 to 195 ppb (180 ppb, average) in milled grain from plots treated with Dol granule. Only α -BHC and γ -BHC were found in grains.

No measurable amount of DDT was found in the paddy water of the DDT-treated plots. About 1 ppm was found in the soil of the DDT-treated plots. The rice plant had a large amount of residue, especially the upper portion since DDT was applied as a foliar spray. The average amounts of DDT in roots was 4 ppm; in the lower portions, 25 ppm; and in upper portions

45 ppm. But DDT found in milled grains ranged from 15 to 178 ppb (50 ppb, average).

Herbicide degradation

The degradation of 2,4-D and 2,4,5-T in submerged Maahas clay soil was examined under aerobic and anaerobic conditions. For the aerobic condition the sample was incubated on a shaker at 30 C. For the anaerobic condition nitrogen was introduced into the solution for 10 minutes, then the system was closed and the sample was incubated at 30 C. The soil particles were centrifuged and samples of the soil suspensions were analyzed periodically for 2,4-D or 2,4,5-T. Ultraviolet spectrometry was used for chemical analysis with absorption peaks of 283 $m\mu$ for 2,4-D and 288 $m\mu$ for 2,4,5-T. By 15 days of incubation no 2,4-D was found in the soil suspension under either aerobic and anaero-

bic conditions. In contrast, no significant change was observed for 30 days of incubation in amounts of 2,4,5-T.

Algal control

Previously we found that Dichlone 50 WP effectively controlled algal growth in direct-seeded rice (1970 Annual Report). Since the chemical is known also as a fungicide, several agricultural fungicides were tested for control of algae in direct-seeded rice. One day after harrowing and fertilizing plots we seeded pre-germinated IR20 at 50 kg/ha. On the third day after seeding we sprayed the chemicals with a boom sprayer at 0.5, 1, 3, and 6 kg/ha. The seedling stand 1 month later indicated that Benlate, Manzate, and copper sulfate can effectively control algae. The best control of algae resulted from Dichlone WP at 6 kg/ha.

Soil chemistry

Of 52 varieties tested for adaptability to three aerobic soils, on the average, M1-48, E425, and IR661-1-170 performed best. Peta, a typical lowland indica, was the worst. M1-48 and the IR661 line did uniformly well, and Peta, uniformly badly on the acid, neutral, and alkaline soils; E425 fared relatively poorly on the acid soil. Among 80 varieties screened for resistance to iron toxicity, IR20, IR22, IR665-8-3, and H 4 were the least susceptible; IR5, IR8, IR424-21-PK2, and IR878B4-220-3 were among the most susceptible. Of 98 varieties, IR5, IR20, IR22, H 4 and IR400-5-12 were most resistant to phosphorus deficiency; IR8, Dawn, IR498-42-1, IR626-1-112, and IR878B4-220-3 were the least resistant. Twenty-nine of 32 varieties grown on a zinc-deficient soil perished within 5 weeks of transplanting, but IR5, IR20, and H 4 survived. IR20 and H 4 were the best of 92 varieties in resistance to reduction products; the upland varieties, along with IR5 and IR8, performed the worst. The improved variety adapted to the widest range of adverse soil conditions was IR20.

Zinc deficiency occurred on alkaline soils and, regardless of pH, on continuously wet soils. Zinc extractable in EDTA and ammonium carbonate was a good measure of its availability to rice. Both soils and plants that were zinc deficient had a high magnesium content.

A nutritional disorder of rice on an acid ferrallitic soil from Colombia was diagnosed as iron toxicity and corrected by liming. The problems with two sandy soils from Badeggi and Agaie, Nigeria, were largely severe deficiencies of N, P, and K, and, in the Agaie sandy loam, zinc deficiency, too.

Studies on acid sulfate soils showed that some may be improved by leaching; others, by liming.

Varietal resistance to injurious soils

Rice breeders have used genetic variability to produce varieties that have the right plant type and that can tolerate cold, disease, insects, drought, and even floods. But apart from testing and breeding rice varieties for resistance to the straighthead disease of rice and some selecting for resistance to salinity, little has been done to identify and breed varieties adapted to adverse soil conditions that cannot be easily corrected by management. Among such unfavorable soil conditions are strong acidity, alkalinity, salinity, iron deficiency, iron toxicity, phosphorus deficiency (in soils that fix P strongly), and certain effects of oxidation or reduction. If the natural genetic resistance that some varieties may have to these conditions can be combined with the right plant type and resistance to pests, it may be possible to produce improved varieties suited to these soil conditions. Preliminary tests indicate that varietal differences exist in resistance to growth-limiting factors in aerobic soils, to iron toxicity, to phosphorus and zinc deficiency, and to reduction products.

Aerobic soils. The poor yield of rice on non-flooded fields is usually attributed to water stress and weed competition. But we found (1970 Annual Report) that even in the absence

1. Changes in redox potential and soil moisture tension of three soils.

of water stress and weeds, rice yields less in aerobic than in anaerobic soils. We identified the main retarding factors in aerobic soils at field capacity as iron deficiency on neutral and alkaline soils, and manganese and aluminum toxicity on acid soils fertilized with ammonium sulfate. Since the severity of iron deficiency decreases while that of manganese toxicity increases as pH decreases, a calcareous soil, a neutral soil, and an acid soil, all at field capacity, were used to screen varieties for resistance to factors that limit yield in aerobic soils.

Two common drawbacks of field experiments with upland rice are the absence of quantitative data on two important parameters — redox potential and soil moisture tension (redox potential reveals whether a soil is aerobic or anaerobic; soil moisture tension indicates the degree of moisture stress). In the absence of the control and the measurement of these two factors, yield differences among varieties depend on the rainfall pattern and cannot be related to resistance to the growth-limiting factors in aerobic soils. For this reason, we controlled and measured both factors.

We conducted a screening test in three concrete tanks, each 10.8 x 8.3 x 0.3 m, and filled with air-dry Louisiana clay (pH 4.6, organic matter, 3.2%), Maahas clay (pH 6.9, organic matter, 2.4%), or Maahas clay limed to pH 7.6. To maintain the soils at field capacity, we installed sprinklers above the tanks and fitted drainage pipes at the bottom. The seedbed was prepared, fertilizer at 100 kg/ha N, 50 kg/ha P, and 50 kg/ha K was broadcast, and pre-soaked seedlings of 45 varieties were sown in furrows 20 cm apart. We grouped the tall varieties together and at later growth stages they were supported to prevent lodging. Eight tensiometers and eight platinum electrodes were set 10 cm deep in each tank. We took the tensiometer readings daily at 2 PM and redox potentials, weekly. The soil moisture tension was kept at 0.1 to 0.2 atm. The low soil moisture tension and the strongly positive redox potentials observed (fig. 1) showed that the soils were moist but aerobic.

The two top yielders were the upland varieties M1-48 and E425; the lowest was Peta, a typical lowland variety (Table 1). IR5, which has been

Table 1. Mean yields (per linear meter) on three aerobic soils.

Variety or selection	Yield (g/m)	
	Grain	Straw
M1-48	151	247
E425	120	228
IR661-1-170	119	133
PI 215936	105	163
IR577-11-2	102	123
IR127-80-1	102	147
Taichung Native 1	101	156
CI 5094-1	99	257
IR12-178-2	99	143
IR24	94	126
IR305-3-17	92	122
IR130-136	90	133
IR159B3-1	89	195
IR424-21-PK2	89	161
IR759-53-5	88	137
IR773-112-2	88	113
CP231 x SLO-17	85	133
IR20	81	130
IR262-43-8	81	130
IR789-8-3	81	146
IR22	72	106
Azmil 26	70	170
IR790-5-1	70	135
IR648-2-8	69	124
Nira	69	171
Dickwee 328	68	243
IR8	68	151
Azucena	65	163
C4-63G	61	174
Palawan	60	165
Texas Patna	56	263
Milfor	55	182
IR5	53	284
Agbede	51	132
Dima	50	293
Pinulot 330	50	155
IR159B2-3-1	49	111
IR878B4-220-3	48	168
Dinalaga	47	165
M1-139	36	232
Original Century Patna	32	97
Century Patna 231	32	96
IR332-2-10	32	210
Peta	14	462

reported to yield well as an upland rice, was 34th in rank among the 45 varieties tested because it suffered severely from iron deficiency on limed Maahas clay and from manganese toxicity on Luisiana clay. On Maahas clay, however, it had the fifth highest yield. In spite of good vegetative growth, Peta, Dima, Texas Patna, M1-329, and IR332-2-10, on the average, produced little grain. The Philippine upland varieties, Azmil 26, Azucena, Palawan, and

Table 2. Comparison of grain yields (per linear meter) of 15 varieties on three aerobic soils at field capacity.

Variety	Luisiana clay		Maahas clay		Limed Maahas clay	
	Yield (g/m)	Rank	Yield (g/m)	Rank	Yield (g/m)	Rank
M1-48	138	1	154	1	161	1
IR661-1-170	129	2	116	4	115	5
IR577-11-2	104	4	111	7	91	11
IR127-80-1	109	3	104	11	92	9
CP231 x SLO-17	82	15	91	20	83	17
IR22	69	25	77	28	71	26
C4-63G	52	33	74	30	58	30
M1-329	21	45	50	42	36	42
Original Century Patna	18	46	45	44	34	43
Peta	6	48	28	46	9	46
Taichung Native 1	82	16	118	3	104	6
E425	83	15	150	2	124	2
IR24	76	21	112	6	94	8
IR20	87	12	108	8	48	34
IR5	42	35	113	5	3	47

Dinalaga, produced moderate amounts of straw but little grain.

Most varieties roughly maintained their relative ranks on all three soils but there were some variety-soil interactions (Table 2). On all three soils, M1-48 was the top yielder, IR22, a moderate yielder, and Peta, the lowest yielder. But Taichung Native 1, E425, and IR24 fared badly on Luisiana clay compared with their performance on Maahas clay and limed Maahas clay. IR5 did much better on Maahas clay than on the other two soils.

The upland variety M1-48, in spite of its moderate height and poor tillering, produced the highest yield of grain on the acid, neutral, and calcareous soils. The Nigerian upland variety E425 yielded almost as much as M1-48 on the neutral soil, but had low yield on the acid soil. Of the IRRI lines, only IR661-1-170 approached M1-48 in yield.

M1-48, E425, IR661-1-170, and IR424-21-PK2 were greener than the others and showed no signs of iron deficiency or manganese toxicity. A healthy green color may be a sign of adaptability to aerobic soils that are not under water stress.

A test of 12 selected varieties in the wet season was spoiled by bad weather, pests, and diseases. Once again, however, a soil-variety interaction was clearly discernible. The conclusions (Table

3) agree with those of the earlier experiment.

Ten of the promising varieties were grown in an unreplicated observational experiment on an acid sloping soil, without bunds, in a farmer's field in Laguna province (Philippines) in the 1971 wet season. The plots received 100 kg/ha N, 50 kg/ha P, and 20 t/ha of straw compost. The rainfall was above average and fairly well distributed except for a brief dry spell in August. The slope of the field precluded waterlogging and anaerobic conditions. Thus, in the absence of pest damage, it was not surprising that the relative performance of the varieties paralleled their performance on Luisiana clay at field capacity in the controlled experiment. The selection IR661-1-170, which heads the list in Table 4, gave the second highest yield in the earlier experiment (Table 2); E425 and IR24 had low yields. The low-tillering M1-48 might have been beaten IR661-1-170 if it had been planted at closer spacing. The grain yield would have been higher but for bad weather and mild nitrogen deficiency in the seedling stage.

Intermittently aerobic soils. Rainfed paddy fields cover more than 50 percent of the rice area in Asia. These fields are banded, puddled, and direct seeded or transplanted. If rainfall is less than evapotranspiration, the fields dry, crack, and become oxidized. As a result, rice plants suffer from moisture stress, root pruning, and nutritional deficiencies or toxicities. The response of 12 varieties to these unfavorable soil conditions was observed in a field experiment on Maahas clay in the wet season. Because

ammonium sulfate was expected to alleviate iron deficiency when the soil turned aerobic, we included ammonium sulfate and urea as sub-treatments.

The rainfall was well distributed and the soil was almost saturated for the first 6 weeks. Redox potentials indicated that the soil was anaerobic. During the seventh and 12th week after seeding, the soil dried, the soil moisture tension rose to 0.2 atm, and redox potentials became strongly positive. Then the plots were irrigated. An outbreak of tungro spoiled the experiment. IR20, which of the 12 varieties is most resistant to tungro, gave the highest grain yield (4.2 t/ha). Two short periods of water stress and of soil oxidation apparently did not harm IR20 on Maahas clay. Although the pH values of the plots treated with ammonium-sulfate were on the average 0.1 unit lower than those of the urea-treated plots, there was no significant difference in the yield of straw or grain at 125 kg/ha of N.

Iron toxicity. Iron toxicity is a widespread physiological disorder of paddy rice. It occurs on strongly acid ferrallitic (lateritic) soils in India, Ceylon, Thailand, Malaysia, Indonesia, the Philippines, Senegal, and perhaps Colombia. Iron toxicity is also one of the main impediments to rice growth on acid sulfate soils, of which there are more than 15 million hectares in Asia alone. Since liming, perhaps the best remedy, may not always be economic, the possibility of selecting and breeding resistant varieties was investigated.

In the dry season, we grew 54 varieties outdoors in pots containing a lateritic soil (1970 Annual Report) that built up water-soluble iron concentrations exceeding 400 ppm and induced iron toxicity even in the presence of adequate amounts of phosphorus and potassium.

All plants showed signs of iron toxicity, but the degree and expression of the symptoms differed among varieties. The discoloration of the leaves ranged from light orange through orange and brown to purple. Some varieties showed marked leaf rolling, others little. The symptoms varied even within lines from the same cross. For example, IR759-79-2 had light orange leaves while IR759-54-2 had purple leaves; IR790-28-5 showed severe leaf scorch

Table 3. Relative suitability of 12 rice varieties to aerobic soil conditions assumed to be related to pH.

Variety	Suitability to soil conditions ^a		
	Acid	Neutral	Alkaline
IR5	x	✓	x
IR20	✓	✓	x
IR24	✓	✓	x
IR305-3-17	✓	✓	x
IR332-2-10	✓	x	x
IR661-1-170	✓	✓	✓
IR424-21-PK2	✓	✓	✓
Taichung Native 1	✓	✓	✓
PI 215936	x	✓	✓
Peta	x	x	x
M1-48	✓	✓	✓
E425	x	✓	✓

^a✓ = suitable; x = unsuitable.

while IR790-54-1 exhibited severe bronzing. Based on grain yield, the varieties least susceptible to iron toxicity were IR22, H 4, IR95-43-13, IR506-1-89, H 105, and RD 17-1-3. Among the susceptible varieties were RD-3, IR20, and IR24. Among the very susceptible varieties were IR661-1-170, Palawan, and RD-1. Among the highly susceptible varieties were IR8, E425, and IR5.

A better measure of resistance to iron toxicity would be the yield on the ferrallitic soil relative to the yield on a good soil like Maahas clay. So 56 varieties were grown side by side on the two soils in pots in the greenhouse. The grain yield, both absolute and relative to Maahas clay, paralleled the visual symptoms of iron toxicity (fig. 2).

The eight least susceptible varieties were Dima, IR665-8-3, BG79, RD-1, IR506-1-89, IR22, Sigadis, and RD-17-1. On the ferrallitic soil these varieties gave 30 to 45 percent of the yield on Maahas clay. Five of the varieties were bred in countries where strongly acid ferrallitic soils are widespread.

The susceptible varieties included H 8, Tadu-kan, PI 215936, IR20, IR24, LD27, IR661-1-170, IR262-43-8, H 4, RD-3, IR790-5-1, IR400-5-12, and Taichung Native 1. They gave relative yields of 15 to 30 percent.

The following varieties yielded less than 7 g of grain per pot or less than 8 percent of the yield on Maahas clay: CP231, IR95-43-17, Wagwag, IR790-28-2, IR8, IR589-66-2, IR759-53-5, PD46, IR790-28-5, IR878B4-220-3, and IR424-21-PK2. The last variety died on the ferrallitic soil 6 weeks after planting (fig. 2), but gave 99 g of

Table 4. Grain and straw yields of 10 varieties of rice on an upland soil (pH 4.9). Laguna, Philippines, 1971 wet season.

Variety or selection	Yield (t/ha)	
	Grain	Straw
IR661-1-170	3.4	3.5
IR12-178-2	3.0	4.1
M1-48	2.3	3.8
IR20	2.2	2.8
CI 5094-1	2.2	4.0
IR140-136	2.2	2.0
IR127-80-1	2.1	2.5
IR24	2.1	2.9
PI 215936	1.5	2.4
E425	1.1	2.5

grain per pot on Maahas clay. This group of varieties is highly susceptible to excess iron.

The fairly consistent behavior of the varieties that have been grown in several experiments makes possible their classification into two extreme groups according to susceptibility to iron toxicity: *least susceptible* — IR20, IR22, IR262-43-8, IR506-1-89, IR665-8-3, H 4; *most susceptible* — IR5, IR8, IR424-21-PK2, IR759-79-2, IR790-28-1, IR878B4-220-3.

Phosphorus deficiency. Phosphorus deficiency limits the growth of rice on vast areas of lateritic and acid sulfate soils, which not only are low in available P but also fix fertilizer phosphate as highly insoluble minerals. In these soils, the increase in availability of phosphorus brought about by soil submergence is slight. The phosphate fertilizer needs of such soils can be reduced if varieties that can extract phosphorus more efficiently can be developed. Since phosphorus deficiency and iron toxicity often go together

2. Degrees of susceptibility to iron toxicity. Left: IR665-8-3, least. Middle: Peta, intermediate. Right: IR424-21-PK2, most.

but can occur independently, the soil used for screening should be deficient in phosphorus but should not induce iron toxicity. Fifty-two rice varieties were grown outdoors on such a soil, Luisiana clay, (pH 4.6; organic matter, 3.2%) in pots fertilized with 100 ppm N and 50 ppm K.

The following yielded at least 50 percent more grain than IR8: IR20, IR22, IR665-58-2, IR790-28-2, IR790-28-1, IR790-28-6, IR879-183-2, IR1168-21-3, H 105, and H 4. The selection IR878B4-220-3 yielded 50 percent less than IR8. E425 yielded practically no grain at all.

In a parallel experiment, 52 varieties were planted in rows on flooded Luisiana clay in outdoor concrete tanks in the dry season. Unseasonally heavy rains and several typhoons damaged some rows and depressed the grain yield of all varieties. Of the 37 varieties harvested, nine yielded more than IR8. One, IR1006-28-6, yielded nearly three times as much as IR8. Seven of the IRRI lines that outyielded IR8 had BPI-76 as one of the parents. None of the varieties that were inferior to IR8 had BPI-76 as a parent.

In the wet season, bad weather and pests and diseases spoiled a test of 12 varieties for resistance to phosphorus deficiency. In spite of bacterial streak disease, IR790-28-2 gave the highest yield (5.0 t/ha). This selection also had the top yield in the pot experiment during the dry season. On the other hand, IR498-42-1, though disease-free, yielded only 2.9 t/ha. It was one of the lowest yielders in the previous season. Because of disease and insect injury other comparisons are not valid. It is, however, noteworthy that IR20, IR22, IR400-5-12, IR790-28-2, and IR1168-21-3, all of which outyielded IR8 in the pot experiment during the dry season, remained superior to IR8 even in the wet season.

As grain yield on a phosphorus-deficient soil alone is not a safe criterion of resistance to phosphorus deficiency, we observed the performance of 44 varieties with and without 50 kg/ha of P in an unreplicated trial in a farmer's field in the wet season in Laguna province (Philippines) on an irrigated paddy soil believed to be phosphorus deficient.

Almost all varieties responded positively to the phosphate application, but both the yield without phosphorus and the response to phos-

phorus varied greatly. RD-1, IR5-81-3, IR937-76-2, IR5, IR874B2-121-3, and IR1170-261-3 produced 5.5 to 6.6 t/ha of grain and gave no significant response to phosphate. Varieties that yielded about 5.5 t/ha without P and increased their yields by 10 to 20 percent when P was added included IR937-55-3, IR937-76-2, IR24, and IR878B2-83-3. The following yielded 3.5 to 4.5 t/ha without phosphate fertilizer and gave responses of 26 to 44 percent to added P: IR506-1-38, IR626-1-112, IR751-59, IR759-54-2, IR878B1-15-2, and IR878B4-220-3. Four of these low yielding, phosphorus-responsive lines were rated as susceptible to phosphorus deficiency in one or the other of the two previous experiments.

The combined results of these experiments on flooded Luisiana clay makes the following provisional grouping possible: *resistant* — IR5, IR20, IR22, H 4, H 105, IR400-5-12, IR790-28-1, IR790-28-2, IR878B2-121-3, IR937-55-3, IR937-76-2, IR1163-153-1, IR1163-142-3, IR1170-261-3; *susceptible*—Dawn, IR8, IR498-42-1, IR506-1-38, IR626-1-112, IR759-54-2, IR759-79-2, IR878B2-71-2, IR878B4-220-3.

Reduction products. When a soil is submerged and the oxygen supply is cut off, soil microorganisms use oxidized soil components such as nitrate, manganese dioxide, ferric oxide, sulfate, and even organic metabolites as electron acceptors in their respiration. As a result, nitrate is reduced to nitrogen gas, and manganic and ferric oxides are reduced to manganous and ferrous compounds which are highly soluble. Also, organic reduction products may accumulate and poison the rice plant or cause nutritional disorders. Since the obvious remedy of draining and re-oxidizing the soil is not always feasible, varietal resistance to these reduction products merits study.

We have in our collection of problem soils a soil (Tungshan silt loam) from Taiwan on which a nutritional disorder known as "suffocation" disease occurs. The symptoms of the disease are stunting and a brownish discoloration of the leaves. The disease occurs only when the soil is submerged and is corrected by the application of such retardants of soil reduction as nitrate and manganese dioxide (1965 Annual Report). It is not caused by excess iron: the symptoms

differ from those of iron toxicity and the soil solution does not contain harmful levels of iron. Thus the disease appears to be due to unknown organic reduction products. Tungshan silt loam was therefore used for testing varieties for resistance to harmful reduction products.

The upland variety Palawan showed the most acute symptoms and yielded no grain at all. H 4 showed mild symptoms and produced the third highest grain yield. The 10 most resistant varieties were IR20, IR22, IR95-43-13, IR400-5-12, IR24, IR937-76-2, IR874B2-121-3, IR790-28-1, H 4, and H 105. The least resistant varieties included IR5, IR8, IR879-183-2, IR878B4-220-3, E425, Azucena, and Palawan. In an earlier experiment (1969 Annual Report) the upland varieties, Dinalaga, Azucena, and Palawan yielded poorly on the same soil although they gave some of the highest yields on aerobic, oxidized soils. Apparently, these upland varieties cannot tolerate the toxins that accumulate in reduced soils.

IR20 and H 4 appear to combine resistance to four soil problems: iron toxicity, phosphorus deficiency, zinc deficiency (see below), and injury due to reduction products. These varieties should do well on strongly acid soils and continuously wet soils. IR20, in addition, should yield well on neutral and acid upland soils.

Zinc deficiency

Zinc deficiency in rice is widespread in Agusan del Norte, Mindanao (Philippines). It occurs on the continuously wet, poorly drained soils described as "hydrosols," on soils of the Butuan series bordering the hydrosols, and on the slightly alkaline soils, San Manuel clay and Umingan clay loam. The total area involved is

about 121,000 hectares. Although year-round rice production is possible on these wet, flat soils which are well supplied with N, P, and K, less than 18,000 hectares is planted to rice largely because of zinc deficiency. To investigate the causes and remedies of zinc deficiency, and to explore varietal resistance, field experiments were established at the Northern Mindanao National Agricultural College and in farmers' fields.

Removal of weeds. Between the annual rice crops, the soils of the Butuan series carry a dense growth of marsh plants, chiefly *Cyperus imbricatus*. Farmers plow under 30 to 100 tons of weeds while preparing the land for rice. Since excess organic matter inactivates soil zinc and retards its uptake by the rice plant, we conducted a replicated experiment to observe the response to removal of weeds before land preparation in the presence and absence of zinc chloride.

Incorporation of weeds at 20 t/ha was not injurious. Rice in plots treated with zinc chloride at 20 kg/ha Zn gave a yield of 4.9 t/ha of grain both with and without incorporation of weeds. But without zinc chloride, plants in all plots died within 40 days of transplanting. Table 5 shows that the plants that died of zinc deficiency had a lower content of zinc but a higher content of magnesium and manganese than the plants that produced grain.

N, P, K fertilizers. Extension workers had reported that the incidence of a disorder, later diagnosed as zinc deficiency, had increased as the use of improved varieties and the accompanying good cultural practices had increased. We suspected that N and P fertilizers might be immobilizing zinc as zinc ammonium phosphate or zinc phosphate. We conducted a replicated experiment at Abilan, Butuan and found that,

Table 5. Influence of adding 20 t/ha of weeds with and without zinc chloride on the grain yield, mineral composition, and severity of zinc deficiency symptoms of IR22^a. Abilan, Butuan, Philippines, May-September, 1971.

Weeds incorporated	Zn applied (ppm)	Plant composition ^b							Zn def. symptoms ^c	Yield (t/ha)
		Zn (ppm)	Mn (ppm)	Fe (ppm)	K (%)	Ca (%)	Na (%)	Mg (%)		
No	0	11.4	797	295	1.06	0.12	0.26	0.53	5	0
Yes	0	11.2	955	486	0.97	0.12	0.27	0.47	5	0
No	10	14.4	698	261	1.31	0.11	0.23	0.38	2	4.9
Yes	10	15.6	687	289	1.43	0.12	0.27	0.43	2	4.9

^aN P K applied basally. ^b28 days after transplanting. ^c0 = symptoms absent; 5 = symptoms most pronounced.

Table 6. Effects of two methods of zinc application with and without N P K fertilizers on the grain yield, mineral composition, and zinc deficiency symptoms of IR22. Abilan, Butuan, Philippines. 1971 dry season.

Treatment		Composition (ppm)			Composition (%)				Zn def. symptoms ^a	Yield (t/ha)
N P K	Zn	Zn	Mn	Fe	K	Ca	Na	Mg		
No	No	11.4	791	288	1.26	0.12	0.28	0.51	5	0
Yes	No	11.2	597	257	1.20	0.12	0.26	0.47	5	0
Yes	Yes ^b	13.2	472	200	1.66	0.12	0.29	0.35	0	4.2
No	Yes	15.0	785	286	1.59	0.12	0.31	0.43	2	4.2
Yes	Yes ^c	15.3	663	282	1.52	0.13	0.29	0.40	2	4.9

^a0 = symptoms absent; 5 = symptoms most pronounced. ^bSeedlings dipped in 2% ZnO suspension. ^c10 ppm ZnCl₂ applied to soil.

on this soil, fertilizers did not cause or aggravate zinc deficiency (Table 6). It is remarkable that a yield of 4.2 t/ha of rice was obtained, without N, P, K fertilizers, merely by applying 40 kg/ha zinc chloride worth about P160.

As in the previous experiment, the magnesium content of the zinc-deficient plants was higher than that of the plants treated with zinc.

Residual available zinc. A 10-ton crop of rice (straw and grain) removes no more than 0.5 kg/ha of zinc. If the zinc is not tied up, a 20 kg/ha application of zinc should suffice for several years. Table 7 shows that there is ample available zinc in the plots that received a direct application of zinc. Observations on the second crop on the same plots agree with the soil test.

Soil test for zinc deficiency. Available zinc was determined by the method of Trierwieler and Lindsay in 20 air-dry soils used in greenhouse and field studies. Only soils with less than 1.5 ppm of available zinc, the critical level observed by IRRI physiologists (1969 Annual Report), showed clear symptoms of zinc deficiency (Table 8). Four of them had pH values below 7.0.

Table 7. Residual available zinc after the first crop, as affected by form and method of zinc application. Butuan, Philippines.

Treatment	Rate	Available Zn ^a (ppm)	Residual applied Zn (%)
Control	—	1.0	—
Seedling dip			
ZnO	2%	1.6	—
ZnCl ₂	2%	1.4	—
Seeds soaked in ZnCl ₂	1%	1.1	—
ZnO	10 ppm	8.5	77
ZnCl ₂	10 ppm	8.6	77
ZnSO ₄	10 ppm	7.4	66
Battery	1/sq m	22.4	—
Battery	2/sq m	37.2	—

^aZn extractable in 0.01 M EDTA + 1 M (NH₄)₂CO₃.

Zinc-magnesium interaction. Chemical analysis of the plants in three experiments revealed that magnesium content was always higher in the zinc-deficient plants than in the healthy plants. Soil analysis (Table 9) showed that zinc deficiency was associated with high magnesium content in the soil. Plants in San Manuel clay loam showed zinc deficiency symptoms for a while even in the presence of 20 kg/ha of applied zinc. This finding suggests that magnesium and calcium carbonates temporarily inactivated the applied zinc.

An equilibration study showed that, of the carbonates likely to be present in slightly alkaline soils in the submerged state, magnesium carbonate had the greatest affinity for water-soluble zinc (Table 10). The adsorbed zinc was completely extractable in EDTA + (NH₄)₂CO₃, however, and therefore was available to rice. The transitory zinc deficiency observed in the zinc-treated San Manuel clay loam may be due to the immobility of the adsorbed zinc.

Varietal resistance. Although zinc deficiency can be corrected by applying zinc to the soil or to the plant, resistance to zinc deficiency in improved varieties might help the small farmer. We tested the performance of 32 varieties on a zinc-deficient soil in a replicated experiment at the Northern Mindanao National Agricultural College. The soil was a dark-grey clay of the Butuan series (pH 6.2; organic matter, 5.0%; total Zn, 73 ppm; available Zn, 0.8 ppm; and available P [Olsen], 78 ppm).

Two to three weeks after planting, all varieties showed zinc deficiency symptoms, but they were least in IR5, IR20, and H 4. Five weeks after transplanting these three were the only varieties surviving in all plots; the lines IR1561-189-3 and IR1561-284-3 survived in some

Table 8. Correlation between available zinc content of 20 soils and zinc deficiency symptoms of rice.

Soil	pH ^a	Organic matter (%)	Available zinc (ppm) ^b	Zn deficiency symptoms ^c
Luisiana clay	4.6	2.9	11.4	0
Paete clay loam	5.2	16.0	9.0	0
Pila clay loam	6.7	4.0	8.6	0
Antipolo clay loam	5.8	2.6	5.8	0
Acid sulfate clay (Philippines)	3.4	4.4	3.4	0
Maahas clay	6.8	2.4	3.2	1
Buenavista clay loam	6.8	2.9	3.0	0
Hydrosol (Pampanga)	7.1	3.3	2.8	0
Acid sulfate clay (Vietnam)	3.6	7.2	1.9	0
San Fernando clay loam	7.6	2.9	1.5	1
Parayao clay	7.0	1.7	1.5	1
Lipa clay loam	7.0	4.7	1.4	3
San Manuel clay loam (Abilan)	7.5	6.8	1.4	3
San Manuel clay (Cabadbaran)	6.9	1.9	1.3	3
Agaie sandy loam	7.6	1.5	0.8	2
Butuan clay	6.2	5.0	0.8	3
Butuan clay ^d	7.4	4.8	0.7	3
San Manuel clay (Mabini)	6.8	2.0	0.7	3
San Manuel clay (Luna)	7.1	2.0	0.7	3
San Manuel clay loam (Buenavista)	7.4	5.8	0.8	3

^aMeasured in 1:1 soil-to-water ratio. ^bZn extractable in EDTA + (NH₄)₂CO₃. ^c0 = symptoms absent; 3 = symptoms most pronounced. ^dLimed.

replicates. The following died: IR8, IR22, IR24, one IR5 line, one IR262 line, one IR400 line, three IR506 lines, two IR665 lines, one IR759 line, three IR790 lines, three IR878 lines, one IR937 line, one IR1170 line, and one IR1561 line. At 5 weeks after transplanting, the zinc

content of all plants, including those that survived, was less than 13 ppm. But the surviving varieties had lower concentrations of manganese and magnesium (Table 11).

Water regime and zinc deficiency. The water regime of a soil profoundly affects the zinc nutrition of rice (1970 Annual Report): prolonged submergence reduces zinc availability, soil drying increases it dramatically. Our long-term study of the influence of water management on the growth and yield of rice provides further evidence that zinc deficiency can result from continuous submergence of soils.

Three soils (Luisiana clay: pH 4.6; organic matter, 2.9%; Maahas clay: pH 6.6; organic matter, 2.0%; and Pila clay loam: pH 7.6%; organic matter, 1.5%) were subjected, in 220-liter drums, outdoors, to several water treatments for the past 5 years. We grew two crops of rice each year. Weeds, stubble, and N, P, K fertilizers were incorporated. During the period, the organic matter content of the continuously flooded soils increased in all soils, and the pH increased to 6.5 in Luisiana clay and to 7.1 in Maahas clay.

Flood following without midseason soil drying consistently gave the highest yields (Table 12) because it conserved nitrogen and produced a chemical environment favorable to rice (1967, 1969, 1970 Annual Reports). But this treatment brought about slight zinc deficiency even in the acid soil.

Zinc deficiency was first observed on the continuously flooded Pila clay loam, 2 years ago. Last year, it appeared on the continuously

Table 9. Extractable Mg, Ca, and Mn in 10 soils.

Soil	pH ^a	Content (meq/100 g soil)						Zn deficiency ^b
		Extracted with 1 N HCl			Extracted with 1 N NH ₄ OAc			
		Mg	Ca	Mn	Mg	Ca	Mn	
Butuan clay	6.2	97	32.4	4.5	17	25.0	1.10	3
San Manuel clay loam	7.5	66	37.4	1.4	30	23.1	0.10	3
San Manuel clay	7.1	125	26.4	2.9	11	13.5	0.04	3
Lipa clay loam	7.0	21	21.8	1.8	14	8.8	0.10	3
Agaie sandy loam	7.6	2	14.4	1.7	1	8.5	0.10	2
Paete clay loam	5.2	9	22.4	1.2	9	16.0	0.62	0
Maahas clay	6.8	18	23.0	6.1	16	15.0	0.11	1
Luisiana clay	4.6	6	6.2	2.2	3	3.4	2.20	0
San Fernando clay loam	7.6	24	24.8	6.2	21	18.0	1.09	1
Acid sulfate clay	3.4	4	12.0	0.3	3	7.5	0.18	0

^aDetermined in 1:1 soil-to-water ratio. ^b0 = symptoms absent; 3 = symptoms severe.

Table 10. Adsorption of zinc from an aqueous solution by three carbonates.

Adsorbent	Residual Zn in solution (μg)	Zn adsorbed (%)
Calcium carbonate	2.97	67.4
Manganese carbonate	0.43	95.3
Magnesium carbonate	0.00	100.0

Table 11. Mineral composition and survival of some varieties sampled 5 weeks after transplanting on a zinc-deficient soil.

Variety or line	Zn (ppm)	Mn (ppm)	Mg (%)	Ca (%)	K (%)
<i>Survived</i>					
IR5	12.9	390	0.33	0.13	1.54
IR20	11.3	371	0.33	0.17	1.65
H 4	9.2	310	0.29	0.18	1.34
<i>Survived in some replications</i>					
IR1561-189-3	11.0	445	0.38	0.11	1.55
IR1561-284-3	10.9	606	0.33	0.14	1.44
<i>Died</i>					
IR8	10.5	525	0.40	0.16	1.46
IR22	10.4	780	0.46	0.16	1.15
IR24	11.5	563	0.45	0.17	1.41

Table 12. Influence of four water regimes on the zinc content of the active center leaf 8 weeks after transplanting and on grain yield of IR24 on three soils, in drums, outdoors, in the 11th cropping season.

Water regime ^a	<i>Luisiana clay</i>		<i>Maahas clay</i>		<i>Pila clay loam</i>	
	Zn in leaf (ppm)	Yield (g/drum)	Zn in leaf (ppm)	Yield (g/drum)	Zn in leaf (ppm)	Yield (g/drum)
Flood fallow no msd	7.6	258	6.8	245	9.0	261
with msd	16.2	241	16.2	253	14.1	199
Dry fallow no msd	15.2	292	15.4	258	12.0	242
with msd	17.2	226	18.1	264	20.1	187

^amsd = midseason soil drying.

Table 13. Analysis of two acid sulfate soils.

Soil property	Vietnam	Castañas
Texture	clay	clay
pH	3.6	2.8
κ (mmhos/cm)	8.3	9.3
Organic matter (%)	7.2	3.2
Total N (%)	0.15	0.18
Acetate soluble SO_4^{--} (ppm)	767	2480
Active Fe (%)	0.10	1.87
Active Mn (%)	0.005	0.04

flooded Maahas soils. In 1971, even Luisiana clay showed zinc deficiency symptoms in all three replicates of the continuously flooded treatment. The zinc content in the active center leaf of zinc-deficient plants, 8 weeks after transplanting, was 7 to 9 ppm (Table 12). Even temporary soil drying (midseason soil drying) markedly increased the zinc content of the plant and prevented zinc deficiency.

Problem soils

Investigation of problem soils was continued in the greenhouse and laboratory with chemical kinetics of the submerged soil as the main diagnostic tool.

Leaching alone corrected the toxicity of an acid sulfate soil from Vietnam; liming was necessary for the soil from Castañas, Philippines. The poor growth, the reddish discoloration of the leaves, and the low yield of rice on an acid ferrallitic loam from Colombia were associated with the high concentrations of iron both in the soil solution and in the plant. The sandy soils from Badeggi, and Agaie, Nigeria, were deficient in N, P, and K, and, in addition, in zinc in the case of the soil from Agaie.

Acid sulfate soils. Acid sulfate soils ("cat-clays") and potential acid sulfate soils ("mud-clays") cover more than 20 million hectares of flat land in the tropics, but less than 10 percent are cultivated because of the toxicity of these soils to rice. Acid sulfate soils have excess aluminum at planting and excess iron after soil reduction (1964, 1965 Annual Reports). Proposed amendments include liming, application of MnO_2 , fertilization, and prolonged submergence. Leaching the soil is an additional beneficial operation (1970 Annual Report).

In the field, an acid sulfate soil can be leached and most of the salts can be removed relatively easily by impounding water; plowing, harrowing, and letting the mud settle; draining the surface water; and flooding, harrowing, and draining again. Removal of the salts, chiefly aluminum sulfate, lessens injury from aluminum, salt, and H_2S and lowers the lime requirement. The extent to which leaching could replace lime and manganese dioxide was therefore studied with two acid sulfate soils, one from Vietnam

Table 14. Influence of MnO₂, lime, and leaching on the yield of IR579-48-1 on two submerged acid sulfate soils.

Treatment	Yield (g/pot)			
	Vietnam clay		Castañas clay	
	Grain	Straw	Grain	Straw
Control	21	24	0	0
MnO ₂ (0.5%)	62	64	7	12
Limed to pH 5.5	64	64	79	76
Limed + MnO ₂	72	67	84	75
Leached	78	75	11	20
Leached + MnO ₂	91	82	50	59
Leached + limed	88	78	83	82
Leached + limed + MnO ₂	103	95	92	104

and the other from Castañas, Philippines (Table 13).

Leaching drastically depressed the electrical conductivity and the concentration of water-soluble iron in both soils, but increased the pH appreciably only in the soil from Vietnam (fig. 3). On the Vietnam soil leaching greatly benefited rice and was better than liming, but on Castañas clay leaching had little value (Table 14). A combination of leaching, liming, and application of MnO₂ gave the best yield on both soils.

Leaching alone (with fertilizers) may be sufficient to make some acid sulfate soils productive; other soils may need liming. A combination of leaching, liming, and application of MnO₂ may, however, be the best amendment.

An acid soil from Colombia. This problem soil is a reddish-brown ferrallitic sandy loam (pH 4.5; organic matter, 3.7%; total N, 0.17%; active Fe, 1.27%; active Mn, 0.005%; cation exchange capacity, 12.9 meq/100 g). Since preliminary tests (1970 Annual Report) suggested that rice grown in the soil suffers from iron toxicity, we studied the influence of five treatments designed to minimize iron toxicity: 1) liming to pH 6.5 to prevent the build-up of high concentrations of water-soluble iron, 2) adding 1.0 percent green manure to accelerate soil reduction and hasten the peak of water-soluble iron, 3) presubmergence to avoid the peak of iron, 4) late flooding to avoid excess iron in the early stages while providing sufficient iron in the reproductive phase of the plant's development, and 5) midseason soil drying to oxidize excess iron and other reduction products. All treatments included a basal application of 0.15

3. Effect of liming and leaching on electrical conductivity (EC), concentration of water-soluble iron, and pH in two acid sulfate soils.

percent of a 1:1 mixture of green manure and straw and 100 ppm of N, P, and K. All soils except those in the late-flood treatment were submerged just before 2-week-old IR8 seedlings were transplanted.

Except for the addition of organic matter all amendments increased the yield of both grain and straw (Table 15), but liming resulted in the highest grain yield. The foliar symptoms of iron toxicity were mildest and the content of iron least in the limed treatment. Also, the concen-

tration of iron in the soil solution was less than in the control (fig. 4). Organic matter produced concentrations of iron and organic acids which were harmful to the rice plant.

The study was continued in the wet season as a factorial experiment combining the lime and the water treatments of the previous experiment. The basal application of the mixture of straw and green manure was omitted and urea replaced ammonium sulfate as the source of

nitrogen because organic matter and ammonium sulfate seemed to aggravate iron toxicity.

As in the first experiment, lime resulted in the highest grain yield, but the yield was only 18 percent higher than that of the control because the plants in the control did not suffer from severe iron toxicity. Apparently, the absence of fresh organic matter and the presence of urea prevented the build-up of high concentrations of water-soluble iron. None of the water-control treatments were beneficial.

We concluded that iron toxicity is one factor retarding the growth of irrigated rice on the soil from Colombia. Liming to pH 6.5, avoiding incorporation of organic matter, and liberal fertilization with urea, phosphate, and potash appear to be desirable. The use of resistant varieties may be a valuable adjunct.

Some varieties can be grouped as follows according to their susceptibility to the injurious factors in this soil on the basis of two outdoor pot trials: *least susceptible* — IR20, IR22, IR24, H 105, IR405-5-12; *susceptible* — H 4, PI 215936, IR790-5-1, IR95-43-13; *highly susceptible* — IR5, IR8, IR5-81-3, IR1170-261-3.

Badeggi sandy loam. Soil from Badeggi, Nigeria is a light-grey, fine, sandy loam (pH 4.8; organic matter, 1.7%; total N, 0.05%; cation exchange capacity, 2.78 meq/100 g; exchangeable bases, 1.09 meq/100 g; active Fe, 0.13%; active Mn, 0.01%). Rice does not grow well in it.

In the greenhouse, we studied the influence of treatments designed to improve the cation exchange capacity of the soil, its base status, the macronutrient and micronutrient supply, and available silica content on the chemical kinetics of the soil and performance of IR8.

No injurious concentrations of iron, CO₂, organic acids, reducing substances, or electrolytes occurred at any stage in any treatments, but N and K deficiencies were apparent from the beginning in the unfertilized control, and from the sixth week in the other treatments. The treatments that combined all factors gave 50.4 g/pot of grain compared to 5.4 g/pot for the untreated control. None of the factors other than N, P, K fertilizers contributed significantly to the yield increase.

Thus poor growth of rice on the flooded soil

4. Influence of four treatments on the kinetics of water-soluble iron and organic acids in a soil from Colombia.

Table 15. Influence of lime, organic matter, and some water treatments on the growth, yield, and mineral composition of IR8 on an acid ferrallitic soil from Colombia.

Treatment	Tillers (No./pot)	Composition of straw							
		Yield (g/pot)		Fe (ppm)	Mn (ppm)	Zn (ppm)	P (%)	K (%)	Si (%)
		Straw	Grain						
Submerged	17	23	15	1570	473	54	0.17	2.5	4.6
Limed, submerged	25	43	50	494	339	36	0.11	3.1	5.2
Organic matter added, submerged ^a	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Presubmerged	48	62	42	1505	530	45	0.14	2.5	4.3
Submerged late	56	67	31	1059	426	59	0.11	2.4	2.4
Midseason soil drying	33	48	33	1495	491	70	0.12	2.8	3.3

^aPlants died within 2 weeks of transplanting.

from Badeggi was due largely to N, P, K deficiencies. Split application of large amounts of N and K and the use of rock phosphate and urea merit testing in the field.

Agaie sandy loam. The chemical kinetics of a soil from Agaie, Nigeria (pH 7.6; organic matter, 1.5%; cation exchange capacity, 8.8 meq/100 g; active Fe, 0.8%; active Mn, 0.06%) indicated

no retarding or limiting factor except severe deficiencies of N and K starting at transplanting in the unfertilized soil, and at 6 weeks after transplanting in the fertilized soil. Split application of large amounts of urea, concentrated super-phosphate, and muriate of potash along with 20 kg/ha zinc are promising amendments for field testing.

Plant physiology

Emphasis was placed on two major areas: the search for further increase in yield and response of rice to subnormal environment.

In studies of ways to increase grain yield, CO₂ enrichment before flowering increased the number of spikelets, which in turn increased grain yield by 29 percent in the dry season and by 35 percent in the wet season. Thus, identifying varieties with larger yield capacity—more spikelets per unit land area or larger grain size—might lead to higher yield levels.

It was well established that an optimum leaf area index does not exist in short or tall varieties. Respiration of rice crops was about 40 percent of gross photosynthesis irrespective of growth stage or plant type.

A simple technique for screening varieties for resistance to low temperature at the seedling stage was developed. IR667-98 is an example of an indica-japonica cross that adapts to both the temperate and the tropical environments.

The importance of irrigation water and of fertilizer as sulfur sources was demonstrated. The increasing consumption of high analysis fertilizers may make sulfur deficiency more common in rice.

A study on volunteer rice showed that rice seeds buried in submerged soil could germinate after 1 year. Volunteer rice may therefore be a problem even after the third crop.

In areas where rice plants are completely submerged during early growth, the survival of the seedlings after submergence in water decreases with longer submergence, with increased depth, temperature, and turbidity of water, and with increased rates of nitrogen.

Spikelet formation and grain filling

Previous studies suggest that grain number is a major limiting factor of grain yield under Los Baños conditions. Grain yield is closely correlated with grain number per square meter; grain weight and filled-grain percentage are about the same irrespective of grain number. An increase in grain number, however, may not result in increased grain yield because unfilled grains may also increase as they often do in temperate regions. It is therefore important to determine whether increased grain number per square meter will produce higher yields under a given climatic condition.

We used carbon dioxide enrichment to increase spikelet number (sink size) before heading and to improve grain filling after heading. By using these two treatments separately, we were able to study the effects on grain yield of spikelet number and of increased photosynthesis after heading.

Since light intensity, temperature, and CO_2 interact, the environment under which the CO_2 enrichment was done must be defined. The period for panicle development in the dry season had higher solar radiation and lower temperatures than that in the wet season. The period after heading in the dry season had higher solar radiation and temperatures than the corresponding period in the wet season. The mean solar radiation values for pre- and post-heading time were $478 \text{ cal cm}^{-2} \text{ day}^{-1}$ and $428 \text{ cal cm}^{-2} \text{ day}^{-1}$ in the dry season, and 366 cal cm^{-2}

day^{-1} and $298 \text{ cal cm}^{-2} \text{ day}^{-1}$ in the wet season. The mean temperatures varied from 26 to 28 C.

Chambers (60 x 60 x 150 cm) with open tops were made with transparent plastic sheets. Light conditions inside the chamber were about the same as outside the chamber (control plot), particularly when the sun was high. The temperatures inside and outside the chamber differed by about 1 to 2 C. The maximum deviation was 4 C. Carbon dioxide inside the chamber was increased by adding CO_2 from gas bottles. The CO_2 concentration inside the chamber fluctuated between 700 and 1,500 ppm (fig. 1).

In the dry season, CO_2 enrichment before heading increased yields by 29 percent and after heading by 21 percent compared with the control (Table 1). The yield increase through the pre-heading enrichment resulted from increases in number of grains per square meter and in grain weight. Increased grain number did not accompany decreased filled-grain percentage. On the other hand, the yield increase through the post-heading enrichment resulted from increases in grain weight and filled-grain percentage. Thus, yield was increased either by increasing spikelet number or by improving grain filling.

In the wet season, CO_2 enrichment before heading increased grain number per square meter and grain weight. These increases resulted in a 35-percent increase in grain yield over the control (Table 1). CO_2 enrichment after heading brought about increases in grain weight and filled grain percentage, which in turn resulted in a 21-percent increase in yield. This experiment demonstrates that even under the low solar radiation that prevails in the monsoon season, CO_2 can limit spikelet formation and grain filling.

In both seasons, CO_2 enrichment before heading significantly increased grain number per square meter. The increase was associated with an increase in sugar and starch content in the sheath plus culm and in the crop growth rate.

Environmental conditions in the pre-heading enrichment plot were identical to those of the control plot after heading. Nevertheless the enriched plot before heading had a higher crop growth rate after heading than the control. In

1. An example of fluctuations in CO_2 concentration inside the chamber, on a clear day. IARRI, Sept. 21, 1971.

Table 1. Effects of CO₂ enrichment before and after heading on growth and grain yield of IR8^a IRRI, 1971.

Treatment	Yield (t/ha)	Sugar and starch ^e in leaf sheath and culm (%)	Crop growth rate (g m ⁻² wk ⁻¹)		Grain wt ^f (mg)	No. of grains (10 ³ /sq m)	Filled grains (%)
			Before heading	After heading			
<i>Dry season</i>							
Control	9.0 a	22	173 a	99 a	31.1 a	45.7 a	74 a
CO ₂ before heading ^b	11.6 b	30	224 b	157 b	25.9 b	50.9 b	77 a
CO ₂ after heading ^c	10.9 b	22	173 a	147 b	25.1 c	44.6 a	86 b
<i>Wet season</i>							
Control	5.7 a	18	122 a	-14 a	24.3 a	28.8 a	78 a
CO ₂ before heading ^b	7.7 b	25	179 b	8 ab	26.2 b	34.1 b	81 ab
CO ₂ after heading ^d	6.9 b	18	122 a	38 b	26.1 b	29.5 a	85 b

^aAny two means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^bFor 30 days. ^cFor 28 days. ^dFor 29 days. ^eAs glucose. ^fDried at 75 C for 3 days.

other words, increased photosynthesis from CO₂ enrichment before heading increased grain number per square meter and perhaps the size of hull (sink), which in turn increased photosynthesis (source) after heading. This is an example of a feedback relationship between sink and source. These results indicate that increasing grain number per square meter may be a promising way to increase grain yield.

Although we used CO₂ enrichment to increase grain number, the technique obviously is not practical. The experiment shows, however, that rice yield will be further increased if yield capacity — a larger number of grains per square meter or a larger grain size — is increased, possibly through breeding.

Photosynthesis, crop growth rate, and respiration

Optimum leaf area index (LAI) in plants had traditionally been attributed to a hyperbolic increase in photosynthesis and a linear increase in respiration at high LAI values. In a preliminary experiment in 1970, the respiration rate of detached individual shoots of IR5, an improved variety, grown at different densities suggested that in this variety respiration was also a hyperbolic function of LAI. Since we felt that measurements on detached shoots might not be giving realistic results, we measured the respiration rate of IR8 and Peta in the field.

During the period 4 weeks before flowering, both varieties showed no pronounced optimum

LAI up to LAI values of 8 to 10. At high levels of LAI, respiration did *not* increase linearly with LAI. The gross photosynthesis of the canopy showed a hyperbolic response to LAI. Photosynthesis increased only slightly above LAI values of 5 to 7 (fig. 2).

At low LAI values, the crop growth rates of Peta and IR8 were similar but IR8 had a slightly higher respiration rate. The photosynthetic rate of IR8 was similar to that of Peta at low LAI values, but it was greater at high values. The plateau crop growth rate of IR8 was 20 g m⁻² wk⁻¹ higher than that of Peta. IR8's leaf angle was always greater than Peta's and, unlike Peta's, it did not decrease with increasing LAI (fig. 3). The respiration of IR8 and Peta was approximately 40 percent of gross photosynthesis over a wide range of values for LAI (fig. 4).

In another experiment with six varieties of different plant types, respiration was about 40 percent of gross photosynthesis irrespective of growth stage or plant type.

In previous work at IRRI, IR8 and Peta were compared. To eliminate lodging, Peta plants were supported. IR8 showed a critical LAI while Peta showed an optimum LAI. The presence of an optimum LAI in Peta was attributed to a larger proportion of culm or to droopy leaves which affected the balance between photosynthesis and respiration. The data obtained this year suggest that the balance between photosynthesis and respiration is relatively stable over a broad range of photosynthetic rates for Peta and IR8. But the leaf angle

2. Photosynthesis, crop growth rate (x 0.9) and respiration of IR8 and Peta during the 4 weeks before flowering. IRRI, 1971 dry season.

of Peta decreased as LAI increased. Decreasing leaf angle should decrease photosynthesis.

We found no optimum LAI value in Peta although it may sometimes occur. Heavy nitrogen applications increase the droopiness of Peta. When LAI is varied by changing nitrogen levels rather than by changing spacing, the resulting droopiness at high LAI values may be greater than the amount that occurred in our experiments. The gross photosynthesis thus may be

decreased sufficiently to produce an optimum LAI value, but such an optimum value is not due to an imbalance between photosynthesis and respiration.

Photosynthesis and respiration of plant parts

To evaluate the potential contribution of leaves at different positions, of the leaf sheath, and of the panicle, we measured the photosynthetic activity of these organs under high light intensity (60 klx). The potential net photosynthesis of the leaves was 94 percent of the total. The fourth leaf had a low net photosynthesis, both per leaf and per unit area (Table 2). The top leaf had the highest net photosynthesis per unit area, but the second leaf was larger and had a greater potential net photosynthesis on a per leaf basis. The net photosynthesis of the sheath and panicle was extremely low. Even in terms of the gross photosynthesis, the panicles (8%) and the sheath (5%) have extremely low capacity.

The panicle of IR8 and other improved varieties is barely exerted and it bends so that it is largely below the leaf canopy. Hence its actual photosynthetic activity in the canopy may well be much less than its potential capacity.

3. Leaf angle of IR8 and Peta related to leaf area index. IRRI, 1971 dry season.

Similarly, the sheath and the fourth leaf probably contribute less than their potential capacity. For these reasons, the upper three leaves have the highest photosynthetic capacity among all the green organs on the plant and they contribute more than 86 percent of the net photosynthesis at this stage.

The respiration rate of leaves tended to be lower in leaves with lower photosynthetic rate per unit leaf area and at lower leaf positions. Forty-eight percent of the dark respiration occurred in the panicle, 14 percent in the leaf sheath plus culm, and 38 percent in the leaves.

IR667-98 in the Philippines and Korea

A new Korean variety, Tongil, was developed by the Office of Rural Development, Korea, and IRRI. Tongil, selected from IR8 x (Yukara x Taichung Native 1), has been known as IR667-98 at IRRI. IR667-98 maintains typical improved indica characters in vegetative habits and yet has japonica-type grains.

To collect basic data on the growth performance of IR667-98 for comparison with other varieties in Korea and Philippines, a cooperative study was begun with the Agronomy Department of Crop Experiment Station, Suwon, Korea.

In general, the climate of Suwon had larger daily and monthly variations than the climate of Los Baños (fig. 5). Maximum and minimum temperatures at Los Baños are high and almost constant throughout the rice-growing period. The daily maximum and minimum temperatures differed by about 5 to 7 C. At Suwon, temperatures, particularly the daily minimum, were low during the nursery stage and ripening period. Differences between the daily maximum and daily minimum temperatures were sometimes more than 15 C. Temperatures during the active vegetative growth period did not differ much between Suwon and Los Baños.

Growth duration, dry matter production, and yield. Three varieties, selected primarily on the basis of growth duration, were grown at 10 x 10 cm spacing with 175 kg/ha N at Los Baños, and four varieties were grown at 20 x 20 cm spacing with 150 kg/ha N at Suwon. One of the leading japonica varieties in Korea, Jinheung,

4. Respiration and photosynthesis of Peta 6-4 weeks before flowering and of Peta and IR8 during the 4 weeks before flowering. IRRI, 1971 dry season.

served as a reference against IR667-98 at Suwon. IR667-98 took 103 days to mature at Los Baños while in Suwon it matured in 135 days, nevertheless it was 6 days earlier than Jinheung. The three varieties had much greater production of total dry matter at Los Baños than at Suwon (Table 3).

IR667-98 yielded about the same at Los Baños and Suwon. At Suwon, IR667-98 had a slightly higher rough rice yield than Jinheung, but the two varieties had about the same brown rice yield. IR667-98 produced more panicles

Table 2. Photosynthetic activity (P_N = net photosynthesis, R_D = dark respiration, P_G = gross photosynthesis) of leaves, sheaths and panicles at a light intensity of 60 klx at the milky stage (Variety IR22 grown in the field).

Plant part ^a	Surface area (sq cm)	Assimilation				
		per leaf (mg/hr CO ₂)			per unit area (mg CO ₂ dm ⁻² hr ⁻¹)	
		P_N	R_D	P_G	P_N	R_D
Leaf 1	24	8.3	0.44	8.7	34	1.8
Leaf 2	54	10.1	0.52	10.6	19	1.0
Leaf 3	51	5.6	0.46	6.1	11	0.9
Leaf 4	37	2.2	0.34	2.5	6	0.9
All leaves		26.6	1.76	27.9	—	—
Leaf sheath plus culm		1.2	0.60	1.8	—	—
Panicle		0.6	2.05	2.7	—	—
Total		28.0	4.46	32.4	—	—

^aLeaf 1 is topmost leaf.

5. Solar radiation mean air temperature and rice cultivation calendar at Los Baños, Philippines, and Suwon, Korea (S = sowing, T = transplanting, F = flowering, H = harvest).

and grains than did Jinheung, but the grains were lighter. The two varieties had also the same yield capacity, indicating that their yielding potentials were comparable under the experimental conditions (Table 4).

Tillering and LAI. At Los Baños, IR667-98 tillered much less than IR747B2-6 but a little more than Yoneshiro. IR667-98, however, was as leafy as IR747B2-6 because it had larger

leaves. At Suwon, IR667-98 tillered more vigorously than Jinheung or Yoneshiro but less than IR747B2-6. It had larger LAI values than Jinheung or Yoneshiro at most growth stages (fig. 6). Thus, IR667-98 is characterized by a vigorous tillering habit at early stages of growth and by a more leafy habit than Jinheung.

Plant type. Compared with the two japonica varieties, IR667-98 has shorter and stiffer culms,

Table 3. Growth duration, dry matter production, and grain yield of four varieties at Los Baños, Philippines and Suwon, Korea, 1971.

Varieties	Type	Growth duration (days)		Total dry matter (t/ha)		Harvest index		Yield (t/ha)		
		Phil.	Korea	Phil.	Korea	Phil.	Korea	Rough rice		Brown rice
								Phil.	Korea	
IR747B2-6	Indica	100	107	13.6	8.1	0.42	0.45	6.66	4.25	3.48
IR667-98	Indica-japonica	103	135	14.3	11.8	0.47	0.55	7.74	7.60	5.81
Yoneshiro	Japonica	95	124	14.0	12.2	0.43	0.37	6.98	5.20	4.33
Jinheung	Japonica	—	141	—	11.9	—	0.51	—	7.02	5.86

a desirable characteristic. Indeed, the higher average yields of IR667-98 compared with those of the leading japonica varieties in Korea can largely be attributed to lodging resistance and to greater resistance to the existing races of *Piricularia oryzae*. The leaves of IR667-98 are erect and compactly arranged at flowering time. The less erect leaves of Jinheung, however, could be advantageous at the low LAI values obtained in this experiment.

Cold tolerance at early growth stages. As shown in Table 5, at 13 C and below, IR667-98 had a lower germination percentage than Jinheung. During the two- to three-leaf stage, IR667-98 showed a distinct change in color to yellow and orange when subjected to low temperatures, while Jinheung remained unchanged in color (Table 6). A similar trend was also observed during the four- to five-leaf stage. These data indicate that IR667-98 is more susceptible to low temperatures than Jinheung, a widely planted variety in Korea.

Table 4. Yield components of four varieties. Suwon, Korea, 1971.

Variety	Panicles (no./sq m)	Grains/panicle (no.)	No. of grains (10^3 /sq m)	1000-grain wt (g)	Yield capacity ^a (t/ha)
IR747B2-6	438	62	27.2	19.4	5.28
IR667-98	273	112	30.6	27.8	8.51
Yoneshiro	265	106	28.1	27.4	7.70
Jinheung	238	118	28.0	29.8	8.34

^aGrain number per square meter x grain weight.

Temperatures during the 1971 crop were generally favorable. In June 1971, IR667-98 seedlings in the nurserybed looked quite normal at Suwon, Iri, and Milyang. The minimum temperatures recorded during the nursery stage at Suwon were usually below 15 C. At Sosa, however, IR667-98 seedlings showed yellowing, some brown spots, and discolored tips. The yellowing, however, disappeared quickly when the temperature rose. In addition, because IR667-98 has vigorous vegetative growth habit,

6. Changes in tiller number and leaf area index at Los Baños and Suwon.

Table 5. Effect of temperature on germination of two varieties.

Temperature (C)	Germination ^a (%)	
	IR667-98	Jinheung
10	0	18
13	59	73
16	82	80
19	88	85
22	97	95

^aMean value of percentage germination at three depths of water (1, 3, 6 cm), 15 days after soaking.

an early setback in growth did not seem to cause any serious problem in Korea.

The effect of water and air temperatures on the growth of five varieties at the eight- to nine-leaf stage was also studied in a controlled environment (Table 7). When both water and air temperatures were kept at 12 C, only Yukara showed a significantly greater increase in plant height than other four varieties. At a water temperature of 17 C and above, all varieties had similar increments in height regardless of air temperature. This finding indicates that at the tillering stage, water temperature has a more pronounced effect on height than air temperature and that raising the water temperature can easily overcome varietal differences in susceptibility to low temperature.

Effect of temperature on ripening. In some places in Korea the ripened grain percentage of IR667-98 is lower than that of the japonica varieties. The accelerated leaf discoloration of IR667-98 might partly be responsible.

An experiment conducted in the phytotron shows clear varietal difference in ripening in response to temperatures (fig. 7). With low day and night temperatures, IR667-98 had a low percentage of ripened grains, while the japonica variety Jinheung had a fairly high percentage. The low ripened grain percentage of IR667-98 was accompanied by accelerated leaf discoloration. Therefore, if the average temperature drops rapidly during the ripening period, ripening of IR667-98 will be more severely affected than that of the japonica variety. At Suwon the temperature regime during the early period of ripening is comparable to the 25-15 C treatment in the phytotron experiment (fig. 7). At this temperature regime, ripening of IR667-98 is

Table 6. Effect of temperature on discoloration of seedlings of two varieties.

Temperature (C)		Days after treatment	Discoloration rating ^a			
			Two- to three-leaf stage		Four- to five-leaf stage	
Day	Night		IR667-98	Jinheung	IR667-98	Jinheung
10	10	3	1	0	W	W
		6	3	0	W	W
		9	5	0	D	W
15	10	3	1	0	1	0
		6	4	0	2	1
		9	5	0	4	1
20	15	3	0	0	0	0
		6	0	0	0	0
		9	0	0	1	0
30	25	3	0	0	0	0
		6	0	0	0	0
		9	0	0	0	0

^a0 to 5 in increasing severity; W = wilted, D = dead.

satisfactory. If a temperature drop during the ripening period is lower than that, ripening of IR667-98 will be considerably impaired. It is important to realize that the temperature pattern of Korea is about marginal for IR667-98.

Comparison of rice and sorghum

Grain yields in different seasons. Yields of rice and sorghum with and without irrigation were compared in five crops during the past 2 years. The plant spacings used were 10 x 10 cm for rice and 50 x 8 cm for sorghum. For rainfed rice, the soil was irrigated before land preparation to puddle the soil, but for rainfed sorghum the soil was not irrigated. The yield of rainfed rice was therefore biased upward in the dry season.

In the dry season, yields of irrigated rice and sorghum were comparable. When rainfed, however, sorghum yielded as well as when irrigated, while rainfed rice yielded 48 percent less than the irrigated crop. As expected, sorghum was better adapted to a limited external supply of water (Table 8).

In the wet season, there was no significant difference in yields between the irrigated and rainfed crops because rainfall was abundant. Rice outyielded sorghum by more than 150 percent in the July-October crop and by 35 percent in the September-November crop.

Table 7. Effects of water and air temperatures on plant height increase (measured 11 days after treatment started)^a.

Water temperature (C)	Plant ht increase ^b (cm)				
	IR667-98	IR747B2-6	IR8	Taichung Native 1	Yukara
<i>Air temperature: 12 C</i>					
12	2.3	1.3	2.2	1.9	4.4
17	4.8	5.1	5.9	4.3	5.8
22	—	5.6	6.3	6.4	5.9
<i>Air temperature: 22 C</i>					
12	2.0	2.3	2.9	2.1	1.4
17	5.4	6.2	5.4	4.5	4.4
22	11.2	10.8	12.4	11.1	11.7

^aData were provided by Dr. Y. Shimazaki, Kamikawa Agricultural Experiment Station, Hokkaido, Japan. ^bPlant height at start of treatment: IR667-98, 24.2 cm; IR747-B2, 21.8 cm; IR8, 23.6 cm; Taichung Native 1, 26.9 cm; Yukara, 37.9 cm.

Clearly, rice is better adapted to the monsoon climate than sorghum.

The major agronomic problems of sorghum in the rainy season were lodging and head mold. Rainy weather during the later stages of ripening favored severe infestation of head mold, resulting in lower grain weight, and hence lower yield. Comparison of yield components indicates that grain yield of rice is largely affected by grain number per square meter. Grain weight is fairly constant. In sorghum, however, grain weight is quite variable and closely related to yield while grain number per square meter remains fairly constant. Thus, the influences on yields of rice and sorghum differ greatly.

Leaf area index and dry matter production. In the wet season, rice and sorghum showed

7. Effect of day and night temperatures on ripening of IR667-98 and Jinheung.

similar trends in leaf area development. Both crops produced about the same amount of total dry matter. They differed noticeably, however, in increase in total dry matter after heading. Rice steadily increased in total dry weight after heading; sorghum did not. That may explain the low yield of sorghum in the wet season since a major portion of grain carbohydrates comes from dry matter produced after heading (fig. 8).

In the dry season, the LAI value of sorghum was much lower than that of rice. In rice, the

Table 8. Grain yield, number of filled grains, and 1,000-grain weight of rice and sorghum in different cropping periods. (Sorghum—Variety IS9290. Rice—Selections IR154-18, March-May 1970; IR747B2-6 all other crops).

Cropping period	Water management	Yield (t/ha)		No. of grains (10 ³ /sq m)		1000-grain wt (g)	
		Rice	Sorghum	Rice	Sorghum	Rice	Sorghum
March-May, 1970	Irrigated	5.60	5.55	33.0	24.8	18.3	22.0
July-Oct., 1970	Irrigated	5.24	2.08 ^a	32.6	25.5	18.4	11.6
	Rainfed	5.00	1.82 ^a	30.8	25.6	18.9	11.1
Jan.-Apr., 1971	Irrigated	6.53	5.90	34.2	26.3	20.5	23.6
	Rainfed	3.40	5.52	20.1	26.1	18.6	23.5
May-Aug., 1971	Irrigated	4.75	4.56	29.1	25.6	19.4	19.0
	Rainfed	4.38	4.40	24.3	26.8	20.1	19.4
Sept.-Nov., 1971	Irrigated	3.21 ^b	2.54 ^c	22.5	25.2	18.7	12.4
	Rainfed	3.46 ^b	2.44 ^c	22.1	26.5	19.5	10.8

^aLodged 3 weeks before harvest and ears severely infested with head mold. ^bPartly damaged by tungro virus and rats. ^cEars severely infested with head mold.

rainfed crop developed smaller leaf area and produced less total dry matter than the irrigated crop. As a result, the rainfed crop yielded about 48 percent less than the irrigated crop. In sorghum, the irrigated and rainfed crops were not much different in LAI, total dry matter, and grain yield. Apparently, sorghum became less leafy in the dry season, but produced more dry matter and higher grain yield.

Water use, photosynthesis, and dry matter production. One physiological reason why sorghum is better adapted to rainfed conditions in the dry season than rice is its high efficiency of water use in photosynthesis and dry matter production. We measured photosynthesis and transpiration simultaneously in young rice and sorghum plants. The ratio of transpiration to photosynthesis of sorghum was one-half that of rice (Table 9). Similarly the water requirement of sorghum was about one-half that of rice. Thus sorghum uses water more efficiently in dry matter production. The high efficiency of

sorghum in water use comes from high photosynthetic efficiency.

Sulfur nutrition of rice

A preliminary survey suggested that sulfur deficiency of lowland rice may occur in some areas. The recent increase in use of high analysis fertilizers which are low in sulfur may accentuate sulfur deficiency problems under intensive cultivation.

Sulfur deficiency is characterized by pronounced elongation of the roots, and subsequently, a general yellowing of the younger leaves, then of the older leaves, and eventually of the whole plant. These changes are accompanied by marked reduction in number of tillers and in plant height. Sulfur-deficient plants flower late and have a high percentage of sterile grains.

Critical sulfur content. The critical sulfur content in different tissues was studied by

8. Changes in LAI and total dry weight of rice and sorghum in wet and dry seasons.

Table 9. Efficiency of water use in photosynthesis and dry matter production.

Crop	Water regime	Simultaneous measurement ^a		Transpiration: photosynthesis ratio	Pot experiment ^b		
		Transpiration (mg H ₂ O leaf ⁻¹ hr ⁻¹)	Photosynthesis (mg CO ₂ leaf ⁻¹ hr ⁻¹)		Dry wt (g/pot)	Transpiration (g/pot)	Water requirement (g/g dry wt)
Rice	Flooded	—	—	—	10.75	2405	224 ± 10
	Upland	162	4.1	40	7.55	1847	244 ± 23
Sorghum	Upland	252	12.8	20	8.45	913	114 ± 29

^a3 weeks after sowing. ^bMeasured 5 weeks after sowing.

solution culture technique. We defined two critical contents (fig. 9): DC₁₀₀ is the minimum sulfur content in a given plant tissue required to obtain maximum yield; DC₅₀ is the sulfur content in a given plant tissue required to obtain 50 percent of the maximum yield (DC stands for "deficiency criteria"). Table 10 summarizes the critical contents of sulfur in the leaf blade and straw at three growth stages. The critical sulfur content decreased with plant growth.

The nitrogen-sulfur ratio has been suggested as a useful indicator of the sulfur status of the plant. Our study, however, indicated that sulfur content is as useful as the nitrogen-sulfur ratio, and is preferable because it is easier to use.

Effects of fertilizer and water on sulfur uptake.

In addition to soil, fertilizer and water are the rice plant's major sources of sulfur. To study the effects of fertilizer and water on sulfur uptake, rice plants were grown in pots under upland and lowland conditions on Lipa clay loam, which is an upland counterpart of Maahas clay.

Ammonium sulfate supplied sufficient amounts of sulfur to the plants regardless of water sources. When urea was applied and

demineralized water was used for irrigation, typical symptoms of sulfur deficiency developed under both lowland and upland conditions. The yield (panicle weight per pot) under lowland conditions was only 26 percent of that obtained with ammonium sulfate plus tap water; under upland conditions it was 60 percent. When urea was combined with tap water, the yield rose to 94 to 95 percent of that obtained with ammonium sulfate plus tap water under both water regimes (Table 11). The tap water used in this experiment contained 2.3 mg/liter S.

A comparison of the amounts of sulfur absorbed by the plants when urea was applied indicated that tap water supplied more than twice as much sulfur as the soil under both water regimes (Table 11).

Some workers claim that conversion of sulfates to sulfides under lowland conditions may reduce the availability of sulfur to the rice plant. In our experiments although the sulfur content of the plant was generally higher under

Table 10. Critical sulfur content in leaf blade and straw at different growth stages (DC₅₀ = sulfur content required in plant tissue for 50% of maximum yield. DC₁₀₀ = sulfur content required for maximum yield).

Growth stage	Critical sulfur content (%)			
	Leaf blades		Straw	
	DC ₅₀	DC ₁₀₀	DC ₅₀	DC ₁₀₀
Tillering	0.06	0.16	0.06	0.16
Flowering	0.05	0.10	0.04	0.07
Harvest	0.04	0.07	0.03	0.06

9. Relationship between relative dry matter of shoots and percent sulfur in leaf blades at tillering stage.

Table 11. Effects of fertilizer and mineral content of water on dry matter yield and sulfur uptake of rice plants grown on Lipa clay loam under lowland and upland conditions.

Fertilizer	Water ^a	Dry wt (g/pot)		S content (%)		Total S uptake (mg/pot)
		Panicle	Straw	Panicle	Straw	
<i>Lowland</i>						
(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	D	96	84	0.087	0.175	262
	T	94	87	0.087	0.139	221
Urea	D	25	49	0.034	0.035	26
	T	88	75	0.070	0.044	86
<i>Upland</i>						
(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	D	34	54	0.087	0.219	154
	T	33	53	0.087	0.190	134
Urea	D	20	38	0.050	0.041	25
	T	31	52	0.069	0.107	78

D = demineralized water, T = tap water

upland conditions than under lowland conditions when urea was applied (that is, under limited supply of sulfur), the plants absorbed similar amounts of sulfur under upland and lowland conditions. To estimate the availability of sulfur applied by irrigation water, we compared the amount of sulfur recovered with the total amount supplied by water, using the water requirement and sulfur contents of irrigation water (Table 12). Sulfur supplied by water was more highly available in the soil under upland condition than in the soil under lowland condition.

Sulfur uptake in the field. Sulfur content in straw was high at early stages of growth and declined steadily towards maturity. Rate of sulfur uptake was low at early stages of growth and after heading. The maximum uptake rate was about 2 kg ha⁻¹ wk⁻¹ from active tillering to heading (fig. 10).

In the IR8 crop, straw and panicle removed a similar amount of sulfur. In the Peta crop,

Table 12. Availability of sulfur supplied by irrigation water under lowland and upland conditions.

Cultural condition	S (mg) supplied by			Tap water consumed ^b (liter)	Total S in tap water ^c (mg)	S recovery (%)
	Soil plus tap water	Soil ^a	Tap water			
Lowland	86	26	60	48.9	112	54
Upland	78	25	53	24.9	57	93

^aAmount supplied by soil plus demineralized water. ^bWater requirement is assumed to be 300 g H₂O/g dry matter for both lowland and upland rice. ^cTotal water consumption x 2.3 mg/liter S.

straw removed about 70 percent of the total because of the larger ratio of straw to panicle (Table 13).

The critical sulfur content in the straw and panicle were used to estimate the minimum amount of sulfur required to produce 1 ton of rice. Thus, to produce 6 t/ha of rice in the wet season, 7.8 kg/ha of sulfur must be absorbed; similarly, 11.7 kg/ha of sulfur is needed to produce 9 t/ha in the dry season. These amounts of sulfur can be easily supplied by sulfur-containing fertilizers. For instance, ammonium sulfate equivalent to 100 kg/ha N can supply about 120 kg/ha of sulfur. When the sulfur-containing fertilizers are replaced by high-analysis fertilizers, crops must depend on soil, irrigation water, rainfall, and the atmosphere for sulfur. Thus, sulfur deficiency may occur where the natural supply of sulfur is low.

Possible sulfur deficiency in Indonesia. In some fields at Ngale experimental farm (Indonesia), rice growth is extremely poor, the crop often has uneven growth, stunting, limited tillering, discoloration and withering of lower leaves, and Helminthosporium spots. It was difficult to pinpoint any possible nutritional disorder by visual examination. Chemical analysis of plant samples, however, revealed that the plants were low in zinc (17 to 22 ppm) and low in sulfur (0.06 to 0.12%). Soils at Ngale experimental farm and the surrounding areas are described as grumusols. Three soil samples taken from this area had pH values of 6.7 to 6.9 at 1:1 soil-to-water ratio. These soils contain 1.4 to 4.9 percent organic matter, and 1.0 to 3.3 ppm available soil zinc.

Ngale soil was studied for possible deficiencies of zinc and sulfur in two greenhouse experiments. In the first, the plants supplied with urea developed typical zinc deficiency symptoms 2 weeks after transplanting. A week later, however, all the plants, except those supplied with ammonium sulfate, showed severe yellowing which is a strong indication of sulfur deficiency. Dry weight and zinc analysis are shown in Table 14.

In the second experiment, the effect of sulfur on growth was studied with calcium sulfate as a sulfur source. Urea was as effective as a nitrogen source as ammonium sulfate provided

Table 13. Removal of sulfur by rice crops.

Plant part	S removed (kg/ha)		
	By one crop ^a	By 1 ton of rice	Estimated minimum by 1 ton of rice ^b
		<i>IR8</i>	
Straw	7.6	0.8	0.6
Panicle	7.1	0.8	0.7
Total	14.7	1.6	1.3
		<i>Peta</i>	
Straw	12.0	2.0	—
Panicle	4.8	0.8	—
Total	16.8	2.8	—

^aGrain yields were 9.13 t/ha for IR8 and 6.09 t/ha for Peta.
^bAssuming that DC₁₀₀ value is 0.06% for both straw and panicle, and panicle-to-straw ratio is 1.2.

calcium sulfate was also added (Table 15). Thus, the striking effect of ammonium sulfate found in the previous experiment can be attributed to sulfate. Chemical analysis has confirmed that sulfur content of the plants was below the critical level for sulfur deficiency when sulfur was not added either as ammonium sulfate or calcium sulfate. The two greenhouse experiments suggest that one of the nutritional problems at Ngale is sulfur deficiency. In addition, the sulfur content of irrigation water at Ngale, in June 1971 was only 0.9 ppm which is very low compared with the world average of river waters, 4.1 ppm. Thus, the possible sulfur deficiency at Ngale should be studied in the field in relation to natural supply of sulfur.

Photoperiod

Rice is grown throughout the year in Bangla Dosh. Since temperature, daylength, and precipitation in this region vary greatly, the cropping season is divided into three periods with several variations: aus (April to August), aman (April to December), and boro (November to

Table 14. Effects of different nitrogen sources and zinc chloride on rice growth (1 month after transplanting) on Ngale soil in the greenhouse.

Treatment	Dry wt (g/pot)	Zinc content (ppm)
Urea	0.87	22
Urea plus ZnCl ₂	1.26	62
Ammonium sulfate	5.03	26
Ammonium chloride	1.64	31

10. Dry weight, sulfur content, sulfur-uptake rate of IR8 at different growth stages, IRRI, 1968 dry season.

May). Each season has a specific set of varieties selected according to their response to temperature or photoperiod, or both, which are modified by depth of flood waters. The response to photoperiod of nine leading Bangla Dosh varieties was studied by growing them under 10, 12, 14, and 16 hours of photoperiod.

Habiganj II, IV, and VI are grown in the boro season when the temperatures are low during the seedling and tillering stage and the daylength is short. Such varieties must be either very sensitive to photoperiod and have a short basic vegetative phase, or they must be insensitive to photoperiod. We found that the three

Table 15. Effects of calcium sulfate on rice growth (1 month after transplanting) on Ngale soil in the greenhouse.

Treatment	Dry wt (g/pot)	Sulfur content (%)
Urea plus ZnCl ₂	0.70	0.07
Urea plus CaSO ₄	5.71	0.38
Urea plus CaSO ₄ plus ZnCl ₂	5.87	0.28
Ammonium sulfate	5.77	0.76

varieties are insensitive to photoperiod (Table 16). In the field, these varieties flower in 140 to 170 days while in the greenhouse they flower in only 80 to 85 days. The difference is clearly a temperature effect. These varieties were selected for their high resistance to low temperature during the seedling stage, that is, for their vigorous growth. Low temperature however, extends their basic vegetative phase, hence their growth duration is longer.

Aus varieties are planted when the daylength is long, so they must be insensitive to photoperiod. Results of our test showed Dular, Katakara, and Dhariail to be insensitive to photoperiod as were the boro varieties (Table 16). Probably the main difference between the boro and aus varieties is in their response to low temperature during seedling stage. Both aus and boro varieties will flower in a reasonably short period throughout Bangla Desh whenever they might be planted, provided the temperature is not limiting.

Aman varieties are planted in the main cropping season. Since the crop flowers when the days are becoming short, aman varieties can be sensitive or insensitive to photoperiod. The aus and boro varieties can be planted during the main cropping season if short growth-duration varieties are desired.

DA-31, Latisail, and Nizersail were the three aman varieties tested. Latisail and Nizersail are highly sensitive to photoperiod and did not

flower under the 14-hour photoperiod. DA-31 is weakly sensitive and flowered at all the photoperiods used but was greatly delayed under the 16-hour photoperiod (Table 16).

Since flowering occurs when the days are short, photoperiod sensitivity should not be essential during the aman season. But in areas where deep water is a problem, the growth duration must be extended so that harvest will occur during a dry period. In such areas, photoperiod-sensitive varieties are needed. There are no known varieties that have long growth duration as a result of long basic vegetative phase.

Temperature

Studies on temperature focused on characteristics of varieties tolerant to low temperatures during the vegetative stage.

At Katmandu, Nepal, where the temperatures are high after transplanting, preferred varieties are tolerant to low temperature at the seedling stage, have a subsequent vigorous growth, and are medium tillering when the temperature rises. The growth duration must not become too short as a result of high temperature. In Seoul, Korea, and in Hokkaido, Japan, where the temperatures are low after transplanting, varieties that are medium tillering at low temperatures are needed. Such varieties are usually low tillering and have a very short growth duration when grown at high temperatures.

To find out the growth characteristics of varieties with high tolerance to low temperature, 85 varieties were tested for their reaction to low water temperature (10 to 12 C) and another set was planted in the field to measure their tillering capacity and height.

Yellowing has been the chief criteria for determining lack of tolerance to cold in seedlings. Our preliminary results show that the seedlings that scored 3 to 5 on a scale of 0 to 5 (0 = completely green, 5 = completely yellow) at low temperatures were tall when grown under normal temperatures (fig. 11). Also, the greater the yellowing, the lower the percentage of stunting. At low temperatures, the varieties with yellow leaves increased in height while the varieties with green leaves did only slightly.

Table 16. Response of Bangla Desh rice varieties to photoperiods of 10 to 16 hours.

Variety	Days to flowering ^a (days)			
	10 hr	12 hr	14 hr	16 hr
BPI-76 (control)	67	111	<i>b</i>	<i>b</i>
	<i>Boro varieties</i>			
Habiganj II	80	81	78	82
Habiganj IV	68	71	73	85
Habiganj VI	78	78	77	80
	<i>Aus varieties</i>			
Dhariail	64	63	79	83
Dular	70	66	72	74
Katakara	72	72	81	84
	<i>Aman varieties</i>			
DA-31	49	52	67	110
Latisail	62	79	<i>b</i>	<i>b</i>
Nizersail	64	96	<i>b</i>	<i>b</i>

^aFrom sowing. ^bNo panicle initiation after 200 days of growth.

11. Height of seedlings before the low temperature treatment in relation to degree of yellowing.

The seedlings that did not develop yellowing (scored 0 to 2.5) were usually short, except IR1321-18-2, Norin 21, Nahda, Habiganj VI, Calrose, Jumala, and Madyan. When grown at 28 C, however, Calrose, Madyan, and Norin 21 were low tillering and therefore useless in transplanted rice culture where temperatures are relatively high during vegetative stage. The tiller number was high in varieties that showed yellowing, except in IR1321-18-2, IR1307-1-3, Habiganj VI, and Caloro, which had green leaves and were medium to high tillering (fig. 12).

The tall seedlings with high tillering capacity like IR8 become yellow easily under low temperatures. Discarding varieties that show yellowing would eliminate the vigorous growth types which are necessary when the temperatures increase rapidly as they do in Dokri, Pakistan, and Katmandu. Most of the green-leaved plants, when grown in these places, flower early or have few tillers. What is needed in these areas is a

12. Degree of yellowing in relation to tiller number of untreated plants 30 days after transplanting.

variety with a growth pattern like that of IR8 but with tolerance to cold temperature at the seedling stage. Some varieties remain green during low temperatures and still have a medium tillering ability as temperature rises. Of the 85 varieties tested, two lines had some promise, IR1321 and IR1307. Both are crosses of IR8, which is high tillering, and a japonica, which is cold tolerant but low tillering at high temperatures. Habiganj VI also showed some cold tolerance combined with vigorous growth at high temperatures.

Survival of submerged rice seeds

Volunteer rice plants occur when the seeds of one crop have fallen on the ground and germinate in the following crop. Volunteer rice is a problem if it is a different variety from the current crop. The problem is serious for farmers who want to have a pure stand, especially if they are growing certified seed. It is also a problem for rice breeders. We studied the viability of rice seeds buried in submerged soils to find ways to control volunteer rice.

13. Percent germination of buried and unburied IR8 and H 4 seeds and percentage of empty grains in the buried seeds.

In a greenhouse experiment, we mixed 100 freshly harvested seeds of IR8 or H 4 with soil and placed the mixture in a perforated plastic bag. The bag was buried 22-cm deep in soil in a porcelain pot and the soil was kept submerged. Samples were taken weekly and germinated at 32 C.

Some seeds of IR8 and H 4 remained viable even 1 year after being submerged in soil (fig. 13). Buried seeds of IR8 responded very differently from buried seeds of H 4. Germination of IR8 decreased with time, to 10 percent about 27 weeks after being buried. Even after 1 year its germination was still about 10 percent however. The low germination was also caused by fewer viable seeds. The percentage of empty grains increased with time of submergence. The control seeds still gave high percentage of germination after 1 year.

Few buried H 4 seeds germinated up to 18 weeks, although the seeds were viable. After this period, however, germination increased rapidly and remained high, 70 to 80 percent, up to 44 weeks of submergence. Buried seeds had more than 40 percent germination even after 1 year of submergence. Compared to IR8, H 4 had few empty grains.

Apparently volunteer rice could appear for at least three crops after the seed was grown. A field experiment was conducted to test this finding. We removed all possible volunteer rice

plants from plots. Before the last harrowing, freshly harvested IR8 seeds were broadcast at approximately 100 seeds per square meter. Fujisaka 5 seedlings were transplanted in some of the plots, leaving the others unplanted. After harvest the field was plowed, harrowed and transplanted with IR661-1-170. After the IR661 was harvested, Fujisaka 5 was again transplanted in the same plots.

Table 17 shows the number of volunteer plants under field conditions when IR8 panicles shattered or seeds were artificially added to the soil. During the first crop, 17 of the 100 seeds broadcast per square meter germinated (Table 17). This is a very high rate of volunteer rice. In the area planted to Fujisaka 5, the number of volunteer plants at harvest time was small. The one-sided competition between transplanted rice and germinating IR8 seeds resulted in a low survival of the volunteer rice plants. In a broadcast or drilled-sown area there may be more volunteer rice at harvest since the competition between the planted crop and the volunteer rice will be more equal than in transplanted rice.

The second crop was IR661, which is easily distinguished from IR8 and Fujisaka 5, by its purple leaf sheath. It was planted 94 days after IR8 seeds were broadcast. The uncropped plot had less than one volunteer plant per square meter and there was no volunteer rice in the cropped plot. The third crop, planted to Fujisaka 5, also showed less than one volunteer rice plant per square meter.

If H 4 seeds had been used instead of IR8 seeds, more volunteer rice might have appeared during the second crop.

The experiment showed that volunteer rice is not a problem in transplanted rice if the variety planted is not of the same plant type and growth duration. But with the mechanization of rice culture, the use of broadcast and drill sowing and mechanical harvesting may spread. The widespread use of these practices would increase the problem of volunteer rice.

Survival of submerged seedlings

Experiments on the responses of rice plants completely submerged in water (1969 Annual Report) were continued.

Seeds of early-short Peta (IR262-43-8) were grown in porcelain trays containing 5 kg soil and added fertilizers. The seedlings were grown for 10 days and then submerged in a tank filled with water 35 cm deep.

Critical length of submergence. The seedlings were submerged for different periods of time. More than 80 percent of the plants survived 6 days of submergence (Table 18). Survival decreased sharply after 6 days of submergence. The survival rates at 8 and 10 days of submergence, however, were not significantly different from each other. Leaves of plants that were submerged for 6 to 12 days remained green while submerged but turned brown upon exposure to air. New leaves, which were much shorter than the older leaves, formed later on some plants.

Water temperature. The seedlings were submerged for 10 days in water at two temperatures. At 25 C, 93 percent of the plants survived; at 30 C, only 64 percent survived.

Turbidity of water. One set of seedlings was submerged in clear water and another set in turbid water (56% light transmittance at tray level at 30 C) for 10 days. In turbid water, 52 percent of the plants survived. Under IRRI field conditions, after heavy rains, water in irrigation ditches has 40 to 90 percent light transmittance. The decrease in available light intensity may be the main cause of the low survival of plants submerged in turbid water.

Under clear water, 91 percent of the plants survived the submergence. The constant stirring of the water in this experiment may have caused the higher percentage of survival than that in the other experiments also using clear water. The turbulence may have increased the diffusion of carbon dioxide in the water which in turn increased the photosynthesis of the submerged leaves. Plants submerged in turbid water had lower amounts of nitrogen, starch, and total sugars, which may have caused the lower percentage of survival and recovery.

Light intensity. To confirm the effect of light intensity, seedlings were submerged for 10 days under low and high light intensity. To obtain a low light intensity the plants were shaded with abaca cloth so that they received only 20 percent of the sunlight. Forty-five percent of

Table 17. Number of volunteer rice plants (IR8) in three successive rice crops (IR8 seeds were broadcast at 100 seeds/sq m before field was prepared for the first crop). IRRI, 1971.

Crop	Volunteer plants (no./sq m)		Date of harvest
	Uncropped plot	Cropped plot	
First	17.0	0.1	May 17
Second	0.8	0.0	Sept. 27
Third	0.7	0.0	Dec. 30

the plants survived at high light intensity and only 10 percent at low light intensity.

Floods occur when light intensities are usually low because of cloudy weather. This condition aggravates the already low light intensity resulting from turbidity. The tolerance of plants would therefore be lower under field conditions.

In a similar experiment in which the submergence depths varied from 0 to 70 cm, measured from the tip of the longest leaf to the water surface, the percentage of survival decreased with depth of water. The lower survival of the plants submerged deeper in water may also be attributed partly to lower light transmittance.

Nitrogen status. The sugar and starch content of rice plants measured in the previous experiments indicated the possible influence of accumulated carbohydrate on the resistance of plants to submergence. So in further experiments, we grew seedlings at two nitrogen levels to vary the carbohydrate content of the plant. Ten-day-old seedlings were submerged for 10 days at a water temperature of 30 C.

The percentage of survival was definitely higher in plants grown at the low nitrogen level (Table 19). The amount of starch in plants

Table 18. Survival of seedlings of short Peta submerged for 2 to 12 days.

Duration of submergence (days)	Survival ^a (%)
Not submerged	100 a
2	100 a
4	97 a
6	90 a
8	49 b
10	52 b
12	25 c

^aAny two means having the same letter are not significantly different at 5% level.

Table 19. Survival and changes in total sugar and total starch of short Peta plants grown at two levels of nitrogen and submerged for 10 days.

Time of measurement	Carbohydrate (%)				Survival (%)	
	Starch		Sugar			
	High N	Low N	High N	Low N	High N	Low N
Initial	3.80	9.73	4.53	5.97	—	—
10 days later						
Control ^a	2.01	8.54	1.43	2.18	100	100
Submerged	1.07	0.88	1.62	0.57	15	79
Difference	0.94*	7.66*	-0.19 ^{ns}	1.61*	85*	21*

^aNot submerged.

grown at both the low and the high level of nitrogen decreased with submergence, but the reduction was greater at the low nitrogen level. The high initial carbohydrate content of the plants, particularly the starch content, is probably an important influence on the resistance of the plant to submergence. The data show that

plants with more accumulated starch and sugar before submergence survive better.

Longer duration of submergence, higher water temperature, greater turbidity, lower light intensity, higher soil nitrogen, and deeper submergence, may decrease the plant's carbohydrate content, and decrease the percentage of survival under submerged conditions.

Establishment of dapog seedlings

In a dapog nurserybed, seedlings are germinated without soil on a flat surface such as a concrete slab or an earthen bed covered with banana leaves. Dapog seedlings can be planted sooner than seedlings from an ordinary wetbed and they have a less pronounced recovery period after transplanting. For farmers the main drawback of dapog seedlings is that they feel many seedlings must be planted per hill to prevent missing hills and ensure good seedling establish-

Table 20. Seedling characters of IR532-1-218 and IR8 30 days after transplanting. IRRI, 1971 dry season.

Nitrogen applied (kg/ha)	Spacing (cm)	Seedlings (no./hill)	Ht (cm)	Tillers (no./sq m)	Leaves (10 ³ /sq m)	LAI	Shoot wt (g/sq m)
<i>IR532-1-218</i>							
0-120	15 x 15	2	48	364	16	1.5	94
		20	46	893	34	2.8	160
	30 x 30	2	50	196	7	0.6	38
		20	50	354	15	1.2	65
60-60	15 x 15	2	57	569	23	2.3	156
		20	59	1155	49	4.9	284
	30 x 30	2	54	291	10	0.8	55
		20	59	468	20	1.9	155
120-0	15 x 15	2	61	795	32	3.3	197
		20	68	1444	62	6.9	376
	30 x 30	2	57	346	11	1.1	71
		20	64	591	25	2.8	160
<i>IR8</i>							
0-120	15 x 15	2	46	396	16	1.5	91
		20	40	991	38	2.5	138
	30 x 30	2	45	173	6	0.4	26
		20	48	297	12	1.1	56
60-60	15 x 15	2	53	547	21	2.2	135
		20	56	1231	50	5.3	273
	30 x 30	2	53	268	9	0.8	46
		20	55	460	19	1.7	104
120-0	15 x 15	2	62	720	28	3.2	183
		20	66	1538	68	6.6	322
	30 x 30	2	55	310	10	0.9	65
		20	60	601	25	2.8	146
LSD (5%) same N application			4	125	6	0.7	31
LSD (5%) between N applications			5	145	6	0.7	33

Nitrogen was applied either 30 days after transplanting (0-120), 60 kg before and 60 kg 30 days after transplanting (60-60), or before transplanting (120-0).

14. Seedling establishment of IR8 and IR532-1-218 (tiller number 30 days after transplanting) in relation to grain yield and yield components.

ment. They plant from two to 40 seedlings per hill with an average of 10 seedlings per hill.

Little is known about the effect of good seedling establishment on grain yield in the tropics. In a study this year with IR8 and IR532-1-218, an early maturing line, we found that better seedling establishment — measured by tillers per square meter, leaves per square meter, LAI, and shoot weight per square meter — was obtained with more nitrogen, more seedlings per hill, and closer spacing (Table 20). The four measures of seedling establishment are closely related. Since tiller number per square meter is the simplest to measure and since measuring tiller number does not destroy the plant we used it to evaluate seedling establish-

ment. It was highly correlated with leaves per square meter ($r = 0.99$), LAI ($r = 0.97$), and shoot weight per square meter ($r = 0.96$).

Although high levels of nitrogen applied before transplanting and closer spacing promoted better seedling establishment, these factors did not greatly affect the grain yields of IR8 and the IR532 line, if the total nitrogen applied was the same (Table 21). The difference in grain yield is small compared to the difference in number of tillers per square meter at 30 days after transplanting (fig. 14). More tillers produced more panicles per square meter at harvest, but this increase was accompanied by a decrease in number of spikelets per panicle and resulted in more or less the same yields.

Table 21. Grain yields of IR8 and IR532-1-218 planted at different spacings, seedling rates, and nitrogen levels. IRRI, 1971 dry season.

Spacing (cm)	Seedlings (no./hill)	Yield (t/ha)			
		0-120 ^a	60-60 ^a	120-0 ^a	LSD (5%)
<i>IR532-1-218</i>					
15 x 15	2	7.5	8.2	8.0	0.7
	20	8.1	7.8	7.2	0.7
30 x 30	2	7.2	7.7	7.9	0.7
	20	8.2	7.6	7.4	0.7
<i>IR8</i>					
15 x 15	2	8.4	8.9	8.5	0.7
	20	6.6	7.4	7.4	0.7
30 x 30	2	7.9	8.0	8.2	0.7
	20	7.3	7.4	7.3	0.7
LSD (5%)		0.6	0.6	0.6	

^a0-120 = 120 kg/ha N applied 30 days after transplanting; 60-60 = 60 kg/ha N applied before and 60 kg/ha N applied 30 days after transplanting; 120-0 = kg/ha N applied before transplanting.

The plants during the cropping season showed little difference in grain yields regardless of the time of application of the fertilizer (Table 21). The growth of the plant after seedling establishment seemed more important in determining grain yields.

Grain yields of IR8 always decreased significantly with increased seedling rates. The high tillering rate of IR8, coupled with its longer growth duration, resulted in lower grain yields as the number of seedlings per hill increased.

In the IR532 line, increased seedling rate did not improve grain yields significantly except when nitrogen was topdressed and no basal application was made. Most early varieties might be expected to require more seedlings per hill under wide spacing because of the short time they have to put out tillers. But that is not true of the IR532 line because it tillers so vigorously. In addition, its short growth duration lessens the period of severe mutual shading of leaves.

With the IR532 line, if all the nitrogen is applied basally, a lower seedling rate gives higher yields. If nitrogen is topdressed 30 days after transplanting, a higher seedling rate gives higher yields. Thus nitrogen application and rates of tillering are closely related. If the rate of tillering is low because of low nitrogen, then high seedling rates will compensate for it, as they do in an early maturing variety.

This experiment shows that increasing the number of seedlings per hill generally has little effect in grain yields; it may even decrease yields. The use of 10 to 40 dapog seedlings per hill is therefore unnecessary. Two seedlings per hill is sufficient even if the nitrogen level is low or the growth duration of the variety is short. The use of a low seedling rate reduces the amount of seeds needed, thereby lowering the cost of production.

Statistics

Two methods of measuring leaf area were evaluated under varying conditions. For the length-width method, an adjustment factor of 0.75 should be used except at harvest at which time 0.67 should be used. For the ratio estimate with dry weight of leaves as covariate, the commonly used procedure of taking the top two leaves of the tallest tiller gave a biased result.

For the measurement of yield components, the sampling procedure using the panicle as the sampling unit was undesirable because of high variation among panicles. Ratio estimate with grain weight as covariate can be used in determining the number of grains.

A plot technique and sampling procedure that adequately measure protein content in varietal tests in spite of the large environmental effects were developed.

A survey was conducted to examine sampling procedures for the estimation of damage from stem borers in farmers' fields. The screening technique was found to give an underestimation of about 5 percent. In the assessment of yield loss, multiple regression techniques gave satisfactory results.

Field plot technique

Missing hills. Previous experiments on the date of occurrence of missing hills (1970 Annual Report), using IR22 as the indicator variety, showed that the death of a hill before 3 weeks after transplanting significantly affected the yield and other characteristics of the adjacent hills. In the 1971 trials, the effects occurred even when the hills died as late as 6 weeks after transplanting, not only for IR22 but also for IR844-86-1 which has longer growth duration and more tillers (Table 1).

These results strongly suggest that plant characters and grain yield should not be measured in hills immediately adjacent to a hill that died before 6 weeks after transplanting.

Replanting dead hills. Previous experiments on replanting dead hills (1970 Annual Report), using seedlings taken from the original seedbed as replanting material, showed that hills replanted 7 days after transplanting or later had lower grain yields, fewer panicles, and shorter plants than the normal hills. While we recommended excluding these replanted hills from measurement of plant characters, we also showed that missing hills must be replanted to provide borders for the surrounding hills.

This year experiments were undertaken to find out which of several sources of replanting

Table 1. Grain yield and panicle number of IR22 and IR844-86-1 hills (unfertilized) surrounding a missing hill that occurred at various dates. IRRI, 1971 dry season. (Data are averages of 14 replicates.)

Missing hill occurrence (weeks after transplanting)	IR22		IR844-86-1	
	Yield (g/hill)	Panicles (no./hill)	Yield (g/hill)	Panicles (no./hill)
0	24.2**	12.7**	26.1**	15.6**
1	23.1**	12.0**	25.4**	15.8**
2	24.4**	12.2**	24.0**	15.7**
3	22.9**	11.7**	25.2**	15.7**
4	21.8**	11.0**	25.5**	15.7**
5	20.9**	10.5**	24.2**	14.8*
6	20.4**	10.5**	23.6*	15.7**
7	18.9	10.1	23.0	13.7
Control ^a	18.3	9.5	21.6	13.6

^aHills surrounded by living hills at all growth stages.

material could best protect the surrounding hills: the original seedbed (source *A*), seedlings left in bunches at the ends of rows (source *B*), or plants thinned from hills in rows (second outermost row in the dry season and outermost row in the wet season) bordering an unplanted alley (source *C*).

Replanting hills with seedlings from the original seedbed (source *A*) gave the poorest results. That is, for each date of replanting, plants from source *A* had lower yields than plants from the other two sources (Table 2). Moreover, the poor growth of replanted hills

Table 2. Grain yield of a replanted hill and its surrounding hills of IR747B₂-6-3 as affected by time of replanting and source of replanting material. IRRI, 1971 dry season (Data are averages of six replicates).

Replanting (days after transplanting)	Yield (g/hill)					
	Source A ^a		Source B ^b		Source C ^c	
	Replanted hill	Surrounding hills	Replanted hill	Surrounding hills	Replanted hill	Surrounding hills
	<i>0 kg/ha N</i>					
7	14.5	14.4	14.6	14.8	15.7	15.4
9	11.9*	14.8	12.4	14.1	13.4	14.9
13	7.3**	15.5	10.8**	14.7	13.4	13.8
15	9.9**	15.2	10.7**	15.3	8.5**	14.1
23	4.6**	15.5	9.4**	15.8	6.8**	14.8
Control ^d		14.4		14.3		14.6
	<i>80 kg/ha N</i>					
7	18.2*	26.3*	19.5	24.8	22.0	25.0
9	15.6**	22.9	20.8	25.7	16.2**	22.8
13	10.5**	25.5*	16.3**	22.2	18.0**	21.5
15	8.2**	24.5	12.3**	24.6	12.4**	22.5
23	3.0**	27.0**	8.6**	22.5	6.7**	25.2
Control ^d		21.6		22.8		23.1

^aOriginal seedbed. ^bBunches left at ends of rows. ^cHills in rows bordering unplanted alley. ^dNormal hills.

from source *A* also affected the yields of surrounding hills.

Seedlings thinned from hills in rows bordering an unplanted alley (source *C*) seemed to be more promising than seedlings left in bunches at the ends of rows (source *B*). In a trial in the wet season, seedlings of IR747B₂-6-3 from source *C* could be used for replanting up to 6 days later than seedlings from source *B* without significant effect on their yield (Table 3). Furthermore, hills from source *B* replanted 15 days after transplanting had a significant effect on surrounding hills, but hills from source *C* did not. This difference, however, did not occur with IR24. The IR747 line has a 3-week shorter growth duration than IR24 and apparently was more affected by the source of seedlings used for replanting.

In summary, material used for replanting should be thinned from hills of the outermost row bordering an unplanted alley; dead hills should be replanted at all times to protect the surrounding hills; and all replanted hills, regardless of time of replanting, should be marked and excluded from measurements of plant characters and grain yield.

Number of plants per hill. Since plant characters and some yield components are affected by the number of seedlings transplanted per hill, we recommended that a constant number of seedlings be used throughout an experiment (1970 Annual Report). This year we tried to determine the optimum number of seedlings to be transplanted per hill. The best number is the one that gives the lowest variability among hills but, for practical reasons, we felt that not more than six seedlings should be transplanted per hill. Thus, for this study we grew from one to six plants per hill of two varieties that differ in tillering capacity, under two nitrogen levels and two plant spacings.

While the 1970 experiments showed little difference in grain yields among one, two, and three plants per hill, this year we found that the number of plants per hill can significantly affect grain yields of both IR127-80-1 and IR844-86-1 (Table 4). In the wet season, one plant per hill consistently gave the lowest yield while six plants per hill gave the highest yield. The number of panicles increased, while the

Table 3. Grain yield of a replanted hill and its surrounding hills of IR747B₂-6-3 and IR24 (unfertilized) as affected by time of replanting and source of replanting material. IIRI, 1971 wet season (Data are averages of three replicates).

Replanting (days after transplanting)	Yield (g/hill)			
	Source <i>B</i>		Source <i>C</i>	
	Replanted hill	Surrounding hills	Replanted hill	Surrounding hills
<i>IR747B₂-6-3</i>				
5	11.5**	—	13.6	13.3
7	9.4**	15.9	12.9	14.6
9	9.7**	15.9	13.5	15.6
11	7.1**	16.4	10.2**	14.3
13	6.5**	14.3	7.7**	15.3
15	5.3**	19.4*	5.8**	14.9
Control ^a	16.0		15.2	
<i>IR24</i>				
5	11.0*	16.8	9.7**	14.2
7	9.9**	15.6	13.0	11.2
9	9.6**	15.0	9.1**	13.3
11	7.9**	14.2	6.4**	15.6
13	5.9**	13.2	6.8**	15.5
15	6.6**	14.6	5.4**	13.8
Control ^a	14.0		14.4	

^aNormal hills.

number of filled grains per panicle, panicle length, and percentage of unfilled grains decreased with more plants per hill (Table 5).

In the dry season, significant effects on grain yield were found only in fertilized plots of the IR127 line. It seems that the performance of

Table 4. Grain yields of IR127-80-1 and IR844-86-1 as affected by the number of plants per hill, under varying conditions. IIRI, 1971. (Data are averages of three replicates.)

Season	N level (kg/ha)	Spacing (cm)	Yield (t/ha)					LSD (5%)
			Plants (no./hill)					
			1	2	3	4	6	
<i>IR127-80-1</i>								
Dry	0	20 x 20	4.60	4.68	4.93	4.95	4.89	n.s.
		25 x 25	4.75	4.65	4.61	4.49	4.78	n.s.
Wet	120	20 x 20	6.61	7.04	7.06	6.97	7.42	0.65
		25 x 25	6.26	6.83	6.35	6.92	6.66	n.s.
	90	20 x 20	2.87	3.52	2.93	3.56	3.76	0.52
		25 x 25	2.50	2.91	2.81	3.10	3.45	0.52
<i>IR844-86-1</i>								
Dry	0	20 x 20	4.32	4.10	3.81	4.31	4.30	n.s.
		25 x 25	4.03	3.97	4.21	3.97	3.96	n.s.
Wet	120	20 x 20	6.94	6.47	6.62	6.72	6.42	n.s.
		25 x 25	6.84	6.84	6.83	6.58	6.62	n.s.
	90	20 x 20	3.76	4.38	4.60	4.52	4.84	0.52
		25 x 25	3.26	3.64	3.53	3.88	4.21	0.52

Table 5. Yield components of IR127-80-1 and IR844-86-1 (90 kg/ha N) as affected by the number of plants per hill. IRRI, 1971 wet season. (Data are averages of 16 hills from two replicates.)

Plants (no./hill)	Panicles (no./hill)	Filled grains (no./panicle)	Unfilled grains (%)	Panicle length (cm)	100-grain wt (g)	Grain:straw ratio
<i>IR127-80-1</i>						
1	4.4	161	45.7	22.0	1.9	0.43
2	5.8	146	43.3	21.6	1.9	0.52
3	5.9	110	45.9	20.6	1.9	0.42
4	8.0	108	34.3	19.5	2.0	0.57
6	7.4	116	36.1	19.5	2.0	0.54
<i>IR844-86-1</i>						
1	11.0	66	29.2	21.4	2.4	0.81
2	9.5	62	28.0	21.2	2.4	0.74
3	9.8	70	19.3	21.1	2.5	0.90
4	10.4	60	33.1	20.2	2.4	0.68
6	13.2	57	21.2	20.5	2.4	0.81
LSD (5%)	1.5	24	n.s.	1.3	n.s.	n.s.

the IR844 line, which is relatively high tillering, was less affected by the varying number of plants per hill. Since planting two seedlings per hill instead of one reduced variability greatly and since planting more than two seedlings per hill did not cause any substantial further reduction in variability (Table 6), we recommend planting at least two seedlings per hill.

The highest percentage of missing hills occurred in plots with one plant per hill (Table 7). Plots with four or more plants per hill did not have significantly fewer missing hills than plots with three plants per hill. Since it is desirable to minimize the occurrence of missing hills to

control experimental error in rice field experiments, two to four plants per hill should be used. The use of one seedling per hill definitely should be avoided.

Residual effect of nitrogen. In field experiments involving application of nitrogen at different levels, the residual effect of previous nitrogen applications can result in bias or in a greater soil heterogeneity in succeeding plantings. To assess the magnitude of the residual effect of nitrogen on rice, we planted IR22 uniformly in an area which in the previous season had been treated with 0, 60, or 120 kg/ha N. We found that grain yield and number

Table 6. Coefficient of variation in plant height and panicle number among hills as affected by the number of plants per hill. IRRI, 1971. (Estimated from 64 hills for the 20 x 20 cm spacing and 60 hills for the 25 x 25 cm spacing.)

Plants (no./hill)	Dry season IR844-86-1 (20 x 20 cm)	Coefficient of variation (%)				Average
		Wet season				
		IR844-86-1		IR127-80-1		
		20 x 20 cm	25 x 25 cm	20 x 20 cm	25 x 25 cm	
<i>Plant height</i>						
1	6.4	7.8	8.8	4.8	9.8	7.1
2	5.1	6.4	5.2	3.4	3.8	4.8
3	5.2	7.4	7.2	4.7	4.3	5.6
4	4.6	4.2	8.8	3.2	3.2	4.8
6	4.1	3.3	4.1	2.9	3.5	3.9
<i>Panicle number</i>						
1	22.7	23.8	18.2	29.6	27.3	24.6
2	21.6	21.9	19.2	23.0	19.5	21.0
3	24.5	20.3	19.4	23.1	19.1	22.4
4	22.7	19.5	16.8	22.6	25.1	22.5
6	18.6	18.9	15.2	19.9	22.9	19.2

Table 7. Percentage of missing hills occurring in fertilized and unfertilized plots of IR127-80-1 and IR844-86-1 as affected by the number of plants per hill. IRRI, 1971 (Data are averages over two plant spacings each having three replicates).

Plants (no./hill)	Missing hills (%)							
	Dry season					Wet season		
	0 kg/ha N		120 kg/ha N		Mean ^a	90 kg/ha N		Mean ^a
	IR127-80-1	IR844-86-1	IR127-80-1	IR844-86-1		IR127-80-1	IR844-86-1	
1	27.1	13.8	24.3	11.9	19.2 a	0.7	0.3	0.5 a
2	16.6	11.9	13.3	7.1	12.2 b	0.3	0.0	0.1 b
3	11.8	8.8	14.2	5.1	10.0 b	0.1	0.0	0.1 b
4	8.8	10.1	8.3	2.2	7.3 c	0.0	0.3	0.1 b
6	6.4	11.4	7.2	1.8	6.7 c	0.0	0.0	0.0 b

^aAny two means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

of spikelets per panicle were significantly higher in plots that received 120 kg/ha N in the previous season (Table 8). No significant residual effect was observed in plots that received 60 kg/ha N in the previous season. Thus the presence of residual effects of nitrogen, though not large, will increase experimental error in following plantings if not properly controlled.

Variability in protein content

Protein content in rice is greatly affected by numerous environmental factors, such as time and rate of nitrogen application, plant spacing, time of harvest, crop season, and location (1970 Annual Report). These environmental effects, if not adequately controlled, make evaluation of genetic differences among genotypes difficult in a varietal test. Our primary concern in this year's study, therefore, was to evolve a plot technique and sampling procedure that can adequately measure protein content in varietal tests, in spite of the large effects of environment. Our evaluation was based on data obtained with 13 varieties grown in two seasons and subjected to different nitrogen levels and plant spacings.

Plot technique. We examined the relative performance of varieties, as affected by the various combinations of fertilizer and spacing variables, and found that under unfertilized conditions and wide spacing of 40 x 40 cm, the interaction between variety and season was relatively small (Table 9). Moreover, varietal difference was higher and experimental error

was smaller than under any of the other conditions tested.

The optimum plot technique for evaluating varieties should accentuate genetic differences among genotypes and at the same time reduce, as much as possible, the disturbances caused by environment and its interaction with genotype. With these requirements as the basis for choosing among various combinations of fertilizer and spacing variables, our results indicate that in varietal tests for protein wide spacing should be used with no nitrogen application.

Sampling technique. Only a small sample is used in the actual chemical analysis for protein

Table 8. Grain yields and other characters of unfertilized IR22 plants grown on areas fertilized with different nitrogen rates in the preceding season. IRRI, 1971 dry season (Data are averages of 12 replicates).

Character	N applied preceding season (kg/ha)			LSD (5%)	cv (%)
	0	60	120		
Plant ht (cm)					
30 DAT ^a	34.5	34.6	35.6	n.s.	6.0
flowering	71.9	72.1	72.2	n.s.	2.8
maturity	73.9	74.0	75.0	n.s.	3.1
Tillers (no./hill)					
30 DAT ^a	9.3	9.4	10.1	n.s.	14.4
flowering	8.9	8.9	9.1	n.s.	9.1
Panicles (no./hill)	9.3	9.5	10.1	n.s.	8.0
Grain:straw ratio	1.18	1.18	1.16	n.s.	4.7
Panicle length (cm)	21.0	20.8	21.2	n.s.	6.7
100-grain wt (g)	2.32	2.29	2.32	n.s.	3.4
Unfilled grains (%)	8.8	8.9	9.3	n.s.	14.7
Filled grains (no./panicle)	62.8	62.9	68.2	4.6	3.0
Yield (t/ha)	3.64	3.75	4.10	0.32	9.3

^aDays after transplanting.

Table 9. Estimates of components of variance in varietal tests for brown rice protein content involving 13 varieties, conducted under varying environmental conditions. IRRI, 1971 dry and wet seasons.

Component of variance	Unfertilized			Fertilized ^a		
	Variance	cv (%)	Proportion of total variation (%)	Variance	cv (%)	Proportion of total variation (%)
			<i>20 x 20 cm</i>			
Among varieties	0.4378	8.1	43.8	0.5243	8.1	50.9
Interaction with season	0.1960	5.4	19.6	0.0377	2.2	3.7
Experimental error	0.3658	7.4	36.6	0.4669	7.7	45.4
			<i>40 x 40 cm</i>			
Among varieties	0.8620	10.7	82.1	0.4732	7.1	55.2
Interaction with season	0.0352	2.2	3.4	0.0000	0.0	00.0
Experimental error	0.1530	4.5	14.5	0.3837	6.4	44.8

^a120 kg/ha N in dry season and 90 kg/ha N in wet season.

content so it must be properly selected. It should give an unbiased estimate and a small experimental error, and it should be practical. We evaluated three types of sampling procedures for determining the protein content of brown rice: *A*) Two 2-gram samples taken from the bulked plot harvest; *B*) grains from the topmost panicle of each of the two hills taken at random from each plot; *C*) grains from four panicles obtained by stratified random sampling with two strata from each of two hills from each plot.

Although the mean values were similar, the error variance was smallest with method *A* (Table 10). This suggests that brown rice protein should be determined from grain samples taken from the bulked harvest of each plot rather than on per-hill or per-panicle bases.

Table 10. Mean and error variance of percentage of brown rice protein determined with three sampling procedures in a varietal test involving different nitrogen levels and plant spacings. IRRI, 1970 wet season.

Sampling procedure ^a	20 x 20 cm		40 x 40 cm	
	Mean	Variance	Mean	Variance
	<i>0 kg/ha N</i>			
<i>A</i>	10.4	0.5246	10.6	0.5168
<i>B</i>	10.3	0.8665	10.7	1.2353
<i>C</i>	10.3	3.3535	10.8	4.4517
	<i>60 kg/ha N</i>			
<i>A</i>	11.0	0.9496	11.1	0.7855
<i>B</i>	10.8	0.7379	11.0	2.5208
<i>C</i>	11.2	3.9138	11.4	4.4021

^a*A*) Two samples taken from the harvest sample; *B*) grains from the topmost panicles of two hills per plot; *C*) grains from four panicles taken by stratified random sampling from two hills per plot.

To compare the determination of straw protein and brown rice protein, two two-hill sampling units were taken at random from each plot. A sample of 10 grains was taken from the threshed grains of each sampling unit and the protein content was determined. For straw protein, the straw of each sampling unit was first chopped into pieces about 2 cm long. These pieces were mixed thoroughly and a sample of about 50 g was ground. The protein content was determined from a subsample of 0.05 g from the ground sample.

The variation in the determination of the protein content of the straw was consistently higher than that in the determination of the protein content of the brown rice (Table 11). Since the mean values of straw protein (dry season: 3.6%; wet season: 4.4%) were much lower than those of brown rice protein (dry season: 8.0%; wet season: 9.2%), the difference in the percentage of error would be even greater. The present procedure for determining the protein content of the straw apparently needs improvement.

Measurement of yield components

For measuring yield components in rice, a sampling technique which stratifies the panicles in a hill according to tiller height was suggested by the findings that the variation of most yield components among panicles within a hill is more than twice the variation among hills (Table 12) and that the values of these characters vary with the height of the tillers (1970 Annual

Report). While the stratified sampling technique increased the precision of estimates, we found that stratifying the panicles is tedious and time-consuming, and that under fertilized conditions, only a small gain in precision is obtained.

A promising alternative procedure is the "ratio method." This procedure eliminates the time-consuming counting of grain. Instead, grain weight, which is easy to measure and is highly correlated with grain number (fig. 1), is used as the auxiliary variate. Thus, the ratio estimate of the total number of grains in a hill, for example, is $R = yX/x$, where y is the number of grains from the sample, x is the grain weight of the sample, and X the grain weight of the whole hill.

We compared the "ratio estimate" with the "direct estimate," a procedure many rice researchers use, with the top two panicles in the hill as the sample. For percentage of unfilled grains, we found that the ratio estimate remedied the underestimation inherent in a direct estimate (Table 13). The variance of the ratio estimate, however, was very high probably because the grains classified as unfilled were actually slightly filled, but to different degrees. Thus, the weight and number were poorly correlated. Apparently a complete count of unfilled grains from all sample hills is necessary. This procedure is not impractical considering that the percentage of unfilled grain is generally small.

For panicle length, the ratio method gave an underestimation while the direct method gave an overestimation. The bias in the ratio method probably occurred because the grain weight per

Table 12. Coefficients of variation among hills and among panicles within hills of some yield components of unfertilized IR8. IRRI, 1969 wet season (Data are averages of 793 panicles from 100 hills).

Character	Mean	Coefficient of variation (%)	
		Among hills	Among panicles
Filled grains (no./panicle)	89.1	11.1	26.4
Unfilled grains (%)	14.1	22.7	49.9
100-grain wt (g)	2.94	9.3	6.1
Panicle length (cm)	21.6	2.9	7.9

unit length is higher in the upper panicles than in the lower panicles (fig. 2).

For number of filled grains per panicle, the direct estimate consistently gave an overestimation while no significant bias was observed from the ratio estimate. In fact, the value derived from the ratio estimate was quite close to the value calculated from complete enumeration of panicles. Furthermore, sampling variance of the ratio estimate was also reduced.

The ratio method thus can be used for determining the number of filled grains per panicle while a complete count of the number of unfilled grains must be used for determining percentage of unfilled grains.

Table 11. Components of error variance for determining protein content in brown rice and in straw based on split-plot experiments with four combinations of fertilizers and plant spacings as main plot and 13 varieties as subplot treatments. IRRI, 1971.

Component of error variance	Brown rice protein		Straw protein	
	Variance	cv (%)	Variance	cv (%)
<i>Dry season</i>				
Main plot error	0.463	8.5	1.448	33.1
Subplot error	0.319	7.1	0.665	22.4
Sampling error	0.291	6.8	1.001	27.5
<i>Wet season</i>				
Main plot error	2.005	15.4	2.866	38.1
Subplot error	0.340	6.4	1.739	29.6
Sampling error	0.770	9.6	1.011	22.6

1. Relation between number and weight of filled grains per panicle of IR8 (unfertilized). IRRI, 1969 wet season.

Table 13. Direct estimate and ratio estimate^a of some yield components of IR8 (unfertilized) and IR579-48-2 (120 kg/ha N), with two uppermost panicles in a hill as sample.

Character	Actual mean	Direct method			Ratio method		
		Estimate	Bias ^b	cv ^c (%)	Estimate	Bias	cv (%)
<i>IR8</i>							
Filled grains (no./panicle)	88.6	107.1	18.5**	19	88.1	-0.5 ^{ns}	15
Panicle length (cm)	21.6	22.6	1.0**	6	19.1	-2.5**	13
<i>IR579-48-2</i>							
Filled grains (no./panicle)	66.7	85.4	18.7**	18	65.0	-1.7 ^{ns}	16
Unfilled grains (%)	21.5	14.2	-7.2**	21	21.7	0.2 ^{ns}	37

^aFrom 100 hills of IR8 and 12 hills of IR579. ^bThe mean difference between the estimates and actual values. ^cCoefficient of variation among hills within plots.

Estimation of leaf area index

The method for estimating leaf area index, the area of leaf surface per unit area of land surface, has two parts: the sampling procedure which specifies the number and location of leaves to be measured, and the procedure for measuring the area of a sample leaf. In the first procedure, the leaf samples selected must adequately represent all leaves in the plot. In the second procedure, the measurement technique must be simple but accurate.

Sampling for leaf area determination. Appropriate sampling procedures can be developed only after determining the magnitude of sources

of variability. Some of the sources of variability in leaf area are variation among leaves within a tiller, variation among tillers in a hill, and variation among hills in a plot. Table 14 shows that leaves within tillers had the largest variation (64% of total variation) followed by tillers within hills (31%). The upper leaves of a tiller were consistently larger than the lower leaves (Table 15). Similarly, taller tillers produced bigger leaves (fig. 3). The variance component among hills was relatively small and sometimes negligible.

Because of the large variation among leaves within tillers (coefficients of variation ranging from 35% to 46%) a complete enumeration of all leaves from a selected tiller seems appropriate. Sampling of tillers should receive more emphasis than sampling of hills.

Leaf area, like other rice characters, should not be sampled from hills in the outermost rows bordering an unplanted alley because the leaf areas are significantly higher than those

2. Relation between grain weight per unit length and height of tillers of IR8 (unfertilized). IIRI, 1969 wet season.

Table 14. Coefficients of variation among hills, among tillers within hills, and among leaves within tillers, of leaf area of IR22 and IR662-2-7 measured at 45 days after transplanting, under varying fertilizer levels. IIRI, 1970 dry season.

N level (kg/ha)	Leaves (no.)	Mean leaf area (sq cm)	Coefficient of variation (%)		
			Among hills	Among tillers	Among leaves
<i>IR22</i>					
0	257	17.5	0.0	18.2	34.8
60	344	17.9	5.0	19.8	42.6
120	298	17.7	5.2	18.3	45.5
<i>IR662-2-7</i>					
0	261	15.1	2.9	25.5	41.0
60	260	15.4	0.0	23.1	46.2
120	423	20.8	10.4	17.7	45.2

3. Relation between leaf size of IR22, measured at 45 days after transplanting, and height of individual tillers in a hill. IRRI, 1970 dry season.

from plants inside the plots. Unfertilized IR22 grown in the 1971 dry season showed a leaf area index of 2.70 from the outermost row and 1.79 from the second row compared with the mean of 1.58 from the third to the fifth rows.

Measuring area of a sample leaf. Two methods of measuring the area of a sample leaf are commonly used—the length-width method and the ratio method.

In the length-width method, the length and

Table 15. Mean leaf area of IR22 and of IR662-2-7 measured at 45 days after transplanting at different positions on a tiller. IRRI, 1970 dry season.

Leaf position ^a	0 kg/ha N		60 kg/ha N		120 kg/ha N	
	Leaves (no.)	Leaf area (sq cm)	Leaves (no.)	Leaf area (sq cm)	Leaves (no.)	Leaf area (sq cm)
	<i>IR22</i>					
1	78	22.2	99	25.2	98	23.7
2	77	18.0	99	18.6	98	16.7
3	68	13.4	92	12.6	76	13.0
4	31	14.0	46	12.4	21	21.1
5	2	11.3	6	12.1	5	10.8
6	0	—	2	3.0	0	—
	<i>IR662-2-7</i>					
1	78	19.7	72	22.1	121	29.2
2	78	16.1	72	16.3	121	21.8
3	68	12.0	65	12.1	104	17.9
4	30	9.0	34	10.5	56	13.2
5	6	5.1	13	5.7	11	8.5
6	1	4.4	3	5.1	3	7.1
7	0	—	0	—	2	4.6

^a1 = the uppermost leaf in a tiller.

4. Correlation between the ratio of length over width and the adjustment factor, K , in the estimation of leaf area based on bi-weekly measurements of leaf area of IR22 and IR662-2-7 under three nitrogen levels. IRRI, 1970 dry season.

maximum width of a leaf are measured and actual leaf area (A) is computed as $A = Klw$, where K is the "adjustment factor," l is the length and w is the width. The accuracy of this procedure depends primarily on the correct choice of the K value. The procedure is most useful when leaf area has to be determined

Table 16. Estimated adjustment factors (K), under varying conditions, in estimating leaf area with the length-width method.

Growth stage (days after transplanting)	0 kg/ha N		60 kg/ha N		120 kg/ha N	
	Leaves (no.)	K	Leaves (no.)	K	Leaves (no.)	K
<i>IR22</i>						
30	126	0.744	96	0.747	74	0.712
45	247	0.724	334	0.702	417	0.711
60	127	0.731	139	0.748	184	0.762
75	206	0.713	257	0.717	385	0.737
90	83	0.644	106	0.659	123	0.677
<i>IR662-2-7</i>						
30	110	0.719	72	0.760	131	0.799
45	247	0.714	243	0.721	285	0.717
60	92	0.716	201	0.749	143	0.753
75	286	0.703	502	0.736	476	0.763
90	155	0.739	241	0.750	279	0.759
105	89	0.644	78	0.698	124	0.697

without the removal of leaves, for example when measuring leaf area at different stages of growth.

The method was evaluated with bi-weekly measurements starting 30 days after transplanting two varieties, IR22 and IR662-2-7. Three levels of nitrogen fertilization (0, 60, and 120 kg/ha N) were used. Actual leaf area was obtained with an automatic area meter. Under all conditions, the assumed relationship was found to be valid. The factor K , however, seemed to vary with the shape of the leaf, which in turn was affected by the variety, fertilizer level, and growth stage of the leaf (Table 16). The correlation coefficient between the estimated K values and the ratios of length over width, representing the shape of leaf, was computed to be 0.69** (fig. 4). It seems, however, that this high correlation was brought about primarily by the low K values at harvest. Hence, except at harvest, a K value of 0.75 should give a reasonably accurate estimate of the leaf area, while at harvest, a K value of 0.67 should be used.

The ratio method uses the relationship between area and dry weight of leaves so it requires the destruction of leaves.

The ratio estimate is computed as $Y = yX/x$, where Y is the total leaf area per hill, y is the leaf area of the sample leaves, X is the total dry weight of the leaves of the whole hill, and x is the dry weight of the sample leaves.

The accuracy of the ratio method depends primarily on the assumption that the relationship between area and dry weight of leaves is linear and passes through the origin. We found that this relationship was valid under all conditions tested. But, when we compared the ratio estimate to the actual leaf area using the top two leaves of the tallest tiller in a hill as the sample leaf area, it gave an underestimation at all growth stages, except at 30 days after transplanting (Table 17). This bias probably occurred because the ratios of leaf area over weight of the sample leaves were different from the ratios of the rest of the leaves in a hill. Except at 30 days after transplanting, the ratio of area over weight of the top two leaves tended to be smaller than that of other leaves (Table

Table 17. Ratio estimates and actual values of leaf area of IR22 and IR662-2-7 measured at different growth stages. IIRI, 1970 dry season.

Growth stage (days after transplanting)	Nitrogen level (kg/ha)	Leaf area (sq cm/hill)					
		IR22			IR662-2-7		
		Ratio estimate	Actual value	Difference (%)	Ratio estimate	Actual value	Difference (%)
30	0	160	180	-13	166	161	3
	60	125	119	5	110	105	4
	120	91	88	2	190	206	-8
45	0	470	498	-6	411	435	-6
	60	628	685	-9	404	444	-10
	120	554	584	-5	911	973	-7
60	0	852	900	-6	591	725	-23
	60	1078	1206	-12	1631	1854	-14
	120	1659	1861	-12	1386	1608	-16
75	0	444	464	-4	682	675	1
	60	711	738	-4	1327	1457	-10
	120	1040	1208	-16	1819	1950	-7

18). The results indicate that the top two leaves of the tallest tiller should not be used as sample leaves for the ratio method.

Estimation of stem borer damage

Survey studies were conducted on farmers' fields in Nueva Ecija during the 1970 wet season and the 1971 dry season to evaluate sampling procedures for estimating the incidence of stem borers and the resulting loss in yield.

Table 18. Comparison between ratios of area over weight of leaves from top two leaves of the tallest tiller and from other leaves in a hill measured at different stages of growth and under varying conditions. IIRI, 1970 dry season (Data are averages of nine hills).

Growth stage (days after transplanting)	Leaf area/unit weight (sq cm/g)					
	0 kg/ha N		60 kg/ha N		120 kg/ha N	
	Top two leaves	Other leaves	Top two leaves	Other leaves	Top two leaves	Other leaves
<i>IR22</i>						
30	185	179	185	177	185	173
45	160	160	155	166	152	156
60	171	181	176	196	176	195
75	170	180	175	182	178	199
<i>IR662-2-7</i>						
30	194	171	204	197	206	228
45	162	171	166	174	179	201
60	141	179	160	188	188	209
75	160	160	174	190	180	203

Bias in the screening technique. Stem borer incidence is generally defined as $P = 100 I/T$, where P is the percentage incidence, I is the number of infested tillers and T is the total number of tillers in the sample area. The usual sampling procedure for estimating percentage incidence is the screening technique (1965 Annual Report). It involves counting the healthy and damaged tillers from infested hills only. The total number of tillers is then computed, assuming that the infested and uninfested hills have the same number of tillers.

Our studies showed that such an assumption is not valid. We found that infested hills had significantly more tillers at all stages of measure-

Table 19. Average number of tillers per hill from the stem borer infested and uninfested hills determined at various growth stages. Nueva Ecija, Philippines, 1970 and 1971.

Growth stage ^a	Tillers ^b (no./hill)		
	Infested hills	Uninfested hills	Difference
	<i>1970 wet season</i>		
50 DAT	18.2	17.1	1.1**
90 DAT	17.2	16.6	0.6*
Harvest	17.1	16.4	0.7*
<i>1971 dry season</i>			
50 DAT	18.0	17.4	0.6**
Harvest	17.4	16.1	1.3**

^aDAT = days after transplanting. ^bFrom four 1-sq m cuts per farm; 32 farms in the wet season and 16 farms in the dry season.

Table 20. Stem borer incidence estimated from complete tiller count and from the screening technique, Nueva Ecija, Philippines, 1970 and 1971.

Stem borer incidence	Growth stage	Complete tiller count	Screening technique	Underestimation (%)
<i>1970 wet season</i>				
Dead hearts	50 DAT	3.88	3.76	3.8**
White heads	90 DAT	1.61	1.56	3.2**
White heads	harvest	2.26	2.14	5.6**
<i>1971 dry season</i>				
Dead hearts	50 DAT	1.91	1.83	4.4**
White heads	harvest	2.08	1.94	7.2**

ment (Table 19). The death of some tillers at early growth stages apparently induced greater tiller production. Hence, estimates of stem borer incidence with the screening technique are biased. Underestimation ranged from 3.2 to 7.2 percent, with an average of 4.8 percent (Table 20).

Multiple regression technique. Regression technique establishing the relationship between the degree of pest incidence and yield is one of the commonly used devices for estimating yield loss. We used our 1970 wet season and 1971 dry season survey data to examine this technique.

Because of the large differences in yield levels, both among different varieties and among farms planting the same varieties, the percentage yield loss was used instead of yield. Percentage yield loss was computed as $(100)(Y_p - Y_o)/Y_p$, where Y_p is the potential yield based solely on the yield of uninfested plants and Y_o is the observed yield coming from both infested and uninfested plants. Simple and multiple linear regression and correlation coefficients, with percentage of yield loss as the dependent variable and stem borer incidences measured at different growth stages as the independent variables, are given in Table 21.

The results show, first, that percentage of white heads measured at about 90 days after transplanting did not significantly improve the assessment of percentage yield loss from that already obtained with percentage dead hearts measured about 50 days after transplanting and percentage of white heads measured at harvest.

Table 21. Estimated simple and multiple regression coefficients and their correlation coefficients (R) in the assessment of percentage yield loss based on stem borer incidences measured at various growth stages in farmers' fields (From 32 farms in the wet season and 16 farms in the dry season). Nueva Ecija, Philippines, 1970/71.

Independent variable ^a	Constant	Regression coefficients				R
		X ₁	X ₂	X ₃	X ₄	
<i>1970 wet season</i>						
X ₁ (0.2-12.6)	1.976	1.677**				0.619
X ₂ (0.3-5.9)	2.028		3.232**			0.467
X ₃ (0.4-6.3)	0.923			2.973**		0.506
X ₄ (13-52)	-6.423				0.519**	0.713
X ₁ , X ₃	-2.214	1.520**		2.529**		0.752
X ₁ , X ₂ , X ₃	-2.163	1.545**	1.329 ^{ns}	1.493 ^{ns}		0.756
X ₁ , X ₂ , X ₄	-7.514	0.819**		2.099**	0.322**	0.826
<i>1971 dry season</i>						
X ₁ (1.0-3.9)	2.426	1.120*				0.283
X ₃ (0.7-3.5)	-1.553			3.131**		0.651
X ₄ (13-31)	2.973				0.088 ^{ns}	0.106
X ₁ , X ₃	-2.987	0.804*		3.006**		0.681
X ₁ , X ₃ , X ₄	-3.986	0.818*		2.978**	0.050 ^{ns}	0.684

^aX₁, X₂, and X₃ are percent incidences measured at 50 and 90 days after transplanting and at harvest; X₄ is the yield potential in g/sq m; data in parentheses show range of values of the independent variable.

For the latter two measures, the multiple correlation coefficient was 0.752 in the wet season and 0.681 in the dry season.

Second, percentage of yield loss varied with the yield level of the different varieties. In the wet season, when eight varieties were involved, the multiple correlation increased appreciably from 0.752 to 0.826 when "potential yield" was used as another independent variable. That is, percentage yield loss was greater with varieties of higher yielding ability.

It seems, therefore, that the percentage yield loss caused by stem borers could be assessed reasonably accurately with two measurements of the incidences, one about 50 days after transplanting and another at harvest and with information on the yielding abilities of the varieties under study. Based on our data, in fields with a potential yield of 4 t/ha, 2% dead hearts and 2% white heads should reduce yield by about 4.9% in the dry season and by 6.4% in the wet season.

Agricultural economics

We continued our analysis of the employment effects of the new rice technology, placing particular emphasis on the factors affecting the rate of mechanization. Tractors are being used principally for land preparation in rice production in some areas. As a result labor used for this activity has declined although, on balance, per-hectare labor requirements with the new rice technology have tended to increase. The rate of increase in tractor use in the Philippines seems to have been influenced more by government policies than by the introduction of high yielding varieties, however.

Analysis of changes in land and labor productivity and in the land: worker ratio shows that the Philippines in 1960 had reached a stage similar to that of Taiwan in 1930 where labor productivity could be increased only through the improvement in land productivity. Growth in irrigation and in yield per hectare have both been instrumental in explaining gains in Philippine land productivity and rice output in the past few years. Farm survey results, however, continue to show that most farmers are not yet approaching the economic yield potential suggested by experimental research.

Rice technology and employment

Many observers are concerned that the new seed-fertilizer technology is leading to a higher rate of mechanization and displacing labor. This year we updated previous work (1970 Annual Report) on employment effects and examined in detail the factors that have influenced the rate of tractor use on farms.

Employment. Changes in labor requirements, machine use, and yield occurred between 1966 and 1970 on 76 farms surveyed along the main highways in Central Luzon and Laguna province (Table 1). About two-thirds of these farms planted high yielding varieties in 1970. There was a modest gain in total labor requirement per hectare but marked changes in labor use occurred (fig. 1). The labor used for land preparation fell from 27 to 15 percent of total labor, while the labor used for weeding rose from 8 to 17 percent.

In a survey of 153 farms in Laguna, which is a very progressive area, all farmers practiced weeding in 1966, even before the introduction of the high yielding varieties (Table 2). One-fourth of the farmers used chemicals only, another fourth used chemicals and hand weeding, and one-fifth used chemicals and mechanical weeding. By 1970, two-thirds of the farmers

were using chemicals plus hand weeding plus mechanical weeding.

The Central Luzon-Laguna survey showed that between 1966 and 1970, non-weeders dropped from 25 to 16 percent while many farmers shifted from hand weeding only to some combination of weeding methods (Table 2).

The two surveys show that the increase in chemical and mechanical weeding has been accompanied by an increase in labor used for weeding. One does not need to travel very extensively in Central Luzon and other parts of the Philippines to recognize that weed control is still a major problem. The introduction of the new seed-fertilizer technology exacerbates the problem because fertilizers stimulate the growth of weeds as well as of rice. Philippine farms are small, but not nearly as small as farms in Japan, Taiwan, Korea, and central Java, so family labor is often inadequate for proper weed control. Policies that encourage mechanical or chemical weeding, therefore, are likely to increase output rather than resulting in labor substitution.

Land preparation is the only task for which labor requirements have declined, and this can be attributed directly to the use of tractors. Four-wheel tractors are more common in Central Luzon than in Laguna where the two-

Table 1. Labor input and mechanization on 76 farms in Central Luzon and Laguna Province, Philippines, 1966-67 and 1970-71 crop year.

Year	Farms (no.)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Labor input (man-days/ha)					Total	Machine users (%)		
			Land preparation	Weeding	Other pre-harvest	Harvesting and threshing	Tractor		Weeder	Thresher	
<i>Rainfed</i>											
1966	30	2.2	19	4	25	17	65	7	0	70	
1970	29	2.5	10	9	24	22	65	48	3	83	
<i>Irrigated one-crop</i>											
1966	28	1.8	18	5	24	16	63	7	4	93	
1970	24	2.7	9	12	25	21	67	50	17	83	
<i>Irrigated two crops—wet season</i>											
1966	18	1.9	13	5	19	24	61	39	17	0	
1970	23	2.9	11	12	26	21	70	46	35	13	
<i>Irrigated two crops—dry season</i>											
1967	18	2.5	12	8	23	18	61	61	22	63	
1971	23	2.6	10	13	26	22	71	74	35	74	
<i>All farms</i>											
1966	76	1.9	17	5	23	18	63	14	9	62	
1970	76	2.7	10	11	23	21	67	49	17	61	

1. Distribution of labor requirements on 76 farms located along the main highways in Central Luzon and Laguna Province, Philippines, 1966 and 1970.

wheel models are more popular. The former are owned by landowners, the latter by tenants. Custom operation is common since less than 10 percent of the farmers using tractors own them. Farmers normally hire tractor services for only a portion of land preparation, usually the plowing. They use water buffalo for harrowing and leveling. When tractor services are contracted, hired labor replaces the labor of the tenant-operator who normally does the land preparation.

Change in labor productivity. The farm survey data suggest that the per-hectare demand for labor for rice production has increased slightly. The increase in labor input is small in relation to the increase in yield. The result is an increase in labor productivity, which is expected from new technology.

The magnitude of the change in labor productivity can be measured by calculating the man-days required to produce a ton of rice (Table 3). From 1966 to 1970 the labor requirement per ton fell from 34 to 25 man-days. But if we compare the 1970 local and the high yielding varieties, the labor requirement differs by only 3 man-days/t because changes occurred on farms growing local as well as on those shifting to high yielding varieties.

The farm survey indicates that the new rice technology has tended to increase the per-hectare demand for labor in rice production. Government policies that encourage tractor

adoption have reduced the labor requirement for land preparation, but this has been offset by increased use of labor for weeding. Fortunately the short-run technological change has increased land productivity rather than displacing labor. Moreover, labor productivity has also increased as expected. Thus in the long run it will take less labor to produce a given quantity of rice, and the incremental change in employment per unit change in output will probably be lower than it has been in the past.

Factors influencing tractor use

A wide range of economic and non-economic factors affect the growth of mechanization in

Table 2. Methods of weeding used by 153 farmers in a Laguna survey and by 76 farmers in a Central Luzon-Laguna survey, 1966 and 1970 wet seasons.

Method of weed control	Farmers (%)			
	Laguna		Central Luzon-Laguna	
	1966	1970	1966	1970
Chemical only	25	0	4	3
Hand only	8	1	53	37
Rotary weeder only	6	1	4	0
Chem. and hand	25	15	9	28
Chem. and rotary weeder	22	11	0	1
Rotary weeder and hand	1	3	1	7
Chem., hand, and rotary weeder	13	69	4	9
No weeding	0	0	25	16

Table 3. Change in labor productivity due to technological change on 76 farms in Central Luzon and Laguna, Philippines, 1966 to 1970.

Category	Labor (man-days/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Labor productivity (man-days/t)
All farms			
1966	64	1.9	34
1970	67	2.7	25
1970 wet season			
Farms growing local varieties	63	2.3	27
Farms growing high yielding varieties	69	2.9	24

rice production. In the Philippines, before the 1960's, tractors were heavily concentrated in the sugar industry. The most rapid increase in tractor use in rice production occurred from 1966 to 1969, which almost coincides with the introduction of high yielding varieties. Although no exact estimates are available, nearly all of the sugarcane area and perhaps one-quarter of the rice area are being served by tractors at present.

We examined three aspects of tractor use in rice production—the economic advantage, the effect of the high yielding varieties, and government policies.

Economic advantage of mechanization. Mechanization becomes profitable when it lowers the cost of producing a commodity. Lower costs can be achieved either by expanding output with existing resources or by producing a given output with a lower level of inputs. In agriculture, the former method increases the productivity of both land and labor. The latter

method usually increases labor productivity by substituting capital for labor.

Relationships among the prices of production factors have a major influence on mechanization activities as can be seen by comparing the Philippines with Taiwan, Thailand, and Japan (Table 4). In Taiwan, the ratio of price per horsepower of mechanical power to daily farm wage is 108 and the horsepower per agricultural worker is 0.07. In the Philippines the cost of mechanical power is higher than in Taiwan and the farm wage is lower so the Philippines has a higher factor price and a lower horsepower per agricultural worker. Although Thailand has a lower farm wage rate than the Philippines, the average price of mechanical power is also lower so that both the factor price ratio and the horsepower per agricultural worker fall between those of Taiwan and the Philippines. The prices of mechanical power in Japan and Thailand are nearly identical, but wages in Japan are about five times the wages in Thailand, hence, the horsepower per worker is much higher in Japan. Small farm size seems to have favored the use of two-wheel power tillers in Taiwan and Japan. On the other hand, rapid growth in use of four-wheel tractors in Thailand has been encouraged by prices that have favored large tractors over power tillers.

The economic advantage of mechanization differs from crop to crop. Among the major agricultural commodities, sugarcane is at present the most highly mechanized crop in the Philippines. The use of four-wheel tractors over a large area gives rise to economies of scale

Table 4. Selected indicators of factor use and factor prices in the Philippines, Thailand, Taiwan, and Japan, in the mid-1960's. Sources: Bureau of Agricultural Economics, Philippines, Central Bank of the Philippines, N. Alviar, unpublished, and Asian Productivity Organization.

	Philippines (1967)	Thailand (1963-64)	Taiwan (1965-66)	Japan (1965-66)
Mechanical horsepower available (000 hp)	279	605	130	15997
Power tiller (000 hp)	13	5	110	15517
Tractor (000 hp)	266	600	20	480
Power per agricultural worker (hp)	0.05	0.06	0.07	1.05
Price of mechanical power (\$/hp)	129	67	112	68
Power tiller (\$/hp)	154	133	112	68
Tractor (\$/hp)	128	66	—	—
Farm wage (\$/day)	0.88 ^a	0.53	1.04	2.60 ^a
Ratio of factor prices ^b	147	126	108	26

^aSince meals were given together with money wages, wages reported for the Philippines were raised by 33% and for Japan by 10%.

^bPrice of mechanical power divided by farm wage.

Table 5. Grain yield and percentage of tractor users by farm size in Gapan, Nueva Ecija, 1970 wet season.

Farm size (ha)	Farms (no.)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Tractor users (%)
<i>Irrigated</i>			
Less than 2	83	2.9	20
2 to 4	221	2.6	37
More than 4	21	2.2	43
<i>Rainfed</i>			
Less than 2	27	1.9	26
2 to 4	81	1.8	22
More than 4	24	1.6	33

which have made it profitable to substitute capital for labor even when wage rates are relatively low.

Rice does not offer the same economic advantage to mechanization as sugarcane. First, certain tasks in rice production are not easily mechanized. Tractors do not operate efficiently in deep mud and can frequently be used only for plowing, with water buffalo doing the harrowing. Second, rice farms are much smaller than sugarcane operations.

Even among rice farms, size influences the rate of tractor adoption. On both irrigated and rainfed farms in Gapan, Philippines, in 1970, higher tractor use was observed on the large farms while average yields were higher on the smaller farms (Table 5).

Influence of high yielding varieties. The relationship between increasing use of tractors and the introduction of the high yielding varieties can be seen by examining the farm survey data from the Central Luzon-Laguna study (Table 1). The most rapid increase occurred in 1966 and 1967 (fig. 2), while the first major planting of high yielding varieties was made in the latter half of 1967. Thus, the upsurge in tractor use was already in progress before the high yielding varieties were available. Furthermore, when farms growing rice in the wet season of 1970 were divided into those planting high yielding varieties and those planting local varieties, we found that in both groups 49 percent were using tractors. The growth in tractor use slowed greatly in 1969 and 1970, the period in which high yielding varieties were being widely adopted. Therefore, introduction of the high yielding varieties does not seem responsible for the change in the rate of tractor adoption.

Table 6. Items purchased with loans from the Central Bank's first and second loan programs (Source: Central Bank of the Philippines).

Item	Distribution (%)	
	First loan program \$5 million Apr. '66 to May '68	Second loan program \$12.5 million ^a Sept. '69 to Aug. '71
Four-wheel tractors	66.3	68.6
Power tillers	21.6	7.4
Other	12.1	24.0

^aLess than 20% was released during the first 2 years of this 3½ year program.

Government programs and mechanization. The Central Bank of the Philippines has negotiated two loans with the International Bank for Reconstruction and Development to promote farm mechanization. The first loan, for \$5 million, covered the period from April 1966 through May 1968. The second, for \$12.5 million, began in September 1969 and will expire in March 1973. Both programs have been administered through the rural banking system. They were designed to encourage mechanization on small farms, defined as operational units of not less than 5 hectares nor more than 50 hectares. An examination of the geographical distribution of loans under this agreement shows that they were heavily concentrated in the rice growing areas of Central Luzon.

The first loan program resulted in a rapid expansion of tractor sales. Most of the money loaned was used for purchases of four-wheel tractors on larger farms (Table 6). Sales of

2. Proportion of farmers using tractors for land preparation by year and type of farm, 76 farms on main highways in Central Luzon-Laguna, Philippines.

3. Annual sales of power units under Central Bank credit programs, 1966 to 1970. Source: Agricultural Machinery Dealers Association and Central Bank of the Philippines.

power tillers also increased rapidly, however (fig. 3). When funds from the first credit line were exhausted, power tiller sales fell sharply.

The second loan preceded the adoption of the floating peso exchange rate by only a few months. When the floating rate was adopted in February 1970, local peso counterpart funds for financing became difficult to obtain and the rise in machinery prices discouraged purchases. In addition, financial requirements for obtaining loans through the second program became stricter and in particular hurt the sales of power tillers to smaller farmers. These requirements plus the higher machinery prices resulting from devaluation discouraged tractor and power tiller purchases, although the impact was not as dramatic as the expiration of the first loan program. As a result during the first half of the second loan period of 3½ years, only a small part of the \$12.5 million was used. The bias toward four-wheel tractor purchases (Table 6) is even more pronounced than under the first loan, and power tiller sales have fallen to 7.4 percent of the total funds released.

The foreign exchange rate has also had a major effect on the domestic price of tractors and, hence, on tractor sales. From price indices for durable equipment, tractors, work animals, and farm labor (fig. 4), it is apparent that

government policies on foreign exchange and wages have greatly influenced changes in prices of machinery and farm wages. As a result of a gradual devaluation of the peso (from P2 = US\$1 to P4 = US\$1), which had its major impact between 1959 and 1962, the price of machinery rose rapidly. Between 1963 and 1969, the cost of work animals and farm wages tended to increase somewhat more rapidly than the price of machinery and durable goods. Also, during this period, the minimum wage was increased and the first Central Bank loan program was exhausted. The adoption of the floating rate in 1970 (about P6.40 = US\$1) again resulted in a sharp rise in the prices of imported durable goods. But the cost of work animals rose simultaneously because of inflationary pressures. Farm wages are rising due to another increase in the minimum wage in June 1970.

While higher incomes generated by the use of high yielding varieties have probably permitted more small farmers to purchase hand tractors or rent tractor services, it seems clear that the large increase in tractor purchases after 1965 could not have occurred without the two Central Bank loan programs for mechanization. These loans apparently were the biggest single influence on tractor purchases between 1966 and 1970.

Trends in Philippine agriculture

We analyzed historical trends in resource use and productivity in terms of their relationships with labor productivity. Labor productivity, although a partial measure, is usually considered a good indicator of economic efficiency. Labor is a major input and increased labor productivity leads to a higher per capita income and standard of living.

Our analysis is based on the relationships:

$$Y/L = (Y/D) (D/L) \quad (1)$$

$Y/D = (Y/K) (K/D)$, and $Y/L = (Y/K) (K/D) (D/L)$, where Y is gross value of crops and livestock production at constant prices (average of 1955, 1960, and 1965 prices); K is the value of annual fixed capital services consisting of farm equipment, work animals, and irrigation, and cost of operating capital consisting of

feeds, seeds, fertilizer, agricultural chemicals, and irrigation fees at constant prices; L is labor measured in number of workers employed; and D is land measured in hectares of cultivated land area.

Increases in labor productivity (Y/L) can be achieved by raising land productivity (Y/D) or increasing the land:worker ratio (D/L). Since the decline of the land:worker ratio is inevitable as the farm population grows, increased land productivity must offset this decline if labor productivity is to increase. Reducing labor use and thus raising the land:worker ratio does not solve the productivity problem if labor is abundant and few alternative opportunities for employment exist. Increasing land productivity, on the other hand, can be accomplished by improving capital productivity (Y/K), for example by introducing high yielding varieties or by increasing the degree of capital intensity (K/D), for example by irrigating two crops a year instead of one.

But the complementary relationship between capital productivity and capital intensity means that a technology which increases capital productivity at the same time raises the profitable level of capital intensity. In other words, increases in labor productivity depend on the relative use of complementary inputs—land and capital—and their respective productivities. With limited land and abundant labor, the growth of agriculture through increases in labor and land productivity ultimately depends on the rate and efficiency of capital use in agriculture.

Post-war Philippine agriculture has been characterized by changing development patterns. These patterns may be identified in terms of changes in the relationship between land productivity and the land:worker ratio. We compared the historical experience of the Philippines with that of Taiwan, a country which like the Philippines has been confronted with abundant labor and scarce capital, but which is at a more advanced stage of development. This comparison is useful in illustrating the periods at which the two countries were at a similar stage of development and the pattern of development necessary if labor productivity is to increase in Philippine agriculture.

Figure 5 represents equation (1) for the agricultural sectors of the Philippines from 1948 to 1968 and of Taiwan from 1896 to 1960. The growth path for labor productivity (Y/L) is charted by plotting land productivity (Y/D) against land:worker ratio (D/L). The variables are expressed in index numbers. Each point in the figure denotes a combination of 3-year averages for the Philippines and 5-year averages for Taiwan of Y/D and D/L , giving a level of labor productivity (Y/L) as represented by the isoquants.

The growth process in Taiwan and the Philippines may be classified into three phases, each reflecting different trends in capital intensity (K/D) and capital productivity (Y/K) (which taken together determine land productivity), and in land:worker ratio.

Phase 1 in Philippine agriculture (Table 7) was characterized by land-extensive cultivation: the cultivated area increased at a higher rate than the growth of agricultural labor. Population pressure on the land was alleviated by opening new lands for cultivation. At the same time moderate increases in land productivity occurred because of increasing capital intensity per unit of cultivated area, despite a deterioration in capital efficiency. Labor productivity increased at 3.1 percent per year during this phase. Similar indices published by R. Hooley for 1902 to 1948 indicate that the land expanded more rapidly than the agricultural labor force

4. Price indices of tractors, durable equipment, work animals, and agricultural labor. Source: C. Crisostomo (unpublished).

5. Historical growth path of labor productivity of agriculture in the Philippines, 1948 to 1968 (1960 = 100), and in Taiwan, 1896 to 1960 (1926-30 = 100). Source: C. Crisostomo (unpublished) and T. H. Lee (unpublished).

in the pre-war period, too. Thus, for the first 6 decades of the century, productivity gains were attained within the framework of traditional agriculture and with increasing use of relatively limited land and capital resources. This phase corresponds to Taiwan's Phase 1 which occurred from 1896/1910 to 1926/1930. The growth rate in labor productivity in Taiwan, 2.7 percent per year, is remarkably similar to that of the Philippines in its Phase 1.

In Phase 2 in the Philippines, the trend in resource use in Phase 1 was continued, but the results were disappointing. Although cultivated area continued to expand more rapidly than the use of labor and growth in capital intensity per unit of land area was at a rate almost 50 percent higher than that in the previous phase, growth in inputs exceeded growth in output. Partial productivity indices for land, labor, and capital all declined. It appears that cultivation was extended to marginal land and increasing capital use per unit of land could not compensate for the land's low productivity. The result was a rapid decline in capital productivity. But only 3 years are averaged, so the decline in productivity may be due in part to a drop in yield as a result of poor weather.

Taiwan seems to have had no comparable phase except during World War II. Apparently the point of diminishing returns to land was successfully offset by capital investment and the technical change started in Taiwan's Phase 1.

In Phase 3 in the Philippines, the unfavorable trends of the previous period were reversed. Although population pressure on cultivated land continued to grow, as shown by a declining land:worker ratio, labor productivity managed to improve at a moderate pace because of a higher rate of growth in land productivity. Capital intensity likewise increased and capital productivity, while still declining, decreased at a relatively slower rate. Moreover, the nature of the capital increase seems to have been labor-complementing. In this phase an increase in labor intensity per unit of cultivated area accompanied the increase in capital intensity. In contrast, in the previous phases labor intensity declined as capital intensity increased.

Phase 3 in the Philippines may be characterized as the general case of agricultural development comparable to Taiwan's Phase 2. But labor productivity in Taiwan was increasing at a much faster rate during this period in spite of the greater population pressure exemplified by its relatively smaller farm size. This is not surprising since Taiwan at this time was relatively more advanced in the development of its irrigation infrastructure and use of fertilizer (Table 8).

Table 7. Annual rate of growth of resource productivities and resource intensities in the Philippines and Taiwan. (Sources: C. Crisostomo, unpublished, and T. H. Lee, unpublished).

Phase	Period	Annual increase (%)				
		Labor productivity	Capital intensity	Land per worker	Capital productivity	Land productivity
<i>Philippines</i>						
1	1948/50-1954/56	3.06	2.90	0.90	-0.98	1.95
2	1954/56-1957/59	-0.79	4.58	0.81	-5.85	-1.25
3	1957/59-1966/68	1.33	3.40	-1.34	-0.62	2.69
<i>Taiwan</i>						
1	1896/1910-1926/30	2.71	5.42	0.1	-3.26	1.87
2	1926/30-1936/40	2.23	3.18	-0.93	-0.36	3.15
3	1946/50-1956/60	5.29	9.02	0	-0.30	6.29

The pattern of resource use and productivity in the post-war agriculture of Taiwan (Phase 3), where the doubling of labor productivity between 1946 and 1960 resulted entirely from improvements in yield per hectare of land area, should serve as a model for the next phase of Philippine agricultural development. Rapid improvements in land productivity are now needed in the Philippines to offset the declining land: worker ratio to achieve increases in labor productivity. It should be emphasized that we have defined land productivity as output per unit of land area and, thus, it can be increased by a technology such as irrigation which permits double or multiple-cropping and by a technology which increases yield per hectare of crop area.

The transition periods in each country from increase in output through increase in land area to increase in output through increase in land productivity have some common features which

influence the pattern of agricultural development and also some important differences which explain the higher growth rate in both labor and land productivities in Taiwan. The most notable common factor is the introduction of high yielding varieties of rice. Rice is Taiwan's staple food and its most important crop in terms of production and area. The "ponlai" rices, introduced in 1922, had a potential yield 40 percent higher than the traditional varieties available at that time. Within 15 years after their introduction, approximately 50 percent of Taiwan's rice area was planted to ponlai rices. In addition, the application of chemical and organic fertilizers and pesticides increased, and irrigation facilities were expanded.

In 1966, rice varieties with yield potentials of 5 to 7 t/ha were introduced in the Philippines. The adoption of these varieties has been widespread in areas where the environment is conducive to their use. This technological breakthrough induced a general intensification of government efforts in agriculture, particularly extension work, seed distribution, and irrigation development. Farm surveys show also that farms shifting to high yielding varieties increased their use of modern inputs, such as fertilizers and agricultural chemicals.

Although only a few years have elapsed since the introduction of the high yielding varieties in the Philippines, an upward shift in yields has occurred that is even more dramatic than that caused by the adoption of ponlai seeds in Taiwan in 1922 (fig. 6). The explanation is the more rapid adoption of the new high yield-

Table 8. Selected characteristics of the agricultural sector in the Philippines in 1960 and Taiwan in 1930. (Sources: Bureau of Census and Statistics and Bureau of Agricultural Economics, Philippines, Fertilizer Institute of the Philippines, T. H. Lee unpublished, Y. Hayami and V. Ruttan, *Agricultural Development: An International Perspective*).

Characteristic	Philippines	Taiwan
Farm size (ha)	3.58	2.00
Cultivated area per agricultural worker (ha/man)	1.08	0.68
Crop area per agricultural worker (ha/man)	1.45	0.83
Proportion of irrigated area to cultivated area (%)	11	53
Chemical fertilizer consumption per unit crop area (kg/ha)	26	33

ing varieties. In the Philippines, approximately half of the rice crop area was planted to the new high yielding varieties within 5 years after introduction.

The new technology may, however, lead Philippine agriculture into a new phase by a different path because of differences between the two countries. In general, Philippine agriculture has been subjected to less population pressure than Taiwan's agriculture and has had less infrastructural development, particularly investment in irrigation facilities. These characteristics have resulted in a lower intensity of land use. In the Philippines in 1960, the average farm size was 80 percent higher than in Taiwan in 1930 and the cultivated area per agricultural worker was 60 percent higher. In 1930, the proportion of irrigated area in Taiwan was almost five times that of the Philippines in 1960. The difference in resource endowments (land and labor) seems to explain the differences in government policies toward the development of infrastructure during these periods.

The Philippine government pursued a vigorous program of land settlement during Phase 1 and 2. Taiwan, during its Phase 1, was already laying the foundation for a more intensive

6. Average yields of rough rice in Taiwan and the Philippines. Source: Bureau of Agricultural Economics (Philippines) and Taiwan Provincial Land Bureau.

agriculture. Investment in irrigation development reached a pre-war peak in the 1920's, at about the time the high yielding "ponlai" rice varieties were introduced. These developments were the result of efforts of the Japanese government to increase exports of rice from Taiwan to Japan. The growth of productivity in Philippine agriculture during the 1960's was much lower than that of Taiwan's agriculture in the 1930's as a result of delays in the development of infrastructure and technology.

Causes of growth in rice production

Yields of rice in the Philippines remained rather constant before 1960, but crop area expanded rapidly keeping pace with population growth. After 1960, crop area remained constant but yields rose, stimulated in part by the rise in the proportion of crop area irrigated.

The first major planting of the high yielding varieties occurred in the wet season (first half) of the crop year 1967-68. By the 1970-71 crop year, half of the 3 million hectares planted to rice were in high yielding varieties (Table 9). The new varieties have been planted principally in the irrigated areas, but there has also been a steady increase in plantings in non-irrigated (rainfed) areas.

The growth in rice output was greatly affected by the change in yield, the change in irrigated area, and the change in non-irrigated area (Table 10). From 1948 to 1960, all three factors made about the same contribution to growth. In the early 1960's, the rainfed paddy area declined largely as a result of strong competition from an expanding sugar industry. Due to a decline in the crop area, the production growth rate slowed and depended entirely on the growth in yield per hectare. In the late 1960's, irrigation expansion in Luzon made a major contribution to the 4.6 percent annual growth rate, but yield increases also played a significant role.

The largest expansion in irrigated land area occurred in the three regions of Luzon (Table 11). A large decline occurred in rainfed rice in Northern Luzon and in upland rice in Southern Luzon. Mindanao showed an appreciable decline in both rainfed and upland rice.

Table 9. Percentages of lowland rice planted to high yielding varieties on irrigated and non-irrigated lands in the Philippines, 1967-68 to 1970-71. (Source: Bureau of Agricultural Economics, Philippines. Includes IRRI, UPCA, and BPI varieties).

Crop year	Area of lowland rice in high yielding varieties (%)		
	Total	Irrigated	Non-irrigated
1967-68	22	33	13
1968-69	41	54	28
1969-70	50	61	39
1970-71	57	67	45

What impact has the introduction of the high yielding varieties had on production growth? The yield contribution alone to annual growth in output has been about 2 percent per annum between 1964/66 and 1969/71. In addition, the expansion of irrigated area as well as the decline in nonirrigated area may have been the direct or indirect result of the introduction of high yielding varieties. It is impossible to consider those effects independently and therefore impossible to say precisely how much of the 4.6 percent growth rate should be attributed to high yielding varieties. Nevertheless, the yield gains have not come up to the expectation of many scientists and policy makers.

Rice production and input use in Gapan

A study of the diffusion of high yielding varieties of rice in the municipality of Gapan, Nueva Ecija, Philippines, was completed in 1969 (1969 and 1970 Annual Reports). In 1970

Table 10. Annual growth in rice production and contributions of change in yield per hectare, irrigated area, and non-irrigated area to growth for selected time periods and regions in the Philippines from 1948 to 1971. (Source: Bureau of Census and Statistics and Bureau of Agricultural Economics, Philippines).

Period ^a	Annual production growth (%)	Production growth (%) due to change in		
		Yield per hectare	Irrigated crop area	Non-irrigated crop area
1948-1960	4.6	31	36	33
1961-1964/66	1.7	136	-6	-30
1964/66-1969/71	4.6	60	82	-42

^a1948 refers to the crop year from July 1947 to June 1948 and similarly for all years.

a second survey was started to study changes in yields and in the use of inputs. Farm operating units were stratified according to tenure. A 20 percent sample of share tenant and leasehold farms (cash rent farms representing more than 90 percent of the total) was drawn in each barrio. Due to the small population, a 40 percent sample of owner-operators was drawn. We interviewed 513 farmers to identify trends in yield and input use between 1965 and 1970.

Irrigation facilities. The sample of farms was divided according to irrigation facilities and a comparison was made of varieties planted, yields, and input use. All irrigated two-crop farms were further subdivided first by size and tenure group and then by barrio to compare yield and input differences.

A sharp difference exists in the rate of adoption of high yielding varieties on irrigated land

Table 11. Change in area of rice production by land type, Philippines 1948 to 1971. (Source: Bureau of Census and Statistics and Bureau of Agricultural Economics, Philippines).

Area	Total crop area (000 ha)			Change in crop area (000 ha)		
	Start of period	End of period	Total change	Irrigated lowland	Nonirrigated lowland	Upland
Philippines						
1948-1960	1834	2730	896	365	209	322
1961-64/66 ^a	3198	3132	-66	-10	-100	44
1964/66-1969/71	3132	3186	54	483	-213	-216
Regions (1964/66-1969/71)						
Northern Luzon	464	449	-15	119	-125	-9
Central Luzon	508	628	120	125	3	-8
Southern Luzon	762	743	-19	117	-31	-105
Visayas	685	699	14	47	-11	-22
Mindanao	712	667	-45	76	-50	-71

^aThe large difference between the total crop area for 1960 and 1961 is partly due to the differences in sources. The census area figures for a given year are always lower than the area estimates of the Bureau of Agricultural Economics.

7. Proportion of area planted to high yielding rice varieties (HYV) and yield and input use for all varieties by land type in the wet season. Gapan, Nueva Ecija, Philippines.

as compared with rainfed land (fig. 7). Change has been most rapid on the irrigated two-crop farms. Almost all of these farms have adopted the high yielding varieties and the level of nitrogen application has risen from 10 kg/ha

to 50 kg/ha. Considering the magnitude of change in inputs, the yield increase of little more than half a ton seems somewhat modest.

Nearly all irrigated farms switched from local to high yielding varieties between 1967 and 1970 (Table 12). In 1970, however, 43 percent of the rainfed area was planted to both local and high yielding varieties. On the irrigated farms, the move from local to high yielding varieties seems to have raised the yield level from 2.2 to almost 3 t/ha. No yield advantage for high yielding varieties on rainfed land was distinguishable until 1970. At the same time, rainfed farmers themselves clearly saw an advantage for high yielding varieties, particularly IR5, as shown by the continued expansion in the area planted to them. If we accept these yield differences between local and high yielding varieties as being accurate, the benefit:cost ratio for the increase in cash inputs even on the rainfed land would be at least 4 to 1.

We asked each farmer to indicate his expected yield under average conditions, the best conditions, and the worst conditions. The yield expectations of the farmers in the irrigated two-crop area under average conditions were almost the same as the yields they reported in the 1970 wet season (Table 13). But under average conditions rainfed farmers felt that they would obtain yields 33 percent higher (from 1.8 to 2.4 tons) by using high yielding varieties. Under the worst as well as under the best con-

Table 12. Area, grain yield, and nitrogen applied for high yielding varieties (HYV) and local varieties on irrigated and rainfed farms in Gapan, 1965 to 1970.

Year	Area (%)			Yield (t/ha)				Nitrogen ^a (kg/ha)			
	HYV	Local	Mixed	HYV	Local	Mixed	Avg	HYV	Local	Mixed	Avg
<i>Irrigated two-crop farms</i>											
1965	0	100	0	—	2.2	—	2.2	—	10	—	10
1966	1	99	0	3.4	2.2	—	2.2	12	12	—	12
1967	8	92	1	2.9	2.3	1.8	2.3	40	14	22	16
1968	35	59	6	2.8	2.2	2.1	2.4	37	15	25	23
1969	75	18	7	3.0	2.0	2.4	2.8	45	21	33	41
1970	94	1	4	2.8	1.9	1.6	2.7	48	33	34	47
<i>Rainfed paddy</i>											
1965	0	100	0	—	1.7	—	1.7	—	10	—	10
1966	0	98	2	—	1.8	2.9	1.8	—	10	21	10
1967	0	98	2	—	1.9	4.2	2.0	—	13	0	13
1968	3	94	4	1.1	1.7	2.8	1.7	37	15	15	16
1969	9	78	13	1.5	1.5	1.9	1.6	36	18	17	19
1970	16	41	43	2.1	1.7	1.7	1.8	32	16	18	20

^aAverage of all farmers whether or not they used nitrogen.

ditions, farmers expect high yielding varieties to out-perform local varieties.

The first of the high yielding varieties to be introduced into Gapan, IR8, reached a peak in acceptance in 1968 when it was planted on almost one-third of the irrigated farms (Table 14). By 1969, IR5 and C4-63 had surpassed IR8 in popularity. By 1970, IR8 had almost disappeared in Gapan and IR20 was the most popular variety. Although we do not have complete records for 1971, it is clear that IR22 and IR20 were the two most popular varieties in the irrigated areas during the past wet season.

Rainfed farms were much slower to adopt the new varieties but by 1970, IR5 had gained considerable acceptance. In 1971 it undoubtedly was the most widely planted variety in the rainfed area.

Farm size and tenure. In many parts of Asia, farm size has an important influence on the rate of adoption of the new technology. It has been observed that large farms with a stronger financial base are the first to adopt, and some writers argue that large farms are gaining an economic advantage over small farms. The term "large," however, is relative. In the Philippines, under the existing tenure system, nearly all rice farm operating units tend to be fairly small. This is particularly true in Gapan where only 54 of the 513 farms surveyed exceeded 4 hectares.

Over the years there has been a consistent difference in yield according to farm size in Gapan (fig. 8). Small irrigated farms have had

Table 13. Average yield in sample and farmers' yield expectations on irrigated and rainfed farms. Gapan, Nueva Ecija, 1970 wet season.

Variety	Farms (no.)	Yield reported (t/ha)	Yield expectation ^a (t/ha)		
			Average condition	Best condition	Worst condition
<i>Irrigated two-crop</i>					
Local	16	1.9	2.0	2.6	1.4
HYV	321	2.8	2.8	3.8	1.8
<i>Rainfed</i>					
Local	109	1.7	1.8	2.6	1.0
HYV	68	2.1	2.4	3.4	1.5

^aBased on answers from 322 irrigated two-crop farms and 131 rainfed farms. Some farms grew both local and high yielding varieties.

Table 14. Varieties grown on irrigated two-crop and rainfed farms, Gapan, Nueva Ecija, wet season, 1966 to 1970.

Year	No. of farms planting							
	IR20	IR8	IR5	C4-63	Binato	Intan	Tjeremas	Other
<i>Irrigated two-crop</i>								
1966	0	2	0	0	290	0	0	14
1967	0	19	2	2	288	0	0	7
1968	0	94	18	20	204	0	0	8
1969	8	58	127	88	67	0	0	22
1970	190	3	67	75	8	0	0	26
<i>Rainfed paddy</i>								
1966	0	0	0	0	0	89	33	2
1967	0	0	0	0	0	96	34	2
1968	0	0	2	0	0	99	34	7
1969	0	0	21	11	0	98	36	9
1970	12	0	47	21	0	88	29	17

higher yields than large ones. This is true even though there is no difference in rate of adoption of high yielding varieties or rate of nitrogen

8. Grain yield, percentage of area planted to high yielding rice varieties, and nitrogen input by size and tenure status on irrigated two-crop farms, wet season, Gapan, Nueva Ecija.

Table 15. Grain yield for irrigated two-crop farms, by tenure and farm size, Gapan, Nueva Ecija, 1970 wet season.

Farm size (ha)	Yield (t/ha)			Mean
	Leasehold	Share tenant	Owner operator	
Less than 2	2.7	3.2	2.9	3.0
2 to 4	2.6	2.6	2.7	2.6
Over 4	2.3	^a	^a	2.2
Mean	2.6	2.7	2.7	

^a Average yield not calculated for categories with less than 10 farms.

input among farm size groups. One hypothesis which we have not yet fully tested is that the small farms tend to be located on the more fertile soils. The only other factor besides yield that seems to be influenced by the size of farm is the rate of mechanization (Table 5).

The yields of share tenant and leasehold farms in 1970 were essentially the same, although owner-operators tended to show a lower rate of adoption of high yielding varieties and a higher level of fertilizer input (fig. 8). It should be noted that the leasehold farmers as of 1970 were not all in leasehold during the previous 5 years.

Table 15 presents a cross classification of farms by tenure and size. A chi-square test indicated that there was no significant relationship between size and tenure. On small farms, however, yields are significantly higher for share tenants than for operators of leasehold farms. There is no apparent explanation for

Table 16. Grain yield, nitrogen applied, and farm size for two-crop irrigated barrios, Gapan, Nueva Ecija, 1970 wet season.

Village	Yield ^a (t/ha)	Nitrogen ^a (kg/ha)	Farm size ^a (ha)
San Nicolas	3.7 a	75 a	2.3 ab
Santo Cristo S.	2.9 b	64 ab	2.8 bc
Santo Cristo N.	2.8 b	63 ab	2.7 abc
Malimba	2.3 b	48 abc	2.1 a
Pambuan	2.6 b	47 abc	2.3 ab
Mangino	2.7 b	40 bc	2.7 abc
Baluarte	2.7 b	40 bc	2.9 c
Santa Cruz	2.3 b	33 bc	2.4 abc
Kapalangan	2.7 b	21 c	2.2 a

^a Any two means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

this. Yields also differ significantly by size group for all farms.

Differences among barrios. When yields and input levels are examined by barrio, San Nicolas stands out (Table 16). What explains its high yields—better management, higher level of input use, better soils, or some combination of these factors? The rate of fertilizer application is the highest among the barrios. The farm size is relatively small suggesting that the soils may in fact be very productive. The irrigation facilities do not appear to be superior to those in several of the other barrios, although in 1970 this part of the municipality did receive water priority which allowed plantings to take place about a month earlier than other areas. Farmers themselves suggest that one reason for their good performance is the proximity of their houses to the rice fields.

After San Nicolas, the neighboring barrios of Santo Cristo Norte and Cristo Sur show the highest yield and fertilizer levels. These three barrios appear to have had the highest yields even before the introduction of the high yielding varieties. For the remaining six barrios, there is no relationship between yield level and fertilizer input. The multiple range tests indicate that there is a wide variability in yields and nitrogen input per hectare within the barrios.

In general, straight-row planting is not practiced in Gapan. Only 26 of the 513 farms interviewed used straight-row planting in the 1970 wet season. Of this number almost half were located in the barrio of Mangino. Further investigation indicated that an earlier extension program conducted by the Philippine Rural Reconstruction Movement in Mangino had emphasized straight-row planting as an improved cultural practice. But many farmers who tried straight-row planting went back to the old method. They said that it was difficult to find people willing to plant in straight rows and that it cost too much. The cost is surprisingly high. Laguna farmers currently pay P60/ha for straight-row planting and the majority of farmers use this method. In Gapan it costs P60/ha for ordinary planting and P90/ha for straight-row planting. At the same time poor weed control is a major problem in many rice

fields in Gapan. The current use of herbicides and hand weeding is not adequate.

Reasons for differences. To identify more clearly some of the reasons for the yield differences, the five highest yielding and five lowest yielding farms in each of the 10 barrios were re-interviewed. Rainfed farmers and five farmers who we found did not belong to the top or bottom group because of errors in the original yield estimates were excluded.

Soils and management were identified by the farmers as the principal reasons for their above-average or below-average performance (Table 17). The farmers described five soil types in this area.

—*banlik* or *lupain*. A clay soil that is not sticky and is easy to plow with 30 cm or more topsoil. Considered the best soil in the area.

—*mestisong dilain*. A fine soil, a bit sticky, and hard to plow with a thick topsoil. Considered a second-class soil.

—*mestisong galas*. Thick topsoil, with or without a stony bottom; soil is sandy with clay and some bigger stony particles. Considered third class because it does not hold water well, becomes harder when harrowed, is difficult to transplant, and does not hold nitrogen well.

—*galas* or *galas na pula*. A soil with a thin top layer of 18 cm or less. The soil is sandy with clay and some big stony particles, and a hard stony bottom. This soil has all of the problems of *mestisong galas* plus the discomfort to both the operator and water buffalo of the hard stony bottom during land preparation.

—*dilain*. A thin topsoil of 18 cm or less. The soil is fine, sticky, and hard to plow with water buffalo. It is also hard to dry.

A better understanding of the location and yield responses of these soils would help explain some of the differences in yield and management practices that we are observing.

Surprisingly, there was no significant difference in nitrogen input and farm size between the top and bottom farm group. Distance from farm to home was a significant factor, however. Among the 39 farmers with the lowest yields, 10 required a half hour or more to walk to the field from the house. Failure to give close day-

to-day management of the crop may be a major factor depressing yields.

Tungro and planting time

Much of the rice crop in Central Luzon in the 1971 wet season was seriously damaged by an outbreak of tungro virus disease. Gapan was heavily infested, but some areas within Gapan clearly were more seriously damaged than others. In the survey of 100 Gapan farmers conducted in late October and November, we asked farmers several questions about tungro and their answers indicated that tungro damage was related to when farmers received enough irrigation water to start planting.

The municipality of Gapan is served by the Peñaranda River Irrigation System. Water flow in the three major laterals of the system, C, D, and E, is rotated to give first priority for water use to a different lateral in each crop year. In the 1971-72 crop year, the priority was given to lateral C which serves the barrios on the eastern and southern side of Gapan. Water became available to most farmers in these barrios in May, and as a result the majority had transplanted their rice before July 1. In the other

Table 17. Factors contributing to yield differences among five best and five poorest farms on irrigated two-crop land.^a

	Based on yield estimate	
	Best farms	Poorest farms
Total no. of farms	37	39
Explanation of farmer ^b		
Good soils	12	0
Poor soils	0	19
Higher elevation	0	5
Good management ^c	21	0
Poor management	0	13
Crop damage	0	2
Farm size (ha)	2.3	2.5
Distance from home to farm (minutes) ^d	7.2	15.2
Nitrogen applied (kg/ha)	56	45
Yield (t/ha) ^e	3.7	1.7

^aNineteen rainfed farms and five farms with error in yield estimate excluded from sample of 100 farms. ^bBased on open-ended question: How do you compare your yield with other farm yields (average, above average, below average), and why do you belong to this category? ^cPractices noted by farmers such as number of visits to farm, level of fertilizer, method of transplanting. ^dSignificantly different at 5% level. ^eSignificantly different at 1% level.

Table 18. Survey of 100 farmers in Gapan, showing pattern of tungro damage according to irrigation situation and variety planted (Lateral C received water before the other laterals, allowing many farmers to plant as early as May).

Item	No. of farmers		
	Irrigated		Rainfed (three barrios)
	Lateral C (four barrios)	Lateral D, E, A (five barrios)	
Transplanting date			
before July 1	25	11	0
after July 1	10	39	19
Reduction in yield of IR5, IR22 ^a			
None	1	0	0
Under 25%	5	0	0
25 to 50%	5	2	0
Over 50%	4	32	13
Reduction in yield of "IR12," IR20, C4-63, Intan ^b			
None	2	3	2
Under 25%	12	4	1
25 to 50%	4	2	1
Over 50%	2	12	4
Variety preferred for next crop			
"IR12"	2	4	1
IR20	12	32	2
IR24	7	5	0
C4-63	4	2	2
Intan	14	9	10
Other	3	2	2

^aSusceptible varieties. ^bResistant varieties.

irrigated barrios and on the rainfed farms, most farmers transplanted after July 1. Farmers who were able to plant before July 1 for the most part escaped severe crop damage.

Farmers were asked to compare this year's yield with their normal yield. In the badly infested areas, the resistant varieties often were severely damaged (Table 18). But it was still clear that the resistant varieties gave higher yields than the susceptible ones even under the worst conditions. Fortunately, there was sufficient planting of resistant varieties and farmers were able to compare varieties. In Gapan farmers now have a strong preference for varieties that are resistant to tungro.

During the tungro outbreak, 43 of the 100 farmers sprayed their fields and 18 farmers drained water from the fields. They observed little effect from these practices. With few exceptions, farmers did not understand what caused the disease, nor did they know what protective measures to take to prevent another occurrence, other than to plant a resistant variety. Only 19 of the 100 farmers interviewed associated the disease with the green leafhopper, the vector of the virus.

Plant pathology

The stability of resistance to blast in rice varieties that have a broad spectrum of resistance was further confirmed.

Enzymes associated with the blast disease were further studied. The discoloration of lipid globules seems to be the primary response of the host to the invading pathogen.

Systemic fungicides that control blast were found to affect the reproduction of two virus vectors, *Nilaparvata lugens* and *Nephotettix virescens*.

Artificial inoculations of 126 rice varieties with 27 virulent isolates of *Xanthomonas oryzae* have led to the identification of several new varieties that have a broad spectrum of resistance to the organism.

Several hundred varieties were screened for resistance to sheath blight. Several varieties show much greater resistance than others. The possibility of selecting resistant varieties seems promising.

Many hybrid lines were screened for resistance to tungro and grassy stunt. Resistant varieties previously identified were further evaluated by testing with three strains of tungro virus. A new variety, Habigonj, was found to be highly resistant to tungro. Varieties that are highly resistant in India are moderately resistant to the Philippine strains. A new vector, *Nephotettix parvus*, was found to transmit both tungro and yellow dwarf. Plants that partly recovered from tungro infection seem to contain less virus as indicated by a lower percentage of transmission.

Many crosses and selections were made to produce disease-resistant isogenic lines and to transfer resistance to varieties that have good plant type.

Blast

Screening for resistance. Sixty-four mutant lines selected for blast resistance in France and Italy from irradiated variety Maratelli were tested for resistance in our blast nursery. Three lines, mutant nos. 5, 27, and 62, were highly resistant. Two other lines, mutant nos. 24 and 26, were moderately resistant; they had only intermediate type (type 3) lesions. TP309-FMS-1-R, a resistant mutant line from Taiwan from irradiated material of unknown variety, was also resistant in our blast nursery. These lines are, to our knowledge, the most resistant materials developed by irradiation. Their resistance to races in other localities is yet to be determined.

We screened about 470 varieties of the Assam collection in our blast nursery. Eighty showed resistance. More tests are required to evaluate their resistance in other locations and seasons.

Resistance evaluation methods. Varietal resistance to blast may be measured by the number of pathogenic races to which a variety is resistant. In the International Blast Nursery (IBN), varieties are exposed to races present at many locations at different times. Thus the results of IBN are the best measure of varietal resistance. We attempted to find out if inoculation with a large number of races at one location

would provide results comparable to those of the IBN by studying tests with 18 varieties which have been used as race differential varieties in our artificial inoculations during the past several years. About 2,000 isolates from the Philippines, consisting of 178 races, have been inoculated to these 18 varieties.

In general we found that the artificial inoculation results agree with the results of the IBN (Table 1). Some minor differences exist, possibly because some races are not present or have not been identified in the Philippines, as shown by varieties Kanto 51, Dular, and Taichung T.C.W.C. On the other hand, more races in the Philippines are pathogenic to certain varieties, such as Raminad Str. 3 and Usen, than in the IBN.

Although the number of races involved in the IBN is not known, the percentage of resistant cases in the IBN is a good indication of the relative resistance of the varieties to races present in various countries.

Stable resistance. Our previous studies showed that varieties such as Tetep that are highly resistant to blast in the international blast nurseries have stable resistance. Even though pathogenic races may be found on these varieties, isolation and re-inoculation of the pathogenic races produce only a few lesions.

Table 1. Relative resistance of differential varieties to 178 pathogenic races of *Pyricularia oryzae* compared with results from International Blast Nursery (IBN) tests.

Differential variety	Races resistant to, by inoculation		Resistant cases in IBN		Resistance ranking by	
	No.	%	No.	%	Inoculation	IBN
Zenith	160	89.9	181	93.3	1	1
Pai-kan-tao	147	82.6	125	89.9	2	2
NP-125	132	74.2	171	85.5	3	5
Kataktara DA-2	125	70.2	171	89.5	4	3
Kanto 51	122	68.5	141	74.2	5	9
Dular	119	66.9	139	71.7	6	11
Wagwag	117	65.7	136	86.1	7	4
Chokoto	112	62.9	143	80.8	8	7
CI 5309	111	62.4	148	79.6	9	8
CO 25	109	61.3	110	73.3	10	10
Raminad Str. 3	80	44.9	137	85.1	11	6
Taichung T.C.W.C.	71	39.9	59	38.6	12	16
Peta	68	38.2	81	68.6	13	12
CI 8985	62	34.8	99	53.2	14	14
Caloro	47	26.4	51	32.4	15	17
Sha-tiao-tsao(s)	45	25.3	36	30.5	16	18
Usen	15	8.4	106	58.9	17	13
Khao-teh-haeng 17	4	2.2	43	47.3	18	15

Table 2. Qualitative (pathogenic races) and quantitative (no. of susceptible-type lesions) pathogenicity of monoconidial isolates of *Pyricularia oryzae* from six resistant varieties on their original host varieties, on other resistant varieties, and on the susceptible variety KTH 17.

		Races (no.)								
Fungus races isolated from	Total	Pathogenic to								
		Carreon	Tetep	R 67	C46-15	Nang-chet-cuc	Dissi Hatif	Mamoriaka	Ca 435	KTH
Mamoriaka	6	0	0	0	—	—	6	4	—	6
Dissi Hatif	8	0	0	0	—	—	6	4	—	6
C46-15	3	0	0	—	0	1	1	0	—	3
Ca 435/b/5/1	3	0	0	—	1	—	1	0	0	3
R 67	2	1	0	0	1	2	—	—	—	2
Nang-chet-cuc	2	1	0	0	0	1	—	—	0	2

		Subcultures (no.)								
Total		Pathogenic to								
		Carreon	Tetep	R 67	C46-15	Nang-chet-cuc	Dissi Hatif	Mamoriaka	Ca 435	KTH
Mamoriaka	49	0	0	1	—	—	45	43	—	49
Dissi Hatif	67	0	0	2	1	—	46	41	—	67
C46-15	28	0	0	—	0	2	2	0	—	28
Ca 435/b/5/1	20	0	0	—	2	—	1	0	0	20
R 67	16	2	0	0	2	12	—	—	—	16
Nang-chet-cuc	5	1	0	0	0	2	—	—	—	5

		Lesions caused by all monoconidial subcultures (no./plant)								
		Carreon	Tetep	R 67	C46-15	Nang-chet-cuc	Dissi Hatif	Mamoriaka	Ca 435	KTH
Mamoriaka		0.01	0.01	0.03	—	—	8.7	3.8	—	66
Dissi Hatif		0.01	0	0.1	0.1	—	10.1	6.1	—	104
C46-15		0.01	0	—	0	0.2	0.4	0.1	—	94
Ca 435/b/5/1		0.02	0	—	0.1	—	0.1	0.1	0	47
R 67		0.7	0.1	0	0.2	6.6	—	—	—	120
Nang-chet-cuc		0.3	0	0	0	3.2	—	—	—	116

Evidence has also been obtained that the fungus is very variable: the progenies of these races change into many other races to which the variety is resistant. Only small populations of the progenies are pathogenic and thus few lesions are produced.

This year six other resistant varieties were studied. The few lesions that appeared on varieties Mamoriaka, Dissi Hatif, C46-15, Ca 435/b/5/1, R67, and Nang-chet-cuc in our blast nurseries were isolated and a number of single-conidial subcultures were made from each isolate. The subcultures were inoculated to their respective host varieties and at the same time to the eight international and 12 Philippine differential varieties, to other resistant varieties including Tetep and Carreon, and to a susceptible variety, Khao-teh-haeng 17 (KTH), which served as control. Thus we were able to deter-

mine the races in the progenies and the number of monoconidial subcultures that are pathogenic to each of the resistant varieties. The susceptible-type lesions (Type 4) on each variety were counted to give a quantitative picture of the pathogenicity of these subcultures. Occasionally, the fungus was reisolated from the previous inoculation and reinoculated.

Monoconidial subcultures of all isolates from the resistant varieties produced much fewer lesions on their respective original host varieties than on KTH (Table 2). In fact, monoconidial subcultures of some isolates produced no lesions on their original host varieties. Isolates and subcultures from Mamoriaka and Dissi Hatif produced more lesions on their respective host varieties than those from other varieties and are pathogenic to each other. The two varieties seem to have the same gene or genes

for susceptibility. Among the monoconidial subcultures of the two isolates, some produced as many as 30 to 40 lesions per plant while others produced few.

Most races and monoconidial subcultures from isolates of Mamoriaka and Dissi Hatif are qualitatively pathogenic to both varieties. The races and subcultures from isolates of other varieties, however, are seldom pathogenic to the original host varieties even qualitatively. Varieties Tetep and Carreon are resistant to all isolates and subcultures.

These data seem to support our previous finding that the resistance in these varieties is

Table 3. Philippine and international races of *Pyricularia oryzae* as determined by samples collected at early and late stages of a blast nursery test.

Race	Isolates (no.)	
	Early	Late
<i>Philippine</i>		
P6	0	1
P8	161	87
P9	8	1
P12	21	14
P15	1	0
P16	2	0
P17	1	3
P20	0	2
P21	0	2
P23	2	1
P29	0	1
P31	0	1
P36	0	1
P50	0	1
P52	3	0
P58	1	0
P62	2	0
P71	1	0
P81	5	35
P95	3	1
P96	0	1
P97	1	0
P153	1	0
P199	1	0
P200	1	1
<i>International</i>		
IA-45	0	37
IA-105	0	1
IA-109	204	108
IA-110	5	4
IA-111	3	0
IA-112	1	0
IA-125	1	0
ID-13	3	1
ID-14	1	0
IG-1	0	1

stable and that the fungus is variable in pathogenicity.

Races in the blast nursery. In previous experiments we found 60 races of *Pyricularia oryzae* in our blast nursery during a period of 21 months. The composition and frequency of races changed from month to month. The number of samples collected for each month however was small, about 25. This year we attempted to find out how many races are present in a single blast nursery test. We collected more than 200 samples at the beginning of infection and 200 at the end of the test about 2 weeks later. The samples were isolated and inoculated to differential varieties.

The results of inoculation of 218 samples collected at the early stage and 152 at late stage show that at least 25 different races were present in the test (Table 3). Race P8 was most common at both stages. Race P81 had increased by the late stage. Several races found at the early stage did not appear in the late stage, others appeared at the late stage but not in the early stage. Based upon international differentials, IA-109 was the most common race. IA-45 increased greatly by the late stage. The experiment provided more evidence that many races are present in a blast nursery test and showed that the composition and frequency are different even during the early and late stages of a blast nursery test.

New races of *P. oryzae*. Each year several new races have been identified from our artificial inoculations. From several hundred inoculations made this year only two new races were found. They were designated P199 and P200 (Table 4). By international differentials they are races IA-111 and IA-109. This brings the number of races in the Philippines to 200.

Crossing *Pyricularia* spp. To explore the possible mechanisms of variability, we attempted to cross *Pyricularia* on *Canna* sp., on *Panicum repens*, and on rice by mixing the spore suspensions in three combinations, *Canna*-rice, *Canna*-*Panicum*, and *Panicum*-rice, and culturing them on PDA with coconut milk. Since the three species alone did not infect the other hosts after repeated tests, and since the spore of *Pyricularia* on *Canna* can be differentiated from the others

1. Spores of *Pyricularia* isolates from *Canna* sp. (left) and from rice (right).

by its longer conidia (fig. 1), any changes in pathogenicity or in spore morphology of the progenies could be observed.

After 3 weeks, the progeny spores of the *Canna*-rice culture were examined and tested. One hundred conidia from the mixed cultures were measured and compared with conidia of the original cultures. They remained rather separated groups (fig. 2). Twenty-three of the monoconidial subcultures from the mixed culture were tested for pathogenicity. Twelve infected *Canna* alone and 11 infected rice alone. None infected both hosts. Crossing apparently did not occur.

Biochemistry of blast disease. The resistance or susceptibility of rice varieties to blast disease is influenced by the race of the pathogen with which it is in contact. The phenolic compounds and the enzymes associated with the phenol oxidation—polyphenol oxidase and peroxidase—have been correlated with disease resistance, since both unoxidized and oxidized phenolic compounds, particularly the latter, are toxic to pathogens. Further studies were made this year on the associated enzymes of the host varieties and of the fungus races and the changes after the infection takes place.

Polyphenol oxidases of different races. The activity of polyphenol oxidase produced in

culture by seven races was generally weak though the races differed widely in their ability to produce the enzyme. There was no correlation between the activity of the pathogen and its virulence.

Peroxidase of host plants. In rice leaves peroxidase oxidizes the phenolic compounds since polyphenol oxidase is not present in rice leaves nor can it be detected in the inoculated tissues. We tested a highly resistant and a very susceptible variety and found no major difference in the level of tissue peroxidase. This finding is logical since resistant varieties do become susceptible to the new virulent races.

Table 4. Reaction of differential varieties to two new races of *Pyricularia oryzae* (● = resistant; S = susceptible).

Philippine differential variety	P199	P200
Kataktara	●	●
CI 5309	●	●
Chokoto	●	●
CO 25	●	S
Wagwag	S	S
Pai-kan-tao	●	S
Peta	●	S
Raminad Str. 3	S	S
Taichung T.C.W.C.	S	S
Lacrosse	S	●
Sha-tiao-tsao (s)	●	S
Khao-teh-haeng 17	S	S

2. Distribution of spore sizes of *Pyricularia* isolate from rice and from *Canna* sp. and from *Canna*-rice mixed culture.

The responses of the varieties to inoculation with a particular race differ greatly, however. A resistant host-parasite combination (involving Peta) resulted in greater (and immediate) increase in the amount of oxidase than the susceptible host-parasite interaction (involving Khao-teh-haeng 17).

Post-infection responses. The changes in the peroxidase activity of the rice plant in response to infection seem to be influenced by the race of the pathogen (Table 5). The variety Peta inoculated separately with four different races behaved differently. Again, the resistant type of host-parasite combination showed a greater and more rapid increase in the amount of oxidase than the susceptible type of host-parasite interaction. This illustrates the importance of the post-infection reaction of a variety which determines its resistance or susceptibility.

The qualitative nature of the peroxidase increases in the susceptible host-parasite interaction on the fourth day after inoculation, as revealed by gel electrophoresis, suggests that

Table 5. Changes in peroxidase activity of Peta in response to inoculation with different races of *P. oryzae*.

Days after inoculation	Peroxidase activity of healthy plant ^a	Change (%) in peroxidase activity of plant inoculated with			
		P26 ^b	P149 ^b	P38 ^c	P150 ^c
2	0.550	34	-5	4	-5
4	0.513	7	65	9	-21
6	0.613	50	61	12	31
8	0.602	8	33	16	41

^aΔO.D. min⁻¹ ml⁻¹ extract at 470 mμ. ^bRace to which Peta is resistant. ^cRace to which Peta is susceptible.

three new peroxidase isozymes are synthesized by the host plant and that a quantitative increase of the other three isozymes already present in rice leaf tissues occurs (fig. 3). When the infected leaves were treated on the second day after inoculation with Actinomycin-D, an inhibitor of protein synthesis, the appearance of the three new isozymes and the quantitative increase of the already occurring isozymes on the fourth day after inoculation were inhibited completely, which suggests that an increased *de novo* synthesis of new enzymes (proteins) occurs in response to fungal infection. The rate and time at which this synthesis takes place might be determined by the host variety and the fungus race involved.

Hydrolytic enzymes. In the diseased area of the leaf, the tissue disintegrates completely as a result of the invasion of the fungus. The fungus gets its nutrients both from the living cell and the dead tissue by secreting extracellular enzymes which break down complex organic materials. Different races of the pathogen differed in their ability to produce such hydrolytic enzymes which make pathogenesis more effective. The virulent race P150, which is capable of infecting all the 12 Philippine differential varieties, produced more invertase, amylase, and cellulase than the less-virulent race P26, which could infect only the susceptible variety Khao-teh-haeng 17 (fig. 4). The capacity of the pathogen to establish itself on the host tissue after overcoming the primary defensive responses of the variety is also an important factor in the mechanism of resistance, although it is a secondary one.

Histochemistry of infected tissue. In several varieties before the symptoms of the disease

3. Electrophoretic pattern of peroxidase isozymes from leaf extracts of Khao-teh-haeng 17. A) Leaf extracts from healthy intact plants, B) from inoculated intact plants, C) from healthy, water-treated leaves, D) inoculated, water-treated leaves, E) from inoculated, actinomycin-D treated leaves. Solid block indicates greater quantity than shaded block.

become visible, the cells of the leaves react to the pathogen by discoloring the abundant lipid globules distributed throughout the chlorophyll-containing parenchyma tissue (fig. 5). These spherical globules average 3.3μ in diameter. They are various shades of reddish brown to dark brown depending on the stage of disease and distance from the infection site. They also occur on leaf spots caused by other fungi (*Helminthosporium oryzae* and *Cercospora oryzae*), leaf streak due to *Xanthomonas translucens* f.sp. *oryzicola*, and leaf yellowing due to tungro virus. In type 4 blast lesions on Khao-teh-haeng 17, the browning of these globules is greatly delayed, while in type 3 or type 2 lesions on the variety Peta, the discoloration is much faster. The discoloration of lipid globules seems to be the primary cellular response of the host to the invading pathogen, which might also be influenced by the variety and the fungus race involved. The presence and discoloration of

4. Invertase, amylase, and cellulase activity in culture filtrates of different races of *P. oryzae* (Amylase activity measured by hydrolysis of 2 mg amylose by 0.1 ml of 1:10 dilution of culture filtrate for 15 min at pH 7.0 and 37 C; cellulase activity measured by loss in viscosity of 1.2% carboxy methyl cellulose).

the lipid globules apparently has not previously been reported in leaf spot diseases.

Resistance to sheath blight

Previous tests have shown that Katakara DA-2 is resistant to sheath blight (disease index: 30% or below) and Dawn is susceptible (disease index: 70% or above). These two varieties were used as resistant and susceptible check varieties in this year's screening tests involving the 470 rice varieties of the Assam collection and 218 other entries.

A disease index was determined by counting

5. Large number of brownish lipid globules in and near blast lesions.

number of leafsheaths infected and the number of exposed leafsheaths of 25 seedlings of each variety. The method of testing is similar to the blast nursery except that resistant varieties are used for border rows (to maintain high humidity). Seedlings, about 20 days old, are inoculated by placing young cultures on 10-cm-long rice straw on the soil surface close to the rows of seedlings.

Twenty-nine percent of the 470 varieties in the Assam collection showed resistance (disease

index: 30% or below), 65 percent were intermediate, and the rest were susceptible. The resistance of some of the resistant varieties was confirmed in a second test.

We also tested F_5 selections from the cross (IR8 x Dawn) x (IR8 x Katakara) which was originally made to combine the blast resistance of Dawn and Katakara with the improved plant type of IR8. More than 70 percent of the selections seemed to show high levels of resistance to sheath blight. Since the results tend to

6. Sclerotia formed by sheath blight fungus on the susceptible variety Dawn, right, and on the resistant variety Katakara, left.

Table 6. Effects of three methods of inoculating kernel smut.

Method of inoculation	Filled spikelets			Empty spikelets		
	Grain infected (%)	Chlamydospore masses on hulls (%)	Healthy (%)	Chlamydospore mass in ovary (%)	Chlamydospore masses on hulls (%)	Healthy (%)
			<i>IR20</i>			
Spraying	3.7	3.7	34.1	0.9	12.0	45.6
Dipping	4.7	5.9	13.3	16.2	20.4	39.4
Injection	22.4	2.4	9.9	38.4	14.1	12.8
Control	0.0	0.2	57.7	0.2	0.9	41.0
			<i>IR22</i>			
Spraying	11.5	34.2	16.0	13.9	14.7	9.7
Dipping	20.7	9.7	25.9	24.5	12.2	7.0
Injection	24.0	17.9	8.2	17.6	20.8	11.5
Control	0.6	1.6	83.1	2.0	1.8	10.9

be somewhat variable ($\pm 10\%$) from one test to another, more tests will be made. Nevertheless these tests showed that selection for sheath blight resistance is feasible.

Resistant varieties showed not only much less infection on the sheath but also produced much fewer sclerotia of the fungus (fig. 6). The numbers of sclerotia counted on 179 varieties were positively correlated ($r = 0.8$) with the degrees of sheath infection. In 40 replications, the resistant variety Kataktara had 31.3 sclerotia per 25 seedlings while the susceptible variety Dawn had 277.9.

Kernel smut

Kernel smut, caused by *Neovossia barclayana*, is common in rice growing areas of the world but it causes little damage. Ordinarily only a few grains are infected. Recently, however, it was reported to have caused considerable damage in Pakistan.

We were able to germinate chlamydospores on sugar-water agar 72 hours after exposing the petri dish to direct sunlight for 4 hours. The germinated spore produces a promycelium which bears many (10 to 20) primary sporidia in a single whorl. These sporidia further produce many secondary and tertiary sporidia in different sizes and shapes (fig. 7). The colonies were well-developed within a week after the germinated spores were transferred on PDA.

In trying to develop a convenient method for inoculating large numbers of plants in the field, we compared three simple methods in a pre-

liminary experiment—spraying, dipping, and infection with sporidia suspension. Two varieties, IR20 and IR22, grown in field were transplanted into large pots just before flowering. Five hills of each variety were inoculated. All the three methods were tried in each hill, on different tillers.

Infection (suspension injected into the leaf-sheath enclosing the young panicle before emergence) and dipping (dipping the panicle in the sporidia suspension at the flowering) produced more infected kernels (Table 6) than spraying (spraying the panicle at flowering). Many sterile spikelets were observed after inoculation (partly due to the transplanting at this late stage). Some empty spikelets contained small masses of chlamydospores at the site of the ovary. The ovaries were destroyed while very young. On other empty spikelets chlamydospores were formed on the hulls. On the

7. Masses of secondary and tertiary sporidia *Neovossia barclayana* formed on PDA. Upper left, enlarged sporidia.

Table 7. Reaction of some resistant varieties to bacterial blight inoculated with 27 isolates of *Xanthomonas oryzae*.

Variety	Overall disease index	Virulent isolates (no.)				
		Disease scale ^b				
		5	6	7	8	9
Nagkayat	2.2	1	-	-	-	-
Kerang Serang	2.7	3	-	-	-	-
Casca Branco	3.1	3	-	-	-	-
Lang Chung Yi Lung Ju	2.6	-	1	-	-	-
Dayaggot	2.8	-	1	-	-	-
H-29-50	3.0	-	1	-	-	-
Tainan No. 7	3.1	1	1	-	-	-
Wan Chan	3.2	-	2	-	-	-
D44-1	3.3	1	2	-	-	-
Pagentinawonqon qipuson qi teneggen	3.0	-	-	-	1	-
M. Sungsong ^a	2.1	2	1	-	-	-
Lacrosse x Zenith ^a	3.3	1	2	-	-	-
TKM 6 ^a	3.2	-	4	-	-	-
Lacrosse x Zenith x Nira ^a	3.0	-	1	1	-	-
Zenith ^a	2.9	1	1	1	-	-
BJ 1 ^a	3.3	-	-	2	-	-
IR8 (check)	6.8	4	3	4	4	6
JC-70 (check)	8.2	-	-	9	1	15

^aResistant varieties reported previously. ^b1 = highly resistant, 9 = very susceptible.

Table 8. Growth of two isolates of *Xanthomonas oryzae* on WF-P medium containing different concentrations of Celdion S.

Days after inoculation	Growth (scale ^a)							
	0 ppm	100 ppm	200 ppm	300 ppm	400 ppm	500 ppm	600 ppm	700 ppm
	<i>B82</i>							
2	4	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
3	5	1	2	2	0	0	0	0
4	5	2	2	1	0	0	0	0
5	5	2	2	1	0	0	0	0
6	5	3	3	2	1	1	0	0
7	5	3	3	2	1	1	0	0
8	5	4	4	2	1	1	0	0
9	5	4	5	2	1	1	1	0
10	5	5	5	2	2	1	1	0
15	5	5	5	3	2	2	1	0
	<i>B73</i>							
2	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
3	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
4	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5	5	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
6	5	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
7	5	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
8	5	2	1	0	0	0	0	0
9	5	2	1	0	0	0	0	0
10	5	2	1	1	0	0	0	0
15	5	3	1	1	0	0	0	0

^a0 = no growth, 1 = few colonies, 2 = small number of colonies, 3 = colonies covering less than one-half plate, 4 = growth covering one-half to three-fourths plate, 5 = growth covering more than three-fourths plate.

filled grains, besides infection of the endosperm some grains had chlamydospores masses on the hulls while the grains inside were intact (fig. 8). A few infected spikelets occurred on the control tillers as a result of contamination since the control tillers were in the same hills as the inoculated tillers. From these preliminary experiments it seems that either the injection or the dipping method may be used for screening varietal resistance, though injection seems the most effective.

Bacterial blight

Varietal resistance. A group of 126 varieties selected from 8,700 varieties of the world collection were further screened for bacterial blight resistance by needle inoculation with 27 new and old virulent isolates. Several varieties were found to have a broad spectrum of resistance aside from those previously reported (1970 Annual Report). In this year's experiment, eight isolates were obviously very virulent. Table 7 shows the reaction of the most resistant varieties in the test. Reactions below the disease scale 5 are not included as they are not important. Several varieties previously reported to have broad spectrum of resistance were rather susceptible to a few isolates in this experiment.

No variety seemed to be highly resistant to all isolates. For the time being we must be contented with using varieties that have a broader spectrum of resistance for breeding progress. Combination of resistance from two or more varieties is being attempted. The variability of the organism presents another obstacle in evaluating varietal resistance to bacterial blight. Some virulent isolates lose their virulence after reisolation from plants or after storage.

Disease incidence and yield losses. While the scales for measuring varietal resistance to bacterial blight are in common use, no standard way to estimate yield losses in fields has been developed. In trying to work out a scale which will measure yield losses according to various degrees of disease incidence in field, we studied fields with uniform plant growth that had been naturally infected with bacterial blight. Five hundred to 1,200 hills from each field with varying degrees of incidence were cut near the

base. We selected the three tallest tillers from each hill and measured the diseased area on three uppermost leaves. We also threshed the grains from each panicle, weighed them, and counted the number of empty grains. The tillers were grouped according to the percentage of infected area on the three leaves.

So far, the data from two varieties (IR24 and IR841) in different fields have been calculated. The relation between percentage of leaf infection and yield losses is shown in figure 9. The losses are mainly due to increase in sterility and decreased 1,000-grain weight.

An accurate estimate of yield losses due to the disease is always difficult to make. With this scale, losses may be roughly estimated by sampling a number of diseased tillers and measuring the infected area on the top three leaves. The suitable number of samples is to be determined.

Resistance of *Xanthomonas oryzae* to Celdion S. Celdion S (TF-130) has been effective in controlling bacterial blight by experiments both in pots and in fields, but the compound is no longer manufactured because of residue problems. We have found another problem: resistance of *X. oryzae* to the chemical. When the bacterium was plated on a medium containing various concentrations of Celdion S, resistant colonies gradually appeared at higher concentrations as the days in culture continued. Table 8 shows part of our data. The rate of development of resistant strains seems to vary according to isolates. By further plating on high concentrations, we obtained strains resistant to 1,000 ppm of Celdion S. The resistant strains remained resistant after 15 transfers in ordinary medium.

For an unknown reason, when Celdion S is autoclaved no resistant strains will grow above 200 ppm (Table 9). Autoclaved Celdion S has a similar bactericidal effect to un-autoclaved Celdion S.

Strains that are resistant to Celdion S are highly virulent; the higher their resistance, the more virulent they are. A much higher concentration of Celdion S is required to reduce the size of lesions (Table 10).

In 1968 we obtained strains resistant to 2,000 to 4,000 ppm streptomycin. In tests this year these strains remained resistant to those levels

8. Rice kernels infected by kernel smut at various stages of kernel development.

of streptomycin after 153 transfers in ordinary medium. They retained their resistance even after passing through host plants.

Optimum and selective media. Many experiments were conducted to improve agar media that will permit the growth of single cells of *X. oryzae* in dilute suspension and media that will

9. Relation between yield losses and percentage area of top three leaves infected by bacterial leaf blight.

Table 9. Effect of autoclaving Celdion S (800 ppm) on growth (on scale of 0 to 5) of resistant strain, R2-5-6-8.

Treatment ^a	Days after inoculation									
	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	15
T1	3	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
T2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
T3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
T4	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5

^aT1 = no autoclaving of Celdion S, adding to medium before pouring (usual method). T2 = autoclaving of Celdion S along with media. T3 = autoclaving of Celdion S separately then adding to the medium before pouring. T4 = control (no Celdion S).

also inhibit the growth of undesirable bacteria in field samples. These media are essential for ecological studies of bacterial blight.

Previous experiments (1970 Annual Report) showed that WF-P medium (Wakimoto medium with FeSO₄ without potato) gave best recovery of colonies. The medium however has precipitates and is not clear. Filtering the precipitates reduced colony recovery.

The second best medium was SB medium (Silva-Buddenhagen) developed in Hawaii. It gives 10 to 20 percent less colony recovery, but it is clear, producing recognizable colonies of both *X. oryzae* and *X. translucens oryzicola* and allowing easier differentiation of common saprophytes (fig. 10). The original SB medium is modified by replacing glucose with sucrose because glucose produces a toxic substance after autoclaving that inhibits growth and by replacing glutamic acid with sodium glutamate to reduce the acidity of the medium. The modified medium consists of 5 g yeast extract, 5 g

peptone, 5 g sucrose, 1 g sodium glutamate, and 1 liter water. The medium is adjusted to pH 7. Adding FeSO₄ did not improve colony recovery. Several experiments indicated that FeSO₄ is not essential for growth; its function is to overcome the inhibitory effect of the mixture of other salts.

Several liquid media allow growth of the bacterium from dilute suspension (about 10⁻⁸), while the solid forms of the same media do not. The media known for the organism may be grouped into 1) media that allow growth in both liquid and solid form—WF-P, SB, Suwa, and Goto (compared with the colony recovery on solid WF-P, recovery on SB is 80 to 90%, and on Suwa and on Goto, 70%); 2) media that allow growth in liquid form only—Watanabe, Tanaka, NIAS, and Wakimoto (growth possible in solid form if concentration of cells is high, about 10⁻⁵ cells/ml); 3) media that do not allow growth in either liquid or solid form—Kado and Heskett.

Although we have not been able to develop a selective medium yet, some information has been uncovered: 1) commercial Xanthomonas polysaccharide is not useful; 2) MnSO₄ reduces the size of the colony even at very low dilution; 3) the bacterium is rather intolerant of bile products (but two or three such products may be tried again); 4) heat-killed cells of the bacterium are a good medium for growth when added to peptone; 5) among many antibiotic preparations few have promise as a selective medium because the bacterium is very sensitive to most antibiotics.

During the investigation on selective media many saprophytes of rice leaf were found. About 15 different types are readily classifiable and five to eight types are common.

Virus diseases

Screening for resistance to tungro. Employing the mass screening method, we tested 4,042 entries consisting of 275 varieties, 2,828 selections from IRRI and the University of the Philippines College of Agriculture, 101 Indonesian and Thai selections, 689 entries of genetical study materials and 149 duplicates or

Table 10. Effect of different rates of Celdion S as soil treatment on lesion development of the resistant strain R2-5-6 (resistant to 600 ppm), and the original isolate R₀, on variety IR8.

Rate (g/pot)	Days after inoculation	Area of lesions (sq cm)	
		R2-5-6	R ₀
0.04	14	6.05	0.07
	21	21.97	1.52
0.10	14	5.38	0.00
	21	18.84	0.38
0.15	14	2.40	0.00
	21	13.11	0.00
Control	14	9.52	7.39
	21	23.89	19.95

check varieties for resistance to tungro, using the "S" strain, the most virulent strain of the virus. Most of the varieties were susceptible. A new variety, Habigonj (DW 8-2 and DW 8-3), was highly resistant—comparable to Pankhari 203. Crosses involving Pankhari 203 had large percentages of selections in the resistant group (Table 11).

The 63 varieties known to be resistant and five Indian resistant varieties were further tested both by mass screening and by individual plant inoculation with the three strains ("S," "M," and "T") of the virus to see if differential reaction exists. We found that the "S" strain is the most virulent and the "T" strain the least. There seems to be no differential reaction, that is, resistant to one strain but susceptible to another strain. The 63 resistant varieties are listed in Table 12. All the five Indian varieties are highly resistant in India, but were only moderately resistant (31 to 60% infection) in our tests (Table 13). It has been reported that varieties that are highly resistant in the Philippines are only moderately resistant in India. These findings suggest that the virus strains are different in the two countries.

Outbreak of tungro. The severe outbreak of tungro in the Philippines this year raised the question of whether it was caused by a new strain of the virus. We collected and tested 72 diseased plant samples from all major infested areas. The virus was transmitted by *Nephotettix*

10. Colonies of *Xanthomonas oryzae* (small) and *X. translucens* f. sp. *oryzicola* on modified SB medium.

virescens (new name for *N. impicticeps*). All samples produced typical symptoms of tungro on Taichung Native 1 and chlorotic stripes on FK-135, a differential host variety for the "S" strain of the virus. Thus the virus in the infected areas is the common "S" strain.

The population of *N. virescens* and *N. nigropictus* (new name for *N. apicalis*) was high in all infected fields during the period of severe infection. Insects collected from various areas of the fields were immediately tested. We found that 17 to 58 percent of *N. virescens* individuals and 0 to 13 percent of *N. nigropictus* individuals were infective (Table 14). Daily transmission

Table 11. Reaction of tungro disease (strain S) of IRRI crosses tested by mass screening.

Cross no.	Parents	Selections (no.) showing infection range of		
		0 to 30%	31 to 60%	61 to 100%
IR822	IR8 x Pankhari 203	11	2	2
IR825	(IR8 x Pankhari 203) x (Peta/6 x TN1)	22	15	0
IR854	(IR8 x Pankhari 203) x IR262-43-8	11	4	0
IR932	IR8/3 x Pankhari 203	1	8	0
IR1464	IR497-84-3 x IR825-28-4	1	4	1
IR1480	IR790-28-1 x IR825-28-4	13	82	86
IR1487	IR127-80-1 x IR442-2-50	43	91	29
IR1529	IR305-3-17 x IR661-140-3	41	291	39
IR1539	IR661-1-140-3 x (Mudgo x IR8)	44	160	41
IR1541	IR661-1-140-3 x TKM 6	3	6	0
IR1545	IR661-1-140-3 x DZ 192	1	0	0
IR1550	IR160-25-1 x DV 133	1	0	0
Other 42 crosses		0	45	303
Total (54 crosses, 1401 selections, 2520 entries)		192	708	501

Table 12. Rice varieties showing infection range of 0 to 30 percent to tungro virus strains S, M, and T.

IRRI acc. no.	Variety
180	Adday local (sel)
177	Adday (sel)
3707	Andi from N. Pokhara
5894	Badshahog T412
6448	Basmati 37
4895	Basmati 370
5323	Bengawan
1456	Chungta 313 Hao x Binastian T3
113	Dee-geo-mean-don
8816	DV 29
5330	Fadjar
57	FB 24
831	Gam Pai 30-12-15
11750	Habigonj DW #8(2)
11750	Habigonj DW #8(3)
155	H4
663	HR21
8319	Indrasil
9076	JC 170
1274	Kai Lianh Hsung Tieng
4216	Ladang
4218	Lantjang
1557	Lang Chung Yi Lung Ju
6176	Latisail (Dacca 17)
8340	Latisail (T. aman)
755	M. Sungsong
8261	Padi Kasalle
5999	Pankhari 203
5000	Pekahok-Kimkan
35	Peta
1537	Pien chan ying tao

Table 12 continued

IRRI acc. no.	Variety
3511	PI 184676
1275	PI 160677-2
7366	PI 184675-2
7368	PI 184675-4
152	Podiuwi A _a
6339	Rajamanda
181	Ram Tulasi
3513	Red Rice
6015	Salak 2885
5346	Seratus hari T/36
5471	Seri-Raja
4095	Sigadis
5331	Tjahaja
34	Tjeremas
327	TP x Rexoro—SB
7315	Tsou-yuen
6016	Urang-Urangan 89
161	59-334 (B-11 x Mass)
721	6517
5350	221b/57/1/4
7589	221b/210/2/1/1/2
7591	221b/212/2/2/2/1
7592	221b/236/2/3/2/1
7614	221C/20/3
7596	221C/53/1/2/1
7597	221C/53/1/3/1
7600	221C/391/1/3/3
7606	221/BCII/11/3
6865	221/BCIV/1/45/10
6866	221/BCIV/1/178/11
7624	268b/Pr/2/2/2
7612	221/BCIIIA/81/2/1

tests showed that incubation period, retention period, and number of disease-transmitting days were normal.

The high population of the insect vector and susceptibility of rice varieties may account for the rapid spread of tungro.

Colonies of *N. nigropictus* and tungro transmission. Last year we found that field populations of *N. nigropictus* differ significantly in their ability to transmit tungro virus. To confirm this, four colonies of the insect from four locations in the Philippines (Baliwag, Bulacan; Los Baños, Laguna (IRRI); Irosin, Sorsogon; and Trinidad, Benguet) were tested. These insect collections were reared in the greenhouse and 78 to 105 individuals were used for each colony.

The Trinidad colony had 48.5 percent active transmitters, the IRRI colony had 20.5 percent, the Baliwag colony had 9.3 percent, and the Irosin colony had none. The virus retention period and number of disease-transmitting days

of the transmitting colonies were the same. Thus, although *N. nigropictus* has been considered as a less efficient vector than *N. virescens*, it appears now that it can be quite efficient.

New vector of tungro and yellow dwarf. *Nephotettix parvus* (fig. 11) was recently found to transmit both tungro and yellow dwarf. It was collected in Santa Cruz, Santa Rosa, and at the IRRI farm, all in Laguna Province. The insect seems to be an inefficient vector for tungro, but an efficient one for yellow dwarf. For tungro, about 7.2 percent of *N. parvus* individuals were active transmitters while for yellow dwarf 62.5 percent were active transmitters. The virus-vector relationship was similar to that of *N. virescens* and *N. nigropictus* for the two viruses.

The primary host of *N. parvus* is *Echinochloa crusgalli* and perhaps other weeds. The life span of the insect on Taichung Native 1 is only about 3 days in comparison with about 12 days on *E.*

crusgalli. About two progeny reach the adult stage on Taichung Native 1 and 45 on *E. crusgalli*.

Dual infection of tungro and grassy stunt. Rice plants sometimes are infected by both tungro and grassy stunt viruses. Such plants exhibit additive symptoms of both viruses which are more severe than those of plants infected with either virus alone. The plants usually die about a month after the double infection (fig. 12).

We collected 54 infected plants from Santa Rosa, Laguna, and the IRRI farm and caged them with *N. virescens*, a vector of tungro, and with *Nilaparvata lugens*, a vector of grassy stunt. Thirty percent of the infected plants yielded both viruses and the remainder had tungro or grassy stunt. By artificially inoculating the plants with the two viruses we found that when the plants were first inoculated with tungro, a higher percentage of tungro was recovered; when grassy stunt was inoculated first, more grassy stunt was recovered (Table 15).

Transmission from partially recovered plants. Seedlings show tungro symptoms 2 weeks after inoculation. A reading of the percentage of infection is therefore normally made at this time. But a month or more after inoculation, some infected seedlings may recover in varying degrees (fig. 13). For close evaluation of tungro resistance, a reading of the degree of recovery must be made. Failure to do so often accounts for differing results from mass screening and field observation (insect resistance in the field is another important cause of differences). We tested the virus recovery from the partially recovered plants and severely infected plants,

Table 13. Reaction of Indian rice varieties to "S," "M," and "T" strains of tungro (Based on 13 to 29 plants of each variety tested with each strain).

Variety	Infected plants ^a (%)		
	S	M	T
Ambemohar 102	32.0	21.0	0.0
Ambemohar 159	44.4	41.1	11.7
Kamod 253	32.0	16.6	3.7
Kataribhog	34.4	31.0	0.0
Latisail	43.7	37.5	7.6
Pankhari 203 (check)	3.8	0.0	0.0
TN1 (check)	85.0	68.4	25.0

^aVirus was recovered from infected plants.

Table 14. Percentage of field insects transmitting the tungro disease (Based on 34 to 192 insects of each species at each location).

Insects collected from	Active transmitters (%)	
	<i>N. virescens</i>	<i>N. nigropictus</i>
Apalit, Pampanga	35.4	9.7
Baliwag, Bulacan	52.2	4.8
Dolores, Tarlac	28.5	8.6
Irosin, Sorsogon	20.7	0.0
Santa Cruz, Laguna	17.7	9.8
Santa Rosa, Laguna	58.4	13.5
Pili, Camarines Sur	19.3	5.2

using Taichung Native 1 as the test plant and *N. virescens* as the vector. We found that 30.6 percent of the insects that fed on partially recovered plants and 77.2 percent that fed on severely infected plants transmitted the virus.

Screening for resistance to grassy stunt. In 1971 we tested 8,042 entries for resistance to grassy stunt: 2,274 varieties, 2,423 IRRI selections, 351 selections from Thailand and the University of the Philippines College of Agriculture, 76 entries of *Oryza nivara* from India, 2,172 entries of genetical study materials, and 746 entries of check varieties. None of the varieties were resistant. Of the 76 entries of *O. nivara*, representing 30 strains, only the one

11. *Nephrotettix parvus*, new vector of tungro and yellow dwarf viruses.

12. From left, healthy IR22 plant, plant infected by tungro virus, plant infected by both tungro and grassy stunt, plant infected by grassy stunt.

that was identified previously was resistant. Many selections from crosses with the resistant strain of *O. nivara* were highly resistant.

Systemic fungicides and reproduction of vectors. We tested three systemic fungicides, Benlate, Topsin M (NF-44), and NF-48, which have been found to control blast effectively, for inactivation of tungro virus. While the chemicals did not inactivate the virus, we found that the vectors did not reproduce normally on plants grown in soil treated with either chemical. To confirm the observation we caged pairs of *N. virescens* and *Nilparvata lugens* on plants grown in pots with soil treated with the chemicals. About 1 month after caging, the progeny of each pair were counted. Table 16 shows one such test. All treated pots produced significantly fewer insects. At high concentrations of the chemicals, most insect pairs did not reproduce or produced few progeny. The causes of the large differences among pairs within the same

treatment are not known. Age of and injury to the insects, resistance of individual insects to the chemicals, and uneven absorption of chemicals by plants, are possible reasons. We also observed that many of the young nymphs failed to reach the adult stage in the treated pots.

Virus recovery from old and young leaves. Previous studies (1967 Annual Report) showed that tungro virus could be recovered from all parts of a diseased plant. An experiment was made to determine if recovery of the virus by insects that feed on the young, green leaves of a tungro-infected plant is different from recovery from old, yellow leaves of the same plant. Three tests were made at different times using a 1-month-old infected plant. Virus-free insects were given 24 hours of acquisition feeding and then serial inoculation feeding for 3 days. The insects on green leaves gave higher levels of infection (62.6%) than the insects on yellow leaves (19.0%). Also, the insects that fed on green leaves were able to transmit the virus during all 3 days of inoculation feeding while those on the yellow leaves lost the virus a day earlier.

Table 15. Virus recovery from plants with mixed infection.

Virus inoculation		Virus recovery ^a (%)	
1st virus	2nd virus	Tungro ^b	Grassy stunt ^c
Tungro	Grassy stunt	80.0	20.0
Grassy stunt	Tungro	13.3	51.0
Check		78.3	44.2

^aVirus was recovered 20 days after inoculation of the second virus. ^b60 plants tested. ^c40 to 45 plants tested.

Disease-resistant isogenic lines

During past years many crosses and repeated backcrosses have been made between several standard varieties and several sources of resistance to diseases blast, bacterial blight, tungro,

and grassy stunt. The primary purpose is to obtain isogenic or near-isogenic disease-resistant lines for genetic, biochemical, and other studies of disease resistance. At the same time the standard varieties are improved by adding disease resistance. These lines also serve as better donors of resistance than the original resistant varieties in the breeding program.

Two or more sources of resistance to a disease have been introduced to each standard variety separately or in combination. Two or more sources of resistance to different diseases have also been crossed with a standard variety. The standard varieties used are IR8, IR20, IR22, IR24, and a line of IR773. Many donor varieties have been used as sources of resistance to different diseases.

For resistance to the two virus diseases, several tungro-resistant lines with good plant type have been obtained from the progeny of IR8/6 x Pankhari 203 and some from IR8/4 x Sigadis. These lines as well as others have been furnished to the breeders for further selection or crossing.

The resistance of *Oryza nivara* to grassy stunt has been transferred to five standard

13. Taichung Native 1 plants infected with tungro, showing partially recovered plant (1) and severely infected plant (2) as compared to healthy check, left.

varieties and lines through IR8/5 x *O. nivara*, IR20/5 x *O. nivara*, IR22/5 x *O. nivara*, IR24/5 x *O. nivara*, IR773/5 x *O. nivara*, and the reciprocal crosses. Many of the resistant progeny have the plant type of the recurrent parents.

Resistance to both viruses are found in IR20/5 x *O. nivara* and will be selected from such crosses as Habigonj x (IR8/3 x *O. nivara*), Habigonj x (IR20/3 x *O. nivara*), Habigonj x

Table 16. Effect of systemic fungicides on the reproduction of *Nephotettix virescens* and *Nilaparvata lugens*.

Replicate ^a	Progeny (no.)						Control
	Benlate		NF-44		NF-48		
	300 ppm	600 ppm	300 ppm	600 ppm	300 ppm	600 ppm	
	<i>N. virescens</i>						
1	0	0	1	0	34	0	71
2	0	0	92	0	2	0	98
3	13	0	0	0	44	0	46
4	32	0	1	68	0	0	80
5	2	0	0	0	14	0	0
6	16	0	0	32	19	1	106
7	2	1	29	1	31	0	129
8	19	0	12	0	18	0	75
9	50	0	0	0	25	0	24
10	32	1	1	2	0	0	55
Average	16.6	0.2	13.6	10.3	18.7	0.1	68
	<i>N. lugens</i>						
1	1	0	124	3	142	67	561
2	0	0	96	33	86	39	453
3	2	0	2	45	41	0	68
4	0	0	46	0	98	5	340
5	133	0	2	61	3	1	0
6	105	0	158	123	0	8	227
Average	40.2	0.0	71.3	44.3	61.7	20.0	275

^aOne pair of insects used per treatment per replicate.

(IR24/3 x *O. nivara*), and Habigonj x (*O. nivara* x IR773/3).

Many crosses have been made for blast resistance. Progeny with good plant type have been selected from such crosses as IR8/8 x Dawn, IR8/5 x ([IR8 x Dawn] x [IR8 x Kataktara]), IR8/4 x Ram Tulasi sel, IR22/2 x Tetep, IR20/2 x Mamoriaka, C46-15 x IR22/2, C46-15 x IR24/2, and IR8/2 x ([IR8 x Carreon] x [IR8 x Tetep]).

Several selections have been made for bacterial blight resistance from such crosses as IR8/5 x Zenith, IR8/5 x Wase Aikoku, and (IR8/4 x Zenith) x (IR8/4 x Wase Aikoku). Some other crosses for bacterial blight resistance

are (Zenith x BJ1) x (BJ1 x IR20), (BJ1 x IR20) (Nagkayat x BJ1), IR22 x (M. Sungsong x BJ1), and IR24 x (M. Sungsong x BJ1).

Several selections from IR8/5 x ([IR8 x Dawn] x [IR8 x Kataktara]) seem to show resistance to sheath blight, too.

Crosses have also been made to combine resistance to several diseases. Examples are (IR20/3 x *O. nivara*) x (IR8 x Dawn), (IR20/3 x *O. nivara*) x (IR8/3 x *O. nivara*), (Zenith x M. Sungsong) x (IR20/3 x *O. nivara*), and (IR20/3 x *O. nivara*) x (Nagkayat x BJ1). IR8 now has resistance to all the five major diseases separately, and combined resistance to two or three of them.

Entomology

The entomology program seeks to develop an integrated method of pest control that is less expensive, long lasting, and free from toxicity and environmental pollution problems. The brown planthopper and the green leafhopper, and the tungro and grassy stunt viruses transmitted by them, were preponderant at IRRI during 1971. Also, tungro virus was quite severe in several parts of the Philippines. More emphasis was therefore laid on these problems.

About 1,800 varieties were evaluated for their resistance to the green leafhopper, the brown planthopper, the white-backed planthopper, and the rice whorl maggot, and several varieties were recorded as resistant. The causes and effects of resistance on these insects and on the striped borer were investigated. IR20 performed well under diverse insect and disease problems. Some progeny of IR20 x TKM 6 possess most qualities of IR20 and in addition are resistant to the brown planthopper.

Several insecticides provided effective control of the common insect pests of rice through contact and systemic effects. Some were also effective as seed treatment or as seedling root-soak before transplanting. Carbofuran was most promising.

Field and greenhouse studies on the population dynamics of green leafhoppers and brown planthoppers emphasized the role of age structure, natural enemies, resistant varieties, crop age, and insecticides on changes in the population density.

Varietal resistance

Stem borers. The resistance to stem borers of selected varieties and their progenies was retested in the greenhouse since the field population of stem borer is generally low at IRRI. Individual plants were infested with a uniform number of first-instar striped borer larvae. No variety or selection has been identified so far that possesses more resistance of the antibiosis type than Taitung 16. The varieties Bir-co 884 and PTB 31, and several selections of IR747 and IR532 were found to be as resistant as TKM 6 or IR20, which are moderately resistant.

Since some workers have found the varieties Middle Farmer, WC1263, and Eswarakora resistant to the yellow borer, *Tryporyza incertulas* Walker, we evaluated them for resistance to the striped rice borer, *Chilo suppressalis*, with the variety Taitung 16 as the resistant check and Rexoro as the susceptible check. Twenty plants of each variety were grown in clay pots and when they were 60 days old they were individually infested with five first-instar larvae. The plants were dissected 30 days later.

The survival of the larvae on the three test varieties was almost identical to that on the susceptible check variety Rexoro but it was significantly greater than that on the resistant variety Taitung 16 (Table 1). The larvae sur-

Table 1. Survival^a of first-instar striped borer larvae on 60-day-old plants. IRRI, 1971.

Variety	Survival (%)	Avg wt (mg)		Total wt (g)
		Larva	Pupa	Larvae + pupae
Middle Farmer	71	67.3	59.4	4.64
WC 1263	72	51.6	46.6	3.66
Eswarakora	68	55.6	61.4	3.81
Taitung 16	43	49.6	^b	2.13
Rexoro	70	76.4	63.5	4.72

^a100 first-instar larvae were caged on each variety at five larvae per potted plant. Data recorded 24 days after infestation. ^bNo pupae recovered at the time of dissection of the infested plants.

living on WC1263, Eswarakora, and Taitung 16, however, weighed significantly less than the larvae on Middle Farmer and Rexoro. Based on survival and the weight of the surviving larvae, WC1263 and Eswarakora can be classified as moderately resistant, and Middle Farmer as susceptible. Since this experiment involved caging the same number of larvae on individual plants of each variety, it did not test the non-preference type of resistance which often has an important influence on the infestation of a variety in the field.

In another experiment we studied the effect of the moderate resistance of IR20 on the development of populations of the striped rice borer. We used Taitung 16 as the resistant check and Rexoro as the susceptible check. Each variety was grown in cages that accommodated 35 pots. Forty days after transplanting,

Table 2. Population growth of the striped borer on selected rice varieties: Rexoro (susceptible), IR20 (resistant), and Taitung 16 (highly resistant). IRRI, 1971.

Generation	Survival (%)	Avg wt (mg)		Days for 50% pupation (no.)	Sex ratio ^a	Egg masses (no./female)	Eggs (no./mass)
		Larva	Pupa				
<i>Rexoro</i>							
1	72.0	^b	87.4	27	1:1.6	5.1	^b
2	^b	68.3	63.9	30	1:0.9	3.5	19.1
3	68.9	63.1	71.6	27	1:1.7	4.9	23.9
4	69.8	85.9	71.4	28	1:1.6	4.2	22.8
<i>IR20</i>							
1	69.7	^b	43.5	26	1:0.9	4.8	^b
2	^b	48.6	46.0	30	1:0.6	2.4	14.1
3	67.0	45.2	47.0	29	1:0.6	2.8	16.4
4	64.8	54.2	47.6	29	1:0.6	2.9	15.4
<i>Taitung 16</i>							
1	49.2	30.8	32.5	30	1:0.8	4.7	19.3
2	52.0	34.3	31.3	31	1:0.9	2.8	15.6
3	41.6	28.5	^c	40	1:0.9	2.7	13.3
4	37.5	25.7	^c	42	1:0.9	2.5	11.3

^aMale:female. ^bNot recorded. ^cNo pupae were recovered at 28 days after infestation, when the plants were dissected.

each of the two seedlings in each pot was infested with five first-instar larvae. The ensuing progeny were maintained on the same variety for four generations. After the second generation, when the borer populations became too large for cages, only 10 pairs of moths were used for further studies.

Fewer larvae survived on Taitung 16 than on IR20 and Rexoro. The survival on Taitung 16 declined with each subsequent generation. On IR20 the larval survival was only slightly lower than on Rexoro but it tended to decline in subsequent generations. The larvae reared on Rexoro were much larger and weighed more than those reared on IR20 or Taitung 16 (Table 2). Consequently, the moths reared on IR20 and Taitung 16 were smaller and laid fewer eggs. Furthermore, the larvae reared on these two varieties took longer to become adults and produced more male moths than females. Together these factors caused large differences in the development of the borer populations on the three varieties (fig. 1). Although the varieties had the same number of larvae at the start, fourth-generation moths produced five times as many eggs on IR20 as on Taitung 16 and 82 times as many eggs on Rexoro as on Taitung 16.

White-backed planthopper. The white-backed planthopper, *Sogatella furcifera* Horvath, is an important pest of rice in several parts of Asia. It damages plants by direct feeding. It is not a vector of any of the virus diseases of the rice plant, although a closely related species, *Sogatodes oryzicola* Muir, is the main vector of hoja blanca virus, a critical problem in the Latin America.

We screened over 1,800 varieties for resistance to this pest through procedures similar to those developed for screening for resistance to the green leafhopper and the brown planthopper (1969 and 1970 Annual Reports). Several varieties were resistant but they are not as highly resistant to the white-backed planthopper as they are to the green leafhopper or the brown planthopper. The first-instar nymphs caged on resistant varieties suffered high mortality, and the surviving insects caused less plant damage than those caged on susceptible varieties (Table 3). But even on the most resistant varieties, 30 to 40 percent of the caged white-backed plant-

1. Population build-up of striped rice borers on three varieties. An initial population of 350 first-instar larvae was caged on each variety. IRRI, 1971.

hopper nymphs survived while the leafhopper and the brown planthopper nymphs generally had much lower survival on resistant varieties. Nevertheless, the surviving nymphs caused almost negligible damage to the resistant plants. This result suggests that varietal resistance can be a practical method of controlling the white-backed planthopper.

In another study, adult insects caged on selected resistant varieties lived for significantly

shorter periods than insects caged on the susceptible check variety Taichung Native 1. Curiously, the male planthoppers had longer life spans than the females on the susceptible variety in these studies (Table 4). In most insect species the females outlive the males.

Table 3. Survival of *S. furcifera* first-instar nymphs 2 to 14 days after being caged on selected rice varieties^a. IRRI, 1971.

Variety	Survival (%)				Plant damage ^b
	2 days	6 days	10 days	14 days	
Balamawee	88	85	60	30	0.0
ARC 5752	73	66	51	33	0.5
CI 5662-2	75	68	54	36	0.0
C 5-17	61	50	41	38	0.0
ARC 6248	81	73	57	40	0.0
Colombo	77	70	59	41	0.0
ARC 7331	60	53	46	45	0.0
J.B.S. 34	84	72	50	46	0.5
ARC 10595	85	70	59	55	0.5
Pankhari 203	91	86	73	64	0.0
3-month variety	93	93	87	81	0.5
Taichung Native 1	99	99	99	98	2.5

^aAverage of 10 replications each consisting of caging 10 first-instar nymphs on a 20-day-old plant. ^bScale: 0 to 5. Larger numbers indicate greater damage.

Table 4. Longevity of *S. furcifera* on selected rice varieties. IRRI, 1971.

Varieties	Longevity (days)			
	Female		Male	
	Range	Mean	Range	Mean
J.B.S. 34	1 to 10	4.0	1 to 13	3.0
Colombo	1 to 12	4.4	2 to 13	5.2
C 5-17	2 to 19	6.0	2 to 20	5.2
Pankhari 203	3 to 18	8.9	2 to 27	12.6
Balamawee	2 to 18	9.3	1 to 19	5.6
CI 5662-2	2 to 20	9.7	2 to 20	5.1
Taichung Native 1	6 to 20	14.1	10 to 48	31.1

Table 5. Preference of *S. furcifera* for selected rice varieties. IRRI, 1971.

Variety	Insects ^a (no./plant)	Egg masses ^b (no./plant)	Eggs ^b (no./mass)	Eggs ^b (no./plant)
ARC 5752	1	10	6	60
ARC 7331	1	11	7	77
ARC 10595	2	20	6	120
ARC 6248	2	19	7	138
Taichung Native 1	6	46	10	460

^aResults from a bulk seedling test on varietal resistance. ^bLarge numbers of adult planthoppers were released in a cage containing 10 randomly arranged potted plants of each variety.

In a host-preference test, the white-backed planthopper adults caged on selected varieties showed a distinct preference for the susceptible variety rather than for resistant varieties. Also, they laid several times as many eggs on susceptible plants as on resistant ones (Table 5). The number of egg masses laid and the number of eggs in each mass were larger on the susceptible variety than on the resistant varieties. Thus the shorter life span of the insects, the smaller number of eggs laid by them, and the higher mortality of the nymphs on resistant plants than on susceptible plants should affect the cumulative development of insect populations on resistant varieties.

Green leafhopper and brown planthopper.

About 1,300 varieties, mostly new additions to the IRRI germplasm collection, were screened for resistance to the brown planthopper and the green leafhopper. Many of these varieties were collected in Assam, India, and are believed to be resistant to several pests and diseases. The varieties found to be resistant in the bulk seedling tests were subjected to tests of the survival of insects caged on them and the plant damage caused by a known number of insects on individual plants. These studies revealed that several varieties were highly resistant to the green leafhopper (Table 6).

Although in screening trials all varieties showed little plant damage, while the susceptible check variety Taichung Native 1 was killed, the survival of nymphs caged on varieties ARC 6038 and ARC 10746 was comparatively high. High insect survival suggests that these two varieties are more tolerant to damage by green leafhoppers than the susceptible check, Taichung Native 1. Also, since the insects surviving on them were much smaller than those on Taichung Native 1 (fig. 2), these varieties may possess some resistance of the antibiosis type. Most other test varieties, particularly DV 29 and DV 139, had a much higher level of resistance. DV 29 and DV 139 appeared even more resistant than the varieties previously reported as most resistant, Pankhari 203 and IR8 (1969 and 1970 Annual Reports).

Twenty-nine varieties were resistant to the brown planthopper (Table 7); some of them were even more resistant than Mudgo. Fifty-

2. Differences in the body size and in the number of green leafhopper nymphs that survived from a total of 50 first-instar nymphs caged for 12 days on selected varieties.

three varieties resistant to the brown planthopper have now been identified. Most of these varieties are from one geographical location (southern India and Ceylon), and it is not known whether they possess different genes for resistance. Except for ASD7, resistant varieties have been reported to possess the same gene for resistance as Mudgo (1970 Annual Report). Locating different genes for resistance is important as a safeguard against the breakdown of resistance if biotypes of the brown planthopper capable of surviving on Mudgo or ASD7 develop. In the bulk seedling tests several lines from the Assam rice collection reacted as resistant, but in further tests they were only tolerant to brown planthopper damage.

Resistance of Mudgo to brown planthopper. The resistance of the variety Mudgo was further evaluated by testing it against populations of brown planthoppers collected from 14 locations on Luzon, Philippines. These insects were reared in the laboratory for at least one generation, then 10 first-instar nymphs were caged on individual 30-day-old Mudgo and Taichung Native 1 plants. The survival of the insects was recorded every 2 days.

The brown planthopper populations differed significantly in their ability to survive even on the susceptible check variety, Taichung Native 1 (Table 8). The populations from several locations, such as Maligaya, Tiwi, and College, had almost twice as many survivors on Taichung

Native 1 as the population collected from Calamba. Similar differences were also recorded in the survival of different populations on the resistant variety Mudgo. The insects from all localities, however, suffered high mortality on Mudgo and their survival percentages on Taichung Native 1 and Mudgo were not correlated. Furthermore, the survival of the least adaptive population on Taichung Native 1 was considerably higher than that of the most adaptive population on Mudgo. These data indicate that the resistance of Mudgo to brown planthoppers is effective throughout most of Luzon. Experiments conducted in India, Korea, and Taiwan also have shown Mudgo to be highly resistant to the brown planthopper.

Table 6. Survival of first-instar nymphs of green leafhopper 2 to 14 days after being caged on seedlings. IRRI, 1971.

Variety	Plant damage ^a	Survival (%)			
		2 days	6 days	10 days	14 days
DV 29	1.0	3	0	0	0
DV 139	1.0	4	0	0	0
Jhingasail	1.0	65	6	3	2
IR8	2.0	42	4	4	3
ASD 8	1.0	15	10	99	7
CO 9	1.0	11	9	9	9
Godalki	1.0	58	32	27	27
ARC 6038	1.0	95	89	89	88
ARC 10746	1.0	79	59	54	52
Taichung Native 1	4.5	99	98	98	98

^a Based on a bulk seedling test. Scale: 0 to 5. Larger numbers indicate greater damage.

Table 7. Resistance of selected rice varieties to the brown planthopper. IRRI, 1971.

Variety	Grade of	
	Nymph survival ^a	Plant damage ^b
Heenukkulama	0.0	0.0
Periamorungan	0.0	0.0
Sinnakayam	0.1	0.5
Hondarawala 378	0.3	0.5
Rathu Heenati	0.3	0.5
Tibiriwewa	0.3	0.0
Hondarawala 502	0.4	2.0
Murungakayan 304	0.4	0.0
Pawakkulama	0.4	0.0
PK-1	0.5	1.0
Madayal	0.5	1.0
Murungakayan 101	0.5	1.0
Murungakayan 303	0.5	0.5
Ovarkaruppan	0.6	0.5
Ptb 18	0.7	1.0
M.I. 329	0.8	1.0
Palasithari 601	0.9	0.5
Murungakayan 3	0.9	0.5
Murungakayan 104	0.9	1.0
Murungakayan	0.9	1.0
Andaragahawewa	0.9	0.5
Podiwee	1.0	1.0
Sinnasuappu	1.2	1.0
Sinna Karuppan	1.2	1.0
Ptb 21	1.3	1.0
Kosatawee	1.3	1.0
Mahadikwee	1.3	1.0
Malkora	1.5	
Sinnavellai	1.5	1.0
Dikwee 328	2.5	1.0
Mudgo ^c	1.0	0.5 to 1.0
Taichung Native 1 ^d	1.7 to 3.8	3.0 to 4.5

^aBased on 100 first-instar nymphs caged for 22 days on each variety. Ten nymphs were caged per plant. ^bFrom bulk seedling tests. 0 = No visible damage; 5 = plants killed. ^cResistant check. ^dSusceptible check.

Combining resistance to several pests. Mudgo, which is resistant to the brown planthopper, has been crossed with IR8, which is resistant to the green leafhopper, to combine the resistance to these two insects in an IR8-type plant (1969 and 1970 Annual Reports). The F₇ and F₈ progeny of this cross were evaluated this year. Several selections were highly resistant to both insects and also had an improved plant type. Most of these selections, however, are susceptible to bacterial leaf blight, bacterial leaf streak, and sheath blight, and have coarse grains. A few are comparatively less susceptible to these diseases, and one selection also possesses field resistance to tungro virus.

Table 8. Survival on Taichung Native 1 and Mudgo of first-instar brown planthopper nymphs reared from insects collected from different locations in the Philippines. IRRI, 1971.

Locality	Survival ^a (%) of nymphs on	
	Taichung Native 1	Mudgo
Maligaya	61 a	20 abc
Tiwi Tiwi	58 abc	15 bc
College	57 abc	12 cd
Candelaria	52 abcd	25 a
Imus	56 abcd	18 abc
Iloilo	54 abcd	17 abc
IRRI	51 bcd	17 abc
Poypoy	51 bcd	7 d
Bay	50 cd	19 abc
Calauan	50 d	23 ab
Santa Rita	49 de	25 a
Macabling	49 de	8 d
Los Baños	42 ef	25 a
Calamba	38 f	18 abc

^a22 days after infestation. Average of 10 replications each consisting of caging 10 first instar nymphs on an individual plant of a variety. Any two means followed by the same number were not statistically different at 5% level.

In 1970, F₃ progeny of (IR8 x Mudgo) x IR841 ([Peta₃ x Taichung Native 1]) x Khao Dawk Mali) were evaluated. They were grown under a severe natural incidence of the rice leaf folder, *Cnaphalocrosis medinalis* Guenee, and were inoculated with bacterial leaf blight suspension. About 1,400 improved type plants that were comparatively free from the leaf folder and showed fair resistance to bacterial blight were selected for further evaluation in 1971.

The plants were grown as pedigree rows in 2- x 5-m plots and were exposed to a severe natural outbreak of the brown planthopper (fig. 3), tungro virus, bacterial leaf blight, and bacterial leaf streak. About 500 apparently healthy plants were selected for evaluation in the F₅ generation. They were planted as pedigree rows in two replications, one with and one without insecticidal protection. Several lines resistant to the green leafhopper and the brown planthopper, and moderately resistant to bacterial leaf blight, bacterial leaf streak, and tungro virus were selected for further evaluation. These lines also have long, slender grains with 26 to 28 percent amylose content.

Some promising selections have been developed by crossing IR20 with TKM 6. During 1971, 158 F₄ and 16 F₅ progenies were evaluated

3. A selection from IR841-131-1 x (Mudgo x IR8) remained unaffected while adjacent plants suffered severe hopperburn.

for their general resistance in field experiments and for resistance to the green leafhopper and the brown planthopper in greenhouse experiments. Several lines were highly resistant to both insects. Their resistance to the brown planthopper is significant considering that none of the parents are resistant to this insect. In plant type and in general field resistance to common pests and diseases, several of these lines are similar to IR20 and a few mature about 15 days earlier. Their yielding ability has not yet been tested.

The wider resistance a variety possesses to various adversities it is grown under, the greater will be its practical utility. The broad resistance of IR20 to pests and diseases (fig. 4) and

tolerance to several soil problems have made it a very popular variety. Breeding for resistance to several organisms can be simultaneously accomplished by using parent materials that are resistant to several pests and diseases.

Causes of resistance to leafhoppers and planthoppers. Our previous studies have shown that resistance to the green leafhopper and the brown planthopper in rice varieties is not due to biophysical factors. Rather, resistance to brown planthopper in Mudgo results from the presence of a strong feeding repellent or from the lack of a feeding stimulus, while the varieties resistant to green leafhopper either possess toxicants or are nutritionally inadequate for the insect. To identify the exact cause of resistance

4. Relative performance of the four IRR1 varieties grown under a severe incidence of tungro and grassy stunt viruses. IRR1, 1971 wet season.

Table 9. Nutrient solutions for feeding insects in bioassay.

Nutrient	Brown planthopper		Green leafhopper	
	Concn of solution (%)	50% survival (days)	Concn of solution (%)	50% survival (days)
Sucrose	5	8	1	16
Glucose	5	8	1	8
Fructose	5	7	1	3
Maltose	5	8	1	3
Glucose + fructose	2.5 + 25	7	—	—
Sucrose + maltose	2 + 34	7	—	—
Sucrose + asparagine	0.5 + 0.5	10	0.1 + 0.1	7
Asparagine	0.5	1	0.1	5
Sucrose + 10 amino acids	5 + 0.1	9	—	—
Sucrose + essential amino acids	5 + 0.1	12	—	—
Distilled water	—	1	—	3

a bioassay technique for feeding the green leafhopper and the brown planthopper must be standardized and the nutritional requirement of these insects must be determined.

Insects that feed on plant extracts of either susceptible or resistant varieties die within a few days. Therefore, we mix solutions with plant extracts to make them acceptable to the insect. The test solution is placed inside a sachet (enclosure formed by two layers of Parafilm-M membrane) through which the insects can feed (1970 Annual Report).

Various nutrient solutions on which adult insects could live for several days were standardized (Table 9). Based on the results bioassay material was offered to the brown planthopper in a 5-percent sucrose solution but in a 1-percent sucrose solution to the green leafhopper.

Table 10. Preference of *Nilaparvata lugens* for different nutrient solutions based on number of adults settled on sachets containing the solutions 5 to 72 hours after caging.

Solution	Adults on sachets (no.)			
	5 hr	24 hr	48 hr	72 hr
Sucrose 5%	27	64	156	243
Glucose 5%	9	13	42	76
Fructose 5%	11	23	49	71
Maltose 5%	15	30	64	94
Sucrose 5% + asparagine 1%	41	161	275	362
Asparagine 1%	15	23	37	63
Distilled water	6	23	33	65

Using these solutions, we found distinct differences in the suitability of various extracts of rice plants for the green leafhopper and the brown planthopper, but the results did not adequately account for varietal differences.

In another experiment we studied the preference of the brown planthopper for different sugar solutions and a mixture of sucrose and asparagine. The test solutions were placed in sachets similar to those used in feeding tests and were arranged randomly on the periphery of a cylindrical cardboard container (25 cm in diameter and 4 cm high). Fifty brown planthopper adults were released in the center of the box and the number of insects on different sachets was recorded periodically. In all observations, most insects were recorded on the sachet containing 5 percent sucrose and 1 percent asparagine (Table 10). The 5 percent sucrose solution had the next highest number. Interestingly the insect was not attracted to 1 percent asparagine alone. The low level of asparagine in Mudgo, compared with the level in the susceptible variety Taichung Native 1, has been considered one of the causes of the resistance of Mudgo to brown planthopper (1969 Annual Report).

Brown planthoppers also showed differences in preference for different extracts of varieties Taichung Native 1 and Mudgo. The insect preferred ethanol extracts of both varieties to the other extracts but its preference for the Taichung Native 1 extract was more distinct (Table 11). All extracts of Taichung Native 1, except those in acetone and distilled water, were distinctly preferred to distilled water alone (Table 12). But for Mudgo extracts brown planthoppers showed a strong attraction only for the extract in ethanol. The susceptible variety Taichung Native 1 apparently has more substances that are attractive to the brown planthopper than the resistant variety Mudgo.

Effect of nitrogen fertilizer. Since a low proportion of the amino acid asparagine in a plant is considered an indication of nitrogen deficiency, we attempted to find out whether the resistance of Mudgo changes under different nitrogen fertility levels. Taichung Native 1 was used as the susceptible check.

Individual 10-day-old seedlings were trans-

planted in 25-cm-diameter porcelain pots containing Maahas clay soil. Before transplanting, nitrogen was added to each pot, the soil was flooded, and the fertilizer was incorporated thoroughly into the soil. Each treatment was replicated five times. At 25 days after transplanting, 20 first-instar brown planthoppers were caged near the base of the plants. The nymphs were counted every 5 days and the adult insects were carefully removed and caged on another tiller of the same plant. The number of nymphs produced by these adults was recorded every other day until all eggs had hatched. In a separate experiment, similarly treated plants were caged with 10 freshly emerged adults (five males and five females) and their survival was recorded periodically.

There was no significant difference in the survival of either the nymphs or the adults caged on plants of the same variety but treated with different levels of nitrogen. The nymphs that became adults on plants at high fertility levels, however, produced significantly more progeny than those reared on plants that received 0 or 50 kg/ha N (Table 13). Thus the quantity of fertilizer used made a difference in the overall suitability of a plant for the insect's multiplication. Also, on Mudgo a high level of nitrogen fertilizer increased the number of progeny produced by the second-generation females.

Differences in insect survival on the two varieties were distinct. With 200 kg/ha N about 130 times more nymphs were produced on Taichung Native 1 than on Mudgo plants. There was a large difference in the number of nymphs produced per female on the two varieties, and there were more males than females on Mudgo than on Taichung Native 1. Thus, although the high levels of nitrogen fertilizer made both Taichung Native 1 and Mudgo plants more susceptible to the brown planthopper the difference in susceptibility of the two varieties was exceptional. This experiment also shows that Mudgo plants retain their resistance even when grown at high fertility levels.

The effect of different amounts of nitrogen fertilizer on the population growth of *Nilaparvata lugens* and of *Nephotettix virescens* (for-

Table 11. Preference by brown planthopper adults for different extracts of the rice plant.

Solvent used for extraction	Insects attracted ^a (%)	
	Taichung Native 1	Mudgo
Ethanol	24	19
Methanol	11	17
Acetone	11	14
Petroleum ether	12	12
Benzene	15	15
Chloroform	10	16
Distilled water	17	8

^a12 hours after caging. Three-hundred insects were used for each experiment (50 insects per replication, six replications).

Table 12. Relative preference by the brown planthopper adults for the different extracts of the rice plant and for water.

Solvent used for extraction	Insects attracted ^a (%)			
	Taichung Native 1 extract	Distilled water	Mudgo extract	Distilled water
Ethanol	73	27	65	35
Methanol	72	28	41	59
Acetone	42	58	43	57
Petroleum ether	80	20	41	59
Benzene	80	20	37	62
Chloroform	80	20	55	45
Distilled water	32	68	50	50

^aTwelve hours after caging. 100 insects were used for each experiment (20 insects per replication and five replications).

Table 13. Survival and development of brown planthoppers caged on Taichung Native 1 and Mudgo plants growing at different nitrogen fertility levels in a greenhouse experiment. IRRI, 1971.

Nitrogen applied (kg/ha)	Adult survival ^a (%)	Nymphs ^b			
		17 days after caging		30 days after caging	
		Survival ^c (%)	Sex ratio ^d	Nymphs (no.)	Nymph/female
<i>Taichung Native 1</i>					
0	88	50	1:2.3	4775	111
50	87	51	1:1.4	5139	139
100	72	62	1:1.2	6835	163
150	78	58	1:1.4	8875	211
200	78	68	1:1.6	9363	180
<i>Mudgo</i>					
0	10	12	1:0.7	11	3
50	10	15	1:0.7	0	—
100	10	25	1:0.5	19	2
150	19	30	1:1.0	85	5
200	0	26	1:1.1	70	4

^aFifty adults caged on plants in each treatment. Data for Taichung Native 1 were collected 7 days after caging and data for Mudgo, 5 days after caging. ^b120 nymphs caged on plants in each treatment. ^cExcept for the nymphs caged on Mudgo, all insects recovered were adults. ^dMales:females.

merly *N. impicticeps*) was also investigated in the field. Using ammonium sulfate, we applied nitrogen at 0, 50, 100, and 150 kg/ha to a crop of IR22 in two doses, 60 percent of the full amount in the first dose. The population density of the two species was measured throughout the crop's growth. Three complete generations of *N. lugens* occurred in all treatments. The fewest nymphs were found where no nitrogen was applied. The number collected increased as the amount of nitrogen increased. The maximum density at 150 kg/ha N was 60 nymphs per hill. These results show that adding nitrogen can increase the density of the brown planthoppers. They also suggest that a farmer should take this into account when estimating the economics of fertilizer use. For *N. virescens*, however, no relationship between the density of the nymphs and the different amounts of nitrogen applied was apparent.

Varietal trials. In the dry season 26 varieties or selections were tested for their resistance to the major insect pests at three field stations of the Bureau of Plant Industry: Maligaya Rice Research and Training Center, Cagayan Valley Rice and Corn Experiment Station, and Visayas Rice Experiment Station. Some Mudgo x IR8 lines and some selections and varieties that had shown resistance to stem borers in earlier studies were planted. No insecticide was applied.

At Maligaya, several varieties and lines had a low percentage of hills damaged by the whorl maggot at 21 days after transplanting: Sanna swarnavari TKM 6, ASD 8, TKM 6, IR20, IR580-E1264, and three selections of Mudgo x IR8. Unfortunately for valid screening work, damage by the two main borer species, *Sesamia inferens* and *Tryporyza incertulas*, was too light and the density of leafhoppers and planthoppers was too low. The maximum population density of *Nephotettix* spp. adults only reached one or two per hill.

In the Cagayan Valley, the dominant borer species, *T. innotata*, caused 6 to 18 percent dead hearts at 35 days after transplanting. But there were not enough significant differences in borer resistance among the lines to enable us to select those that definitely showed some resistance in the vegetative growth phase. Several selections were as resistant to white-head forma-

tion as the variety Sanna swarnavari TKM 6, and none had as high a percentage of white heads as the susceptible variety Rexoro.

At the Visayas station, even though the whorl maggot damaged up to 30 percent of the hills, the differences among the lines in percentage of damaged hills were small. At 55 days after transplanting, dead hearts caused mainly by *Chilo suppressalis*, *S. inferens*, and *T. innotata* were least common in IR22 and in three Mudgo x IR8 selections.

In the wet season, IR20, IR22, and IR24 were evaluated with and without insecticide at the Visayas station. Insecticide treatment for a given variety generally decreased insect damage and the number of green leafhoppers per plant, and increased yield (Table 14). Under either treated or untreated conditions, the varieties did not differ significantly from each other in percentage of hills damaged by the whorl maggot, and in number of green leafhopper nymphs on the plants. Also there was no significant difference among the varieties in the dead-heart counts in treated plots. But in the untreated plots, IR20 suffered less borer damage than IR24. In the treated plots IR20 yielded more than IR22, and IR22 more than IR24. Without insecticide, IR20 and IR22 yielded equally well, and both yielded better than IR24 (IR24 suffered from a severe infection of bacterial leaf blight). There was an insignificant difference between the grain yields of untreated IR20 and of treated IR22.

Insecticides

At the IRRI farm green leafhoppers and brown planthoppers together with the tungro and grassy stunt viruses, which they transmit, were pervasive during 1971. The performance of insecticides in this year's field evaluation strongly reflected their effectiveness against these problems.

Contact toxicity and systemic effects. In laboratory tests several compounds were found highly effective against the brown planthopper and the green leafhopper when sprayed on insects from a Potter's spray tower (Table 15). Most were equally effective in controlling both the green leafhopper and the brown plant-

hopper, but a few were specific, that is, effective against one and not the other. When applied to paddy water of potted plants, only a few chemicals acted systemically to control the insects caged on the plants (Table 16). More compounds were effective against the green leafhopper than against the brown planthopper.

Carbofuran was the most effective compound tested. It caused more than 70 percent mortality in both species up to 20 days after each application. When used as a seedling root soak treatment (Table 17), it was also the most effective against the green leafhopper and the brown planthopper, followed by TBPMC, XMC, and Terracur. Several other insecticides were highly effective against the green leafhopper but had relatively little effect on the brown planthopper.

Application to paddy water. Selected compounds found effective in 1971 and earlier experiments were further evaluated in a field test. All were highly effective against the whorl maggot, the stem borer, the green leafhopper, and the brown planthopper (Table 18). The plots treated with these insecticides produced significantly higher yields than the untreated control plots. The compounds lindane + dimethoate, lindane + metacrate, and chlorphenamidine + carbamult had shorter residual effects than the other insecticides. Plots treated with lindane + mecarbam or lindane + dimethoate suffered hopperburn but the populations of brown planthoppers in other plots were low. The insecticide GS 13006 was not

effective against the stem borer but it was effective against the other test insects.

All compounds other than carbofuran and GS 13006 in the above experiment were mixtures of two insecticides. To separate the effects of these insecticides, they were tested individually. Except for lindane none were effective against the whorl maggot and the stem borer. But most were effective against the green leafhopper and the brown planthopper (Table 19), while lindane was not. This explains the reason for adding lindane (gamma-BHC) to these compounds.

Effectiveness of carbofuran. Carbofuran has been one of the most effective insecticides against insect pests at the IRRRI farm. But in some field experiments it produced inconsistent results particularly in protecting rice from the grassy stunt virus (1970 Annual Report). One possible explanation was a change in the formulation of carbofuran used. In some experiments

Table 15. Contact toxicity of insecticides (0.04%) sprayed on insects from a Potter's spray tower. IRRRI, 1971.

Insecticide	Formulation ^a	Insect mortality ^b (%)	
		<i>N. lugens</i>	<i>N. virescens</i>
WL 21427	30 EC	100 ^c	92
WL 23327	40 EC	100 ^c	97
Formetanate	50 SP	100 ^c	0
WL 19232	25 EC	98 ^c	74
Methamidophos	50 EC	98 ^c	78
Bux 300	35 EC	97	100
Carbofuran	75 WP	95	100
CPMC	20 EC	95	—
Meobal	30 EC	95	—
MIPC	50 WP	94	100
XMC	50 WP	94	99
C570 Mg. 584 A3804	SCW 100	93 ^c	100 ^c
TBPMC	50 WP	90 ^c	81
M 3019	40.8 EC	90 ^c	9
Methomyl	90 Technical	89	100
C22598 Mg. 299 A4090	50 EC	89 ^c	10 ^c
SD 9097	20 EC	82 ^c	25
WL 19561	50 WP	71	100
Carbaryl	85 WP	67 ^c	98
Phosphamidon	50 EC	65 ^c	15
WL 24052	30 EC	40 ^c	49
R 25829	43.7 EC	28 ^c	54
SD 8713	40 EC	24 ^c	87
WL 23911	40 EC	8 ^c	89
GS 13006 P.4 E 3931	30 EC	8 ^c	32 ^c
GS 13006 P.7 E 3741	30 EC	2	—

^aEC = Emulsifiable concentrate, WP = Wettable powder, SP = Soluble powder, SCW = Soluble concentrate in water. ^bValues adjusted using Abbott's formula. 24 hr after treatment. ^cAt 0.1% concentration. The compounds were less effective at 0.04% spray.

Table 14. Performance of three varieties with and without insecticide (Dolmix applied at 2 kg/ha a.i. at 15, 35, 55, and 75 days after transplanting). Visayas, Rice Experiment Station, Philippines, 1971 wet season.

Variety	Whorl maggot damage ^a (%)	Dead hearts ^b (%)	Green leafhopper nymphs ^c (no./20 hills)	Grain yield (t/ha)
<i>Treated</i>				
IR20	17	0.1	0	5.06
IR22	19	0.4	0	4.22
IR24	25	1.0	0	2.25
<i>Untreated</i>				
IR20	36	2.1	107	3.94
IR22	45	3.6	46	3.29
IR24	45	10.5	45	1.55

^aPercentage of hills showing damage 20 days after transplanting. ^b55 days after transplanting. ^c79 days after transplanting.

infection down. When the insects were very abundant, no treatment was really satisfactory.

Ecology

Several studies were begun on environmental influences on the reproduction, mortality, behavior, and control of *Nilaparvata lugens*, the brown planthopper, and *Nephotettix virescens*, a species of green leafhopper.

Population dynamics of *N. lugens*. Diazinon formerly controlled *N. lugens* on the IRRRI farm. But recently we have observed that diazinon-treated fields develop larger populations of this insect than untreated fields. This may also be true for fields treated with lindane, a pesticide used in rice largely against the stem borers.

We investigated changes in the density and age structure of a population of *N. lugens* in a crop of IR20 that was treated six times with diazinon. Two major population peaks developed. The first peak was almost twice as high as the second (fig. 6). Hopperburn occurred after the second peak. The numerical relationship between nymphs and adults indicates that

at least three generations occurred. When the numbers of first-instar nymphs and of adults only were plotted, each adult peak was followed by a peak in the number of first-instar nymphs, thus proving the existence of distinct generations. Practically all the adults had long wings at 45 and at 100 days after transplanting, but only about 70 percent were macropterous in between, a period of plentiful food supply and possibly little migration.

When IR20 was not treated with diazinon, only one peak developed in the population, and the density was low (fig. 7). The reason for the higher population density when diazinon was applied is not known for certain. Perhaps the good growth and the different environment, both physical and biological, of the treated plants affected the planthoppers. The age composition of the first major peak in figure 6 appears in figure 8. Initially the population was composed almost entirely of adults. A large hatch of nymphs followed. Some died, and some matured into adults, which may have emigrated. However the insects in untreated IR20 (fig. 9) apparently reproduced at a low

Table 31. Effect of applying insecticides for control of green leafhoppers and crop protection from tungro virus in IR20 and IR22, 40 to 75 days after transplanting (DAT). Maligaya Rice Research and Training Center, Bicol Rice and Corn Experiment Station, and Mindanao Rice and Corn Experiment Station, Philippines, 1971 wet season.

Treatment ^a	IR20			IR22		
	Adults ^b (no.)		Tungro hills (%)	Adults ^b (no.)		Tungro hills (%)
	40 DAT	50 DAT	75 DAT	40 DAT	50 DAT	75 DAT
<i>Maligaya station</i>						
Diazinon granules	5	18	10	8	18	46
Carbofuran # 1	8	49	14	10	20	33
Carbofuran # 2	21	104	26	68	355	89
Carbaryl spray	3	6	15	8	7	78
Control	80	95	26	90	301	91
<i>Bicol station</i>						
Diazinon granules	6	3	3	6	3	10
Carbofuran # 1	5	2	2	7	4	1
Carbofuran # 2	26	14	4	33	12	40
Carbaryl spray	60	7	5	17	9	48
Control	186	23	15	78	28	100
<i>Mindanao station</i>						
Diazinon granules	1	1	0	3	1	0
Carbofuran # 1	1	0	0	1	0	0
Carbofuran # 2	6	3	0	9	3	1
Carbaryl spray	3	1	0	7	2	2
Control	8	8	7	12	4	60

^a*Diazinon granules*: Virus-infected plants rogued at 14 DAT. Diazinon granules applied at 20, 40, 60, 80, and 100 DAT at 2 kg/ha a.i.; *Carbofuran # 1*: Germinated seeds soaked for 12 hours in 600 ppm solution. 1 kg/ha a.i. sprayed on seedbed 14 days after seeding. Seedling roots dipped for 24 hours in 1,200 ppm solution. Granules applied at 20 DAT at 1.5 kg/ha a.i.; *Carbofuran # 2*: Seeds soaked and seedling roots dipped only; *Carbaryl spray*: Carbaryl (0.09%) sprayed on seedbed 7 and 14 days after seeding and on field at 15, 30, 45, 60, 75, and 90 DAT. ^bPer 10 strokes of a sweep net.

Table 32. Change in planthopper density and age structure on Mudgo x IR8, a brown planthopper-resistant selection, and on IR8. IRRI, 1971 dry season.

Days after transplanting	Planthoppers (no./10 hills)			
	Nymphs		Adults	
	Mudgo x IR8	IR8	Mudgo x IR8	IR8
31	0	0	0	0
38	0	0	11	16
45	0	0	2	6
52	17	42	3	7
59	22	280	2	11
66	34	112	20	103
76	4	6	9	25
80	4	355	6	48
87	50	1284	3	23
94	82	1499	6	62
102	4	347	17	331

rate, or many eggs and young nymphs died, because there were fewer adults at the end of the generation than at the beginning.

One possible cause of mortality in the untreated plots is a predator, *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis*, which was present in large numbers. This predator was less numerous in the lindane-treated and diazinon-treated plots (fig. 10). Evidently the insecticides killed some of the predators, permitting more pests to survive and multiply. Whatever the cause of the higher planthopper density in treated plots, it is clear that if an insecticide is used for controlling one pest, stem borers for example, other pests may become more important than they would be ordinarily.

Besides insecticides, the insect resistance in a variety of rice is a major influence on population development. The effect of host-plant resistance on brown planthoppers is shown in Table 32. The insect population developed very slowly on the resistant selection of Mudgo x IR8, but rapidly on the susceptible variety IR8. Thus insect-resistant varieties can effectively deter population increase.

These findings suggest six points for the control of the insects in rice fields:

- Use resistant varieties when they are available.
- Sample the insect population regularly.
- If a small hatch occurs and can be tolerated economically, do not apply insecticide.
- If a large hatch occurs, apply an insecticide

6. Change in planthopper density in a plot of IR20 treated with the insecticide diazinon (2 kg/ha a.i.) at 18, 38, 56, 76, 97, and 118 days after transplanting. IRRI, November 1970 to March 1971.

specific to the pest at a time when the density of the population and its reproductive potential can be reduced. One application may be enough.

—If insecticides are used to control other pests, watch for unexpected effects on the planthoppers.

7. Change in planthopper density in an untreated plot of IR20. IRRI, November 1970 to March 1971.

8. Change in planthopper density by instar in an insecticide-treated (diazinon) plot of IR20. IRRI, November-December 1970.

—Consider the long-term economics of controlling planthoppers that survive on ratoon plants in the off-season.

Population dynamics of *N. virescens*. Fluctuations in the population density of *N. virescens* in an IR22 crop that received no insecticide are shown in figure 11. A hatch of nymphs about 50 days after transplanting led to a peak in the number of adults. Subsequent peaks were

smaller. The occurrence of these peaks suggests the existence of reasonably distinct generations in a given crop.

In an experiment with IR20, a different relationship between nymphs and adults occurred. When the number of nymphs decreased, the number of adults rose much above the expected level (fig. 12). Adult leafhoppers may have immigrated into this crop. The large

9. Change in planthopper density by instar in an untreated plot of IR20. IRRI, November-December 1970.

number of adults present in an adjoining plot probably served as the source.

In a preliminary experiment populations of *N. virescens* on three varieties, IR8, IR20, and IR22, were compared to see what effect the variety has on the insect. The leafhoppers reproduced most effectively on IR22 (fig. 13). The number of nymphs on IR8 was initially higher than that on IR20, which is surprising since IR8 is considered more resistant to *N. virescens* than the other two varieties.

Predators of planthoppers and leafhoppers. The suspected predatory activity in the field of several arthropods on *N. lugens* and *N. virescens* was confirmed in the laboratory. One species of predator was caged with one prey species, and the prey mortality was determined. Large and small coccinellid beetles, one species of spider, and *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis* were included in the test. The coccinellids were especially effective against *N. lugens* adults and *N. virescens* nymphs, and the spiders against *N. virescens* nymphs.

10. Density of adults of the predator *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis* in plots of IR20 that were treated with lindane or diazinon (2 kg/ha a.i. every 20 days), or left untreated. IRRI, December 1970 to January 1971.

C. lividipennis was caged with nymphs only and killed a majority of both pest species.

Insect preference for diseased plants. Green leafhoppers often appear to be more numerous on hills infected with tungro virus than on healthy hills. To investigate this point, we

11. Change in density of *Nephotettix virescens* on IR22. IRRI, December 1970 to March 1971.

12. Change in density of *N. virescens* on a selection of IR20 susceptible to *N. virescens*. IRRI, August to October 1971.

13. Change in density of nymphs of *N. virescens* on IR8, IR20, and IR22. IIRRI, December 1970 to March 1971.

selected 10 pairs of hills from an IR22 plot and 10 from an IR24 plot. Each pair consisted of one healthy hill and one adjacent infected hill.

All insects were removed from these hills every day for 19 days. We found that virus-infected hills had more adult and nymphal green leafhoppers than the healthy hills. The differences were highly significant for IR22. For IR24, however, only the difference in the number of adults was significant. The apparent preference of green leafhoppers for virus-infected plants to healthy plants leads to a larger percentage of viruliferous insects than would otherwise be the case.

There was no indication that the brown planthopper preferred the plants infected with tungro virus.

Flight behavior. Flight in and out of a paddy field influences the growth of the insect population in the field and the spread of virus diseases. To measure this dispersal flight, wooden boards painted dark green were erected around a plot in which a selection of IR20 that is susceptible to the green leafhopper was growing. Each board was covered with a thin coating of a clear sticky material called Tanglefoot. During 5 days in August and September, all insects caught on the boards were counted in the morning, at dusk, and again the next morning. Most of the adults of the brown planthopper and *N. virescens* that were trapped were caught during the nighttime.

Agricultural engineering

A highlight of the year's activities was the development of a simple power tiller which uses readily available components and can be produced in Asia with low-volume production techniques. The single hopper seeder for pregerminated rice continued to receive good market acceptance. A second low-profile multihopper seeder was developed which is easier to produce. High grain losses that were encountered with the earlier stripper harvester were reduced to about 1.5 percent in a laboratory machine. Work was continued on optimizing the efficiency of the sand conduction paddy drying and parboiling equipment.

As a result of field tests, the bearings and the drive system configuration of the table thresher were changed to reduce wear during operation. Tests of manufacturers' models of the power grain cleaner led to several design modifications to improve safety and performance.

Economic analysis of production tasks shows that hand tractors are economic for 4 to 50 hectares of annual use. The IRRI seeder for pregerminated rice is economic when used on more than 1.5 hectares annually. The IRRI power weeder is a good investment when used on more than 6 hectares a year. The paddy thresher is a good economic choice for operators who thresh between 60 and 300 tons per year.

Field machinery

Extendible blade-lug wheel. Cage wheels can be used with rubber-tired tractors to improve tractor mobility in wet paddy fields. In tropical rice growing regions, fixed lug wheels are quite popular. Although extendible lug wheels have been developed in Japan and Great Britain, they have not been well accepted in the tropics due to their high cost. A simple strake wheel that has gained popularity in Malaysia consists of five or six 10 x 10 cm wooden strakes mounted radially on a metal frame. The strakes can be extended and locked in position to provide the desired degree of traction assistance. Wooden strake wheels have several drawbacks: the strake ends have a large footprint area and when the strakes are extended beyond the tire periphery the tractor tends to move with a rocking motion, the strakes are not wide enough to develop adequate traction, and the strakes are difficult to adjust because the wood swells.

We constructed an experimental wheel with thin-edged, wide steel blades that can be extended. It was designed so five or six lugs could

be installed on the wheel frame for testing. One face of the lug had a 25° angle with the radial line while the other face was along the radial line. Interchanging the left-side lugs with the right-side ones permitted testing of two possible lug face angles. The wheels were designed so the blade lugs could be locked at -5.08, -1.27, +2.54, +6.35, and +10.16 cm (-2, -0.5, +1, +2.5, and +4 in.) from the periphery of the tractor tire. We found that traction did not improve significantly at the -5.08 cm setting. This position, however, was convenient for traveling on hard ground. The -1.27 cm setting seems to be a critical one. The effect of the lug position on traction was more pronounced beyond this setting. Five and six lugs were compared at the +6.35 and +10.16 cm positions. With six lugs, about 50 percent wheel slip gave maximum drawbar pull while with five lugs maximum drawbar pull occurred at 85 percent slip. The following desirable design criteria were established for extendible traction-assisting lug wheels: six lugs with blade settings of -5.08, +2.54, +6.35, and +10.16 cm from the tire periphery.

Based on these criteria, we developed a prototype extendible blade lug wheel (fig. 1). To facilitate commercial production the wheels were designed with standard structural steel sections that are readily available. Each lug wheel weighs 135 kg. A local firm has started marketing this wheel with tractors.

Differential slip tiller. The concept of differential slip tillage is to rotate the front and rear cage wheels of a tractor at different speeds to provide mobility as well as soil tillage (1970 Annual Report). The major experimental difficulty has been maintaining a constant speed differential between the front and rear cage wheels which are independently powered. This year we equipped a standard 7-hp walking tractor (fig. 2) with an extra pair of cage wheels which are driven from the front tractor wheels through two independent chain transmissions. All four cage wheels are identical in design. The drive ratio between the front and the rear set of wheels is 1:1.875. To turn the tiller, the right or left pair of wheels can be disengaged with the tractor steering clutches.

The tiller has excellent mobility and tillage

1. Extendible lug wheel for improving traction.

action in soft paddy fields. The four-wheel drive arrangement permits the machine to cross levees as high as its wheel diameter. The tiller, with the two chain drive transmissions and the extra set of cage wheels, weighs 315 kg. When it was operated alongside a conventional light-weight tiller weighing 130 kg in a paddy field with a very deep hardpan, the differential slip tiller continued to be mobile while the lighter tiller was repeatedly bogged.

Sharp turns are difficult to make with this tiller. Since the tractor is equipped with dog-type steering clutches, power is completely cut off from the inner set of wheels during turns, and slip increases on the outer set of wheels, reducing mobility. Using disc-type steering clutches would solve the problem because power would not be completely cut off from the inner wheels. Or, an articulated chassis could be used, but the transmission of power to the rear wheels through the point of articulation might result in higher costs.

From the experiment, we have concluded that the concept of a differential slip tiller can provide improved mobility and achieve tillage without additional implements in soft paddy fields.

Power tiller. The high cost of imported power tillers is an impediment to mechanization of tropical agriculture. Power tiller designs from industrialized countries are not suited for manufacture in the less developed regions because they require capital-intensive, mass-production technology. Recently, however, small machine shops in Thailand have started to build simple power tillers of local design with readily avail-

able components. They are inexpensive and are rapidly gaining popularity, but they are quite heavy. We began a project to develop a better power tiller for manufacture in tropical Asia.

We designed the tiller to weigh less than 112 kg to improve its mobility in softer fields and so that two to three men can easily lift it when it is bogged down. In addition, the machine is designed to be simple for the tropical farmer to understand. Few adjustments and controls are needed to operate it. Furthermore, with the exception of the engine, the tiller can be fabricated by small shops with standard machine tools in most developing countries. A sealed oil-bath chain transmission with standard sprockets, chains, and seals that are widely available in Asia is used in its design. Except for the bearing seats and the bearing housings, no precision machining is required. All sheet metal components have been designed for manual fabrication with simple forming tools. No stampings have been used since these would require large investments in stamping facilities. Only two pulleys, which can be cast by small foundries, are used in the tiller.

The first prototype tiller is equipped with a 5-hp aircooled gasoline engine which provides sufficient power for lowland plowing and harrowing operations. The tiller has a power transmission ratio of 72:1 between the engine and wheels. The prototype has been tested for over 100 hours without any mechanical problems. A second improved prototype unit (fig. 3) is being extensively field tested. The design will soon be released for trial production in the Philippines. Preliminary quotations from local

2. Differential slip tiller.

3. Low-cost 5-hp power tiller.

manufacturers indicate an approximate price of US\$450 for the tiller complete with a 5-hp engine. This is less than half the price of a comparable imported machine.

Six-row multihopper seeder. The response of Philippine farmers to the single-hopper paddy seeder (1970 Annual Report) has been encouraging. We believe, however, that a six-row seeder with separate hoppers for individual rows would be cheaper to construct and would give better seed placement. In addition, it would have a lower center of gravity and improved handling characteristics. The prototype seeder we have developed (fig. 4) has a sled with six hoppers, each with its own seed-metering roller.

4. Six-row multihopper seeder.

A single ground wheel, mounted directly on the roller shaft, operates the six seed-metering rollers. This wheel is also used for transporting the seeder to the field. The seeder has been released for manufacture in the Philippines. A few seeders are being ordered for field evaluation in other Asian countries.

PTO-driven thresher. The multicrop thresher operated from a tractor power take-off (1970 Annual Report) has three major sections: threshing, separating, and straw throwing. The threshing section consists of a spike-tooth cylinder and concave arrangement with a housing fitted with internal spiral fins. During threshing most of the grain is separated at the concave. The remaining grain goes with the straw and moves axially along the threshing cylinder and is delivered into a rotary separator.

We conducted tests to establish the optimum number of spikes on the threshing cylinder and concave to obtain satisfactory threshing without excessively breaking or shredding the straw. The test results indicate that 42 spikes in the cylinder and 12 on the concave perform well. On the cylinder the spikes were evenly spaced in a spiral arrangement. On the concave, the spikes were mounted in two rows near the feed opening of the concave.

To improve primary separation of grain at the concave, we evaluated several concave designs. A concave with 0.64 cm round bars with 0.95 cm spacing in the leading half and 0.64 cm in the rest performed well. This concave gave up to 93 percent grain separation

when threshing freshly harvested paddy. To minimize the passage of straw pieces through the concave, 0.64 cm crossbars were welded 3.2 cm apart on the concave. This modification minimized the amount of shredded straw in the grain without affecting the efficiency of the grain separation.

The separating section is composed of three concentric sheet metal cylinders. The inner cylinder (no. 1) has perforations 1.27 cm in diameter and the central cylinder (no. 2) has perforations 0.95 cm in diameter. The outer cylinder (no. 3) has no perforations. The grain separated at the concave is delivered by an auger directly into the no. 2 cylinder while the grain mixed with the straw passes through the no. 1 and no. 2 cylinders. All grain falls through to the no. 3 cylinder.

Some difficulty was encountered in the axial movement of straw in the no. 1 cylinder. A set of paddles, mounted spirally on a central shaft (fig. 5), helped in the axial movement of the straw and in breaking up lumps of wet straw. After a series of trial runs, the length of the rotary separator was changed from 117 to 147 cm to improve grain separation.

To optimize the screening of grain in the no. 2 cylinder, a series of baffles and grain pockets

with slanting sidewalls were tried. The buckets scoop and carry the grain around to the other side of the cylinder to increase the effective screening area. The slanting sidewalls of the pockets help move the impurities axially to the straw thrower. The optimum speed of the rotary separator is 16 rpm. The grain is winnowed in the no. 3 cylinder as it tumbles and moves against an airstream. After the separation of residual grain, straw is delivered into the straw thrower section.

Tests indicated that most of the separating loss occurred in the no. 1 and no. 2 cylinders. With high moisture paddy, the loss was high in the no. 1 screen. With dry paddy, the loss was relatively high in the no. 2 screen. The thresher is now being tested with the straw thrower.

Stripper harvester. High grain losses have been encountered with the field stripper harvester (1970 Annual Report). Two kinds of losses occur: unthreshed grain left on panicles and grain scattered on the ground during harvesting. Because it is difficult to control the variables with the field machine, a laboratory stripper harvester (fig. 6) was built. The laboratory machine permitted easier alterations and evaluation of the performance of the

5. Schematic drawing of modified tractor PTO-driven thresher.

6. Schematic drawings of stripper harvester. Field machine, left; laboratory unit, right.

components. It was equipped with two variable hydrostatic transmissions for driving the threshing belt and the plant-gathering mechanism.

7. Loss of unthreshed and scattered grain by the laboratory stripper harvester at different gathering bar velocities and with different bar spacings at a simulated ground speed of 0.6 kph.

Rice plants clamped on a movable frame simulated the field movement of the harvester.

The angle of the threshing belt with respect to the ground was 40° in the field machine and 9° in the laboratory machine. The threshing belt velocity of the field harvester was 4.3 m/sec as compared to a variable belt velocity of up to 9.1 m/sec with the laboratory unit. The simulated ground speed of the laboratory machine was 0.6 kph. The plant-gathering bar velocity was variable from one to 11 times the ground speed. At threshing belt velocities over 5.6 m/sec, harvesting was satisfactory. But we felt that if the velocity were too high the wire loops riveted to the rubber belt might not last long. After a series of trials at threshing belt velocities of up to 9.1 m/sec, we decided to limit the tests to a threshing belt velocity of 7.1 m/sec.

Tests were conducted to establish the optimum gathering bar spacing and the effect of the bar velocity on losses from unthreshed and scattered grain. Gathering bar spacings of 7.6, 15.2, and 30.8 cm were tried. With closer bar spacings and with gathering bar velocities above 2.5 times the ground speed, plants did not enter between the bars, rather they were pulled downward and fed to the front end of the threshing belt first.

Figure 7 shows the grain loss at different gathering bar velocities with bar spacings from 7.6 to 30.8 cm. Irrespective of bar spacing, increased bar velocity reduced unthreshed-grain loss but increased scattered-grain loss. Closer bar spacings and higher bar velocities kept the paddy pressed against the threshing belt and resulted in an action somewhat like that of a concave. With 7.6 cm spacing and bar

velocities ranging from one to eight times the ground speed, the combined loss of unthreshed and scattered grain remains within 2 to 3 percent.

Since the open space between the gathering bars could have been responsible for the scattering loss, we installed deflectable flaps on the bars spaced 15.2 cm apart. These flaps entered the plants in a vertical position and then were deflected parallel to the threshing belt. Thus the flaps closed the open spaces between the bars while the plants were being threshed. It was not possible to test the deflector flaps at above three times the ground speed because of the mechanical problems with the deflecting action. Test results, however, show that the use of deflecting flaps does not improve performance. Bars with the 7.6 cm spacings were, therefore, selected for more intensive evaluation.

With some modifications in the front end and at gathering bar spacing of 7.6 cm and velocity of four times the ground speed, the total grain loss was about 1.5 percent.

Low-lift bellows pump. A manually operated pump has been developed for low-lift irrigation (fig. 8). The pump works in water as little as 8 cm deep. It is composed of two canvas bellows sandwiched between two hinged metal frames. Each bellows has a pair of flap valves for suction and delivery. Foot rests for the operator

are provided on the top frame. The operator shifts his weight from one foot rest to operate the pump (fig. 9).

The bellows are made of double-walled canvas but other flexible bellows materials are being evaluated. Sheet metal pieces inserted between the two canvas layers provide the necessary rigidity at certain points. Three bellows of different sizes are being evaluated for operator fatigue. A delivery of 300 liter/min at 1 m head has been obtained in preliminary tests. The pump is quite simple and can be produced economically.

Drying and processing

Rotary screen parameters. Little information on rotary screens for cleaning paddy is available in the literature. Since we are developing several machines that use perforated sheet metal rotary screens, we began a study on rotary screens. To study the effect of screen perforation size, peripheral screen velocity, screen inclination angle, diameter of the screen, and length of screen, an experimental rotary screen test stand was constructed.

We have found that 9.5 mm round perforations provide optimal performance with IR22 paddy. Increasing the rotation of the screen from 12 to 22 rpm decreased output for screens

8. Schematic drawing of the foot-operated low-lift pump.

that had perforations smaller than 9.5 mm. The increase in rotation speed had little effect on screens with larger perforations than 9.5 mm. The optimum inclination of the rotary screen axis was 5° from the horizontal. Angles greater than 5° reduced output. Screens with diameters of 53.3, 61.0, and 76.2 cm were tried. There was no significant change in output for the three largest screens from 16 to 32 rpm. At these speeds, however, there was a large reduction in output with the smallest screen. Screen lengths of 20, 40, 60, 80, 100, and 120 cm were then tested. With a fixed output of 1 t/hr, the 80-cm screen was optimum. With shorter screens, all the grain could not pass through, and with longer screens, the screening output per unit length decreased. The screens with diameters of 61.0, 68.0, and 76.2 cm performed well at peripheral velocities of 42.7 to 67.1 m/min.

Rice hull furnace. The sloping-grate rice hull furnace (1970 Annual Report), in tests this year, burned 6 kg of hulls per hour and provided a drying air temperature of 43 ± 3 C at an air flow rate of $35 \text{ m}^3 \text{ min}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-3}$ grain. The furnace dried 1,140 kg of paddy at 27 percent moisture content (dry basis) placed 0.3 m deep in a flat-bed drier to 16 percent moisture in 4 hours.

9. Foot-operated low-lift pump.

To develop a more compact furnace, four new designs were tried (fig. 10). These furnace designs confine the combustion to a small area by introducing air into the hull through various arrangements of V-channels and louvers.

The furnace that gave the best performance has a tapered combustion column with louvered openings at its midsection on all four sides. The louver area is enclosed in a housing that is connected to the suction end of a blower. Air enters at the bottom of the combustion column and is sucked out through the louver openings. This arrangement permits uniform burning of the hulls throughout the combustion column. The tapered, square-section combustion column is 21.6 cm at the top and 30 cm at the bottom. The clearance between the louvers is 1.9 cm. To keep burned hulls from being sucked through the louvers, the area of the louver opening is 2.5 times the opening at the furnace bottom. A grate with a set of stirring rods is provided at the furnace bottom. After initial firing of the furnace, the rods can be pulled out to increase grate spacing to 3.2 cm. A rice hull consumption of 6 to 8 kg/hr (equivalent to 21,000 kg-cal/hr) was obtained during initial tests with this furnace. Some problems have been encountered with the automatic flow of burned hulls through the combustion column.

Heated-sand drying and parboiling. Last year's results indicated that briefly exposing high-moisture paddy to heated sand can substantially reduce moisture and increase head rice yield. The increase in head rice yields with this process is a result of the gelatinization of starch granules as in parboiling of paddy. An initial moisture content of above 27 percent (dry basis) was reported necessary to increase head rice yields by this process. Presoaking paddy in water for 6 to 12 hours introduced sufficient moisture to permit use of this process.

The design of a continuous-flow, heated-sand drying and parboiling machine was modified this year. An auger was installed in the hopper to feed the grain uniformly. The rotary screen was lengthened to improve grain-sand separation. The modified machine gave a stabilized sand temperature of 154 C at a grain feed rate of 54 kg of dry matter per hour. The machine was able to remove 12 percentage points of

10. Schematic drawing of four experimental rice hull furnaces (design that gave the best performance is at bottom).

moisture in 15 seconds from paddy that had an initial moisture level of 32 percent. The outgoing grain temperature was 93 C. The moisture content of the hot grain was further reduced to 16 percent by three methods: 30-minute aeration with ambient air, 10-minute drying with heated air at 37.8 C, or storing in jute bags for 2 weeks.

Additional tests were conducted at different initial grain moisture levels and sand temperatures. Paddy that had initial moisture contents of 21, 23, 25, 27, and 30 percent were subjected to eight sand temperatures between 127 C and 204 C. The grain-sand exposure time was 15 seconds throughout the tests. The paddy was sealed in bottles immediately after processing through the machine and was later dried in the shade to 16 percent moisture before milling.

We found that paddy with above 25 percent initial moisture level gave 5 percent higher head rice yields than the shade-dried control (fig. 11). Paddy with less than 25 percent moisture gave lower head rice yields than the control at grain temperatures of below 118 C. Change in the

color of the milled grain was more pronounced with increasing initial moisture level.

The experimental machine was improved by minimizing the heat losses and increasing heat transfer between the flame and sand. The burners were enclosed in an insulated fire box. The sidewalls of the sandpan were raised to increase its sand-holding capacity. With these modifications the stabilized sand temperature was 204 C at a feed rate of 47 kg of dry matter per hour. The paddy-to-sand weight ratio inside the rotating cylinder was 1:25. Doubling the grain feed rate to 94 kg of dry matter per hour reduced the stabilized sand temperature to 140 C and changed the paddy-to-sand ratio to 1:13. In both cases, a moisture reduction of approximately 12 percentage points was obtained.

Direct-flame drying. Tests were conducted on a laboratory model of a direct-flame drier (fig. 12) in combination with heated air or shade drying. The drying time was reduced by half when direct-flame method was used in combination with heated-air drying. Paddy with an initial moisture content of 32 percent (dry

11. Head rice recovery of paddy at different initial moisture levels when paddy is dried by the heated sand process.

basis) was exposed to direct flame for 40 seconds and then placed in sealed bottles for 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, and 2.0 hours of tempering. The paddy was later dried on a flat-bed drier with heated air. The moisture content of the flame-exposed paddy was reduced to 15 percent after 1 hour of heated-air drying. On the other hand, the same paddy took 2 hours to dry with heated air alone. The head rice yield of the shade-dried control was 62 percent while the same paddy dried for 2 hours with heated air at 54.5 C had 57 percent head rice. Direct-flame exposure in combination with heated-air drying resulted in better head rice yields than the control. But direct-flame exposure in combination with shade drying gave the best head rice yield, 68 percent.

Tests were also conducted to establish the initial paddy moisture level necessary for obtaining high head rice yield for the combination direct-flame and shade-drying method. Irrespective of the initial moisture levels, head rice yields higher than that of the control were obtained in all tests in which the paddy was sealed in bottles for 1 hour (fig. 13). At lower initial moisture levels, flame-exposed paddy that was not tempered in sealed bottles had a lower head rice yield than the control. These experiments indicate that direct-flame exposure in combination with either heated-air drying or shade-drying can accelerate drying and increase head rice yield.

Laboratory test-tube rice miller. Rice breeders and other scientists require small samples of milled rice for studying grain characteristics. Various devices are used for laboratory milling of brown rice samples. These devices generally shake samples of brown rice mixed with an abrasive powder in test tubes at relatively low frequencies and at large stroke lengths. The conventional test-tube millers are bulky and have high power requirements. IRRI, for example, uses a machine which weighs 500 kg and mills 80 samples in 1.5 hours. The machine has a stroke length of 14 cm and operates at 390 strokes per minute. A 2-hp motor is required to operate the machine.

To overcome the problems associated with laboratory test-tube millers, we developed a compact test-tube miller based on high-fre-

12. Schematic drawing of direct-flame laboratory grain drier.

quency and low-amplitude oscillation. The test-tube miller (fig. 14) has two sheetmetal boxes each of which holds a drilled wooden insert for 24 test tubes. The boxes are supported by two pairs of vertical fiber glass strips mounted on an angle-iron frame. Two horizontal fiber glass strips are used to connect the two boxes to a pair of 2.54-cm-stroke cranks on a central drive shaft. The two cranks are 180° apart. This arrangement permits the oscillation of the boxes in opposite directions to provide good dynamic balancing. During operation, the fiber glass strips flex so that hinged or sliding connections are not needed and problems of lubrication are eliminated.

The machine weighs 43 kg and is powered by a one-half horse power motor. It satisfactorily mills 48 samples of 3-gram paddy mixed with aluminum oxide abrasive in 5 minutes at 1,500 cycle/min. Milling is also satisfactory when ground rice hulls are used as an abrasive. Fifteen minutes of milling is necessary, however.

Test and evaluation

Table thresher. In the laboratory, an initial 120-hr, no-load durability test with the table thresher provided no indication of wear or maintenance problems. Field performance tests, however, indicated a weakness in the main drive and bearing assemblies. Because of extensive wear of the bearings and countershafts in the cleaning screen assembly they had to be replaced only after 82 hours of operation. As a result of the test, we changed the type of bearing used and redesigned the drive system configuration. In the new design sealed bearings are used throughout and a countershaft, three pulleys, and one drive belt have been eliminated. The improved machine requires less lubrication, is easier to operate, and weighs less.

Although the total weight is lower, the farmers cooperating in our tests still complain it is difficult to carry into the field. A low-cost wheel carriage has nearly eliminated the problem.

The output of the thresher in our tests has varied from 175 kg/hr under adverse conditions to 450 kg/hr under ideal conditions with an average output of 300 kg/hr. The best per-man

13. Head rice yield of flame-dried (40 sec exposure) paddy as affected by initial moisture content of the paddy, grain flow rate (0.25 and 0.50 kg/min dry matter), and treatment after flame exposure. All samples were variety IR22 milled at 16% moisture content (dry basis).

output is achieved with five men—four men thresh and one man bags the output and places material for the men doing the threshing. At present, the major objection expressed by operators is the amount of trash in the threshed paddy. Several modifications for improving output quality are being tested.

Figure 15 indicates the average cost per ton for the table thresher under two output levels. The fixed and variable costs used in the construction of these curves appear in Table 1. The productivity of the thresher is closely related to crop yield: as yields increase, thresher output also rises. In other words, when yields are high the operator handles less straw per unit of grain than when yields are low. When threshing crops yielding about 4 t/ha, an economic level of operation is reached at approximately 60 t/yr given a custom threshing rate of 5 percent of the crop (paddy valued at P636/t). With low yield (2 t/ha) and low output (260 kg/hr), the

14. Laboratory test tube miller.

break-even point increases to 80 t/yr. If the custom rate increases to 6 percent, the required annual use declines to 46 tons and 56 tons for high and low output rates, respectively. An increase in the price of rough rice would have a similar effect.

Power grain cleaner. Tests of manufacturers' production prototypes of the power grain cleaner revealed numerous minor manufacturing errors. Several design modifications evolved

from these tests. These include safety shields over exposed drives, relocation of components to speed trash elimination and increase operator safety, increased air velocities to improve cleaning quality over a wider range of input conditions, an increase in the height of the spiral louver to 3.18 cm in the outer drum to achieve greater air-grain exposure and conveying capacity, and an increase in the diameter of the feed auger from 6.35 to 16 cm to reduce wear on the feed auger. Excellent cleaning performance has been obtained at the three output levels of 1.5, 2.1, and 2.6 t/hr. A 100-hr, continuous-flow durability test indicated no major wear or maintenance problems. Additional machines are being procured for evaluation in the Philippines and other Asian countries.

The ownership and operational costs for the power grain cleaner are shown in Table 1. Comparing the output of the power grain cleaner with the prevailing custom rate (₱0.64/kg) in figure 16 indicates that use must exceed 240 t/yr to justify buying the machine. Milling operators, grain brokers, warehouses, and co-operatives appear to be the largest potential market for this machine.

Power weeder. In performance tests, the two types of power weeders built by a Japanese

Table 1. Estimated fixed and variable costs for IRRI table thresher and power grain cleaner.

Item	Table thresher (P)	Power grain cleaner (P)
Initial cost	3200	3400
<i>Fixed cost</i>		
Depreciation ^a	640	680
Interest ^b	192	204
Repairs and replacements ^c	320	340
Total	1152	1224
<i>Variable cost/hr</i>		
Fuel and oil ^d	0.22	0.22
Labor ^e	4.50 ^f	2.24 ^g
Total	4.72	2.46

^aStraight-line with estimated service life of 5 years. ^b12% on average investment over life of machine. ^c10% of initial cost. ^d0.67 liter/hr. ^e₱0.75/hr. ^fFour men threshing; two men carrying and stacking. ^gThree men.

company were lighter and easier to handle than the original IRRRI design. Field performance was satisfactory although when operated as three-row weeders, they left a wide unweeded strip under the drive housing. We suggested modifying the center rotor to reduce this problem. In addition, the weeding rotor assembly failed because of metal fatigue and a high wear rate occurred in the rotor fingers. The manufacturer has now corrected the problem by using heavier gage steel.

Japanese grain drier. The performance of a 1.2-ton recirculating-type Japanese drier was evaluated to determine local operating standards. The manufacturer's recommended settings for drying air temperature were used in the first test which resulted in a low moisture reduction rate and an extended drying period. Drying air temperature was increased by 7 C and a drying rate approximately equal to the listed rate was achieved. The capacity of the drier for wet grain was 200 kg less than the rate listed by the manufacturer. The grain used in our tests was probably a different type than that used in the manufacturer's tests and the moisture content of the grain in our tests may also have been higher.

Seeder for pregerminated paddy. Tests were conducted with a seeder which had weights attached to the seed hopper to determine structural defects and the life of the unit. This unit has seeded approximately 30 hectares with no apparent defects.

The first responses from a survey of 65 purchasers of the commercial seeder have been generally favorable. The individuals who were not satisfied with the seeder's performance indicated that they did not completely understand direct seeding methods and the cultural practices required. More information will be added to the instruction manual to clarify cultural requirements for direct seeding.

Seed placement for lowland rice. A study was conducted to determine the effect of depth of planting and seeding rate of pregerminated seeds in puddled soil. Seeds of IR127-80-10, a low tillering line with high resistance to lodging, and IR579-48-1, a high tillering line with moderate susceptibility to lodging, were used. Land preparation was thorough and 70 kg/ha nitrogen

15. Average cost per ton for the table thresher at two output levels.

16. Average cost per ton for the power grain cleaner.

were applied at final leveling and 30 kg/ha at panicle initiation. The field was drained 1 day before seeding.

A modified seeder with an adjustable rate of seeding and variable planting depth was used. Seed was placed on the surface, in rectangular open furrows, 1.9 cm deep, and in 3.8-cm deep furrows. The field was kept drained but moist

17. Economic characteristics of alternative methods of land preparation, planting, weeding and threshing.

tractors is extensive, survey data show that most farmers who own four-wheel tractors operate more than 52 hectares. The effective land area covered by the four-wheel tractors is, however, extended because custom operations are widespread.

Comparing alternative methods of seeding (fig. 17) indicates that the IRRI-designed mechanical seeder becomes a good investment when used on more than 1.6 hectares annually. Responses to a questionnaire mailed to the owners of the mechanical seeder indicate that most of the machines are used on considerably more than 1.6 hectares.

To test the comparative yield and associated input requirements of the mechanical seeder, a replicated trial involving three seeding and nine weeding methods was conducted during the

1971 dry season. The experiment showed (Table 3) that where good weed control is maintained, there is no significant difference in the yield levels obtainable between direct seeding using the mechanical seeder and conventional transplanting. Broadcast seeding, while shown as the least-cost alternative in figure 17, has limited application because of the high quality of water management and weed control it requires.

Of four alternative methods of weeding, granular herbicides remain the least expensive over the complete range considered in the analysis (fig. 17). But recommendations regarding the use of herbicides must be qualified because of their limited availability in many rice growing areas. Comparing the cost of handweeding with the manual rotary weeder and the IRRI-developed power weeder indicates that handweeding is the

18. Heart beat recorder (SAMI) attached to subject.

output per year, the IRRI table thresher becomes a realistic alternative. For outputs of less than 60 t/year, conventional manual methods of threshing are the least-cost methods.

Human energy measurement. In a cooperative study involving the department of agricultural economics, Cornell University, we measured the caloric energy used in the performance of rice production tasks. A replicated experiment involving tasks such as land preparation, weeding, and threshing was undertaken to determine the labor inputs required for alternative methods of performing each task and, in trials involving new techniques, to evaluate the human effort involved in performing the task. The latter tests will allow machine designers to incorporate features which minimize operator fatigue.

In the study we used a compact, lightweight instrument called a Socially Acceptable Monitoring Instrument (fig. 18) which can be easily carried as it records an individual's heartbeat within preset ranges. Heart rate has a well-defined linear relationship with oxygen uptake, except during extremely strenuous exertion. By

19. Relationship between heart rate and oxygen uptake of two subjects (A and B).

careful determination of an individual's metabolic energy expenditure, his energy output can be measured at any level of heart activity.

Figure 19 shows the calibration lines for two subjects in this experiment and clearly exhibits the linear relationship between heartbeat and oxygen uptake. The two lowest points are the resting rates of the subjects. Succeeding points represent higher levels of manual activity. Not only does the basic metabolic rate among individuals differ, but the rate at which they expend energy as they perform progressively more strenuous tasks also varies as shown by the difference in slope between the two lines.

The calibration data which have been collected are being tested for significant differences in slope among individuals and between sex groups. By recording heartbeats and recording the time required to accomplish a specific task, it is possible to determine not only labor input (man-hours) but also the energy cost expressed in calories. Table 5 presents some preliminary results relating to energy expenditures for planting, weeding, harvesting, and threshing-winnowing. These data have been useful in establishing design parameters related to machine performance, size, and cost relative to other techniques available for the performance of the same task.

Agronomy

Several chemicals that increase the protein content of rice grain were identified: tenoran, CP 17029, and benzomarc. Simetryne continued to look promising for increasing protein content.

Chemical weed control with low-cost 2,4-D or MCPA in transplanted rice with butachlor and benthocarb in broadcast-seeded flooded rice was found to be feasible under uncontrolled water management typical of farm conditions. For control of perennial sedge (*Scirpus maritimus*), butachlor followed by MCPA was highly effective. This perennial sedge is becoming a serious weed problem in the Philippines.

This year's results confirmed our previous 2 years' data that IR442-2-58 is the most promising line for upland rice.

Experiments on the effects of water stress indicated that soil moisture tension in Maahas clay, as low as 17 centibar, equally reduced the grain yields of the upland variety M1-48 and the lowland variety IR20. These data suggest that M1-48 does not have higher resistance to soil moisture stress than the improved lowland variety IR20.

Date-of-planting experiment

In the date-of-planting experiment, rice is planted in every month. Figure 1 shows the nitrogen responses of IR8, IR22, IR24, and H-4. The grain yields in both the April and May harvests, 9 t/ha, were higher than the highest yield obtained in any month last year. Although the total solar radiation values for the entire year were lower than the average of previous 5 years, the environment during the ripening period for the April and May harvests nevertheless was better this year than last year.

Because of a severe outbreak of tungro virus, the crops for August and September harvest months were plowed under. When crops were harvested in October and November, which are normal harvest months for the area, all three improved varieties produced good yields.

Many persons believe that the tillering capa-

city of IR22 is lower than that of IR8. Figure 2 shows that, on the contrary, the tiller number at flowering for the 10 harvest months was higher for IR22 than for IR8. But the grain yields of IR8 were generally higher than those of IR22 (fig. 1). The growth duration of IR8 during the 10 harvest months varied from 122 to 130 days, while that of IR22 varied from 113 to 127 days indicating that IR22 has greater photoperiod sensitivity than IR8.

Nitrogen response

Experiments were continued at the IRRI farm and in farmers' fields to study the nitrogen response and growth characteristics of varieties or lines developed by IRRI and by breeders elsewhere.

Promising lines. Eight promising lines from the IRRI breeding program were compared

1. Nitrogen responses of IR8, IR22, IR24, and H-4 (August and September harvests omitted) by harvest month plotted with solar radiation total for 45 days before harvest. Date-of-planting experiment, IRRI, 1971.

Weed control

Phenoxy acid herbicides for transplanted rice.

Last year we reported that all commonly marketed liquid or granular formulations and derivatives of 2,4-D and MCPA were equally effective in controlling barnyardgrass and other annual weeds in transplanted rice.

During the 1971 dry season, granular and liquid formulations of the isopropyl ester of 2,4-D and the potassium salt of MCPA were compared in saturated soil and in flooded soil. IR22 variety was grown with dapog (10-day-old) and regular (21-day-old) seedlings to compare their relative sensitivity to phenoxy acid herbicides applied 4 days after transplanting.

With continuous flooding 3 to 5 cm deep, 2,4-D or MCPA gave satisfactory weed control whether applied in granular or liquid formulation to dapog or regular seedlings (Table 9). Low temperature occurred during the first 2 weeks after herbicide application. During this period the potassium salt of MCPA at 1.6 kg/ha active ingredient, which is twice the recommended rate of application, caused some toxicity to dapog-raised seedlings.

In soil at saturation, the grain yields were generally lower than those under continuous flooding (Table 9). Toxicity of phenoxy acid herbicides to the IR22 plants was higher under saturation than under continuous flooding, explaining part of the yield difference. Further-

more, under the high sunlight and temperature that occur during the ripening period of a dry season crop, it is difficult to provide enough water to avoid incipient moisture stress while maintaining saturation. Moisture stress in combination with toxicity caused by application of high rates of phenoxy acid herbicides makes it difficult for seedlings to recover. Seedlings from the wetbed nursery, however, were able to minimize toxicity of phenoxy acid herbicides under continuous saturation. Our results indicate that if 3 to 5 cm of water cannot be maintained, it is better to use potassium salt of MCPA than isopropyl ester of 2,4-D. Furthermore, it is essential to use regular wetbed seedlings when continuous flooding cannot be maintained.

In the wet season, the experiment was conducted with partially rainfed treatments. For a period in each of the three treatments, the moisture supply was entirely from rainfall (Table 10). IR24 was used as the test variety. The seedlings were grown in a dapog nursery since that is the common practice in many areas in the Philippines.

When the plots were kept rainfed for the first 3 weeks after transplanting, both 2,4-D and MCPA at 0.8 kg/ha a.i. produced significantly higher grain yield than the untreated control. At 1.6 kg/ha a.i., MCPA caused more toxicity to IR24 rice than 2,4-D, explaining the lower grain yield with MCPA (Table 10).

Continuous flooding with 5 cm water during

Table 9. Effect of early application (4 days after transplanting) of 2,4-D and MCPA on the grain yield of IR22 transplanted from dapog and regular wet bed nursery under flooded and continuous saturation conditions. IRRI, 1971 dry season.

Formulation	Rate ^a (kg/ha)	Yield ^b (t/ha)			
		Flooded soil		Saturated soil	
		Dapog	Regular	Dapog	Regular
<i>2,4-D</i>					
Emulsifiable concentrate	0.8	7.3 bc	6.5 b	2.1 de	4.6 c
	1.6	7.5 bc	7.2 ab	3.2 bcd	5.6 bc
Granular	0.8	7.8 abc	7.1 ab	4.4 ab	5.8 bc
	1.6	7.8 abc	7.1 ab	3.9 abc	5.6 bc
<i>MCPA</i>					
Water-soluble liquid	0.8	8.4 a	7.5 a	5.0 a	7.4 a
	1.6	7.2 c	7.3 ab	1.4 e	6.4 ab
Granular	0.8	8.1 ab	6.8 ab	5.4 a	6.6 ab
	1.6	7.0 c	7.2 ab	2.2 de	6.2 ab
Control	—	6.1 d	5.7 c	2.5 cde	2.7 d

^aOf active ingredient. ^bAny two means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

the early stage of crop growth provided adequate control of grassy weeds without herbicide application. Herbicide application did not result in additional grain yield. Such precise water management is rare in farmers' fields in tropical Asia, however.

Herbicide application was essential when the plots were kept at saturation for the first 14 days after transplanting and under 5 cm of flooding for the next 10 days followed by rainfed conditions for the rest of the crop season. Under such conditions, either 2,4-D or MCPA should be applied at the appropriate rate (0.8 kg/ha). At higher rates, toxicity symptoms from either 2,4-D or MCPA will be apparent (Table 10).

These results indicate that even under partially rainfed conditions, the use of a low-cost phenoxy acid herbicide, such as 2,4-D or MCPA, is effective in controlling weeds in transplanted rice in monsoon Asia.

Herbicides for transplanted rice. New herbicides are continuously being evaluated at IRRI and other locations to provide many alternative herbicides for tropical rices. The ultimate choice of any one of the effective herbicides will depend on factors such as availability, cost, relative ease of application, and storage. Results from IRRI and from cooperative experiments conducted during the 1971 dry season demonstrate that three new herbicides, from Ciba-Geigy, C-285, C-288, and C-290, with 2,4-D provided excellent weed control when applied 4 days after transplanting

Table 10. The effect of early application (4 days after transplanting) of 2,4-D and MCPA on the grain yield of transplanted IR24 under adequate, intermediate, and poor early water management conditions. IRRI, 1971 wet season.

Chemical	Rate (kg/ha)	Yield ^a (t/ha)		
		Adequate ^b	Intermediate ^c	Poor ^d
<i>2,4-D^e</i>				
Liquid	0.8	6.1 a	6.6 a	6.2 ab
	1.6	5.9 a	6.8 a	5.9 bc
Granule	0.8	6.0 a	6.6 a	5.7 bc
	1.6	6.2 a	6.8 a	6.4 a
<i>MCPA^f</i>				
Liquid	0.8	6.0 a	6.7 a	5.9 abc
	1.6	6.4 a	5.6 b	5.4 c
Granule	0.8	6.3 a	6.6 a	6.2 ab
	1.6	6.2 a	5.9 b	5.8 bc
Control	—	6.0 a	5.6 b	4.4 d

^aAverage of four replications. ^b5 cm water for 10 days after herbicide application, 1 cm water maintained from the 11th to the 20th day, then rainfed until maturity. ^cRainfed for 20 days after herbicide application, then 5 cm water maintained until maturity. ^d1 cm water for 10 days after herbicide application, 5 cm water from the 11th to 20th day, then rainfed until maturity. ^eIsopropyl ester. ^fPotassium salt.

(Table 11). The mixture of 2,4-D with Ciba herbicides provides better control of broadleaved weeds and sedges and contributes towards the control of grassy weeds.

During the wet season, a large number of chemicals from different companies from all over the world were screened to identify new herbicides for rice. Experimental chemicals which appeared promising for transplanted rice were A-820 from Amchem, USA; C-18649 and C-19490 from Ciba-Geigy, Switzerland; Mon-843, Monsanto, USA; USB-3153 and USB-3584 from U.S. Borax; and U-27267 from

Table 11. Grain yield of transplanted rice as affected by granular herbicides (applied 4 days after transplanting) at IRRI and in three locations in the Philippines. IRRI, 1971 dry season.

Herbicide ^a	Rate (kg/ha)	Yield (t/ha)			
		IRRI	Maligaya	Iloilo	Bicol
2,4-D IPE	0.8	7.6 a	4.9 b	6.3 b	6.4 a
Butachlor	1.0	7.8 a	6.5 a	7.2 a	6.8 a
Butachlor/2,4-D BE	1.0/0.5	8.2 a	6.6 a	6.7 ab	6.6 a
Benthiocarb	1.0	7.7 a	5.8 ab	6.7 ab	6.7 a
Benthiocarb + 2,4-D IPE	1.0 + 0.5	7.7 a	5.7 ab	6.7 ab	6.6 a
C-285 + 2,4-D IPE	0.75 + 0.5	7.8 a	6.4 a	7.2 a	6.6 a
C-288 + 2,4-D IPE	0.75 + 0.5	7.6 a	6.2 a	6.9 ab	6.8 a
NTN 5006/2,4-D IPE	2.0/0.45	7.7 a	5.8 ab	6.8 ab	6.6 a
C-290 + 2,4-D IPE	0.75 + 0.5	7.7 a	6.2 a	6.8 ab	6.6 a
Control	—	4.6 b	1.9 c	2.2 c	5.1 b

^aBE = butyl ester; IPE = isopropyl ester.

Table 12. Grain yield of transplanted rice as affected by promising new herbicides applied before emergence of weeds. IRRI, 1971 wet season.

Chemical ^a	Formulation ^a	Rate (kg/ha)	Yield (t/ha)
A-820	L	1.5	3.8
	L	3.0	3.2
Benthiocarb/simetryne	G	0.7/0.15	3.7
	G	1.4/0.3	3.8
C-18649	G	1.0	3.1
C-18649 + 2,4-D	G	0.5/0.5	3.6
C-19490	G	1.0	3.1
C-19490 + 2,4-D	G	0.5 + 0.5	3.6
MON 843	L	2.0	3.5
USB 3153	G	2.0	3.2
USB 3584	G	2.0	3.6
U-27267	G	2.0	3.2
Butachlor	G	1.0	4.0
TCE-styrene/2,4-D	G	0.75/0.5	3.9
2,4-D	G	0.8	3.6
Control	—	—	0

^aG = granular; L = liquid; + = chemicals applied in immediate succession.

Upjohn, USA. A combination herbicide from Kumiai, Japan and Ciba-Geigy, Switzerland, benthiocarb/simetryne, which is widely used in Japan also looked promising under tropical conditions. The rate found to be effective in the tropics is one-fourth the rate used in Japan, suggesting that the cost of herbicide should be lower in tropical Asia than in Japan (Table 12).

Herbicides for broadcast-seeded rice. Last year we reported that either butachlor or benthiocarb applied at 6 days after seeding rice (when grassy weeds had one to two leaves) completely controlled all weeds in broadcast-seeded rice and caused no toxicity to the crop under controlled irrigation (1970 Annual Report). During 1971, we evaluated these two herbicides under simulated farm-level water supply conditions.

In the dry season, both benthiocarb and butachlor gave significantly higher grain yields than the untreated controls at all water management treatments except continuous flooding with 5 cm water (Table 13). These results indicate that in spite of uncontrolled water supply, both chemicals usually should control weeds in broadcast-seeded rice. Furthermore, if 5 cm of water is maintained throughout the crop season, and land is prepared thoroughly, chemical weed control may not be essential.

In the wet season, when most rice is grown in Asia, chemical treatments with benthiocarb and butachlor produced significantly higher grain yields than the controls under most water management treatments including rainfed conditions (Table 13). Weed growth in the untreated control plots was highly variable

Table 13. Effect of water management practices on weed control by two granular herbicides applied at one- to two-leaf stage of grasses for broadcast-seeded IR22 (avg. of four replications). IRRI, 1971.

Water management ^a	Grain yield (t/ha)					
	Dry season			Wet season		
	Benthiocarb ^b	Butachlor ^c	Control	Benthiocarb ^b	Butachlor ^c	Control
5 cm (A-M)	7.9 a	8.7 a	7.3 a	4.5 a	4.1 a	4.4 a
2.5 cm (A-M)	8.4 a	8.2 a	5.5 b	4.5 a	4.4 a	2.9 abcd
1 cm + 2.5 cm (A-PI) (PI-M)	7.4 a	7.9 a	2.5 c	4.9 a	4.5 a	3.8 ab
2.5 cm (6-M)	8.1 a	7.9 a	1.8 c	5.1 a	5.4 a	2.5 bcde
5 cm + 1 cm + 5 cm (6-10) (11-20) (21-M)	8.1 a	8.0 a	1.2 c	5.0 a	4.6 a	1.8 cdef
2.5 cm + 1 cm + 5 cm (6-10) (11-20) (21-M)	8.2 a	8.3 a	2.6 c	5.1 a	4.7 a	1.5 def
2.5 cm + 5 cm (6-20) (21-M)	8.2 a	8.0 a	1.8 c	5.0 a	5.4 a	1.3 ef
1 cm + 5 cm (6-20) (21-M)	8.2 a	7.8 a	0.8 c	4.4 a	4.4 a	0.4 f
Rainfed	—	—	—	5.2 a	4.5 a	3.4 abc

^aFor each water management requirement, the first line indicates the depth of water and the second line in parentheses indicates the corresponding period (in days) the water level was maintained; A = day herbicide was applied; PI = panicle initiation; M = maturity. ^b1.5 kg/ha active ingredient. ^c1.0 kg/ha active ingredient.

Table 14. Grain yield of broadcast-seeded flooded rice (avg. of four replications) as affected by granular herbicides applied at one- to two-leaf stage of grasses. IRRI, 1971 dry and wet seasons.

Herbicide	Rate (kg/ha)	Yield (t/ha)					
		Dry season			Wet season		
		IR8	IR22	Mean	IR8	IR22	Mean
Benthiocarb	1.5	8.5	9.5	9.0 a	5.7	7.1	6.4 a
Butachlor	1.0	8.2	9.2	8.7 a	5.4	6.7	6.0 ab
NTN 5006	2.0	8.2	8.8	8.5 a	5.5	6.6	6.0 ab
NTN 5006/2,4-D IPE	2.0/0.45	8.1	9.0	8.6 a	5.7	7.2	6.4 a
TCE-styrene/2,4-D IPE	0.6/0.4	8.2	9.0	8.6 a	5.5	7.0	6.2 ab
C-285	1.0	8.3	9.0	8.6 a	6.0	6.5	6.2 ab
C-286	1.0	8.0	9.3	8.6 a	5.6	7.0	6.3 ab
C-288	1.0	8.4	9.3	8.8 a	5.7	6.8	6.2 ab
M-3338 (liquid)	2.0	7.2	8.0	7.6 b	4.9	5.8	5.4 b
Control	—	2.1	3.4	2.8 c	3.2	3.7	3.4 c

because of frequent rains that occurred during the first 5 days after seeding rice and weeds. Also, the rainfed treatment had standing water throughout the experiment, which minimized weed growth.

The effectiveness of granular herbicides and the toxicity to IR8 and IR22 at IRRI farm and to IR24 at the Maligaya Rice Research and Training Center in the Philippines were evaluated during the year. In all these locations C-285, C-288, and C-290, and NTN 5006 with 2,4-D were as effective for broadcast-seeded rice as previously identified successful herbicides, such as benthiocarb and butachlor (Tables 14 and 15).

In Central Luzon, where the Maligaya station is located, the incidence of tungro virus in IR22 was widespread in the wet season. IR24 produced the highest grain yield, only 4.8 t/ha. The low yield was caused by a high incidence of grassy weeds as evidenced by the zero yield in untreated control plots (Table 15).

The chemicals that are effective and safe for transplanted rice were in general effective and safe for broadcast-seeded flooded rice (Table 16). Compounds which can be used for both transplanted and broadcast-seeded flooded rice are highly desirable for marketing in the same country. At least five new compounds appeared to be as good as benthiocarb (Table 16), but they must be evaluated under rainfed conditions before their use can be suggested.

Control of *Scirpus maritimus*. The perennial sedge, *Scirpus maritimus* L., is capable of

becoming a persistent and serious weed in lowland rice fields. The plant produces solitary culms from underground tubers or rhizomes which emerge from the soil about 5 days after the last harrowing. Each plant produces new rhizomes and tubers which in turn give rise to new plants. Infestations cause lodging of the rice plants and reduce grain yield. Herbicides commonly used for controlling annual grasses and broadleaved weeds are not effective against *S. maritimus* at the recommended rates. We examined the life cycle of *S. maritimus* and attempted to develop control measures.

In the greenhouse, each plant developed an average of 10 rhizomatous sprouts and seven new tubers, and grew 60 cm tall in 5 weeks (Table 17). While 5 cm of water did not affect the germination of tubers placed just below the surface of the soil, it markedly reduced the germination of tubers placed more than 3 cm deep in the soil (Table 18).

Table 15. Effect of granular herbicides applied at one- to two-leaf stage of grasses on the grain yield of broadcast-seeded IR24 (average of four replications). Maligaya, Philippines, 1971.

Herbicide	Rate (kg/ha)	Yield (t/ha)	
		Dry season	Wet season
Benthiocarb	1.5	7.8 a	4.8 a
Butachlor	1.0	7.9 a	4.2 a
NTN 5006/2,4-D IPE	2.0/4.5	7.4 ab	3.7 a
TCE-styrene/2,4-D IPE	0.6/0.4	6.8 b	4.6 a
C-285	1.0	7.5 ab	—
C-288	1.0	7.5 ab	4.4 a
C-290	1.0	—	4.5 a
Control	—	1.7 c	0 b

Table 16. Grain yield of broadcast-seeded flooded IR24 as affected by promising new herbicides applied at the one- to two-leaf stage of grasses (6 days after seeding) or the two- to three-leaf stage (8 days after seeding). IRRI, 1971 wet season.

Chemical ^a	Formulation ^b	Rate ^c (kg/ha)	Yield ^d (t/ha)	
			1 to 2 leaves	2 to 3 leaves
A-820	L	1.5	3.8	—
	L	3.0	—	4.7
A-820 + 2,4-D EE	L + WP	1.5 + 0.5	4.4	—
	L + WP	3.0 + 0.5	3.4 ^d	4.1
Benthiocarb/simetryne	G	0.7/0.15	4.4	—
C-18649	G	0.75	4.1	—
	G	1.5	4.3	5.3
C-18649 + 2,4-D IPE	G + G	0.75 + 0.5	4.4	—
	G + G	1.5 + 0.5	3.8 ^d	4.7
C-19490	G	0.75	4.5	3.8 ^d
	G	1.5	4.8	4.4
C-19490 + 2, 4-D IPE	G + G	0.75 + 0.5	4.0	4.4
	G + G	1.5 + 0.5	4.5	4.0
MON 843	L	0.75	3.4 ^d	—
	L	3.0	4.4	4.9
	G	3.0	4.5	3.4 ^d
USB 3153	L	1.0	4.8	—
Benthiocarb	G	1.5	3.6 ^d	—
Control			0.3	

^aEE = ethyl ester; IPE = isopropyl ester. ^bL = liquid; G = granule; WP = wettable powder; + = chemicals applied in immediate succession. ^cOf active ingredient. ^dYield reduced due to lodging.

Herbicides found effective against the weeds were OCS 21799 [2-(4-chlorotolyl)oxy-N-methoxy acetamide], MCP, and butachlor. The effectiveness of butachlor was markedly increased when combined with MCP.

During the 1971 wet season, we evaluated four herbicide treatments for the control of *S. maritimus* in transplanted IR24 rice under four water management conditions. Regardless of water management all the treated plots yielded significantly more than the untreated controls. Butachlor followed by MCP controlled *Scirpus spp.* adequately and gave consistently higher yield than the control under most

Table 17. Growth rate of culms, rhizomes, and tubers in *S. maritimus*.

Days after emergence	Culm ht (cm)	New sprouts/mother tuber (no.)	New tubers/mother tuber (no.)
2	13	0	0
8	27	2	0
15	40	4	2
23	49	5	3
28	56	6	4
34	61	11	7

water management conditions (Table 19). At high rates of MCP (1.5 kg/ha), however, the basal node of rice plants developed abnormal root growth (fig. 3).

Upland rice

Varietal response to soil moisture and solar energy. Experiments were conducted in cooperation with the Bureau of Plant Industry during the 1971 wet season at the Maligaya Rice Research and Training Center and at the La Granja Experiment Station. The objectives were to evaluate rice varieties for high nitrogen response and grain yield under typical upland conditions.

At Maligaya, the highest yield, 6.6 t/ha, was obtained with IR24 seeded on June 9 and fertilized at 120 kg/ha N (fig. 4). The grain yield from the crop seeded on June 29 was slightly lower than that from the first seeding but higher than that of the later seeded crop (Table 20). The lowland varieties, IR24 and IR5, consistently outyielded the upland variety, M1-48, at all dates of seeding.

The crop seeded on July 29 received normal rainfall and solar radiation during the vegetative stage (Table 20). But only 172 mm of rain fell at the reproductive stage and therefore the soil moisture tensions reached more than 25 cm Hg (field capacity) a few days after heading (fig. 5). The crop suffered from soil moisture stress and for this reason, the yields were lower.

At La Granja, which is located in a typical upland rice area, the three varieties did not perform well. The highest grain yield, 3.5 t/ha, was obtained with IR24 from the crop seeded May 21 (fig. 4). The yield response to added nitrogen for crops seeded on June 17 and July 12 was poor.

Table 18. Influence of soil and water depth (0, 3, and 5 cm) on the germination of *S. maritimus*.

Soil depth (cm)	Germination (%)		
	0 cm	3 cm	5 cm
0	53	70	57
3	43	20	3
6	30	0	0
12	23	0	0

Table 19. Effect of water management^a on some promising herbicides (applied 3 days after transplanting) for the control of *S. maritimus* in transplanted IR24 rice. IRRI, 1971 wet season.

Treatment ^b	Formulation	Rate (kg/ha)	Excellent		Good		Fair		Poor	
			Dry weed wt ^c (g/sq m)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Dry weed wt ^c (g/sq m)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Dry weed wt ^c (g/sq m)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Dry weed wt ^c (g/sq m)	Grain yield (t/ha)
Butachlor+ MCPP	L+L	3.0+1.0	9	3.8 a	34	3.7 b	19	4.9 a	100	3.2 a
Butachlor fb MCPP	L+L	2.0 fb 1.5	0	4.4 a	4	5.1 a	0	4.1 b	0	3.3 a
Butachlor+ OCS 21799	L+ WP	1.0+1.0	31	3.8 a	63	3.5 b	37	3.3 c	104	2.9 a
Butachlor/2,4-D BE	G	1.0/0.5	63	3.9 a	71	3.9 b	107	3.3 c	148	3.2 a
Control	—	—	202	2.8 b	290	2.0 c	213	2.6 d	296	2.1 b

^aExcellent: 5 cm continual flooding; moderate: 5 cm to 10 days after herbicide application, 1 cm from 11 to 20 days after, 5 cm from 21 days until maturity; fair: 5 cm to 5 days after herbicide application, 2.5 cm from 6 to 10 days, 1 cm from 11 to 20 days, 5 cm from 21 days until maturity; poor: 1 cm to 20 days after herbicide application, 5 cm from 21 days until maturity. ^bfb = followed by; + = chemical applied in immediate succession. ^c56 days after transplanting.

The low yields and poor nitrogen response at La Granja can be attributed to two things. Compared with Maligaya station, solar energy values at La Granja were slightly lower (Table 20). And although rainfall was adequate during the crop season, the soil (sandy loam) could not retain enough moisture for optimum growth: the soil moisture tensions were often higher than 25 cm Hg (fig. 5). The crop planted on May 21 suffered soil moisture stress during the booting stage. For the June 17 seeding, moisture tensions were high during the vegetative and heading stages of the crop while plants seeded on July 12 experienced stress during the vegetative and panicle initiation stages. As a result of moisture stress, the grain yields at the La Granja station were low.

Results from La Granja indicate that varieties should be bred for higher tolerance to moisture stress in order to increase grain yield of rice under upland conditions.

Yield trial. During the 1971 wet season, several new lines, including a few high yielding lowland varieties, were planted in upland plots at two dates of seeding. The Philippine upland varieties, M1-48, and Palawan, and African upland varieties, OS4, OS649, and E425, were included for comparison (Table 21).

Once again, all lowland varieties and lines consistently outyielded all upland varieties included in the experiment. IR442-2-58, a semidwarf line bred for deep water rice appears to be the most promising line for upland rice. It yielded as well as IR5 under upland conditions and is earlier. Its grain appearance is better than that of IR5. The IR841 and IR937 lines

which had the highest yields in the test are somewhat less promising because of susceptibility to diseases.

Water stress effects on grain yield

Moisture stress and nitrogen response. An experiment was conducted in the 1971 wet season to compare the nitrogen response of flooded rice with the response of rainfed rice suffering water stress. Three rates of nitrogen were used with the highest rate applied as a single or a split dose. The three water management regimes were continual flooding, continual flooding for the first 60 days only, and completely rainfed conditions.

With 100 kg/ha N under rainfed conditions the yield was about twice that of the unfertilized control (Table 22). A response was also observed with split application of nitrogen under the rainfed conditions. The slight response to

3. Abnormal root growth of rice was observed from 7 to 10 days following MCP spray at 1.5 kg/ha active ingredient.

4. Nitrogen response of IR24, IR5, and M1-48 under upland conditions at three dates of seeding. IRRI-BPI cooperative soil fertility experiment. Maligaya Rice Research and Training Center and La Granja Experiment Station, Philippines, 1971 wet season.

split application under irrigated conditions is due mainly to lodging of some varieties with the single application.

Irrigation in response to soil moisture tension.

Last year we described an experiment in which

Table 20. Solar radiation, rainfall, and grain yield of upland rice (avg. of three varieties and three nitrogen levels). Maligaya Rice Research and Training Center and La Granja Experiment Station, Philippines, 1971 wet season.

Planting time	Vegetative period rainfall (mm)	Reproductive period		Yield (t/ha)
		Solar radiation (kcal/sq cm)	Rainfall (mm)	
<i>Maligaya</i>				
June 9	1042	15.3	413	3.6
June 29	1072	13.8	385	3.3
July 29	749	14.6	172	2.0
<i>La Granja</i>				
May 21	1249	14.9	436	2.0
June 17	987	13.8	776	0.8
July 12	669	13.1	713	0.8

5. Soil moisture tension at 20-cm depth during the vegetative reproductive stages (PI = panicle initiation, B = booting, H = heading, and M = maturity) of rice under three dates of seeding (average of three varieties and two nitrogen levels). IRRI-BPI cooperative soil fertility experiment. 1971 wet season.

lowland rice was irrigated in response to soil moisture tension 15 or 30 cm deep. This experiment was repeated in the 1971 dry season with some modifications. Five centimeters of water were applied each time the moisture tension at 15 cm reached either one-sixth bar, one-third bar, or one-half bar. A high tillering lowland variety, IR20, was compared with a low tillering upland variety, M1-48, in an attempt to identify possible varietal differences in moisture stress resistance. Ammonium sulfate at 40 kg/ha N was incorporated in the soil the day before transplanting and an additional 20 kg/ha was topdressed at the panicle initiation stage. The amount of nitrogen applied was low for a dry season IR20 crop and perhaps optimum for M1-48.

Compared with the continually flooded control the yields of both varieties were reduced in all treatments (Table 23). The grain yield of IR20 under continual flooding was low because of the low rate of nitrogen applied. M1-48 consistently produced lower grain yields than IR20, but when compared with the continually flooded control, the percentage yield reduction

was the same, about 30 percent for both varieties, in all treatments. The tillering of IR20 was little affected, but the panicle weight was markedly reduced. In this experiment the upland variety showed no advantage under moisture stress compared with IR20. The low yields of M1-48 are partly the result of low tillering capacity and partly because we planted only one seedling per hill. The tiller production of M1-48 is not sufficient to compensate for such a low number of seedlings per hill.

Irrigation response of varieties. The new rice varieties have been most widely adopted in irrigated rice areas. This is in part because of the greater technical knowledge and skills of the farmers in these areas and because of the incentive provided by assured supplies of water. Another, less thoroughly explored reason is the possibility that the traditional varieties may better tolerate the adverse soil moisture conditions which frequently develop in rainfed areas.

In the 1971 dry season we examined the relative response of traditional and improved varieties to irrigation at different fertilizer rates. Good, average, and poor irrigation conditions were approximated by continual flooding at 5 cm, alternate soil wetting and drying with some moisture stress between irrigations, and alternate soil wetting and drying with more extensive moisture stress between irrigations.

Yields of the improved varieties, IR20 and IR22, decreased as the water management became poorer while yields of the traditional varieties, Peta and Sigadis, increased (Table 24). The improved variety C4-63 was less sensitive to water management because it has a greater tendency to lodge under optimal conditions than IR20 and IR22. Also, the longer growth duration of this variety and heavy rains encountered late in this experiment may have allowed some recovery from the early stress effects.

With good water management and higher rates of nitrogen application, the yields of the traditional varieties were lowered by early and extensive lodging. Less lodging occurred with poorer water management so their yields increased. With poor water management, Sigadis yielded as well as the improved varieties.

Table 21. Upland rice yield trial (seeded August 5 and September 9). IRRI, 1971 wet season.

Variety or line	Growth duration (days)	Grain yield (t/ha)		
		Aug. 5 crop	Sept. 9 crop	Mean (t/ha)
IR841-67-1	118 to 128	4.0	3.6	3.8
IR937-76-2	118 to 133	4.1	3.3	3.7
IR5	120 to 138	4.0	3.3	3.6
IR8	108 to 135	3.8	3.3	3.6
IR442-2-58	116 to 120	3.4	3.6	3.5
IR1416-131-5	118 to 138	3.4	3.6	3.5
IR661-1-140	118 to 124	3.8	3.1	3.4
IR1108-3-5	106 to 128	3.7	3.2	3.4
IR788-21-3	112 to 133	3.8	3.1	3.4
IR1163-135	110 to 131	3.6	3.2	3.4
IR24	116 to 128	3.8	3.0	3.4
OS649	112 to 115	2.2	2.5	2.4
E425	94 to 115	2.4	1.4	1.9
OS4	106 to 115	1.9	1.6	1.8
M1-48	94 to 115	1.6	1.2	1.4
Palawan	106 to 117	1.6	1.1	1.4

Table 22. The effect of nitrogen rate and time of application on grain yield (avg of five varieties or lines) under rainfed and flooded conditions. IRRI, 1971 wet season.

Nitrogen applied ^a (kg/ha)	Yield ^b (t/ha)		
	Rainfed	Flooded then rainfed ^c	Continually flooded
0	2.99	4.01	4.48
50	3.84	4.57	4.90
100	4.58	5.25	5.30
50 + 50	4.66	5.29	5.76
33 + 33 + 33	5.30	5.61	5.68

^aBasal, basal + panicle initiation, or basal + maximum tillering + panicle initiation. ^bMean of two replications. ^cFlooded during the first 60 days then rainfed until maturity.

Table 23. Effect of irrigation at different soil moisture tensions on the grain yields and use of irrigation water of IR20 and M1-48 transplanted in puddled soil. IRRI, 1971 dry season.

Irrigated	Panicles (no./sq m)	Panicle wt (g)	Irrigation water applied (mm)	Yield (t/ha)	Irrigation efficiency (kg ha ⁻¹ mm ⁻¹)
<i>IR20^b</i>					
Continually ^a	337	1.63	850	4.71	5.5
At 17 cb	312	1.41	520	3.14	6.0
At 33 cb	362	1.37	450	3.72	8.3
At 50 cb	371	1.25	390	3.01	7.7
<i>M1-48^b</i>					
Continually ^a	129	2.29	810	2.23	2.8
At 17 cb	104	2.50	480	1.61	3.4
At 33 cb	105	2.41	400	1.52	3.8
At 50 cb	92	2.47	330	1.50	4.5

^aIn continually flooded plots, water was maintained 5 cm deep; in other plots, 5 cm of water was applied when the soil moisture tension reached the indicated value. cb = centibar. ^bIR20 matured in 100 to 110 days; M1-48 in 95 days.

Table 24. Effect of good, average, and poor water management and nitrogen on the grain yield of five rice varieties. IRRI, 1971 dry season.

Nitrogen applied (kg/ha)	Yield ^a (t/ha)			LSD (5%)
	Good	Average	Poor	
	<i>IR20^b</i>			
0	5.93	4.79	4.34	1.35
50	6.80	5.15	5.08	1.35
100	6.56	4.71	5.59	1.35
	<i>IR22^b</i>			
0	5.74	4.02	3.95	1.35
50	5.30	4.08	4.45	n.s.
100	5.95	5.34	5.04	n.s.
	<i>C4-63^c</i>			
0	5.42	4.50	4.74	n.s.
50	6.08	4.71	5.23	1.35
100	5.90	5.18	5.71	n.s.
	<i>Peta^d</i>			
0	4.01	3.97	4.30	n.s.
50	2.88	4.32	4.43	1.35
100	1.64	3.87	4.32	1.35
	<i>Sigadis^d</i>			
0	5.31	5.08	5.33	n.s.
50	5.02	4.74	5.64	n.s.
100	3.56	5.55	5.57	1.35
LSD (5%)	1.03	1.03	1.03	1.03

^aMean of two replications. ^bMatured in 118 days. ^cMatured in 130 days. ^dMatured in 146 days.

This experiment does not clearly differentiate the relative effects of lodging and moisture stress tolerance on rice yield. But the data do show some reasons for the slow adoption of improved varieties in areas with poor or no irrigation.

Time of field drainage. As cropping intensity increases, water management becomes more critical. One problem is the determination of the best time to drain a lowland rice field before harvest. Early drainage may decrease rice yield. In addition, the effect of different times of drainage on the soil moisture conditions must also be evaluated since the soil moisture content largely determines the delay before land preparation can begin for upland crops in rotation with lowland rice.

We attempted to determine the effects of time of field drainage on grain yield and soil moisture by planting six varieties in each of 12 plots in a staggered schedule so that all varieties would flower on the same date. At 3-day intervals near heading, water was drained from the surface of the plots and no further irrigation water was added. The early onset of

the monsoon rains interfered with the experiment. Although no standing water was allowed to remain in the fields, we were unable to determine any effect of the different times of drainage on either the grain yield or the soil moisture content at harvest.

A similar experiment was conducted in the greenhouse in large pots containing 10 kg of oven-dry soil and in small pots containing 6 kg of soil. Two seedlings were planted in each pot. Table 25 shows the effect of withholding irrigation at different times near heading on the yield and yield components of C4-63G. The grain yield was reduced the longer the period without irrigation. Each of the yield components contributed to the decrease in grain yield. Moisture stress near heading prevented the emergence of some panicles. Decreased number of grains per panicle and 100-grain weight were more important contributors to the grain yield decrease when the drainage occurred later. Yields were lower in the small pots than in the large pots because the small pots had less total soil moisture available for plant growth when drained at the same time as the large pots.

Rotational irrigation experiments

Water use efficiency. For locations where it is desirable to irrigate as large an area as possible with limited supplies of water, a rotational irrigation scheme is often recommended. Irrigation water is supplied to different areas at regular intervals in amounts designed to maximize grain production with high water efficiency. The successful operation of such systems obviously calls for reliable data on water use in relation to yield in the irrigation area. In the 1971 dry season we studied the effects of different irrigation intervals and rates on grain yields and on water-use efficiency. As with most irrigation experiments, caution should be used in extrapolating this information to other locations. Both soil and climatic factors strongly influence the results.

Five varieties and selections were irrigated at four different irrigation intervals using four irrigation rates within each interval. The varieties and selection used were IR5, IR20, C4-63,

Table 25. Effect of time of surface drainage on the grain yield and yield components of C4-63G grown in large pots (LP) containing 10 kg of soil and small pots (SP) containing 6 kg of soil in the greenhouse.

Time of drainage (days after heading)	100-grain wt (g)		Panicles (no./pot)		Filled grains (no./panicle)		Yield (g/pot)	
	LP	SP	LP	SP	LP	SP	LP	SP
0	0	0	9	13	0	—	0	0
3	0	1.5	14	7	33	39	1.8	1.5
6	0	1.3	12	12	0	68	0.8	2.2
9	1.7	1.7	23	14	121	77	14.8	6.5
11	1.9	3.0	21	16	155	153	12.5	16.2
13	2.2	2.1	23	14	186	214	22.2	12.5
15	2.4	2.1	22	14	178	190	35.2	10.5
18	2.8	2.0	23	14	246	110	48.0	15.0
21	2.6	2.1	22	15	218	170	49.0	24.2

IR127-80-1, and IR480-5-9. Metal sheets were installed in the levees between the different irrigation treatments to minimize lateral seepage. To further insure against the effects of lateral water movement, the experiment used a split-split plot design with irrigation interval as the main plot, irrigation rate as the subplot, and variety as the sub-subplot. Two replications were used. Ammonium sulfate was incorporated at 75 kg/ha N at transplanting and 25 kg/ha N was topdressed both at maximum tillering and at panicle initiation.

The average grain yields for the five varieties appeared to be independent of irrigation rate within each irrigation interval (fig. 6). For all the irrigation intervals tested, water-use efficiency increased as the irrigation rate was reduced (fig. 6). Since less seepage and deep percolation losses occur when smaller amounts of irrigation water are applied, the improvement in water-use efficiency is a result of reduced water loss and not of increased grain production. Figure 6 also shows that the maximum water-use efficiency was reached at the 4-day irrigation interval, even though equivalent grain yields were obtained at 4-, 6-, and 8-day intervals.

We conclude that frequent light irrigations are better than less frequent but heavier irrigations when the major objective is to maximize water-use efficiency. But when planning the operation of a total irrigation system, other factors such as canal capacities, system distribution efficiencies, and labor requirements must also be considered.

Figure 7 shows that grain yield was relatively insensitive to irrigation interval except at the

10-day interval where a marked decrease in grain yield occurred. Extensive soil drying and cracking was encountered only with the 10-day interval.

Effects on salt movement. In 1970, we showed that under continually flooded conditions salt

6. Effects of irrigation rates on the grain yield and average water-use efficiency of five lowland rice varieties. IRRI, 1971 dry season.

7. Effect of irrigation intervals on grain yield of lowland rice. Each value is the mean of five varieties, four irrigation rates, and two replications. IRRI, 1971 dry season.

was leached more efficiently in uncropped plots than in cropped plots. In fact, the salt concentration tended to increase in the root zone of the planted, flooded fields during periods of vigorous plant growth because of increased water use and the effects of root extraction on soil water movement. On the other hand, under alternately wet and dry soil conditions, salt leaching may be more effective in the presence of a rice crop because the water is extracted below the soil surface and applications of irrigation water should tend to leach the salt to deeper soil depths. Without a crop, salt is carried to the soil surface and deposited there by evaporation. In this case, irrigation water may not leach the salt so effectively.

8. The salt distribution on the rotationally irrigated plots. IRRI, 1971 dry season.

Table 26. Effect of irrigation interval on salt removal (600 kg/ha CaCl_2 added to all plots) as indicated by performance of IR20. IRRI, 1971 dry season.

Irrigation treatment	Dry matter production (g/hill)	Plant ht ^a (cm)	LAI	Yield (t/ha)
Continuous flooding	37	90	4.7	6.98
2 cm every 4 days	35	84	3.9	5.44
3 cm every 6 days	34	79	3.6	5.42
4 cm every 8 days	30	71	2.5	5.36
5 cm every 10 days	31	79	2.5	4.05

^aAt harvest.

We studied the effects of irrigation intervals on the salt movement in soil. Different amounts of water were applied to each of 16 plots at 4-, 6-, 8-, or 10-day intervals so that the average rate in all plots was 5 cm/day. Continually flooded treatments were also included. Calcium chloride was incorporated at 600 kg/ha in the top 15 cm of soil 1 day before transplanting.

The salt concentration in the surface 15 cm of soil in the flooded plots with crop was 355 ppm 2 weeks before harvest while that in the noncropped, flooded plots was 251 ppm. These data support our earlier observation of more efficient leaching under noncropped conditions. The salt concentration in rotationally irrigated plots 1 week before harvest tended to be higher at all sampling depths in the cropped plots probably because of higher evapotranspiration losses from these plots (fig. 8). Also, the salt concentration is higher in the surface 15 cm of the noncropped plots than it is at 15 to 25 cm. The opposite is true with the cropped plots. That clearly illustrates the effect of water absorption by roots on salt movement in the soil.

Table 26 shows the effects of irrigation interval on plant performance and yield of IR20 as affected by salt incorporation. Vegetative growth and grain yield decreased as the interval between irrigation increased although all plots received the same total amount of irrigation water. Thus both irrigation amount and irrigation frequency are important in determining grain yield.

Upland-lowland comparison

Furrow-irrigated nonflooded rice. A desirable alternative to soil puddling for rice cultivation may be the practice of furrow irrigation in

nonpuddled soil. Maintaining the soil in non-flooded condition allows rice to fit into rotations with other crops.

Previous experiments (1969 Annual Report) showed that more than one-third of the water used in evapotranspiration is lost by evaporation from the surface of standing water in a rice field. Evaporation in a furrow-irrigated rice field would be retarded by the mulching effect of the dry soil. Moreover, deep percolation losses could be minimized. Thus, the practice of furrow irrigation might provide an additional benefit by lowering the water requirement of rice.

We grew IR20 in two adjoining 25 x 50 m plots with and without flooding. The three nonflooded replications were separated by the two secondary canals connected to a primary canal at one side of the field. The canals were lined with polyethylene film to minimize lateral seepage and thus permit a more uniform distribution of water. The water applied to the field was measured with a Parshall flume which had a 15-cm throat. The water was admitted to the furrows from the secondary canals.

Five centimeters of water were maintained in the lowland field. Water application was measured using the stilling well and hook gauge techniques.

In the simulated upland field IR20 was seeded at a row spacing of 25 cm. Thus, there were two rows between the irrigation furrows which were 50 cm apart. The nursery bed for the lowland planting was established at the time of seeding so that the simulated upland crop and the lowland crop would mature at approximately the same time. The seedlings were transplanted in the lowland field at a spacing of 25 x 25 cm.

Tensiometers were installed in the upland field 10, 20, and 30 cm deep and irrigation

water was applied when the soil moisture tension reached 33 centibars.

IR20 yielded 7.9 t/ha under puddled conditions and only 3.7 t/ha under nonflooded conditions despite much higher panicle production (Table 27). The remarkable decrease in yield in the upland crop resulted from a significantly lower panicle and 100-grain weight. Moreover, the ratio of grain to straw was much higher in the lowland than in the upland crop.

The water use in the upland field was only 50 percent of that in the lowland field despite the much longer field duration in the former (Table 28). But the water-use efficiency in the lowland crop (9.0 kg grain mm⁻¹ water ha⁻¹) was slightly higher than that in the upland crop (8.3 kg grain mm⁻¹ water ha⁻¹).

Thus furrow irrigation of upland rice did not produce more efficient water use. On the other hand, the use of different varieties, a more intensive irrigation schedule or a modified planting method might give different results.

Upland variety trial. In another experiment the performance and yield of 14 varieties were compared under upland and lowland conditions in the 1971 wet season in Central Luzon. The soil, unlike most lowland rice soils, was quite sandy (sand, 61%; silt, 21%; clay, 18%). It is so well-drained that it can be rotovated 1 day after a heavy rain. For soil moisture conditions between saturation and 1 bar tension, the water conductivity of lighter soils is generally higher than that of soils with a high clay content. Thus, sandier soils transmit more water through the soil to plant roots at the same pressure gradient. These soils should then cause less crop moisture stress when light showers are frequent or if the water table is shallow.

Table 28. Water use and growth duration of IR20 grown under puddled, continually flooded conditions and nonpuddled, furrow-irrigated conditions. IRRI, 1971 dry season.

Soil	Field duration (days)	Water use (mm)			
		Irrigation ^a	Land preparation ^b	Rainfall ^c	Total
Puddled	96	692	190	—	882
Nonpuddled	131	201	0	240	441

^aLowland value includes rainfall. ^bEstimated. ^cTotal rainfall for this period was 316 mm of which 75% was assumed to be effective.

Table 27. Grain yield and yield components of IR20 grown under puddled, continually flooded conditions and under nonpuddled, furrow-irrigated conditions. IRRI, 1971 dry season.

Soil	Panicles (no./sqm)	Panicle wt (g)	100-grain wt (g)	Unfilled grains (%)	Grain: straw ratio	Yield (t/ha)
Puddled	119	2.73	2.26	12.8	1.41	7.9
Nonpuddled	154	1.14	2.00	19.2	0.67	3.7

9. Relationship between tiller number and grain yield for different rice varieties and selections planted under upland and lowland conditions. Pangasinan, Philippines. 1971 wet season.

11. Effect of seedling number and nitrogen level on the grain yield of a high tillering variety, IR20, and a low tillering selection, IR127-80-1. IRRI, 1971 wet season.

10. Soil moisture tension at 15 cm soil depth as a function of time at different levels of supplemental irrigation in plots of IR747B2-6-3 and IR1561-69-6. IRRI, 1971 dry season.

Grain yields varied from 3 to almost 7 t/ha under lowland cultivation (Table 29). The yields were much less variable under upland conditions, ranging generally between 3.0 and 3.8 t/ha. Severe blast in the IR22 and C4-63G upland plots reduced the yield of these varieties. Most varieties produced 40 to 50 percent less in the upland field than under lowland conditions. The yield reduction with the upland varieties M1-48, Palawan, and OS4 was not so large because they lodged under lowland conditions. Thus this experiment does not clearly indicate if these varieties are in fact better adapted to upland conditions.

The relationship between tiller production and grain yield for the varieties that were not seriously affected by lodging or blast is shown in figure 9. Under lowland conditions, grain yield varied widely while tiller production was less variable. Grain yields probably were deter-

Table 29. Grain yield of rice varieties and selections grown under upland and continually flooded conditions. Pangasinan, Philippines, 1971 wet season.

Variety or selection	Growth duration ^a (days)	Yield ^b (t/ha)		Upland:lowland ratio
		Lowland	Upland	
IR661-1-140	129	6.80	3.72	0.55
IR841-67-1	129	6.79	3.60	0.53
IR24	129	6.12	3.31	0.54
IR8	129	5.48	3.18	0.58
IR22	115	5.07	2.26	0.44
IR5	129	4.72	3.07	0.65
IR127-80-1	115	4.68	2.10	0.45
C4-63G	129	4.61	1.67	0.36
IR20	124	4.37	3.78	0.86
IR480-5-9	124	4.24	2.73	0.64
M1-48	114	3.86	3.24	0.84
Palawan	123	3.70	2.57	0.70
OS4	114	3.26	3.35	1.03
IR747B2-6-3	96	3.01	3.40	1.13

^aAverage for the lowland and upland harvests. ^b50 kg/ha N was applied at land preparation and 50 kg/ha at panicle initiation in both the lowland and upland field.

mined by some other plant response such as 100-grain weight or grain number per panicle. For the upland trial, however, the tiller number varied between relatively wide limits with little effect on yield suggesting that the upland yield was limited by some external factor such as moisture or nutrient availability, or both. Less than 300 tillers/sq m were sufficient to remove the dependence of grain yield on tiller production for both methods of cultivation.

Supplemental irrigation of upland rice

Two experiments were conducted to study the effect of small amounts of supplemental irrigation on the yield of upland rice. Irrigation water was applied in low, medium, or heavy amounts whenever the soil moisture tension at 5 cm depth reached field capacity. All the nitrogen was broadcast at seedling emergence. Two short-duration selections were used. IR747B2-6 produced a good crop. IR1561-69-6 developed bacterial leaf streak, tungro, and grassy stunt and did not perform well in this trial.

A large yield response (Table 30) was obtained with 75 kg/ha N and with all amounts of supplemental irrigation even though extensive soil drying was not allowed in any of the treat-

Table 30. Effect of nitrogen and supplemental irrigation on the grain yield of the early maturing selections grown under upland conditions. IRRI, 1971 wet season.

Supplemental irrigation water applied (mm)	Yield (t/ha)		
	0 kg/ha N	75 kg/ha N	150 kg/ha N
<i>IR747B2-6-3^a</i>			
100	1.4	3.0	3.2
130	1.9	3.5	3.8
170	2.2	4.4	4.6
<i>IR1561-69-6^b</i>			
120	0.7	1.3	1.6
160	0.8	1.4	1.8
200	1.1	1.9	2.2

^aSown on May 1, and harvested after 100 days. ^bSown on Aug. 18, and harvested after 108 days.

ments (fig. 10). In the IR747B2-6-3 crop an increase in grain production of 11 kg/mm H₂O was obtained without added nitrogen and 20 kg/mm H₂O at 150 kg/ha N. This increase suggests an improvement in water-use efficiency at higher fertility levels. Also, under farm conditions, in the dry season, 5 t/ha is often obtained with 1,000 mm of water or an efficiency of 5 kg/mm H₂O. In this experiment a much better return per unit of irrigation water was obtained at a time of the year when water is generally more readily available.

Seedling number and grain yield

An experiment was conducted to study the effects of seedling number on grain yield. A high tillering variety, IR20, and a lower tillering selection, IR127-80-1, were used to study the interaction between tillering capacity, nitrogen, seedling rate, and yield. Regular 21-day-old seedlings were used in this wet season experiment. Neither variety showed a response to increased seedling number with no added nitrogen (fig. 11). But, as the nitrogen rate was increased, the yield of IR127-80-1 increased from 2.5 to 4.0 t/ha when the number of seedlings per hill was increased from one to six at 100 kg/ha N. Also, the yields of the two varieties were equivalent only at the higher nitrogen level. That suggests that high nitrogen rate is necessary to obtain a yield response of low tillering varieties to increased seedling rates.

Varietal improvement

Breeding materials were evaluated in the pedigree nurseries, observational yield trials, replicated yield trials, seed purification blocks, and seed-increase plots. Many new crosses were made and F₂ and F₃ bulk populations from several cross combinations were grown. Emphasis in the breeding program continues to be on production of high yielding, improved plant type lines with varying grain shapes and sizes, differing in amylose and gelatinization temperature, and with high levels of resistance to diseases and insects. Many promising lines having several desirable traits which have not been reported earlier were identified. Line IR661-1-140 was named a variety.

Comparisons of upland and lowland varieties grown under both upland and lowland culture suggest that upland varieties should be bred for early vegetative vigor and moderately long and droopy leaves, vigorous root system, high tillering ability, a high harvest index, and resistance to insects and diseases.

Genetic studies were continued on the component characters of plant type, allelic relationships of semidwarfs, photoperiod sensitivity, resistance to insects, and male sterility. Two lines were identified with dwarfing loci non-allelic to that of IR8. "Weakly sensitive" photoperiod response was determined to be under multigenic control. Genes for resistance to brown planthopper in the varieties MGL 2 and PTB 18 were determined to be *Bph 1* and *bph 2*, respectively. Brown planthopper biotype 2 rendered the variety Mudgo (*Bph 1* gene) susceptible. The cytological investigation of sterility in F₂ hybrids was continued and new studies were initiated relating to protein content and the feasibility of intercrossing F₁ hybrids. The cytoplasmic male sterility of Taichung Native 1, which is restored by most indicas but can be maintained by Pankhari 203, was confirmed. The heritability of floral characters affecting outcrossing was estimated. Preliminary tests of gametocides to induce male sterility indicated that Ethrel would not be a useful chemical sterilant for rice.

Breeding program

New varieties. A new variety, IR24, was named by IRRI in May. This is the fifth variety to be named. IR24 was the experimental line IR661-1-140-3. It originated from a cross of IR8 and IR127-2-2 made in 1966. IR127-2-2 was a line selection from the cross CP 231-SLO 17 x Sigadis. CP 231-SLO 17, a breeding line from U.S.A., has long, slender, and translucent grains with low amylose. Sigadis, a variety from Indonesia, is resistant to the green leafhopper, tungro virus, and bacterial leaf blight. As an F₄ row, IR661-1-140-3 was bulk harvested and planted in an observational yield trial plot in June 1968. It was included in the replicated yield trials and seed increase program in January 1969. In cooperative trials in the Philippines and several other countries, it consistently outyielded other IRRI varieties and experimental selections. The original selection was quite heterogenous with respect to grain size and date of maturity. In addition, some plants had purple leaf sheaths while others had green leaf sheaths. The seed was purified during 1970 and a line with a green base and medium-long, translucent grains was selected for large-scale multiplication.

IR24 has vigorous seedlings with erect leaves and a high tillering capacity. It is similar to IR8 in plant height and lodging resistance, but it matures a few days earlier than IR8. It is insensitive to photoperiod.

IR24 is moderately resistant to blast and tungro virus and is resistant to green leafhopper. It is susceptible to bacterial leaf blight and grassy stunt, however. The variety has low amylose content and the grain is moist and soft when cooked and is finding favor with Filipino consumers. IR24 has moderate grain dormancy, similar to that of IR8 and IR22.

Several IRRI selections have recently been named varieties by various agencies. Some were from selections within an IRRI line, while others were the original line itself (Table 1).

Breeder seed. Breeder seed of IR20 and IR24 was produced during the dry and wet seasons. Only lines of IR20 that are resistant to green leafhopper were used for producing breeder seed. Approximately one-fourth hectare is plant-

ed to progeny rows of each variety in a season. We maintain enough breeder seed of all the IRRI varieties to meet requests for breeder seed from the Philippines and other countries.

Seed purification. A total of 115 lines from replicated and observational yield trials were grown in seed purification plots. The purpose of carrying a large number of entries in seed purification plots is to provide seed for yield trials conducted by other departments and for wide-scale on-farm testing in the Philippines and elsewhere. Usually 40 to 50 plant selections from each line are grown; each selection is planted in a four-row plot 5 meters long.

The wet season plots were severely infected with tungro and grassy stunt viruses. The tungro infection, followed by late infection of grassy stunt, was so severe that essentially no seed was produced on susceptible lines.

Three IR841 lines and an IR1110 and an IR1112 line were segregating for reaction to tungro. The susceptible lines produced essentially no grain while adjacent resistant lines showed no apparent injury from the virus. This indicates that the type of tungro resistance involved may be simply inherited. IR665-8-3 showed little damage that could be attributed to the tungro virus. IR833-6-2, had good resistance to tungro virus. It is an early maturing line and has waxy endosperm. It has definite possibilities as a commercial variety.

Replicated yield trials. Since 1964 approximately 1,000 IRRI breeding lines have been evaluated in replicated yield trials. Lines are often discarded after a single test due to undesirable characteristics. About 200 entries are grown in both the dry and wet seasons.

Many lines this year produced yields comparable to those of IR8 (Table 2). The five IRRI varieties and several varieties and lines developed by other agencies were included in these trials. In addition to high yield potential most of the lines have an attractive grain appearance free from white belly. Their grain starch has low, intermediate, or high gelatinization temperature and low, intermediate, or high amylose contents. Grain appearance has been a major breeding objective and the grain characteristics of new lines reflect the success

Table 1. Varieties recently named outside the Philippines from IRRI lines.

Name	IRRI line	Parents	Country where line was named
Cica 4	IR930-31	IR8 x IR12-178	Colombia
Naylamp	IR930-2-6	IR8 x IR12-178	Peru
CS-1	IR262-7-1	Peta/3 x TN1	Ivory Coast
CS-3	IR253-16-1	Gam Pai 15/2 x Taichung Native 1	Ivory Coast
Nilo 11	IR579-48-1	IR8 x Tadukan	El Salvador
Palman 579	IR579-48-1	IR8 x Tadukan	India
Tongil	IR667-98	IR8 x (Yukara x TN1)	Korea

of this program. IR833-6-2, and IR789-98-2 have waxy endosperm and four of the IR841 lines are aromatic.

Most of the lines shown in Table 2 have semidwarf stature conditioned by the dwarfing gene of Taiwan semidwarfs. Exceptions are IR5, IR5-81-3, and C4-63. The height of the semidwarf lines varied from 73 to 106 cm in the dry season and from 91 to 125 cm in the wet season. The taller, more vigorous types which approach IR5 and C4-63 in height are preferred by farmers who use modest levels of nitrogen fertilizer.

The rather high lodging percentage of some lines in the wet season was caused by typhoons which occurred as the lines neared maturity. The low yields of IR8 and many other lines during the wet season were caused by heavy infection of grassy stunt.

The only line showing consistently high protein content was IR480-5-9.

Satisfactory levels of grain dormancy were present in most lines. The main defect of the new lines shown in Table 2 is lack of high levels of resistance to important diseases and insects. Most lines are as resistant to diseases and insects as traditional varieties but under the intense management practices followed with the high yielding varieties, the likelihood of disease and insect attacks is very high. Therefore, high levels of resistance to diseases and insects are being incorporated into new lines.

Cooperative varietal testing. In the dry season a cooperative varietal trial with promising selections from IRRI and the Bureau of Plant Industry was grown at Maligaya Rice Research and Training Center, Muñoz, Nueva Ecija, and at the Rice and Corn Experiment Station, Pili, Camarines Sur. There were 40 entries from

IRRI including all the named varieties and 10 entries from BPI. IR1330-196-2, an insect-resistant line, was the highest yielding entry at Pili, and IR841-67-1 yielded highest at Muñoz (Table 3). The yields at Pili were low because of tungro infection. At Maligaya no serious disease problem was encountered.

Pedigree nurseries. Pedigree nurseries were planted in December 1970 and January, May, and July 1971. Over 30,000 pedigree rows were grown of which 1,570 were planted to parental check varieties. The selections grown were in the F₃ to F₇ generations. Some of the important crosses are listed in Table 4. All the lines grown have improved plant type and clear, translucent grains of varying sizes and shapes.

Lines of IR1060 (Wagwag/3 x IR8) are highly sensitive to photoperiod and should prove to be useful parents as sources of this trait in new crosses. Photoperiod-sensitive varieties are needed for parts of Vietnam, Thailand, Burma, and Bangla Desh where the rice crop can be harvested only after the heavy rains have stopped. Photoperiod-sensitive varieties mature in November and December irrespective of the date of planting.

Selections of IR1357 are resistant to bacterial leaf blight and bacterial leaf streak. Many lines of IR1125 have aromatic, long, slender, and translucent grains and several have low amylose. Lines of IR1480 combine resistance to blast and bacterial leaf blight with moderate resistance to tungro and the green leafhopper. The lines of IR1487 are resistant to bacterial leaf blight and streak and are moderately resistant to tungro and green leafhoppers. Many lines of IR1614 are resistant to bacterial leaf blight, brown planthoppers, and green leafhoppers, and have excellent, long, slender grains. Resistance to

Table 2. Agronomic, disease, insect, and quality data on selected varieties and lines grown in replicated yield trials. IRRI, 1971 dry (D) and wet (W) seasons.

Variety or selection	Parents	Grain yield (t/ha)		Maturity ^a (days)		Plant ht (cm)		Panicles (no./plant)
		D	W	D	W	D	W	
		TN1		6.90	4.90	123	113	
Peta		6.83	1.42	141	145	165	164	12
Mehran 69		5.65	4.04	128	119	95	113	21
Padma		6.04	3.54	110	97	93	105	16
C4-63 (G)	Peta x BPI-76	6.56	3.63	135	131	130	124	11
IR5-81-3	Peta x T. Rotan	6.50	3.74	130	131	112	132	12
IR5	Peta x T. Rotan	6.90	3.27	140	131	117	128	12
IR8	Peta x Dee-geo-woo-gen	6.98	3.82	136	124	84	99	13
IR20	(Peta/3 x TN1) x TKM-6	6.66	4.31	127	124	98	144	13
IR22	IR8 x Tadukan	5.94	4.96	114	124	81	107	14
IR24	IR8 x IR127-2-2	—	5.00	—	119	—	96	13
RD-1		5.50	3.81	135	124	106	125	12
BPI 121-407		5.78	3.05	137	124	102	101	12
IR480-5-9	Nahng Mon S-4/2 x TN1	5.46	4.55	120	106	81	102	11
IR533-1-89-2	[(CP231 x SLO-17/2) x Sigadis] x IR262-24-3	7.36	4.00	135	124	97	108	13
IR665-58-2	IR8 x (Peta/5 x Belle Patna)	7.22	3.95	133	124	103	100	12
IR759-54-2	IR8 x Tadukan	5.13	3.30	123	123	84	110	12
IR759-133-1	IR8 x Tadukan	6.25	4.31	137	124	77	99	13
IR789-98-2	IR8 x Muey Nahng 62M	5.73	5.45	118	117	91	110	12
IR828-28-1	IR8/2 x Basmati 370	6.32	3.38	143	131	88	110	14
IR833-6-2	IR262-43-8 x Gam Pai 15	6.87	4.81	113	104	82	98	13
IR841-5-3	IR262-43-8 x Khao Dawk Mali 4-2-105	—	5.25	—	111	—	112	13
IR841-28-1	IR262-43-8 x Khao Dawk Mali 4-2-105	7.29	5.10	127	119	78	106	13
IR841-67-1-1	IR262-43-8 x Khao Dawk Mali 4-2-105	6.62	5.30	119	119	78	109	11
IR841-67-1-2	IR262-43-8 x Khao Dawk Mali 4-2-105	8.42	4.68	135	119	84	104	13
IR841-85-1	IR262-43-8 x Khao Dawk Mali 4-2-105	6.34	4.91	138	124	92	104	14
IR879-24-1	IR8/2 x (Peta/3 x Dawn)	6.03	4.74	130	124	88	109	12
IR878B4-220-3	IR8/2 x [(CP231 x SLO-17) x Nahng Mon S-4]	6.12	3.48	141	131	101	100	13
IR879-183-2	IR8/2 x (Peta/3 x Dawn)	6.20	4.13	132	121	87	103	12
IR881-5-3	IR8/3 x Wagwag	6.66	4.76	134	123	90	109	12
IR944-102-2-3	(TN1 x Malagkit Sungsong) x IR8	6.63	5.12	133	119	83	99	12
IR1006-20-5	IR8 x BPI-76	6.92	5.00	131	119	86	104	12
IR1093-49-1	IR8 x Intan	7.60	4.37	140	126	95	108	15
IR1093-104-2	IR8 x Intan	7.36	4.90	141	131	82	103	16
IR1093-148-3	IR8 x Intan	7.12	4.46	137	117	97	119	12
IR1100-37-2	IR262-43-8-11/2 x Leuang Prathan 54-7-28	6.71	4.83	123	111	83	107	13
IR1111-46-2	IR262-43-8-11/2 x Khao Med Lek 4-16-136	6.35	4.23	123	135	74	105	13
IR1154-223-2	IR8/2 x Zenith	5.50	4.41	137	119	92	108	12
IR1163-124-3	IR8/2 x BPI-76	6.01	4.79	125	117	73	91	11
IR1163-135-2	IR8/2 x BPI-76	5.95	4.47	128	119	94	116	12
IR1163-153-2	IR8/2 x BPI-76	6.37	5.02	130	117	75	94	12
IR1168-58-2	IR8/2 x IR154-61-1	7.01	5.60	138	123	84	112	20
IR1201-40-3	IR11-288-3 x Intan	7.37	4.36	134	145	90	108	12

^aSeeding to harvest. ^bS = susceptible, R = resistant, R/S = segregating, M = moderately. ^cBacterial leaf blight. ^dGelatinization temperature. H = high, I = intermediate, L = low.

tungro, brown planthopper, green leafhopper, stem borers, and gall midge has been combined in IR1702. Nahng Tay C, a floating variety from Vietnam, was crossed with IR22 (IR1708) and F₄ dwarf lines have been sent to Vietnam for evaluation under local conditions. Lines of IR1364 combine resistance to tungro virus and

the green leafhopper. One line of this cross is highly resistant to tungro and has been used in new crosses as a source of resistance. Many selections from IR1416 have a high level of resistance to blast and have clear, translucent grains. Lines of IR1330 have resistance to tungro virus, green leafhopper, brown plant-

Wet season lodging (%)	Reaction ^b to					Seed dormancy (%)	Brown rice protein (%)		Milled rice (%)		Gel. q temp ^r	Amylose (%)	Variety or selection
	Tungro (%)	Blight ^c	Blast	Brown plant- hopper	Green leaf- hopper		W D		Head	Total			
							Brown rice protein (%)						
							W D						
5	S	S	S	S	S	94	8.2	8.8	51	71	L	27	TN1
90	R	S	S	S	R	14	9.2	7.3	47	67	I	27	Peta
22	S	S	S	S	S	56	8.6	7.7	54	68	L	27	Mehran 69
57	S	S	S	S	S	82	10.2	8.8	60	70	I/L	27	Padma
70	MR	S	S	S	R	15	7.3	7.2	65	70	HI/I	25	C4-63 (G)
100	S	S	S	S	R	25	8.4	7.7	70	69	I	25	IR5-81-3
100	S	S	S	S	R	28	7.8	7.5	51	68	I	28	IR5
50	S	S	S	S	R	70	7.5	6.7	51	69	L	27	IR8
100	MR	R	R	S	R	33	8.7	7.5	56	69	I/L	26	IR20
10	S	R	S	S	S	54	8.1	8.0	61	69	L	28	IR22
—	MR	S	S	S	R	26	6.8	—	53	68	L	17	IR24
37	S	S	S	S	R	53	8.1	7.2	58	69	L	27	RD-1
27	S	S	S	S	R	65	7.5	8.0	58	69	L	25	BPI 121-407
—	MS	S	MR	S	S	30	9.5	9.5	55	67	L	23	IR480-5-9
60	S	MR	MR	S	S	76	7.8	7.7	61	68	H	18	IR533-1-89-2
—	S	S	S	S	R	16	8.1	7.5	61	69	I	27	IR665-58-2
12	S	S	R	S	R	27	8.5	8.9	57	67	I	27	IR759-54-2
—	S	S	R	S	R	30	8.0	8.0	61	69	L	28	IR759-133-1
5	—	S	S	S	S	37	8.5	8.4	61	67	L	waxy	IR789-98-2
62	S	S	S	S	R	78	10.4	6.9	56	66	L	28	IR828-28-1
12	R	S	MS	S	R	56	9.2	8.2	55	68	L	waxy	IR833-6-2
5	MR	S	R	S	R	49	8.2	—	57	68	H	15	IR841-5-3
100	—	S	MR	S	S	18	7.8	8.2	63	69	I	28	IR841-28-1
40	MR	S	MR	S	R	10	7.1	7.4	56	69	L	18	IR841-67-1-1
60	S	S	MR	S	S	22	6.8	7.7	59	68	L	18	IR841-67-1-2
—	MR	S	MR	S	R	13	8.2	9.0	63	68	L	16	IR841-85-1
20	S	S	R	S	R	8	8.0	8.0	64	60	L	28	IR879-24-1
—	S	S	MR	S	R	66	8.5	7.1	54	66	L	27	IR878B4-220-3
—	S	S	R	S	R	46	7.3	8.1	63	60	I/L	28	IR879-183-2
—	S	S	S	S	R	12	8.1	7.4	65	70	L	27	IR881-5-3
5	S	R	R	S	R	28	7.1	8.0	59	70	L	29	IR944-102-2-3
—	MS	S	MS	S	R	32	7.7	7.5	57	69	I/L	28	IR1006-20-5
45	MS	S	S	S	R	8	7.7	7.7	59	70	L	28	IR1093-49-1
42	MS	S	S	S	R	9	8.6	7.6	61	68	I	28	IR1093-104-2
20	MS	S	S	S	R	18	7.5	7.7	51	71	L	28	IR1093-148-3
—	S	S	S	S	R	38	—	8.2	61	62	L	—	IR1100-37-2
25	S	S	S	S	R/S	5	8.4	7.8	57	67	L	28	IR1111-46-2
5	MR	MS	MR	S	R	67	7.8	6.8	65	69	L	17	IR1154-223-2
—	MR	S	S	S	R	29	8.2	8.4	61	68	L	29	IR1163-124-3
68	MR	S	S	S	R/S	20	8.7	7.1	64	69	I/L	27	IR1163-135-2
—	MS	S	S	S	R	6	8.8	8.5	49	67	HI/I	27	IR1163-153-2
20	MS	S	R	S	R/S	59	7.2	6.5	62	70	L	26	IR1168-58-2
—	—	S	S	S	R	12	8.0	7.9	53	69	I/L	25	IR1201-40-3

hopper, and gall midge. The cross IR1537 was made to combine high photosynthetic efficiency with improved plant type. Several dwarf selections from this cross are available but they have not been evaluated for photosynthetic efficiency. Several lines from IR1541 have resistance to tungro, bacterial leaf blight, bacterial leaf

streak, green leafhoppers, brown planthoppers, and stem borers. IR1542 and IR1544 combine the blast resistance of Carreon and Tetep, respectively, with good grain quality and the green leafhopper resistance of IR24. Several lines of IR1545 are resistant to tungro, blast, bacterial leaf blight, bacterial leaf streak, and

Table 3. Yield data of some promising IRRI entries included in IRRI/BPI cooperative yield trials at two locations in the Philippines. 1971 dry season.

Selection/ variety	Parents	Yield (t/ha)	
		Nueva Ecija	Camarines Sur
IR8	Peta x Dee-geo-woo-gen	6.83	4.83
IR20	IR262-24 x TKM-6	5.80	5.13
IR22	IR8 x Tadukan	6.01	5.60
IR24	IR8 x (CP 231-SLO 17 x Sigadis)	7.81	5.25
IR579-48-1	IR8 x Tadukan	5.63	5.42
IR747B2-6	TKM-6/2 x TN1	5.99	5.15
IR841-67-1	IR262-43-8 x Khao Dawk Mali	8.01	5.62
IR790-28-1	IR400-5-12 {IR8 x [IR4-253-3 x (B589A4-18-1/2 x TN1)] }	7.81	4.99
IR1093-49-1	IR8 x Intan	6.87	5.55
IR1093-104-2	IR8 x Intan	7.19	5.37
IR881B2-25-2	IR8/3 x Wagwag	5.82	4.94
IR759-79-2	IR8 x (Peta/3 x Dawn)	6.14	4.41
IR1330-35-2	(Leuang Tawng x IR8) x EK 1263	5.79	5.39
IR1330-51-1	(Leuang Tawng x IR8) x EK 1263	6.87	5.70
IR1330-196-2	(Leuang Tawng x IR8) x EK 1263	6.23	5.72

Table 4. Some hybrid lines grown in pedigree nurseries. IRRI, 1971 wet season.

Cross No.	Parents	Generation
IR1060	Wagwag/3 x IR8	F ₆
IR1125	Khao Dawk Mali x IR262-43	F ₆
IR1330	(Leuang Tawng x IR8) x EK1263	F ₇
IR1357	IR8 x IR127-80-1	F ₇
IR1364	IR262-43 x HR 21	F ₇
IR1416	IR400-26 x Tetep	F ₈
IR1480	IR790-28 x IR825-28-4	F ₈
IR1487	IR127-80-1 x IR442-2-50	F ₈
IR1529	IR305-3-17 x IR24	F ₈
IR1537	T 141 x IR24	F ₈
IR1539	IR24 x (Mudgo x IR8)	F ₈
IR1541	IR24 x TKM 6	F ₈
IR1542	IR24 x Carreon	F ₈
IR1544	IR24 x Tetep	F ₈
IR1545	IR24 x DZ 192	F ₈
IR1561	IR579-48 x IR747B2-6	F ₈
IR1614	IR22 x (Mudgo x IR8)	F ₄
IR1619	IR790-28 x IR747B2-6	F ₄
IR1626	IR24 x IR22	F ₄
IR1628	IR24 x IR1154-243	F ₄
IR1632	IR24 x Co 13	F ₄
IR1642	IR127-80 x IR747B2-6	F ₄
IR1702	IR24 x PTB 18	F ₃
IR1707	IR22/2 x (Mudgo x IR8)	F ₃
IR1708	IR22 x Nahng Tay C	F ₃
IR1712	IR747B2-6 x IR665-40-6	F ₃

green leafhoppers. In addition, they have excellent, long, slender grains. Many lines of IR1529 are resistant to bacterial leaf blight, bacterial leaf streak, blast, and green leafhopper, and have moderate resistance to tungro. The lines of IR1539 are resistant to brown planthopper and green leafhopper, and have excellent, long, slender grains with clear texture. The resistance of IR747B2-6 to brown planthopper has been combined with resistance to blast, bacterial leaf blight, and bacterial leaf streak in IR1619. Many lines of IR1626 are resistant to bacterial leaf blight and green leafhopper and have clear, long, slender grains. The lines of IR1632 also combine resistance to brown planthopper and the green leafhopper. Several lines of IR1642 are early and are resistant to green leafhopper, brown planthopper, bacterial leaf blight, and bacterial leaf streak. All the IR1561 lines are early maturing, have excellent long, slender grains, and are resistant to brown planthoppers, blast, and bacterial leaf blight. Similarly, the lines of IR1712 are also of earlier maturity, have long, slender grains, are resistant to brown planthopper and green leafhopper, and may have some resistance to tungro virus. Resistance to green leafhopper and brown planthopper has also been combined in IR1628.

F₂ and bulk hybrid populations. F₂ and bulk hybrid populations were planted in January and May 1971. The January planting consisted of 22 F₂ populations from single crosses and 13 F₃ bulk hybrid populations. The May planting consisted of 24 single crosses and four top-cross F₂ combinations and six F₃ bulk hybrid populations.

The IR1813 and IR1814 crosses were made to combine blast resistance and tungro resistance. The parents involved in these crosses have excellent plant type and clear, translucent grains. In the IR1816 cross, resistance to blast and resistance to green leafhopper have been combined with desirable traits of IR1561 lines. Resistance to grassy stunt has been combined with resistance to blast in the IR1818 cross. The IR1819 and IR1820 crosses were made to combine brown planthopper resistance with tungro and with blast resistance, respectively. In the IR1823 cross, resistance to brown planthopper has been combined with tungro

resistance. Resistance to brown planthopper and grassy stunt have been combined in the IR1824 cross. Resistance to bacterial leaf blight and brown planthopper has been combined in the IR1829 cross. Crosses IR1830 and IR1833 were made to combine resistance to bacterial leaf blight and tungro and to blast and bacterial leaf blight, respectively.

New crosses. Several single, three-way, and four-way crosses as well as a few backcrosses were made during the year. All parental lines involved in these crosses have improved plant type and clear, translucent grains. Many of these crosses have combined resistance to several diseases and insects. The IR2034, IR2035, IR2039, IR2058, and IR2061 crosses combine resistance to tungro and grassy stunt as well as brown planthopper and green leafhopper. Resistance to two viruses and the vectors, as well as blast has been combined in the IR2035 cross. Resistance to blast, bacterial leaf blight, brown planthopper, green leafhopper, and grassy stunt is present in the IR2030 and IR2031 crosses. IR2048 and IR2054 carry resistance to bacterial leaf blight, blast, tungro, green leafhopper, and brown planthopper. Intermediate amylose lines should come out of IR2053 and IR2055. Early maturity has been combined with resistance to green leafhopper, brown planthopper, grassy stunt, and bacterial leaf blight in the IR2040, IR2042, IR2061, and IR2062 crosses. Gall-midge resistance should segregate in the IR2031, IR2039, IR2045, and IR2054 crosses along with other resistance traits.

Upland x lowland crosses. F_2 plants from crosses between semidwarf varieties (IR8 or IR22) and African upland varieties (Agbede, OS4, OS6, or E425) were planted under upland conditions in the dry season. Water supply was maintained at a low level so that differences in growth vigor of the shoot in terms of tiller number, leaf dimensions, and leaf color were distinct and could be used as an index of root development. Plants that were short and intermediate in height and that showed greater vigor than IR8 were selected. The other plants were also sampled at random to include a broad segment of the variability in the F_2 populations. Agronomic data were taken on many of the F_2 plants sampled.

During the wet season, F_3 lines were planted in the upland plots for observation and selection. Comparison of F_2 and F_3 records showed that the maturity and height varied appreciably in a number of lines, mainly because of the different daylengths prevailing during the two seasons. Tiller number and leaf color were fairly consistent from F_2 generation to F_3 . Individual plant selections were made at three dates to form different maturity groups. Observations on F_3 plants indicated that more vigorous progenies were found in crosses involving IR8 than in crosses involving IR22. Most of the selected F_3 plants showed better growth vigor than the semidwarf parent during the early portion of the growing season when rainfall was below normal.

To broaden the genetic base of the upland x lowland hybrids, three-way crosses involving F_1 hybrids of an upland x lowland combination and another promising upland or lowland parent were made. Three groups of crosses were obtained from (African upland x IR8) x IR5, (African upland x IR8) x Rikuto Norin 21, and (Rikuto Norin 21 x IR5) x IR841.

Seed samples from the African upland x IR8 crosses were sent to the International Institute of Tropical Agriculture for selection under local conditions.

Tungro. An outbreak of tungro in 1971 in the Philippines provided an excellent opportunity for screening breeding lines and varieties for resistance. A nursery consisting of 11 varieties and 481 selections from 36 IRRI crosses were grown at two locations in Camarines Sur, one location in Laguna, and one location in Nueva Ecija. These nurseries were managed to permit the maximum natural infection of the virus. No insecticide was used.

IR22 was used as a spreader variety. Two adjacent plots were planted to the test selections and the third plot was planted to the susceptible check. Thus each test selection was planted next to a susceptible check. Two 5-meter-long rows were planted to each plot.

The virus infection was uniformly good at all the locations. Each selection and variety showed a similar reaction at each of the four locations. The tungro symptoms were expressed as stunting, leaf yellowing, reduction in vigor, delayed

flowering, absence of panicle production, and high sterility. Some varieties showed little leaf yellowing, but the virus infection was expressed in stunting, delay in flowering, and a reduced number of grains per panicle. IR579-48-1 and IR20 expressed these symptoms.

IR5 showed severe stunting and leaf yellowing but later recovered somewhat and a few plants produced some panicles. Flowering took place 140 days after transplanting as compared with 110 days under normal conditions. IR854-184-1 also behaved in this manner. C4-63 showed slight

Table 5. Reaction to tungro and green leafhopper of breeding lines grown in tungro nursery.

Variety/selection	Parents	Entries tested (no.)	Reaction to tungro ^a			Reaction to the vector
			No. R	No. MR	No. S	
TN1		1			1	S
IR8	Peta x Dee-geo-woo-gen	1			1	R
IR5	Peta x Tangkai Rotan	1			1	R
IR20	IR262-26 x TKM-6	1		1		R
IR22	IR8 x Tadukan	1			1	S
IR24	IR8 x (CP-SLO x Sigadis)	1		1		R
C4-63 (G)	Peta x BPI	1		1		R
BPI 121-407	—	1			1	R
RD-1	Leuang Tawng x IR8	1			1	R
RD-3	Leuang Tawng x IR8	1			1	R
IR1006	IR8 x BPI-76	1			1	R
IR841	IR262-43-8 x Khao Dawk Mali	2			2	R
IR878	IR8/2 x (CP-SLO x Nahng Mon S-4)	1			2	R
IR1093	IR8 x Intan	2			2	R
IR751	IR8/2 x (Peta/5 x Belle Patna)	1			1	R
IR879	IR8/2 x (Peta/3 x Dawn)	1			1	R
IR1108	IR262-43-8/2 x Puang Nahk 16	1			1	R
IR1154	IR8/2 x Zenith	2		1	1	R
IR833	IR262-43-8 x Gam Pai	2	2			R
IR828	IR8/2 x Basmati 370	1			1	R
IR944	(TN1 x Malagkit Sungsong) x IR8	2			2	R
IR1008	IR8 x IR154-61-1	1			1	R
IR759	IR8 x (Peta/3 x Dawn)	1			1	R
IR1112	IR262-43-8/2 x Khao Dawk Mali	1		1		R
IR1110	IR262-43-8/2 x Leuang Pratahn	1		1		R
IR879	IR8/2 x (Peta/3 x Dawn)	1			1	R
IR756	IR8/3 x (B589A4-18/2 x TN1)	1			1	R
IR1201	IR11-288-3 x Intan	1			1	R
IR1168	IR8/2 x IR154-61-1	1		1		R
IR881	IR8/3 x Wagwag	1			1	R
IR1480	IR790-28-1 x IR825-28-4	29		8	21	R
IR1487	IR127-80 x IR442-2-50	44		19	25	R
IR1364	IR262-43-8 x HR 21	6	3	3		R
IR825	(IR8 x Pankhari 203) x (Peta/6 x TN1)	19		9	10	R
IR822	IR8/2 x Pankhari 203	4		1	3	R
IR854	(IR8 x Pankhari 203) x IR262-43-8	5		2	3	R
IR1366	(Sigadis/2 x TN1) x IR128-80	21			21	R
IR1330	Leuang Tawng x EK 1263	5	3	2		R
IR1537	T. 141 x IR24	14		1	13	R
IR1541	IR24 x TKM-6	4	2	1	1	R
IR1544	IR24 x Tetep	63			63	R
IR1529	IR305-3-17 x IR24	118		48	70	R
IR1539	IR24 x (Mudgo x IR8)	68		2	66	R
IR1561	IR579-48-1 x IR747B2-6-3	53			53	S
IB23	TN1/4 x ASD 7	1			1	R/S
IB6	TN1/4 x Pankhari 203	1			1	R/S
Pankhari 203	—	1	1			R
ASD 7	—	1			1	R

^aR = Resistant, MR = moderately resistant, S = susceptible.

leaf yellowing, reduction in panicle number, and slight delay in flowering. IR24 showed some leaf yellowing, stunting, and reduction in panicle number and in number of grains per panicle, but it flowered in the normal time, 90 days after sowing. Several selections of IR1529 showed leaf yellowing and slight stunting, but produced the normal number of panicles with good seed set.

The test entries were classified as susceptible, moderately resistant, and resistant on the basis of degree of stunting, leaf yellowing, delay in flowering and panicle production (Table 5). Pankhari, two selections from IR833, three related selections of IR1364, three related selections of IR1330, and two selections of IR1541 were highly resistant. These entries (Table 6) had normal vigor, showed no stunting or leaf yellowing, and flowered in the normal time. IR833-6-2 is an early maturing waxy line; it is being tested on large scale in agronomic trials. IR1541-102-6 is an early maturing line with medium long and translucent grains. IR1364-37-3 has good plant type and is of medium maturity. It has excellent early vegetative vigor.

Several selections from IR1480, IR1487, IR825, and IR1529 were classified as moderately resistant and some of them are listed in Table 6.

The test entries except those of IR1561 are resistant to the green leafhopper, the vector of the tungro virus. In most of the entries, green leafhopper resistance is conveyed by *Glh 3* (Peta gene). The level of resistance conveyed by this gene is not as high as that imparted by *Glh 1* (Pankhari gene) or *Glh 2* (ASD 7 gene). All lines of IR1480 and several lines of IR822, IR825, and IR854 were homozygous for *Glh 1*. The presence of vector resistance whether due to *Glh 1*, *Glh 2*, or *Glh 3* did not provide protection against virus infection. Apparently, the green leafhopper is able to feed on resistant plants for a while and inoculate the plant during this period.

Grassy stunt. Progenies from *Oryza nivara* backcrosses were screened for resistance to grassy stunt by planting in the off-seasons at the IRRI farm. F₃ lines from IR24/2 x *O. nivara* and IR24/3 x *O. nivara* as well as F₂ populations

from IR24/4 x *O. nivara* were planted in May. The natural infection of the grassy stunt virus was so severe that all the plants in the susceptible plots were infected. Plant selections were made from the homozygous resistant plots. Resistant plants were selected from IR24/4 x *O. nivara* F₂ plants. F₄ selections from IR24/2 x *O. nivara* and IR24/3 x *O. nivara* and F₃ selections from IR24/4 x *O. nivara* were planted in September. Natural infection of grassy stunt was again very high and permitted the selection of resistant individuals.

The grassy-stunt resistant lines are similar to IR24 in plant type and have long, slender, and translucent grains. Some have the low amylose content of IR24 while others have high amylose content. Most are resistant to green leafhopper. Selection pressure has been applied against the undesirable traits of *O. nivara*, such as long awns, grain shattering, and weak stems. Table 7 lists the traits of some lines that are resistant to grassy stunt. Some of these lines have been used as parents in new crosses to combine grassy-stunt resistance with other traits such as resistance to blast, bacterial leaf blight, tungro, and brown planthopper.

Insect resistance. During the year, nearly 15,000 varieties and breeding lines were tested for resistance to the green leafhopper and over

Table 6. Disease and insect resistant lines identified in the tungro nursery to be highly resistant or moderately resistant to tungro.

Selection	Reaction to ^a						
	Blast	Blight	Streak	Tungro	GS	BPH	GLH
IR1364-37-3	R	S	MR	R	S	S	R
IR1330-5-3	S	S	MR	R	S	R	R
IR1541-102-6	S	R	R	R	S	R	R
IR833-6-2	MR	S	S	R	S	S	R
IR833-34-1	—	S	S	R	S	S	R
IR1480-125-2	S	R	S	MR	S	S	R
IR1487-141-6	R	R	R	MR	S	S	R
IR1487-194-5	R	R	MR	MR	S	S	R
IR1487-306-3	S	R	R	MR	S	S	R
IR1529-53-2	MR	R	R	MR	S	S	R
IR1529-72-5	R	R	R	MR	S	S	R
IR1529-163-3	R	R	R	MR	S	S	R
IR1529-414-1	R	R	R	MR	S	S	R
IR1529-677-2	R	R	R	MR	S	S	R

^aBlight = Bacterial leaf blight, Streak = Bacterial leaf streak, GS = Grassy stunt, BPH = Brown planthopper, GLH = Green leafhopper.

Table 7. Some promising selections with resistance to grassy stunt.

Selection	Parents	Maturity	Reaction to GLH	Grains	Amylose content
IR1704-3-2	IR24/2 x <i>O. nivara</i>	Early	R	long, slender	High
IR1721-7-1	IR24/3 x <i>O. nivara</i>	Medium	R	long, slender	Low
IR1721-13-5	IR24/3 x <i>O. nivara</i>	Medium	R	long, slender	Intermediate
IR1737-19-7	IR24/4 x <i>O. nivara</i>	Early	R	long, slender	Low

Table 8. Data on agronomic traits, disease and insect resistance, and grain yield of early maturing selections. IRRI, 1971 wet season.

Selection	Parents	Days to maturity	Tillers (no.)	Resistance to						Yield (t/ha)
				Blast	Blight	Streak	Tungro	BPH	GLH	
IR579-48-1	IR8 x Tadukan	110	16	S	R	S	S	S	S	3.2
IR747B2-6-3	TKM6/2 x TN1	102	16	MR	MR	MR	S	R	S	4.0
IR833-6-2-1	IR262-43 x Gam Pai	106	12	R	S	S	R	S	R	3.6
IRATOM-24	IR8 mutant	107	12	S	S	S	S	S	R	3.7
IR1561-43-2	IR747B2-6 x IR579-48-1	107	15	MR	R	MS	S	R	S	4.7
IR1561-132-5	IR747B2-6 x IR579-48-1	106	19	MR	R	MS	S	R	S	4.7
IR1561-156-2	IR747B2-6 x IR579-48-1	107	17	MR	R	MS	S	R	S	4.6
IR1561-189-3	IR747B2-6 x IR579-48-1	108	16	MR	MR	MS	S	R	S	4.6
IR1561-228-3	IR747B2-6 x IR579-48-1	107	15	MR	R	MR	S	R	S	4.5
IR1561-243-5	IR747B2-6 x IR579-48-1	106	16	MR	R	MR	S	R	S	4.6
IR1561-250-2	IR747B2-6 x IR579-48-1	107	15	MR	R	MR	S	R	S	4.1

Table 9. Summary of mean rough and brown rice yields, protein content (at 12% moisture), milling and other data on IR8 and two high protein lines. IRRI, 1971 dry season.

Line	Yield			Protein (%)		Brown rice (%)	Total milled rice (%)	Head rice (%)
	Rough rice (kg/ha)	Brown rice (t/ha)	Brown rice protein (kg/ha)	Brown rice	Milled rice			
	<i>Replicated yield trial^a (120 kg/ha N)</i>							
IR8	7.0	5.5	408	7.4	7.0	78	68	50
IR160-27-3	6.6	5.1	430	8.5	7.8	77	68	45
IR480-5-9	6.0	4.6	402	9.1	8.4	76	66	51
	<i>Variety x fertilizer trial^b (60 kg/ha N)</i>							
IR8	7.3	4.7	410	7.2	6.7	78	68	48
IR160-27-3	6.9	5.2	409	7.8	7.6	76	69	36
IR480-5-9	6.3	4.8	413	8.7	8.4	75	67	45
	<i>Variety x fertilizer trial^b (120 kg/ha N)</i>							
IR8	7.1	5.5	475	8.6	8.0	78	68	41
IR160-27-3	7.1	5.4	554	10.2	9.9	77	68	39
IR480-5-9	7.5	5.7	602	10.6	10.3	76	67	51
	<i>Variety x spacing x fertilizer experiment^c (120 kg/ha N)</i>							
IR8	5.6	4.4	315	7.2	—	78	68	52
IR160-27-3	6.2	4.8	415	8.7	8.2	77	70	48
IR480-5-9	6.3	4.8	433	9.0	8.3	76	68	54
	<i>Observational field trial^a (80 kg/ha N)</i>							
IR8	5.1	3.9	213	6.2	5.4	77	67	48
IR160-27-3	4.9	3.7	289	7.9	6.9	75	67	39
IR480-5-9	4.7	3.6	282	8.0	7.5	75	64	42
	<i>Mean of five trials</i>							
IR8	6.4	5.0	358	7.3	6.8	78	68	48
IR160-27-3	6.2	4.8	412	8.6	8.1	77	68	41
IR480-5-9	6.1	4.6	416	9.0	8.6	76	66	48

^aFour replications. ^bThree replications. ^cAgromony department trial.

10,000 entries were screened for resistance to the brown planthopper. Since varieties that are resistant to green leafhoppers, such as Peta, Sigadis, and IR8, have been used extensively in our breeding program, most breeding lines are resistant to this insect. Most of the resistant lines have *Glh 3* (Peta gene) for resistance. A few crosses such as IR822, IR825, IR854, and IR1480 have *Glh1* (Pankhari gene). The Mudgo gene for resistance to brown planthoppers has been combined with *Glh 3* in several cross combinations such as IR1330, IR1539, IR1614, IR1619, IR1632, IR1642, IR1707, and IR1712. The ASD 7 gene (*bph 1*) for resistance to brown planthoppers has been combined with *Glh 3* in IR1628.

Earliness. Varieties with 100-day growth duration and high yield potential are widely needed. Early maturing varieties must also have good grain quality and disease and insect resistance. Several early maturing, improved plant type lines have been identified from the TKM-6 crosses and from IR8 x Tadukan.

IR747B2-6-3, from TKM6/2 x TN1, is resistant to brown planthopper and blast, matures in 100 days, and has good early vegetative vigor. IR579-48-1, from IR8 x Tadukan, matures in 110 days, has excellent long, slender grains, and is resistant to bacterial leaf blight. These two early maturing lines have given high yields in replicated yield trials at IRRI and at stations of the Philippines Bureau of Plant Industry. IR579-48-1 has been named a variety in El Salvador and in Punjab, India.

A cross between these two lines (IR1561) was made in 1969, the F₂ population was grown in January 1970, the F₃ and F₄ pedigree rows were grown in 1970, and the F₅ and F₇ pedigree rows were grown in 1971. The lines were evaluated for resistance to brown planthopper, blast, and bacterial leaf blight for three different generations. The F₆ lines were tested for tungro resistance by planting in the tungro nursery. Several IR1561 lines outyielded both the parents and are resistant to brown planthopper, blast, and bacterial leaf blight (Table 8). They have early vegetative vigor and have excellent long, slender grains. They are, however, susceptible to tungro and green leafhopper. These selections

obviously are unsuitable as varieties for the areas where tungro virus is a serious problem. Seeds of these selections have been sent to several countries where they are being tested for adaptability. Meanwhile, two selections of this cross have been used in the hybridization program to combine resistance to green leafhopper and tungro virus. Early selections will be made from segregating populations. Early maturing selections from other crosses, such as IR1480, IR1541, IR1619, IR1642, and IR1712, are also being evaluated for various traits.

Protein. It now appears that protein content of rice can be increased 20 to 25 percent without any reduction in grain yield. IR480-5-9 and IR160-27-3 appear to have genetically higher protein content than IR8. These lines yield essentially the same as IR8 but gave higher protein contents (Table 9). IR480-5-9 had 23 percent higher protein content than IR8, or about 16 percent more protein per hectare. IR480-5-9 has consistently given higher protein than other lines through 2 years of comparison. It is highly susceptible to bacterial leaf blight so it is not suitable as a commercial variety.

Several lines from the high protein crosses (IR1101 to IR1105) appear to be genetically high in protein content but none have produced yields comparable to those of IR8. IR1103-15 lines have shown consistently high protein content through all generations in pedigree rows and in yield trial plots in advanced generations. Protein content and other data of the better lines grown in pedigree rows through eight generations are shown in Table 10.

New crosses have been made which combine the high protein content of IR480-5-9 and high protein lines from the high protein crosses. The F₁ plants of some of the new crosses were top-crossed or backcrossed to varieties that have improved plant type to further combine high protein content with other desirable traits.

To reduce environmental variability all pedigree rows and yield trial plots which are to be evaluated for protein studies are transplanted at 20 x 20 cm spacing and all nitrogen fertilizer is applied basally. The closer plant spacing and early nitrogen applications result in lower protein content and reduced variability.

Table 10. Summary of protein content (brown rice at 12% moisture) and other data on high protein lines and IR8 grown in pedigree rows.

Line	Seeding to heading (days)	Protein content (%)			F ₃ rough rice yield (g/plant)	F ₃ fertility (%)
		F ₃ -F ₄	F ₃			
			Avg of two plants	Bulk sample		
IR8 ^a	104	8.5	7.5	7.5	46.2	89
			<i>IR8 x Chow-sung</i>			
IR1103-1-3	102	10.7	10.6	11.1	44.4	94
IR1103-2-3-1-3	100	11.0	10.7	10.7	49.1	88
IR1103-2-3-1-5	102	10.6	10.6	11.1	39.6	90
IR1103-15-8-4	109	11.6	11.4	11.3	32.1	84
IR1103-15-8-5	105	11.6	10.1	10.7	45.5	87
IR1103-52-2	103	10.9	9.5	9.2	32.5	89
IR1103-66-4	85	10.7	10.0	10.5	33.6	89
IR1103-68-6	104	11.0	9.9	10.3	36.6	85
			<i>IR8 x Crythroceros Korn</i>			
IR1104-107-2	107	9.9	8.6	7.6	52.1	89
			<i>IR8 x Rikuto Norin 20</i>			
IR1100-67-5	103	13.0	9.9	10.1	35.4	92
			<i>IR8 x Omirt 39</i>			
IR1101-14-3	85	9.8	7.7	8.3	44.7	83
IR1101-18-3	95	9.9	9.1	8.7	34.3	91
IR1101-29-3	79	12.7	9.2	10.5	35.1	80
IR1101-38-4	76	12.0	10.8	10.5	41.4	87
IR1101-44-3	70	12.8	11.9	11.4	37.8	87
IR1101-45-2	80	12.3	11.1	10.9	30.5	79

^aProtein values are average of plants from IR8 check rows grown in nursery each season.

Cold resistance. A pedigree nursery of 1,165 lines, made up of selections from IRRI and Korea, was evaluated in Bangla Desh for resistance to low temperatures. The nursery was seeded in November 1970 and examined for degree of leaf yellowing and vegetative plant height in February 1971. Much less leaf yellowing occurred than last year partly because temperatures this year were not as low.

At IRRI, over 2,850 lines and varieties were evaluated for resistance to cold as shown by seedling yellowing or discoloration. In soil-filled wood trays, about 30 seedlings of each line were grown in 10-cm rows. Three rows of a resistant and susceptible check variety (Reimei and IR8) were included in each tray. When the seedlings were 7 days old they were placed in cold water tanks for 7 to 10 days. The temperature of the water was 13 to 14 C. Lines were rated from 1 to 7 based on degree of yellowing. IR8 check seedlings were rated 5 to 6 and Reimei check seedlings were rated 2 (normal green). Some of the lines remained green while others turned yellow and brownish (6 and 7).

In previous tests, amylose content appeared to be associated with seedling color, but this year we found no significant correlation. Other characteristics found to be not associated with seedling color were resistance to green leafhopper, panicle exertion from the flagleaf, and plant type.

About 800 single cross F₃ lines of japonica x semidwarf indica crosses were grown in the Swat Valley, Pakistan. These lines were also tested in cold water tanks at IRRI, and grown in pedigree rows at IRRI during the wet season. Plant selections were made from 107 lines grown in Swat Valley that were early maturing and cold resistant and from 88 lines grown at IRRI. At IRRI lines were saved primarily on the basis of plant type. There were only 13 lines from which selections were saved at both locations.

World collection

A total of 1,832 new accessions were received during the year, increasing the world collection to 14,712 accessions. A notably large number

were sent by national agencies in Ceylon, Indonesia, Laos, and Malaysia. Most of the new accessions are indigenous varieties of unknown genetic potential.

During the year, we sent 2,300 packages of seed from the varietal collection to foreign researchers. Research departments at IRRI received 10,600 packages for various tests and chemical analyses.

Records of the characteristics of 1,750 accessions were completed in 1971, bringing the number of recorded varieties to 12,075.

We intensified our efforts to help national agencies conserve indigenous germ plasm resources. Our activities included participation in planning sessions, review of project proposals, preparation of training material for field collectors, and participation in field collection in Nepal.

For the second collection of wild forms and genetic testers, we received 45 mutants and five wild taxa during the year. A total of 325 seed packages were supplied to 10 requesting agencies in six countries.

To meet plant quarantine regulations we generally use Arasan powder and diazinon granules to treat seed samples to be sent abroad. A report was received from Pakistan that seed samples treated with Arasan and lindane did not germinate well. An experiment was set up to test the effect on seed samples of three varieties which were heavily dusted with Arasan, diazinon, Arasan and diazinon, lindane, or DDT, or treated with organo-mercurial dipping.

The varieties (IR8, IR127-80-1, and Peta) differed appreciably in their sensitivity to specific chemicals. Peta was the most sensitive. Organo-mercurial treatment allowed the fastest germination and the highest percentage of germination. All other chemicals applied in heavy doses delayed the germination process, compared with the untreated control. Lindane reduced the percentage of germinated seed in all three varieties, while DDT or Arasan plus diazinon produced lower germination counts on Peta only. When the excess chemical was shaken off the seed before planting, no adverse effect on germination was detected, however. Treated seeds should also be planted

in a large tray or pot rather than in very small containers.

Induced mutants

Through the cooperation of many national research institutions and the International Atomic Energy Agency, we obtained 53 induced mutants and some of the parents for planting in the wet season. Many of these mutants were reported by the originating stations to have promise in rice improvement in some aspect. The trial was designed to compare the mutants with their parents and with seven hybrid varieties in corresponding categories under uniform field conditions at Los Baños. Because some seed samples arrived late, plantings of 76 entries were made on eight dates.

The mutants from Japan and Korea were poorly adapted to the tropical environment and had low yields in the trial. Most of the mutants of tropical or subtropical origin did not express the reported superior feature or features, particularly in grain yield or in protein content (Table 11). Many mutants showed obvious agronomic weaknesses. The range of variability provided by the induced mutants did not appear to be greater than what can be found in a varietal collection or in segregating progenies of wide crosses.

Our yield and protein comparisons might be affected by the different seeding dates involved. Further testing at several sites appears necessary.

Comparison of lowland and upland varieties

The agronomic features and growth characteristics of upland varieties from West Africa, Japan, Philippines, and South America were compared with those of selected lowland types. Twenty varieties in the dry season and 22 in the wet season were grown under three cultural practices: upland, drill-flood, and transplant-flood. The upland treatment in the dry season received some surface irrigation to keep the plants from suffering extreme drought. To compare growth behavior under different cultural methods a plasticity index was com-

flood treatment, and a small reduction in leaf length and area. The lowland varieties showed a marked reduction in leaf length and area when grown in the upland treatment as shown by the plasticity indices (Table 12). The leaf below the flagleaf also showed marked reduction in length and in area for the lowland group grown in upland plots in the wet season. The reductions were much smaller in the dry season because water was supplied rather uniformly during this season.

The African, Philippine, and South American upland varieties had rather droopy leaves at 60 days after seeding. Their leaf angles (of openness) usually were double those of the semidwarfs in different plantings. The two Japanese upland varieties had leaf angles intermediate between the two groups. The differences in leaf angle decreased as the plants approached flowering.

The leaves of drought-resistant varieties tended to roll from 8 AM to 4 PM on hot, sunny days when soil moisture began to diminish. Leaf rolling in Peta began as early as 7:30 AM and continued until 5 PM. The rather short leaves of the semidwarfs rolled only when water stress became severe. Plasticity in leaf rolling appeared to be associated with resistance to water stress.

Although the upland varieties have more droopy leaves, the light transmission values at ground level in the upland planting of the dry season 60 days after seeding were only 20 percent below the values of the semidwarfs in both seasons. At full heading, the light intensity at ground level was 20 percent lower in the upland types than in the lowland types in the wet season and 40 percent lower in the dry season, mainly because most upland varieties have longer leaves and rather droopy flag leaves. The semidwarfs produced fairly good ground cover because of their high number of tillers and the large proportion of lower leaves which remained photosynthetic for a long time.

Growth duration. The ranges of the seeding-to-heading periods of the test varieties were narrow because the varieties were so chosen to facilitate comparison and field management. In the dry season upland planting, the 9 upland varieties headed within a period from 59 to 109 days after seeding, while most of the lowland

2. Leaf number of nine upland and 11 lowland varieties grown under upland and lowland culture (60 days after seeding).

types ranged from 64 to 114 days. IR5 and Peta were weakly photoperiod-sensitive and took about 130 days to head. The seeding-to-heading period was reduced by an average of 10 days in both variety groups when grown under the drill-flood treatment. IR5 showed the greatest reduction of 39 days when drilled and grown in flooded soil. The growth period was generally lengthened in the transplant-flood method by several days, especially in the early maturing varieties.

In the wet season upland planting, the upland varieties took from 65 days (for Rikuto Norin 21) to 98 days (for Palawan) to head and the lowland types took from 68 days (for Dular) to 111 days (for Peta). Slightly shorter periods were found in the drill flood treatment and IR5 again showed the largest reduction in growth period (7 days).

Plant height. Most of the African, Philippine, and South American upland varieties were

Table 12. Plasticity indices of leaf measurements of selected upland and lowland varieties for drill-flood/upland comparisons at 60 days after seeding.

Variety group	No. of varieties	Plasticity index		
		Length	Width	Area
<i>Dry season</i>				
Upland	4	1.32	1.00	1.36
Lowland	9	1.95	1.30	2.37
<i>Wet season</i>				
Upland	7	1.31	0.95	1.19
Lowland	4	1.79	0.94	1.74

3. Number and maximum length of roots of 14-day-old seedlings grown under upland culture.

taller than the semidwarfs, but they were not as tall as in the 1970 wet season possibly because of the more limited water supply in both seasons this year and also the rather late seeding in the wet season this year.

In drill-flood plots, the upland types averaged 115 cm while IR8 measured 85 cm. Peta was 150 cm.

Panicle number. The upland varieties produced fewer panicles (16 to 22) per 50 cm of row in the wet season upland planting than the lowland varieties (20 to 37). The ratios of panicles to tillers, however, were similar between the two groups, ranging from 45 to 65 percent.

In the wet season drill-flood planting, the panicle-to-tiller ratios varied greatly from one variety to another. Most varieties in each variety group produced about 25 panicles per 50 cm of row.

Early root development. Root samples were collected periodically up to 60 days after

seeding from varieties grown on both puddled soil and granulated upland soil. For young plants, the "upland" treatment consisted of planting on fine, granulated soil inside a mylar tube and watering from the bottom of the tube. Figure 3 shows root number and maximum root length of 14-day-old seedlings. At 30 days after seeding, the upland varieties had low root number, the same root length, and a high proportion of thick roots under both cultures (Table 13). On the other hand, the lowland varieties responded to flooding mainly with an increase in root number. Their root length decreased slightly or remained the same. The features of root samples taken from 60-day-old plants were similar to those from 30-day-old plants.

Shoot and root weight. Forty days after seeding, the two variety groups had similar dry root weights in both the upland and drill-flood plots. The lowland group produced heavier shoots, however. The root-to-shoot ratios were about 10 percent higher in the upland group under both cultures and the difference between groups was significant.

Sixty days after seeding, the upland group generally had lower shoot and root weights than the lowland group in both types of culture. In the upland planting, the upland group had a slightly higher root-to-shoot ratio, but the difference between variety groups was not significant. In the drill-flood plots, however, the lowland group showed a higher root-to-shoot ratio than the upland group. The ratios of most of the upland varieties ranged from 8 to 21 percent.

Root system of adult plants. In upland plantings in both seasons, the upland varieties and a

Table 13. Root features of five upland and seven lowland varieties at 30 days after seeding in two types of culture. IRRI, 1971 dry season.

Variety group	Root feature					
	Number		Length (cm)		Diameter	Rootlets
	Range	Mean	Range	Mean		
<i>Upland culture</i>						
Upland	6 to 12	9	8 to 21	10	Many thick	Along entire root
Lowland	12 to 19	14	6 to 22	9	Mostly thin	Along entire root
<i>Drill-flood culture</i>						
Upland	21 to 32	27	8 to 20	10	Mostly thin	Mostly from root tip
Lowland	30 to 55	40	6 to 19	8	Mostly thin	From midportion of root down

Table 14. Root development of selected upland and lowland varieties in 1971 dry season upland planting.

Variety	Predominant type ^a	Density ^b	Rootlets ^c	Length (cm)		Diameter (mm)	
				Mode	Max.	Avg.	Thickest
<i>Upland varieties</i>							
M1-48	4 to 5	3 to 4	3 to 4	16	24	1.25	1.55
OS4	5 to 6	2 to 3	2 to 3	17	26	1.45	1.75
OS6	5 to 6	3 to 5	3 to 4	15	24	1.65	2.00
Rikuto Norin 21	4 to 5	4	3 to 4	22	34	1.30	1.50
<i>Lowland varieties</i>							
IR5	4	4	4	11	18	1.30	1.60
IR8	4 to 5	5	4	15	22	1.45	1.65
IR305-4-20	3 to 4	4	4	16	20	1.00	1.20
IR747B2-6-3	3	1 to 2	4	12	14	1.05	1.30
IR841-67-1	5	4	4	14	22	1.50	1.80

^a1 = very fine, 6 = very thick. ^b1 = very few, 5 = very dense. ^c1 = very few, 2 = from lower portion of root only, 3 = midportion to root tip, 4 = uniformly branched from base to tip.

few lowland varieties which were also reported to be adapted to upland culture, such as Bluebonnet 50, MTU-17, and IR272-4-1, had predominantly very thick roots, and many rootlets branching from the lower portion of roots. In the dry season, the upland varieties produced some of the longest roots (Table 14). In the wet season, the average root length was less and the maximum length was not more than 25 cm. On the other hand, the lowland varieties generally produced similar numbers of roots per plant to the upland types, but a lower proportion of thick roots.

In the drill-flood treatment, the proportion of thick roots and the maximum diameter of thick roots were similar to those in the upland planting in both variety groups, but the number of roots per unit length of the row increased in the drill-flood plots and the branching of rootlets decreased.

Comparisons between the drought-resistant and drought-susceptible varieties as well as between the upland and drill-flood treatment confirm last year's findings that drought resistance is associated with a large proportion of very thick roots, extensive branching of rootlets, and the capacity to produce more long, thick roots when there is water stress.

Recovery from water stress. Plant samples from 90-day-old plants from upland and transplant-flood plots were analyzed for starch and sugar content. The sampling was done when the plants in upland plots began to show water stress symptoms. Six upland varieties contained

lower levels of starch than four lowland varieties in both plantings and the differences were highly significant between groups. Plants in the transplant-flood plots generally had higher starch content than those in the upland plots. In the upland planting, IR8 had the highest starch content, 40 percent. Taichung Native 1 and IR5 contained about 30 percent starch. Six upland varieties averaged 27 percent. Starch content and recovery from desiccation appear associated in some test varieties (1970 Annual Report).

The differences in sugar content were highly significant among 10 varieties, but they showed no consistent trends.

Grain yield. Because of the minimal water supply to the plants in the dry season, yields in the upland planting were generally low. The upland varieties ranged between 1.2 and 2.8 t/ha. M1-48, RT1095, and Rikuto 21 were the top yielders in the upland group. The semidwarf lowland types and the early maturing Dular produced between 1.0 and 2.2 t/ha. The yields of late maturing Peta and IR5 were greatly reduced (less than 1 t/ha) by a severe sheath blight infection. The plasticity indices for the transplant-flood to upland treatment varied from 1.1 to 2.4 in the upland types and from 1.4 to 5.5 in the lowland types. The plasticity indices for the drill-flood to upland yield comparisons were slightly smaller but still distinct between groups: 0.9 to 2.2 in upland types and 1.4 to 4.1 in lowland types.

The grain yields in the wet season were

largely reduced by a dry spell extending from seeding time (August 6) to the maximum tillering period in early October. After 140 mm rain fell on October 3 and 4, little precipitation occurred until November 18 when a long rainy spell began. Heavy incidence of sheath blight broke out in mid-September on susceptible types. This outbreak was followed by leaf blast, sheath blight for the second time, tungro, and bacterial leaf blight.

The yields of upland types ranged from 0.5 t/ha in OS4 to 2.0 t/ha in C22-51. In the lowland group, IR5 benefited from the late rains and produced the top yield, 2.1 t/ha. IR8 and other semidwarfs all yielded less than 1 t/ha. All upland varieties except Miltex gave higher yields in the drill-flood planting than in the upland planting. But the top yield was only 1.6 t/ha. The lowland group generally produced more grain than the upland types in the drill-flood planting and IR841-67-1 gave the highest yield, 2.7 t/ha. In the transplant-flood treatments, the yields of most upland types were reduced by severe zinc deficiency.

Varietal differences. Data obtained in the 1970 wet season and the 1971 dry and wet seasons indicate that most of the upland varieties from Africa and the Philippines have inherently low tillering ability and slow vegetative growth in the juvenile stage; moderately long, light-green, and moderately droopy leaves, which often roll when water stress begins, but which retain nearly constant leaf areas under different water regimes; moderately good to good drought resistance, characterized by the production of long and thick roots and a high root-to-shoot ratio; growth durations of 110 to 135 days; and inherently low yielding capacity, mainly due to limited panicle number.

These observations suggest that several plant characteristics could be combined to raise the yield potential of rice varieties grown under upland culture: early vegetative vigor and moderately long and slightly droopy leaves to provide ground cover and to facilitate leaf rolling when soil moisture becomes deficient; a vigorous root system capable of developing deep and thick roots when moisture supply diminishes near the soil surface; a greater ability to tiller so that the plant can use additional

water and nutrient supply if the climatic conditions become more favorable later in the vegetative phase; a high tiller-to-panicle ratio and a high harvest index; and satisfactory levels of resistance to diseases such as blast, sheath blight, and *Helminthosporium* leaf spots, to insect pests, and to soil problems.

Some of these features are present in various combinations in both upland and lowland varieties and their expression appears to be heritable. Therefore, it should be possible to recombine the desired traits by conventional hybridization, testing, and selection methods.

Genetics and cytogenetics

Component characters of plant type. Studies on the inheritance of the principal component characters of plant type were continued in two crosses representing extreme differences in plant type: IR160-27-3 x Bengawan and IR400-5-12 x BJ-1.

Genetic components of the variability in hybrid populations were concurrently measured in six populations: the two parents, F_1 hybrids, F_2 population, and the two reciprocal backcrosses. Means obtained from the six populations indicated that dominance effects were most important in controlling plant height of juvenile plants and number of days to heading in IR400 x BJ-1, and tiller number, panicle number, and grain weight in both crosses. Additive gene effect was prominent in the number of days to heading in IR160 x Bengawan, adult plant height in both crosses, the angle and area of the leaf below the flagleaf in IR160 x Bengawan, and the flagleaf angle in IR160 x Bengawan. Epistatic effect of an additive x additive nature was detected in tiller number, adult plant height in IR160 x Bengawan, and flagleaf angle in IR400 x BJ-1. The interaction of dominance x dominance effect was indicated by tiller number at 50 days after seeding in IR160 x Bengawan and also by tiller number at later stages in IR400 x Bengawan. The dominance x dominance effect was indicated by grain weight in both crosses.

Correlation analysis of plant characters taken from F_2 plants grown in the dry season indicates strong positive association between the following pairs: days from seeding to heading

and tiller number at 80 days after seeding in both crosses; adult plant height and leaf length at 80 days after seeding in IR160 x Bengawan; adult plant height and flagleaf angle in IR400 x BJ-1; angle of the flagleaf and of the leaf below it in IR160 x Bengawan; leaf length with leaf angle and with leaf area in IR160 x Bengawan; and plant height and leaf area at 65 days after seeding in both crosses.

Lodging susceptibility of semidwarfs. The lodging resistance of improved tropical varieties comes primarily from their short stature and erect leaves, but some semidwarf varieties, however, lodge near maturity when grown in the wet season with high rates of fertilizer. Light to moderate degrees of lodging are frequently observed in Taichung Native 1, IR424-2-1-PK2, RD 3, IR20, and several IR532 lines.

We grew 29 semidwarfs and one intermediately tall selection (IR127-80-1) in the wet season at 0 and 120 kg/ha N, to compare varietal differences and to determine the effect of nitrogen on plant characters related to lodging resistance. The semidwarfs came from 16 crosses. The traits recorded were plant height at heading, length of the two lower elongated internodes (BI_1 and BI_2), the cross-sectional culm area of BI_1 , weight of the main tiller at maturity, sheath wrapping score at maturity, degree of lodging in the fertilized plot, and a lodging resistance factor (cLr) measured by a brass chain in the unfertilized plot.

Analysis of variance indicates that the 30 varieties and selections differed significantly from each other for each of the six plant characters. Most of the lodging-susceptible types, such as Taichung Native 1, IR20, and IR532-1-171, have either small culm areas or long BI_2 , or both. Taller selections, such as IR442-2-1-PK2 and RD 3, have rather poor sheath wrapping at the basal portion of the culm when the plants approach maturity.

Nitrogen fertilization significantly affected plant height at the 1-percent level and the BI_1 length. Variety x nitrogen interaction was significant in five traits and significant in the case of BI_1 length. Varieties showing significant or highly significant differences between the two nitrogen levels in one or more traits belong to the lodging-susceptible types: Taichung

Native 1, IR424-2-1-PK2, IR20, IR532-1-171, and RD 3.

Path analysis by means of partial correlation coefficients indicated that the increased plant height made the largest direct and indirect contributions to lodging susceptibility. In contrast, tiller weight, cross-sectional culm area, and length of the BI_1 internode contributed positively, though to relatively smaller extents, to the lodging resistance factor. On the other hand, the length of BI_2 and the extent of sheath wrapping made small negative contributions to the cLr factor.

Grain dormancy and growth duration. Studies on the relationship between strong grain dormancy and growth duration conducted last year indicated that strong dormancy and late maturity were not necessarily correlated in hybrid progenies as reported in rice literature. But it was not feasible to separate all of the non-dormant lines from dormant lines because of unusually rainy weather during the last quarter of 1970 which enhanced the expression of dormancy in different lines.

This year several dormant and non-dormant lines from three crosses, each involving a non-dormant x strongly dormant combination, were planted in the dry season to determine the degree of dormancy in each line. The breeding behavior on grain dormancy and growth duration obtained from three crosses clearly shows that strongly dormant hybrids can be recovered from early-maturing segregates when selection is made in the F_3 generation.

Allelic relationship of semidwarfs. New sources of short stature are needed to broaden the genetic base of improved varieties. From the world collection, four recently acquired semidwarfs were identified: K8 mutant (Acc. 11073) from Ceylon, C53-39 dwarf (Acc. 11148) from Burma, CN242d3 (Acc. 101934) from Taiwan, and Purbachi (Acc. 11406) from mainland China by way of Bangla Desh. In a June 1970 planting the heights of these varieties were 80 cm for CN242d3, 103 cm for C53-39, 104 cm for Purbachi and 112 cm for K8 mutant compared with 103 cm for IR8.

The varieties were each crossed with IR8 and the F_1 hybrids and their parents were grown in October of 1970. Only the K8 x IR8

4. Distribution of plant height in four semidwarf x semidwarf crosses.

and CN242d3 x IR8 combinations produced F_1 plants taller than the taller parent in the cross concerned. The Purbachi x IR8 and C53-39 x IR8 hybrids were intermediate between the two parents.

About 1,000 F_2 plants of each cross were grown in March 1971 to determine the range of F_2 segregation. Because Purbachi is weakly sensitive to daylength and C53-39 is strongly sensitive, many F_2 plants from the two crosses with these varieties were late maturing. But the two parents retained their semidwarf stature.

The F_2 distribution in K8 x IR8 was transgressive on both tails of the distribution, producing many plants taller than either parent (fig. 4). None of the F_2 plants from CN242d3 x IR8 were shorter than CN242d3 while most were taller than IR8 (fig. 4). The F_2 data indicated that the recessive semidwarf locus of IR8 was non-allelic with that of either K8 or CN242d3.

Most F_2 plants from Purbachi x IR8 and C53-39 x IR8, were similar in height to the two parents, while a few were shorter than IR8.

But in C53-39 x IR8 a few late-maturing plants were tall (150 to 190 cm range) (fig. 4), while all of the tall F_2 plants in Purbachi x IR8 fell within parental limits though the late-maturing plants had long leaves which produced a misleading impression that the plants were tall. Obviously, the loci for short stature in Purbachi and C53-39 are allelic to the locus in IR8. But the locus could be of a compound nature allowing a low frequency of crossing over between units and resulting in a few tall segregates in C53-39 x IR8.

Weak photoperiod sensitivity. Many varieties of tropical or temperate origin have the weak photoperiod response. They show an extended seeding-to-heading period under a lengthening photoperiod beyond 11 hours, but they will eventually flower under any photoperiod. Improved varieties such as Peta, IR5, IR20, and IR22 have this kind of response (fig. 5), though under natural daylength in the tropics the extreme difference in growth duration among round-the-year monthly plantings may not

exceed 30 days. On the other hand, weakly photoperiod-sensitive varieties differ appreciably in length of the basic vegetative phase.

The genetic study of the weak photoperiod response in Peta was continued in two additional crosses, each involving a completely insensitive parent, IR12-178-2 or Milfor-6(2). Estimates of the basic vegetative phase based on the seeding-to-heading period under a 10-hour photoperiod were similarly distributed in the hybrid progenies of the two crosses. In the F_1 hybrids, a short basic vegetative phase was dominant to a long one and the F_2 distribution agreed with previous findings that several *Ef* genes with cumulative and unequal effects conditioned the basic vegetative phase.

The photoperiod-sensitive phase of a plant was estimated by the difference in heading date between the 10-hour and the 14-hour photoperiods. The estimated photoperiod-sensitive phase of Peta ranged from 57 to 76 days, while IR12-178-2 produced estimates of 10 and Milfor-6(2), 21 days. The F_1 hybrids of the two crosses showed different potence values which indicated different degrees of dominance. In

IR12-178-2 x Peta, the potence value indicated a partial dominance of the long photoperiod-sensitive phase or weak photoperiod sensitivity, while in Milfor x Peta a short photoperiod-sensitive phase or insensitivity was partially dominant to a long photoperiod-sensitive phase.

The two F_2 populations showed one similarity—most of the F_2 plants fell between the photoperiod-sensitive-phase values of the two parents, though the IR12-178-2 x Peta cross contained more insensitive F_2 plants than weakly sensitive plants (fig. 6). Few F_2 plants had smaller photoperiod-sensitive-phase values than the insensitive parent. On the other hand, a small number of F_2 plants clearly exceeded the photoperiod-sensitive-phase range of the Peta parent in the Milfor x Peta cross (fig. 6).

A duplicate F_2 sample of the IR12-178-2 x Peta cross was planted in the field in March under a lengthening natural daylength. The F_2 distribution was essentially normal with a small excess of weakly sensitive plants which headed later than Peta.

Fifty-six F_3 lines of IR12-178-2 x Peta were selected and planted in the field during March

5. Types of photoperiod responses.

to represent three classes of F_2 plants: insensitive, intermediate, and weakly sensitive. The variance of the seeding-to-heading period among F_3 plants within a line was much larger in the intermediate group than in the other two groups. But F_3 lines in both the insensitive and weakly sensitive groups also gave variances larger than either parent, indicating that some of the plants were heterozygous for length of basic vegetative phase or for weak sensitivity, or for both. In two other crosses, Kaohsiung 68 x Peta and Chianung 242 x Peta, the variances of F_3 lines were much larger than that of the insensitive parent. From the variable F_1 , F_2 , and F_3 pattern among crosses, it is obvious that the weakly sensitive response is controlled by several genes and its expression is markedly affected by the genetic background of the insensitive parent involved.

In the F_2 population of IR12-178-2 x Peta, long photoperiod sensitive phase was correlated with a short basic vegetative phase ($r = -0.57$). In the Milfor x Peta cross, the relationship between basic vegetative phase and photoperiod-sensitive phase was not so clear-cut.

From the breeding nurseries, six late-maturing (ranging from 105 to 125 days from seeding to heading in November planting) F_6 lines of IR8 x Wagwag/3 were grown under controlled photoperiods to determine their basic vegetative phase and photoperiod-sensitive phase values. The estimates of basic vegetative phase ranged from 48 to 64 days, which may be described as moderately long to long. The values for the

photoperiod-sensitive phase, ranging from 54 days to more than 190 days, indicate that all of the lines belong to the weakly sensitive group. But, such a combination of a long basic vegetative phase (64 days) and a long photoperiod-sensitive phase (74 days), as found in line IR1060-71-2, is rare in commercial varieties.

Protein content in F_1 caryopses. A complete set of diallel crosses involving five high protein and four low-protein selections was completed during 1971. The 72 reciprocal combinations were made by cross-pollinating spikelets emasculated by the hot-water method so that the hybrid seeds retain their normal shape and size. The protein content of the parents and the reciprocal F_1 hybrids was determined on single-kernel brown rice (caryopsis) by the chemistry department. The sample size was 10 caryopses for the parents and four for each non-reciprocal F_1 hybrid.

The 36 groups of reciprocal hybrids along with the nine common parents in each group are given in figure 7. The two-way grouping of the parents and their cross-combinations according to the egg or pollen source are given in Table 15. The 18 group means showed a positive association between the protein content of the hybrids and that of the high-protein female parent and a negative association between that of the hybrids and that of the low-protein male parents. The two-way table indicated maternal influence as well as an interaction effect. Most of the F_1 hybrids showed higher protein values than the high parent.

6. Distribution of photoperiod-sensitive phase (difference between 14-hr and 10-hr photoperiods) in two crosses.

7. Protein content of brown rice in nine-parent diallel set.

The diallel analysis indicates the complex genetic nature of protein content which involves additive effects, dominance at some loci, gene interaction expressed as overdominance, and unequal distribution of dominant or recessive alleles. Marked maternal influence was shown as expected from the triploid endosperm, of which two doses come from the female parent. Estimates of the magnitude of additive and dominance effects from the diallel analyses are biased by the maternal effect and gene interaction, but the presence of such gene effects still holds.

Intercrossing F_1 hybrids. The intercrossing of F_1 or F_2 hybrids in all possible combinations has been suggested as a means of more fully using the genetic variability present in the parents. Four selections (IR127-80-1, IR332-2-10, IR747B2-6-3, and IR781-184-2) that differ markedly in tillering ability, plant height, maturity, panicle length, and spikelet features were crossed to produce six single crosses. Pairs of single crosses were hybridized to form three sets of double crosses, each including more than 250 hybrid seeds. The parents, single-cross F_1

hybrids and double-cross F_1 hybrids, were planted in the dry season for comparison.

Counts and measurements taken on the parents and the F_1 plants showed that at 50 days after seeding, most of the hybrids had more tillers than the higher tillering parent but the F_1 superiority began to disappear 15 days later. After heading all of the hybrids had slightly fewer panicles than the high-tillering parent. The heading date of most hybrids was intermediate between that of the parents or slightly earlier than the mid-parent value, indicating a partial dominance of earliness. Some of the hybrids exceeded the high parent in adult plant height, panicle length, and panicle weight.

Table 15. Mean protein content (in %) of 72 reciprocal F_1 hybrids arranged by the protein content of their male and female parents.

Female parental array	Protein content of male parental array (%)		
	High-protein	Low-protein	Mean
High-protein (9.9 to 12.7%)	13.7	14.2	13.9
Low-protein (5.9 to 7.9%)	11.4	11.8	11.5
Mean	12.5	13.3	

Table 16. Spikelet and pollen sterility of sterile F₂ plants cytologically examined.

Cross	Plants (no.)	Spikelet sterility (%)		Pollen sterility (%)	
		Range	Mean	Range	Mean
IR8 x Boegi Imba	3	17 to 25	14	53 to 96	78
IR8 x Pankhari 203	3	45 to 81	63	69 to 72	62
Basmati 370 x Taichung Native 1	3	25 to 76	42	55 to 74	62
Basmati 370 x Pankhari 203	1	—	15	—	54

Usually, however, the expression of hybrid vigor was not associated with the distance of genealogical relationship between the two parents involved.

The F₁ hybrids of the double-crosses showed a much wider range of variation within a population than the single-cross F₁ populations or the parental populations. Among plant characters, height measured at three stages produced the greatest amount of variability

within the double crosses, while the period from seeding to heading produced the least. All three double-cross populations produced ranges of variation beyond parental limits in all traits observed, except for the period from seeding to heading. When two yield components, panicle number and panicle length, were compared, greater transgressive segregation on the upper end was found in two double-cross combinations which came from 1) two single-crosses each involving unrelated parents, and 2) single-crosses each involving more distantly related parents. A smaller range of variation was found in the third double-cross which involved two single-crosses, one of which came from unrelated parents and the other from more closely related parents.

Cytology of sterility in F₂ hybrids. Cytological investigation of hybrid sterility in F₂ plants of indica x indica and indica x javanica crosses was continued in cooperation with cytogeneticists of the College of Agriculture, University of the Philippines. Six crosses and the corresponding parents were planted during the 1970 wet season. The pollen and spikelet fertility of all the F₂ plants were determined. Only the sterile plants (50% sterility and above) of four crosses were examined cytologically in 1971. The percentage of the pollen and the spikelet sterility of such plants are shown in Table 16.

Examination of cells at pachynema showed loose pairing in all the plants except in the IR8 x Boegi Imba F₂ plants which exhibited a high percentage (88.6%) of unpaired chromosomes. Unequal bivalents, duplication-deficiency loops, T-configurations, and fragments also occurred in some of the crosses but at low frequencies. In one plant of IR8 x Pankhari 203, five out of 49 cells did not have the major nucleolus.

Among the 800 cells of the IR8 x Boegi Imba cross examined at diakinesis and metaphase I, only 9.37 percent were normal and 13 out of 96 cells in one plant produced 24 univalents. Some of the univalents split into chromatids at metaphase I. In the other crosses, from two to 10 univalents were found in most of the plants examined. Quadrivalents were also observed except in the Basmati x Pankhari 203 cross. There were several nucleolar bodies at diakinesis in all crosses. Extra and mis-oriented spindle or

8. Chromosomal aberrations at meiosis I: Mis-oriented spindles at metaphase I, top, precocious disjunction forming a bridge at metaphase I, bottom.

spindles were observed in IR8 x Boegi Imba (fig. 8). In addition, one to two chromosomes in one IR8 x Boegi Imba plant exhibited precocious disjunction, forming a bridge at metaphase I (fig. 8). A high frequency of clumped chromosomes was found in the same cross.

At anaphase I one to six bivalents and laggards and bridges occurred in all the crosses. Other abnormalities such as unequal chromosome segregation, late disjunction, and persistent nucleolus were also observed.

Insect resistance. Last year, we reported that the resistance of Mudgo, CO 22, and MTU 15 to brown planthopper is controlled by a single dominant gene, *Bph 1*, and the resistance of ASD 7 is controlled by a recessive gene, *bph 2*, which is allelic or closely linked to *Bph 1*. Genetic studies this year with MGL 2 and PTB 18, which are both resistant to brown planthopper, showed that MGL 2 possesses a single dominant gene and PTB 18, a single recessive gene for resistance (Tables 17 and 18). In addition, no susceptible segregate was obtained among 438 F₂ seedlings of Mudgo x MGL 2 and 493 F₂ seedlings of PTB 18 x CO 22. The number of susceptible seedlings in F₂ populations of PTB 18 x Mudgo and ASD 7 x PTB 18 was negligible. And when 137 F₃ lines of PTB 18 x Mudgo and 106 F₃ lines of PTB 18 x CO 22 were tested against brown planthopper, all were found to be homozygous resistant. Thus, it appears that in MGL 2 the resistance gene is *Bph 1* and in PTB 18 it is *bph 2*.

When PTB 18 was crossed with Taichung Native 1, which is susceptible, monogenic segregation for reaction to brown planthopper occurred, but crosses with Pankhari 203 as the susceptible parent behaved differently. In repeated tests, the proportion of susceptible F₂ seedlings from Pankhari x PTB 18 was far less than that expected on the basis of monogenic segregation: only 58 plants were susceptible in a population of 943 F₂ plants. Similarly, out of 113 F₃ lines from Pankhari x PTB 18, only four were homozygous susceptible. The reasons for this variation in the segregation patterns of crosses of PTB 18 with different susceptible parents are not clear.

Brown planthoppers normally show poor survival on the resistant variety, Mudgo, but

Table 17. Classification of F₂ populations of crosses and their parents according to seedling reaction to brown planthopper.

Parent or cross	No. of seedlings				P value for 3:1/1:3
	R ^a	I ^b	S ^c	Total	
TN1	—	—	47	47	—
MGL 2	30	—	—	30	—
TN1 x MGL 2 F ₂	326	19	125	470	0.40–0.50
IR8	—	—	47	47	—
Ptb 18	22	—	—	22	—
IR8 x Ptb 18 F ₂	120	63	317	500	0.60–0.70

^aR = resistant. ^bI = intermediate. Intermediate type of reaction was grouped with the dominant reaction type for calculating P value. ^cS = susceptible.

the Institute plant pathologists have reared the insects on Mudgo for 10 generations and found that their average life span improved from 4.2 days in the first generation to 16.0 days in the 10th generation (1970 Annual Report). Sixteen days is comparable to the life span of the insects on Taichung Native 1, a susceptible variety.

We tested Mudgo against brown planthoppers that had been reared on Mudgo for 22 generations and found that it was nearly as susceptible as Taichung Native 1. Apparently, the continuous rearing of the insect on a resistant variety led to the development of a new biotype. Table 19 shows the reactions of a set of varieties to the original culture (designated as Biotype 1) and the new culture (designated as Biotype 2). The data confirm the findings that the resistance genes in Mudgo, CO 22, MTU 15, and MGL 2 are identical because they all were susceptible to Biotype 2. On the other hand, the resistant reaction of ASD 7 and PTB 18 to Biotype 2 supports the hypothesis that the resistance of these varieties is genetically different from that of Mudgo.

Table 18. Classification of F₃ lines of crosses and their parents according to seedling reaction to brown planthopper.

Parent or cross	No. of lines				P value for 1:2:1
	R	Seg. ^a	S	Total	
TN1	—	—	25	25	—
MGL 2	12	—	—	12	—
Ptb 18	13	—	—	13	—
TN1 x MGL 2 F ₃	32	54	31	117	0.70–0.80
TN1 x Ptb 18 F ₃	34	68	33	135	0.95–0.99

^aSeg. = Segregating.

Table 22. Influence of planting time on pollen sterility of parents, F₁, F₂, and backcrosses of Taichung Native 1 (TN1) x Pankhari 203 (P).

Material	April 1970 seeding			December 1970 seeding		
	No. of plants	Pollen sterility (%)		No. of plants	Pollen sterility (%)	
		Range	Mean		Range	Mean
TN1	5	1.5 to 6.2	3.5	9	1.6 to 5.0	2.8
P	5	2.6 to 4.9	4.0	10	4.3 to 9.9	7.0
TN1 x P (F ₁)	4	47.4 to 47.9	47.4	8	90.2 to 96.6	93.6
P x TN1 (F ₁)	4	34.4 to 37.1	35.8	9	68.1 to 97.1	80.4
TN1 x P (F ₂)	51	3.4 to 58.2	21.0	50	6.4 to 100	66.0
(TN1 x P) x TN1 (F ₁)	37	3.7 to 63.6	21.6	17	5.2 to 95.1	41.0
(TN1 x P) x P (F ₁)	30	15.1 to 97.5	55.7	23	9.9 to 100	78.8

with male-sterile Taichung Native 1 x Pankhari/3 plants. We were able to identify at least two plants which are homozygous maintainers of sterility. Further selection and test crossing has led to the development of several F₅ lines with improved plant type, normal pollen fertility, and daylength insensitivity.

The development of a male-sterile line designated D 388 was earlier reported (1969 Annual Report). The line was selected from a cross between IR400-28-4-5 (a derivative of Peta/4 x Taichung Native 1) and Pankhari. The identification of Pankhari as a maintainer of cytoplasmic sterility led us to assume that male sterility of D 388 might be under cytoplasmic control. D 388 was crossed with Pankhari and Peta, using the latter as pollinators. Since D 388 produces some fertile pollen, it was also possible to make the reciprocal cross, Pankhari x D 388. Although the number of plants examined is small, the data on pollen sterility of F₁ plants clearly indicate that the male sterility of D 388 is under cytoplasmic control and that Pankhari maintains the sterility while Peta restores fertility (Table 23).

Natural cross-pollination in the cultivated rice is usually less than 1 percent. Maximum outcrossing on pollen-sterile lines seldom exceeds 10 percent. Improvement of the cross-pollination potential of rice is an essential prerequisite to the use of cytoplasmic male sterility in a hybrid breeding program.

Anther size, stigma size, degree of stigma exertion, and duration of spikelet opening are some of the floral characters that can influence the rate of outcrossing. The genetic variability for these characters was studied in a set of 29

cultivated and wild rices. The anther length, stigma length, and degree of stigma exertion showed large and highly significant variation. The differences in the duration of spikelet opening were, however, relatively small. Among cultivated varieties, RD 1 and BPI 76-1 appear to be good sources of genes for increasing the degree of stigma exertion. Two wild rices, *Oryza sativa* f. *spontanea* (Acc. 100183) and *O. perennis* subsp. *balunga* (Acc. 101173) have large anthers and high degree of stigma exertion. *O. sativa* f. *spontanea* crosses readily with cultivated rice varieties and the progenies show nearly normal fertility.

The estimated heritability of anther length was the highest (98%) and that for duration of spikelet opening was the lowest (19%). The heritability values were also high for stigma length (86%) and degree of stigma exertion (90%). Thus selection for anther length, stigma length and degree of stigma exertion will be quite effective but improvement in the duration of spikelet opening will be difficult.

Chemical male sterility. Screening of selective gametocides to induce male sterility was started in cooperation with the physiology department. An effective gametocide would be useful in multiple or composite crossing programs where

Table 23. Pollen sterility of F₁ in crosses of D 388 with Pankhari 203 and Peta.

Material	No. of plants	Pollen sterility (%)	
		Range	Mean
D 388 x Pankhari 203	7	84.6 to 97.1	92.0
Pankhari 203 x D 388	3	7.4 to 8.9	8.2
D 388 x Peta	2	8.1 to 9.2	8.6
D 388 x Pankhari 203/2	16	76.7 to 100	95.3

9. Changes in size and shape of spikelets of IR262-43-8 caused by application of Ethrel at early booting.

large numbers of hybrid seeds are needed by plant breeders.

Three concentrations (2,000, 4,000, and 8,000 ppm) of Ethrel (2-chloroethylphosphonic acid) were applied once as foliar sprays to IR262-43-8 at three different dates during the early booting stage (ear primordium about 1 mm long). The 8,000 ppm treatment caused severe symptoms of phytotoxicity, such as general yellowing of older leaves, outward spreading of culms and leaves, and impaired panicle development. The 2,000 and 4,000 ppm treatments caused some panicle abnormalities but the development of most panicles was not affected. In general, foliar application at early booting greatly reduced the length of the flagleaf.

The 4,000 ppm application at the earliest application time caused the highest pollen sterility (64%) and spikelet sterility (94%) in the first two panicles to emerge from the boot. But the average pollen and spikelet sterility of the last two panicles to emerge from the boot was 14 and 79 percent, respectively. The last two panicles emerged 6 days after the first panicle. Thus one foliar application of Ethrel at the early booting stage is not sufficient to induce a high degree of sterility in all panicles. The untreated check showed 12 percent pollen sterility and 40 percent spikelet sterility in the first two panicles.

To determine whether Ethrel should be applied

more than once during the early booting stage, we applied 4,000 ppm to IR24 plants once in the early booting stage, every 3 days (three times), or every 5 days (four times). The multiple application gave a high degree of pollen and spikelet sterility. The percentage of pollen sterility was lower than the percentage of spikelet sterility. The extent of spikelet sterility was reflected by an accompanying reduction in the mean number of grains produced.

Application of Ethrel at three growth stages (early, mid-booting, and late booting) was also compared. Treatment at early booting gave higher pollen and spikelet sterility, a lower seed set, and a greater reduction in length of flagleaf than the mid-booting, or the late booting treatments. We also found that more frequent application of Ethrel resulted in more spikelet sterility at all three growth stages.

Ethrel reduced spikelet size and caused other abnormalities of the lemma and palea of IR262-43-8 (fig. 9). The chemical induced femaleness by the formation of multiple stigmas and ovaries within a floret and of stigma-like hairs at the tip of anther filaments instead of an anther. In addition, a green ovary-like growth formed at the base of the filaments. Similar floret deformations were observed in IR24.

Further tests are necessary to determine whether Ethrel can be used effectively to induce pollen sterility without causing ovule sterility.

Rice production training and research

Training programs

Six month course. The seventh annual 6-month rice production training course had 34 trainees from 14 different countries. Since its beginning in 1964, 211 trainees from 24 countries have graduated from the course.

The educational backgrounds of the 1971 class of trainees differed greatly. There were three master's degree holders, 16 persons with B.S.A. degrees, four engineers in agriculture, 10 diploma holders, and one high school graduate. Such a wide variation in educational background, experience, and interest makes the training task difficult. Assignment of extra tasks and continuous evaluation are essential to ensure that the less qualified achieve a satisfactory level of performance. At the start of the course the trainees differed widely in their performance. The class average on the first practical examination was 31 percent with a range of 3 to 81 percent, while the written examination had an average of 42 percent with a range of 12 to 80 percent. On the final examination the average on the practical test was 93 percent and on the written test, 88 percent.

Short courses. Two 2-week short courses in rice production were conducted in November and December. As in 1970, the first course was organized to provide the 6-month rice production trainees with experience in planning and conducting a short course in rice production. The short-course trainees practice all the skills in growing a rice crop, from selecting the seed to drying the harvested grain. This is made possible by use of growth-stages plots where rice is planted every 2 weeks. Thirty-three persons, mostly church workers and farmers, took this course.

The second course was composed of 38 persons: three Israelis, four Japanese, 15 Filipinos, five Americans, one Indonesian, one Pakistani, and nine IRRI scholars. This course was taught by the RPTR staff and IRRI senior and junior scientists.

New directions. This year trainees were selected as a team. We are encouraging countries

that supply trainees to the 6-month rice production training course to send a team of trainees who have been assured of positions operating a training program on their return home. This approach is essential to reduce the number of trainees who take up entirely different occupations when they return home.

Although IRRI emphasizes training in rice production under irrigated conditions, we began training in rainfed and upland rice production. Three field trips were made by the 1971 class to observe IRRI's research on problems of producing rice under upland and rainfed conditions. The trainees also participated in establishing and managing a plot of upland rice near the IRRI farm.

Applied research trials

IRRI cooperates with agencies, such as the Bureau of Plant Industry, the University of the Philippines College of Agriculture, and the Agricultural Productivity Commission, to field test new rice technology. In yield trials (FENSART) of new rice selections in farmers' fields in the dry season throughout the Philippines, 10 of 11 varieties and selections averaged over 5 t/ha (Table 1). IR8 and IR24 had the highest average yields, 6.0 t/ha, followed by IR20 with 5.9 t/ha and C4-137 with 5.8 t/ha.

To determine the economic feasibility of using granular herbicides for control of weeds in paddy rice, six granular herbicides were tested in the 1971 wet season. Twenty kits containing all the required inputs were distributed to extension workers and agricultural schools in six provinces. Unfortunately, torrential rains accompanying a typhoon which hit these areas soon after transplanting flooded most of the locations and destroyed the effects of the herbicides.

Outbreaks of tungro virus in Nueva Ecija, Cotabato, Bicol, and other parts of the Philippines in the 1969 wet season prompted the establishment of a tungro virus control project in the 1970 dry season.

To test the effectiveness of carbofuran

Table 2. Field evaluation of carbofuran for virus vector control. 1971 dry season.

Province	Farmers' method ^a				Carbofuran treatment ^b			
	Tungro virus (%)	White heads (%)	Dead hearts (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Tungro virus (%)	White heads (%)	Dead hearts (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)
Cotabato								
Location 1	85	8	5	4.6	5	3	2	7.8
Location 2	19	8	4	4.6	4	3	2	9.5
Location 3	14	6	2	5.5	6	3	2	8.0
Location 4	11	4	2	5.4	3	3	2	8.7
Location 5	11	3	5	4.9	2	2	2	9.1
Location 6	5	4	3	5.2	1	2	2	9.0
Camarines Sur	31	0	1	5.5	1	0	0	6.6
Batangas	30	21	15	4.2	16	12	9	5.3

^aLocation 1: Thiodan spray in seedbed; and 20 and 27 days after transplanting, one spray of Sevin at milk stage. Location 2: Sevin 85S and Mipcin. Location 3: Sevin and Mipcin spray used alternately. Location 4: Niran 6=3 and Sevin insecticides were used, timing and frequency of application not indicated. Location 5: Sevin and Mipcin once a week. Location 6: Mipcin and Azodrin to control pests, no spray at milk stage. Camarines Sur: Lindane 15 days after transplanting (2 kg/ha a.i.), 0.04% Azodrin sprayed 10, 20, 40 and 60 days after transplanting, and Sevin sprayed 85 days after transplanting. ^bSeeds soaked in clean water and allowed to germinate, followed by soaking 24 hr in a 0.06% carbofuran solution for 12 hr. The seedlings grown from these seeds using the wetbed method were then soaked in a 0.12% carbofuran solution for 12 hr before being transplanted. A field application of the 3% granules were made to the paddy water 20 days after transplanting at 1 kg/ha a.i.

dry period in August and early September, the soil in farmers' fields cracked, the roots of the crop were pruned, and serious damage occurred. The soils in the trial plots, however, remained moist in most locations.

Varieties for rainfed paddies. A variety trial was conducted in typical rainfed paddies using nine of the recommended varieties for irrigated rice land and six new selections. To obtain performance data on the test entries under varying soil types, rainfall, and pest and disease incidence, trials were established in the five municipalities where the project was conducted.

Satisfactory yields of over 4 t/ha were obtained with IR577-24-1, IR20, IR22, and IR24 (Table 3). The combined analysis of variance showed highly significant variety-location interactions. Highest mean yields occurred on Prensa clay loam where IR22 and IR577-24-1, the two top yielders, had yields of 5.9 and 5.3 t/ha, respectively. Most other test entries also performed best on this soil. Prensa clay loam has a better water holding capacity than the other soil types and the area in which it is located had higher and better-distributed rainfall than other areas. The rice paddies were affected by drought for only 1 week in the Prensa clay loam area while in the other areas paddies suffered severe drought for more than 2 weeks. Also, many of the plots were more than 60 days old when the tungro virus started to spread in

the Prensa clay loam area and no visual symptoms of the disease were observed in the plots.

The lowest yields occurred in the Bantog clay loam area in Gapan where a 1-month-long drought started a week after transplanting. The tungro virus disease was very serious by 2 to 3 weeks after transplanting. IR20 and IR5 gave the highest yields in this area, 3.6 t/ha. IR8, IR22, BPI 121-407, and the IR1108, IR937,

1. Rainfed and upland applied research project sites, 1971.

2. Monthly rainfall, Bulacan and Nueva Ecija, Philippines.

and IR1154 lines were severely damaged by tungro which reduced their yields.

IR20, IR5, and C4-63 were among the most stable entries. They were least affected by changes in environment. Bacterial leaf blight and stem borers affected some selections, but not enough

to cause serious reduction in yields. M1-48 and Intan lodged severely in most test locations.

Nitrogen response on rainfed paddies. To determine the optimum level of nitrogen on IR8, a medium-maturity, short-statured variety, and IR5, a taller, longer duration variety, 31

Table 3. Grain yield of 15 varieties and selections in five different types of soil under rainfed conditions. Twenty-four locations, Bulacan and Nueva Ecija, 1971 wet season.

Varieties or selections	Yield (t/ha)					Mean	Maturity ^a
	Prensa clay loam	Buenavista silt loam	Buenavista sandy clay loam	Sibul clay loam	Bantog clay loam		
IR8	5.3	3.2	3.4	4.4	3.2	3.9	135
IR5	5.1	3.4	2.7	3.1	3.6	3.6	145
IR20	5.3	3.6	4.4	4.4	3.6	4.3	130
IR22	5.9	3.5	4.3	4.5	3.3	4.4	130
IR24	4.9	3.0	4.1	5.2	3.2	4.1	128
IR1108-3-5	5.0	3.3	3.3	4.9	3.5	3.7	129
IR577-24-1	5.3	3.8	4.9	4.9	3.4	4.4	130
IR790-28-6	5.0	3.0	3.3	4.8	2.4	3.8	130
IR937-76-2	4.9	2.8	2.7	3.7	2.8	3.4	131
IR1154-243-1	3.5	2.0	3.0	3.0	2.8	2.7	126
BPI 76-1	4.5	2.9	3.3	3.8	2.6	3.4	130
BPI 121-407	4.5	3.1	2.6	3.3	3.0	3.3	134
M1-48	4.1	1.6	2.3	2.4	1.9	2.5	129
C4-63 G	4.8	3.0	3.4	4.0	3.0	3.7	130
Intan	2.9	2.5	1.4	1.8	3.3	2.3	149

^aDays from sowing to harvest.

plots were established throughout the five major soil types found in the project area: Prensa clay loam in Santa Maria, Buenavista silt loam in San Rafael, Buenavista sandy loam in San Ildefonso, Sibul clay loam in San Miguel, and Bantog clay loam in Gapan.

Nitrogen was applied at 30, 60, 90, and 120 kg/ha. The rates of 60 kg/ha N and above were applied in three split doses. A basal application of 60 kg/ha K_2O and 60 kg/ha P_2O_5 was made in all plots.

All the trial sites, except two, were without water for a month starting about 30 to 45 days after transplanting so application of the last dose of nitrogen had to be delayed. Plots with low nitrogen levels suffered more severely from the drought: they dried earlier and the soil cracked. The soil in most plots with 90 and 120 kg/ha N remained moist during the drought period probably because the crop canopy was established more rapidly. The canopy slowed evaporation from the soil. The biggest increases in yield occurred in the Bantog clay loam soils in Gapan where a 60 percent increase in yield (compared with the unfertilized control) was obtained with the use of 90 kg/ha N (fig. 3). The Buenavista silty clay loam, Buenavista silt loam, and the Prensa clay loam gave about 35 to 40 percent increase in yield. The Sibul clay soils in San Miguel had the lowest yield increase, about 32 percent. IR5 yielded more than IR8 at 20 out of 26 locations (fig. 4).

In general, the most profitable levels of nitrogen were 90 and 120 kg/ha N. In the Prensa clay loam and the Bantog clay loam soils, a fertilization rate between 90 and 120 kg/ha N would give a net return in the range of ₱800 to ₱1,000/ha (fig. 5). The Buenavista silt loam soils in San Rafael and the Buenavista silty clay loam soils in San Ildefonso produced the greatest net returns with an application of 120 kg/ha N.

Insecticides on rainfed paddies. Insecticide trials were established to determine the effectiveness of four different combinations of insecticides in controlling the common insect pests in rainfed rice.

The application of insecticides significantly increased yields at all locations. The carbofuran-treated plots (Table 4) yielded 1.0 to 1.6 t/ha more than the control plots in all locations.

3. Grain yields in rainfed paddies on five types of soil as affected by various levels of nitrogen. Bulacan, 1971 wet season.

These treatments were equally effective in controlling the tungro virus damage. The gusathion treatment was effective in controlling the disease at five of the six locations. At one location, however, the green leafhopper population was very high and caused damage to all the plots, but the carbofuran-treated plots had less damage than the others. At three locations

4. Nitrogen response of IR8 and IR5 on rainfed paddies at 26 locations. Bulacan and Nueva Ecija, 1971 wet season.

5. Net profit obtained from nitrogen application on two rice varieties planted in rainfed paddies in five types of soil. Bulacan, 1971 wet season. (Mean of 26 trial locations.)

the lindane-treated plots were just as badly damaged by tungro and green leafhopper as the control plots and the yields were not significantly different.

In general, in these trials, IR20 gave higher yields than IR22. On the average, IR20 produced 1.2 t/ha more than IR22 in untreated plots and 0.8 t/ha more in treated plots. Damage by the tungro virus was very serious on unprotected IR22 (Table 4).

Table 4. Tungro virus infection and grain yield of IR22 and IR20 as affected by insecticide treatment in rainfed paddies. Bulacan and Nueva Ecija, Philippines, 1971 wet season.

Treatment ^a	Rate	Tungro virus infection (%)		Yield (t/ha)	
		IR22	IR20	IR22	IR20
Carbofuran ^b + lindane ^c + folidol ^d	1.0 kg/ha 3.0 kg/ha 0.09% concn	7	1	3.1	3.8
Carborufan ^b + carbofuran ^b + folidol ^d	0.5 kg/ha 0.5 kg/ha 0.09% concn	5	0	3.2	4.0
Gusathion ^e + gusathion ^e + folidol ^e	0.06% concn 0.06% concn 0.09% concn	13	3	2.6	3.5
Lindane + lindane + folidol ^e	2.0 kg/ha 3.0 kg/ha 0.09% concn	15	4	2.5	3.5
Control	—	38	11	1.6	2.8

^aFirst treatment applied 20 days after transplanting; second, 45 days after transplanting; third, 65 days after transplanting; except for first Gusathion treatment which was made 25 days after transplanting. ^b3% granular. ^c6% granular. ^d50% E.C. ^e40% E.C.

Two applications of carbofuran and one of folidol gave the highest return, ₱718/ha (Table 5). The net return from gusathion plus folidol was not as high as that from the carbofuran treatments, but its lower cost per hectare resulted in the highest profit ratio, 7.8:1.

Herbicides on rainfed paddies. Five promising herbicides were tested in 10 locations to determine their effectiveness in controlling the common weeds of the rainfed rice areas. Paddies which were known to be weedy during the past season were selected as test sites.

Unfortunately, weeds were an unimportant factor at seven locations. The low weed populations could be attributed to thorough land preparation, and to high rainfall for 3 to 4 weeks after transplanting which kept the fields continuously under 5 to 8 cm of water and prevented the weed seeds from germinating.

Significant grain yield increases in the treated plots were obtained only where heavy weed populations were observed in the control plots (Table 6). All granular herbicides gave excellent control of grasses and sedges. The 2,4-D spray was effective in controlling sedges, but not grasses. Hence there was no significant difference in the yields between this treatment and the control plot. All the treated plots gave significantly higher yields than the control plot at one location. Sedges, the only weed in this plot, were effectively controlled by all the herbicides.

Stand establishment on rainfed paddies. To determine the yield performance of IR5 and

Table 5. Returns above costs of cash inputs for insecticides under rainfed conditions. Bulacan, 1971 wet season.

Insecticide treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)	Cash costs (₱/ha)	Net return ^a (₱/ha)	Cost:benefit ratio
Control	2.2	—	—	—
Furadan + lindane + folidol	3.5	262	648	2.5
Furadan + furadan + folidol	3.5	192	718	3.7
Gusathion + gusathion + folidol	3.1	72	558	7.8
Lindane + lindane + folidol	3.0	148	412	2.8

^aNet increase compared with the control. Rice price: ₱700/t.

Table 6. Grain yield as affected by herbicides applied 4 days after transplanting under rainfed conditions. Bulacan and Nueva Ecija. 1971 wet season.

Project no.	Yield (t/ha)					Control
	2,4-D IPE G 0.8 kg/ha	2,4-D IPE E.C. 0.8 kg/ha	Saturn/ 2,4-D IPE G 1.0/0.5 kg/ha	TCE Styrene/ 2,4-D IPE G 0.75/0.5 kg/ha	C290/2,4-D IPE G 0.75/0.5 kg/ha	
1 ^a	4.7	4.5	4.5	5.0	4.8	4.9
2 ^a	5.1	5.5	5.7	6.1	5.7	5.5
3	4.2	4.3	3.7	3.8	4.0	3.1
4 ^a	3.5	4.4	4.1	3.5	4.1	3.9
5 ^a	5.0	4.7	4.8	4.8	5.2	4.4
6 ^a	4.1	4.2	3.6	3.7	4.1	3.8
7 ^a	3.3	3.8	3.3	3.7	3.6	3.3
8 ^a	3.5	3.8	3.6	3.6	3.7	3.9
9	4.3	3.8	4.4	3.8	4.4	3.4
10	3.3	2.8	3.7	3.6	3.9	2.2

^aWeed population low.

IR20 when broadcast and transplanted under various nitrogen levels, eight trial plots were established in rainfed paddies. The broadcast plots were seeded at 80 kg/ha. A 20- x 20-cm spacing was used in the transplanted plots.

No yield data were obtained from three trial sites because of the poor stand obtained in the broadcast plots. Stand establishment in these plots was poor due to growth of algae and continuous flooding. In three trials (Table 7), the yields of the broadcast plots were similar to or higher than those of the transplanted plots. The stand of the crop in these plots was uniform as there were no problems of algae and flooding. The difficulty in establishing a uniform stand strongly suggests that under the present method of land preparation and water management in the rainfed areas, transplanting is more reliable.

Management for rainfed paddies. Yields obtained under farm conditions depend greatly on weed control, prevention of insect and disease damage, and soil fertility.

To determine the yield levels that could be obtained from four different levels of management and the profitability of each level, 12 trials were established in typical rainfed paddies during the wet season. Table 8 gives the details of each management level. IR5 was used in all the trials.

Management level 4, which carried an effective control for the green leafhoppers and other pests, a high level of nitrogen, and sufficient phosphorus, gave the highest yields in nine of

the 10 locations (Table 9). Yields obtained from management levels 1, 2, and 3, in general, were very low and at several locations no grain was harvested.

Serious damage by the tungro virus disease was an important reason for the low yields under management levels 1, 2, and 3. The insect control measures used in these three levels of management did not control the green leafhopper which transmits the tungro virus disease. In addition, the soils in the area are generally low in nitrogen and phosphorus. Applications of 40 and 60 kg/ha N were generally too low for high yields. The lack of phosphorus under management levels 1, 2, and 3 also contributed to the low yields.

Table 10 shows the returns above cash costs of inputs from the different levels of management. Management level 4 which had the highest cash inputs, P594/ha, gave the highest

Table 7. Effects of two methods of stand establishment, in rainfed paddies on the grain yield of IR5 and IR20 under five levels of nitrogen. Bulacan and Nueva Ecija, 1971 wet season.

Trial no.	Yield (t/ha)									
	Broadcast					Transplant				
	0	30	60	90	120	0	30	60	90	120
	<i>IR5</i>									
1	4.0	4.5	4.7	4.8	4.1	3.3	4.4	5.0	5.9	5.4
2	2.4	3.3	4.3	4.7	4.4	2.5	3.1	3.7	3.9	3.7
3	1.7	1.6	1.5	2.2	1.9	2.3	3.0	3.5	3.6	3.4
4	2.3	2.4	2.9	3.4	3.2	2.8	3.4	3.8	4.2	4.2
	<i>IR20</i>									
5	1.7	2.0	2.6	3.6	4.1	1.8	2.2	3.3	4.1	4.0

Table 8. Cultural practices for four levels of management.

Cultural practices	Management level 1	Management level 2			Management level 3			Management level 4		
		Chemical	Rate (kg/ha)	Applied	Chemical	Rate (kg/ha)	Applied	Chemical	Rate (kg/ha)	Applied
Fertilization	none	N	20	basal at panicle initiation	N	20	basal	N	60	basal
		N	20		N	20	30 DAT	P ₂ O ₅	40	basal
					N	20	40 DAT	N	20	30 DAT
Weed control	none	2,4-D E.C.	0.8	4 DAT	2,4-D G	0.8	5 DAT	Machete G	1	5 DAT
		2,4-D E.C.	0.8	25 DAT						
Insect control	none	Folidol	0.09% concn	40 DAT	Carbofuran	1	20 DAT	Carbofuran	300 ppm	^a
								Carbofuran	1	20 DAT
		Folidol	0.09% concn	heading	Folidol	0.09% concn	heading	Carbofuran	1	50 DAT
							Folidol	0.09% concn	heading	

^aSeed and seedling treatment.

net returns at eight of the 10 locations. Its net returns are more than twice that of management level 3. They doubled from the use of P₂O₅, more N, and about 1 kg/ha a.i. of 3 percent carbofuran granules at an additional cost of P 281/ha. These inputs were the key factors that ensured high yields in management level 4. The absence of any one of these inputs would have greatly reduced yields and net returns. The net returns from management level 3 were high in four locations, but were relatively low in the other locations. The returns from management level 1 and management level 2 were very low and the chances for a total loss extremely high. There was no harvest from six of the 10 locations for management level 1.

Results from these trials demonstrate the need to use a package of cultural practices

Table 9. Effects of different levels of management on the grain yield of IR5 under rainfed conditions. Ten locations, Bulacan and Nueva Ecija, 1971 wet season.

Trial no.	Grain yield (t/ha)			
	M1	M2	M3	M4
1	3.1	3.3	4.1	5.3
2	2.6	3.5	5.3	5.9
3	0.0	0.0	0.0	3.8
4	1.8	2.4	3.4	3.2
5	0.0	2.1	2.7	4.1
6	0.0	0.0	0.0	2.7
7	0.0	0.9	1.9	3.5
8	1.2	1.4	2.3	3.4
9	0.0	0.0	1.1	4.4
10	0.0	0.0	2.0	2.3
Mean	0.8	1.2	2.3	3.9

similar to those used in management level 4 if high yields are to be obtained and risk minimized. It is essential to control weeds, insect pests, and provide an adequate supply of N and P₂O₅ to produce rice successfully under rainfed conditions in the project area.

Direct seeding on unpuddled soil. One cause of low rice yields in the rainfed paddies is the delay in transplanting when not enough rain falls to permit puddling of the soil. Transplanting is often delayed until August. By then the seedlings are usually more than 2 months old; consequently the yield is reduced.

To determine if high yields could be obtained when rice is sown directly on an unpuddled rainfed paddy at the start of the rainy season, trials were established in five locations. The plots were plowed and harrowed in May. As soon as rain was sufficient to saturate the soil the plots were seeded. Only two of the five plots had acceptable stands but the weed population was very high. In one of the two locations bermudagrass and nut grass were abundant and could not be effectively controlled by handweeding. In the other location the plot was sprayed with NTN 5006 at 2 kg/ha a.i. This treatment effectively controlled the grasses and broadleaved weeds but it had a phytotoxic effect on the rice plants when the paddy was flooded by rain. The toxic effect of the herbicide persisted until about 40 days after seeding.

The other three plots were flooded by early

rains in June. Seed germination was poor. So these three plots were puddled and reseeded with pregerminated seed. They became very weedy, too. Saturn granules were applied 7 to 10 days after seeding but they did not control grasses. Apparently they were applied too late to control the weeds effectively. Establishing a uniform stand in these plots proved difficult. The algae problem was serious at all locations.

Yields obtained from the trial were impressive in spite of the relatively high weed population and the poor stand of the crop. The plots direct seeded on dry soil gave an average yield of 3.3 t/ha. The plots seeded on mud produced yields of 4.2 t/ha.

Experience gained from this trial points to the need for more research to determine the best methods and timing of land preparation; method and timing of seeding; kind, rate, and timing of herbicides; and the most economic means of controlling algae.

Upland variety trial. To determine the yield performance of 15 promising varieties and selections under upland conditions, eight trials were established during the 1971 wet season.

The yields obtained at all locations were low (Table 11). The highest yield was 3.0 t/ha with IR5. IR8 had an average yield of 2.7 t/ha. All other entries, except the IR937 line, had yields lower than 2 t/ha. A drought which started about 70 days after seeding and lasted for more than a month accounts for the low yields. The entries that were at the panicle initiation stage at the start of the drought were severely affected. They formed spikelets that were mostly unfilled or light. In most of the test sites, panicle initiation of IR8 and IR5 was delayed. Panicle initiation in IR5 and IR8 was about 100 days after seeding, about 30 and 15 days respectively after the drought. After the drought, the leaves and culms of IR8 and IR5 elongated and new tillers formed before panicle initiation occurred. This probably partly explains why these two varieties gave better yields than the others.

The growth durations of all entries were 15 to 21 days longer than normal.

Nitrogen response in upland fields. To determine the optimum level of nitrogen fertilization for IR8 and IR5 under upland conditions, eight trials were established. Nitrogen rates of 0 to

Table 10. Returns above costs of cash inputs from four levels of management, 10 locations, Bulacan and Nueva Ecija, 1971 wet season.

Trial no.	Return ^a (₱)			
	M 1 ^b	M 2	M 3	M 4
1	2170	9	387	946
2	1820	499	1577	1716
3	0	- 131	- 313	2066
4	1260	289	807	386
5	0	1339	1577	2276
6	0	- 131	- 313	1296
7	0	499	1017	1856
8	840	9	457	946
9	0	- 131	457	2486
10	0	- 131	1087	1016
Mean	609	212	674	1499

^aCash costs of inputs: M 1, P0; M 2, P131; M 3, P313; M 4, P594.

^bValue of yield obtained from M 1. Rice price: P700/t.

120 kg/ha N were used with all rates above 30 kg/ha N applied in split doses. All plots received a basal application of 60 kg/ha P₂O₅ and 60 kg/ha K₂O.

Yields of the plots that received no nitrogen reflect the low natural nitrogen fertility of upland soils in the project area (Table 12). Plants in these plots rarely grew over 30 cm tall. Application of 90 kg/ha N produced optimum yields. At this nitrogen level, IR8 yielded 2.9 t/ha and IR5 yielded 2.7 t/ha, or nearly 2 t/ha more than in the plot that was not fertilized with nitrogen. Maximum economic returns occurred with 90 kg/ha N (Table 13).

Table 11. Grain yield of 15 varieties or selections under upland conditions at seven locations, Bulacan and Nueva Ecija, 1971 wet season.

Variety or selection	Growth duration ^a (days)		Yield (t/ha)
	Mean	Range	
IR8	134	126 to 141	2.7
IR5	153	147 to 161	3.0
IR24	134	126 to 141	1.9
IR1108-3-5	134	124 to 145	1.8
IR577-24-1	132	126 to 135	1.8
IR790-28-6	132	126 to 135	1.3
IR937-76-2	136	126 to 141	2.3
IR1154-243-1	135	124 to 145	1.4
MI-48	126	114 to 135	1.3
BPI 9-33	135	124 to 145	1.0
Azucena	124	114 to 135	1.0
Palawan	131	126 to 135	1.7
HBDA ₂	122	114 to 134	1.3
Azmil 26	132	122 to 137	1.6
BPI 76	134	126 to 141	1.9

^aFrom sowing to harvest.

Table 12. Nitrogen response of two varieties under upland conditions in four locations. Bulacan and Nueva Ecija, 1971 wet season.

Nitrogen applied (kg/ha)	Yield (t/ha)				Mean
	Experiment no.				
	1	2	3	4	
	<i>IR8</i>				
0	1.2	1.4	0.8	^a	1.1
30 ^b	1.7	2.1	1.2	0.7	1.4
60 ^c	2.7	2.8	2.5	1.6	2.4
90 ^d	3.3	3.4	2.6	2.2	2.9
120 ^e	3.6	3.4	2.7	2.0	2.9
	<i>IR5</i>				
0	0.7	1.1	0.9	0.4	0.8
30	1.6	2.2	2.0	0.6	1.6
60	2.4	2.2	2.5	1.4	2.1
90	2.5	2.6	3.4	2.2	2.7
120	2.6	3.0	3.9	2.4	3.0

^aLess than 0.1 t/ha. ^bApplied 10 days after seeding (DAS). ^c30 kg/ha N applied 10 DAS, 15 kg/ha N applied 35 DAS and 65 DAS. ^d30 kg/ha N applied 10, 35, and 65 DAS. ^e40 kg/ha N applied 10, 35, 65 DAS.

Insecticides for upland fields. An insect control trial was established in six locations to determine the kinds of insect pests present and the extent of their damage and to assess the effectiveness of three combinations of insecticides in controlling common insect pests.

The few insect pests observed in the six trial locations were of no economic importance. The rice bug, which is considered one of the most important insect pests on upland rice, was not observed at any location. Grain yields ranged from 1.1 to 3.2 t/ha but there were no differences between untreated plots and treated plots.

Table 13. Returns above costs of cash inputs for fertilizer for IR8 and IR5 under upland conditions. Bulacan and Nueva Ecija, 1971 wet season.

Nitrogen applied (kg/ha)	Grain yield ^a (t/ha)	Cash costs ^b (₱/ha)	Net return ^c (₱/ha)
	<i>IR8</i>		
0	1.1	—	—
30	1.4	42	168
60	2.4	84	826
90	2.9	126	1134
120	2.9	168	1092
	<i>IR5</i>		
0	0.8	—	—
30	1.6	42	518
60	2.1	84	826
90	2.7	126	1204
120	3.0	168	1372

^aMean of four locations. ^bUrea in 50 kg bags costs ₱1.40/kg N. ^cNet increase compared with the control. Rice price: ₱700/t.

Herbicides for upland fields. Weeds are one of the most important reasons for low yields of upland rice. Plots treated with four promising liquid herbicides and handweeding were compared with an untreated control plot at six locations. All test sites had large populations of broadleaved weeds, sedges, and grasses.

In general, the four herbicides and handweeding satisfactorily controlled the weeds. Preforan and handweeding gave the best control. Effective control of broadleaved weeds, sedges, and grasses was obtained in four of six locations with handweeding and in five locations with Preforan. NTN, CP53619, and Saturn gave satisfactory control in three locations and fair control in the other three locations. All the treated plots gave significantly higher yields than the untreated control (Table 14). But, while Preforan and handweeding performed better than the other treatments in controlling the weeds, no significant yield differences were observed between these treatments and the other herbicide treatments.

Multiple cropping. Rice fields in the Philippines are generally left idle after the harvest of the rice crop. To determine if another crop could be grown following harvest of the rice crop, several plantings of field crops, such as soybean, sweet potato, sweet corn, sorghum, field corn, and tomato, were made at 16 locations. The first planting was made in late September in the sandy clay loam areas in San Rafael. Intermittent rains in November and December delayed planting in the heavy clay soil areas of Santa Maria, San Miguel, and Gapan. The plantings in these areas could not be established until December.

Observations obtained from the 16 plots indicate that it is possible to grow another crop in both the upland and rainfed areas following rice. The best yields were obtained from the plantings made in the sandy clay loam areas in San Rafael planted in late September. The soybeans and cowpeas were harvested as green pods with yields ranging between 8 and 9 t/ha. Sweet corn produced about 51,500 well-filled ears per hectare.

Sweet potato varieties Jewel and Centennial produced yields of 8 to 10 t/ha. These yields are below those obtained at the IRRI farm.

Possibly the continuous rain in November and December hindered root development. The sweet potato crop intercropped with sweet corn produced much lower yields—only 2.4 t/ha for Centennial and 4.4 t/ha for Jewel.

The sorghum crop planted in late September using varieties Darso and Cosor produced yields of only 2.3 and 2.0 t/ha, respectively. The plot was waterlogged for about 1 month during the crop's early growth which slowed its development. Due to the wet soil, weeding could not be done effectively. Thus weeds contributed to the low yields.

The plantings made in early October in general were not successful. Except for sweet potato, all the other crops were completely destroyed as a result of heavy rainfall. Several replantings were attempted but without success until the last week of October when it stopped raining for a week. The late October and early November plantings of sorghum, soybean, cowpea, and sweet potato performed better than the other crops.

Continuous rain until December delayed plantings in the Prensa clay, Sibul clay, and Bantog clay soils. These areas were too wet and sticky in October and November to establish trials in these locations. Of the crops planted in these areas in December, soybean and sorghum had the best stands.

Weeds were a serious problem in all the trial sites and several species of leaf-eating insects caused serious damage to all the crops. Weekly spraying of malathion, sevin, folidol, meptox, or gusathion was necessary to protect the crops. Among the most common insects were red mites

Table 14. Effects of different weed control treatments on grain yield of IR8 under upland conditions, six locations. Bulacan and Nueva Ecija, 1971 wet season.

Treatment	Rate (kg/ha a.i.)	Yield (t/ha)
NTN 5006 50% E.C.	2	2.18
CP53619 48% E.C.	2	2.28
Saturn 50% E.C.	2	2.17
Preforan 30% E.C.	2	2.41
Handweeding (2 x)	—	2.39
Control	—	1.38

of cowpea, aphids, corn earworm, and cutworms. Diseases present in the area were downy mildew of corn, damping off of mongo, bacterial wilt of tomato, and an unidentified disease which caused cowpea to wilt and die.

These trials permit several conclusions. First, it is possible to grow a crop of soybean, sorghum, corn, sweet corn, sweet potato, mongo, cowpea, and other similar crops in the rainfed and upland areas of Nueva Ecija and Bulacan after harvest of the rice crop, especially on soils with good internal drainage. Second, in the sandy clay loam areas, two crops can be grown following rice, if the rice crop is harvested as early as the third week of September to permit the planting of short maturing crop such as soybeans, mongo, or sweet corn by the last week of September. Third, successful planting of any crop following rice depends greatly on proper timing of planting, efficient drainage, thorough land preparation to conserve the soil moisture and control weeds, use of raised beds or ridges, proper use of fertilizers, effective control of weeds and insects, and use of high yielding disease-resistant varieties.

Training programs

The Institute provides training to young research scientists and extension workers from rice-growing countries around the world. The scientists receive training leading to a degree as well as non-degree training in different disciplines. The extension workers participate in the Institute rice production course. In addition, the Institute conducts a course in multiple cropping systems centered on rice. A booklet describing the types of training is available from the Institute on request.

During the year, 94 rice research scientists were in residence (Table 1). Of these 42 worked for a master of science degree and four for a Ph.D. degree. The Institute is not a degree-granting agency, but it has cooperative arrangements with universities to permit our scholars to complete their course work elsewhere. All except one of the master's candidates attended the College of Agriculture of the University of the Philippines (UPCA). Three of the Ph.D. students were enrolled for course work at U.S. universities and one at UPCA. Thirteen scholars with bachelor's degrees and 21 with master's degrees received non-degree training by working on specific research projects under the guidance of Institute scientists. A degree candidate is usually in residence for about 2 years and a non-degree candidate for 6 to 12 months. The Institute also had 14 post-doctoral fellows who carried out advanced research in their areas of specialization. The duration of a post-doctoral fellowship usually is 1 to 2 years.

Of the 94 individuals, 51 completed their training during the year. To prepare young scientists to assume leadership in rice research, the Institute is accepting an increasing number of post-doctoral fellows and individuals working for a Ph.D. degree. The post-doctoral fellows are usually young scientists who have had good basic training, but lack the experience of doing production-oriented research. By spending 1 or 2 years at the Institute, they develop the necessary background to carry out research on problems that affect production.

Table 1. Distribution of different categories of scholars according to area of specialization.

Research area	Scholars (no.)			Total
	Research scholars	Post-M.S. fellows	Post-doctoral fellows	
Agronomy	10	4	1	15
Rice breeding and genetics	13	3	3	19
Plant physiology	4	4	2	10
Entomology	5	3	3	11
Plant pathology	4	—	4	8
Soil chemistry	3	2	1	6
Soil microbiology	2	3	—	5
Agricultural economics	6	2	—	8
Agricultural engineering	1	2	—	3
Chemistry	1	1	—	2
Statistics	4	—	—	4
Communication and extension	2	1	—	3
Total	55	25	14	94

The International Rice Research Institute and the Indian Agricultural Research Institute last year started a joint training program leading to the Ph.D. degree. The first group of three graduate students are completing their course work at the IARI Post-Graduate School. They will then move to IRRI to carry out their thesis research. Two new scholars were enrolled for coursework at IARI in 1971.

The Institute also supported advanced study for four scientists from Bangla Desh and five from Ceylon in the United States and England. The funds were specifically provided for this purpose in the country projects funded by the Ford Foundation. Mr. P. S. Y. Fernando, from Ceylon, completed his master's degree from the University of Hawaii in 1971.

A rice field experimentation workshop was held from January 23 to March 19. It was designed to train the technical staff of rice experiment stations in the problems and practices of tropical rice production, the design and management of conventional field experiments, the use of experimental tools and scientific instruments, and the recording, analysis, interpretation, and reporting of experimental data. Nineteen persons from Indonesia, Thai-

land, Laos, and the Philippines participated in the workshop.

The regular 6-month rice production course was held from June to November to train rice production specialists and extension workers in the principles and practices of modern rice production. Thirty-four participants from 14 countries attended the course.

The primary purpose of the rice production course is to train individuals to conduct similar training programs in their home countries. The 1971 group of trainees organized and conducted a 2-week rice production course. Another 2-week rice production course was organized by the staff of the Office of Rice Production Training and Research. A total of 71 individuals from the Philippines and six other countries attended the 2-week courses.

The Institute organized a 1-month course for 22 officials of the Agricultural Productivity Commission, which is the main extension agency of the Philippine Government. These officials now work with the Institute staff on a cooperative project to evaluate the available rice technology for rainfed production on farmers' fields.

The regular 4-month multiple cropping course was held from February to June. The objective of this course is to train individuals in the theory and practice of multiple cropping systems centered on rice. Twenty-two trainees from eight countries attended.

During the last decade, the Institute has trained 656 individuals from 39 countries. In addition, about 400 persons have attended short courses mostly of 1 or 2 weeks duration. About 90 percent of all participants came from South and Southeast Asia where most of the world's rice is grown. The training output increased from 14 man-years in 1962 to a record 84 man-years in 1971.

During 1971, 169 scholars, fellows, and other trainees representing 27 nationalities were in residence for all or part of the year. The names and home institutions of those who completed their training during the year are given below. (An asterisk indicates research scholars who completed the master of science degree and research fellows who completed the Ph.D. degree). The major research of each research scholar or fellow is indicated. In addition,

information regarding individuals who came to the Institute for short-term study or observations programs is included.

RESEARCH SCHOLARS

Agronomy

*Meenhon Khan Abbasi**, research assistant, Rice Research Station, Dokri, Pakistan. Chemical weed control in direct-seeded, flooded rice.

*Nagamattu Devasundarajah**, research officer, Rice Research Station, Bombuwela, Ceylon. Levels of land preparation and water management in broadcast-seeded rice.

B. S. L. Munasinghe, teaching assistant, University of Ceylon. *Scirpus maritimus* control for direct-seeded rice.

*Wittaya Seetanun**, 2nd grade agricultural officer, Technical Division, Rice Department, Thailand. Effects of time of nitrogen application on the optimum time of harvest, milling, and seed qualities of flooded rice.

Agricultural Economics

*Moises Sardido**, instructor, University of Eastern Philippines. An analysis of income and resources productivity on alternative rice farm crop patterns in Bicol.

Agricultural Engineering

*Vicente Uichanco**, instructor, College of Agriculture, University of the Philippines. Rotary screen parameters for rice.

Chemistry

*Ngamchuen Kongseee**, 3rd grade officer, Breeding Division, Rice Department, Thailand. Physicochemical properties of the rice grain and starch of selected lines differing in amylose content and gelatinization temperature.

Communication and Extension

*Diosdado Castro**, instructor, College of Agriculture, University of the Philippines. The Filipino graduates of the rice production training program: A follow-up study.

*Eddie Chu**, Sorsogon, Philippines. High-yielding varieties at the crossroads: Three post-trial alternative decisions among farmers.

Entomology

Alicia Pineda, laboratory technician, Centro Internacional de Agricultura Tropical, Colombia. Varietal resistance of rice to the brown planthopper and studies on biotypes of the brown planthopper.

*Caesar Pura**, Philippines. Resistance to *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stål) in varieties of rice.

Farm Operations

Bhupendra N. Phukan, farm manager, Rice Research Station, Assam, India. Farm operations and experiment station management.

Plant Pathology

*Chi-lu Chu**, plant pathologist, Taiwan Agricultural Research Institute, China. Effects of temperature and light on transmission of rice tungro virus.

Plant Physiology

Jong Sung Ahn, assistant researcher, Radiation Agriculture Research Institute, Korea. Zinc nutrition of rice.

*Douglas Forno**, Queensland, Australia. Zinc nutrition of rice.

*Rashid Chaudhry**, research assistant, Government Rice Farm, Kala-Shah-Kaku, Pakistan. Sulfur nutrition of rice.

Soil Chemistry

*Tasnee Attanandana**, assistant lecturer, Kasetsart University, Thailand. Amelioration of an acid sulfate soil.

Statistics

*Renato C. Bernardo**, instructor, Central Luzon State University, Philippines. Sampling technique for estimation of rice stem borer's incidence in farmers' fields.

*K. M. Palaniswamy**, statistical officer, Agricultural College and Research Institute, Coimbatore, India. Sampling in rice experimental plots.

Varietal Improvement

Chong-ho Kim, senior researcher, Honam Crops Experiment Station, Korea. General rice breeding.

*Fu-hsiung Lin**, assistant agronomist, Kaohsiung District Agricultural Improvement Station, Taiwan, China. Inheritance of weak photoperiod sensitivity in rice varieties.

*Cesar Martinez**, auxiliary geneticist, Centro Nacional de Investigaciones Agropecuarias, Colombia. Inheritance of resistance to brown planthoppers, *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stål) in some breeding lines of rice (*Oryza sativa* L.).

Nazmi B. Mursal, inspector of agriculture, Department of Agriculture, Sudan. General rice breeding.

*Suvit Pushpavesa**, 2nd grade officer, Breeding Division, Rice Department, Thailand. Studies on the association of the glabrous character (*gl*) with yield and other characters in F₃ and F₄ pedigree lines from the cross IR8 x (Acc. 6993 x Sigadis).

Narayan Reddy, research field officer, Koronivia Research Station, Fiji. General rice breeding.

Bambang Soeprihatno, research assistant, Central Research Institute for Agriculture, Indonesia. General rice breeding.

Ramien Thongsodseng, rice technician, Salakham Rice Station, Directorate of Agriculture, Laos. General rice breeding.

RESEARCH FELLOWS

Post-M.S.

*Shamsul Alam**, entomologist, Bangla Desh Rice Research Institute. Population dynamics of the common leafhopper and planthopper pests of rice.

Gora Beye, soil scientist, Station de Recherches Rizicoles de Djebelor, Senegal. Effects of leaching, liming, and the application of manganese dioxide on the chemical kinetics and the growth of rice on two acid sulfate soils.

Mannu Lal Bhendia, assistant professor of agronomy, Indian Agricultural Research Institute. Water management effects on improved and traditional rice varieties.

Chandra Breckenridge, research officer, Central Agricultural Research Institute, Ceylon. Quality tests on rices with similar amylose content.

Leonard Ho, Taiwan, China. Introduction of some vegetable crops in multiple cropping systems.

V. M. Khaire, rice entomologist, Agricultural Research Station, Kolaba, India. Varietal resistance to the green leafhopper.

Masayuki Koike, Kyoto University, Japan. Dynamic analysis of rotary tillage.

Liu Fu-Shan, research fellow, Ministry of Economic Affairs, Taiwan, China. Input diffusion and growth in rice production — A case study of Gapan, a municipality in Central Luzon.

M. G. Mane, lecturer in agronomy, College of Agriculture, Poona, India. Effect of water management, weed control, fertilizer management, and environmental interactions on rice growth and yield.

Kazuhiko Miura, Hokkaido University, Japan. Studies on the microflora of the rice root-zone under flooded soil conditions.

*V. V. S. Murty**, assistant rice specialist, Agricultural Research Institute, Hyderabad, India. Studies on the inheritance of resistance to bacterial leaf blight (*Xanthomonas oryzae*) in rice varieties.

Hooshang Nazarian, Tehran, Iran. General rice breeding. *K. D. Singh*, agricultural officer (botanist), Rice Research Station, Manipur, India. General rice breeding.

Suartini, research assistant, Central Research Institute for Agriculture, Indonesia. Bionomics of *Nephotettix apicalis*. *Masaaki Suzuki*, Nagoya University, Japan. Microbial studies on the zinc availability of some flooded rice soils in the Philippines.

*Remigio D. Torres**, instructor, College of Agriculture, University of the Philippines. Economic analysis of gravity irrigation systems in the Philippines.

Vo-Tong Xuan, head, Bio-Agronomy Department, University of Cantho, South Vietnam. Training in rice production techniques and organization of training programs.

Post-doctoral

A. O. Abifarin, International Institute of Tropical Agriculture, Nigeria. General rice breeding.

K. C. Agrawal, rice pathologist, Jawaharlal Nehru Agricultural University, India. Some studies on the chemical control of the bacterial leaf blight of rice and resistance of *Xanthomonas oryzae* to TF-130.

James Cock, Centro Internacional de Agricultura Tropical, Colombia. Photosynthesis and respiration of a rice canopy.

A. K. Ghosh, professor and head, Agronomy Department, Allahabad Agricultural Institute, India. Weed control problems in rice with particular reference to the control of *Scirpus maritimus*.

Syed Md. Ghufuran, assistant plant pathologist, Agricultural Research Institute, India. Stable resistance to blast in some varieties of rice.

M. B. Kalode, insect physiologist, Central Rice Research Institute, India. Biochemical basis of resistance or susceptibility to brown planthopper and green leafhopper in some rice varieties.

Jonathan C. Nwigwe, Nigeria. Studies on the survival of the bacterial leaf blight pathogen, *Xanthomonas oryzae* (Uyeda et Ishiyama) Dowson.

RICE PRODUCTION TRAINEES

J. P. G. Abeykone, agricultural instructor, Department of Agriculture, Ceylon.

J. P. Amara, assistant agricultural officer, Ministry of Agriculture and Natural Resources, Sierra Leone.

Aye Myint, district agriculture officer, Department of Agriculture, Burma.

M. M. Bari, lecturer, Institute of Agriculture, India.

S. K. Basu, plant protection assistant, The Fertilizer Corporation of India, Ltd.

Chuy Puy, assistant chief of rice research, Directorate of Agriculture, Khmer Republic.

S. K. Das, agronomist, The Fertilizer Corporation of India Ltd.

M. I. A. Gunatilleke, assistant agricultural officer, River Valleys Development Board, Ceylon.

D. K. Gupta, agronomist, The Fertilizer Corporation of India, Ltd.
Ram Jattan, research assistant, Koronivia Research Station, Fiji.
C. H. de A. Jayasinghe, teaching assistant, University of Ceylon.
A. R. Husein, extension specialist, Ministry of Agriculture, Indonesia.
Khin Mg. Chit, district agriculture officer, Department of Agriculture, Burma.
Khamphai Kongdara, technician, Rice Experiment Station, Department of Agriculture, Laos.
Mel Sahak, chief, rice experimental station, Kauk Trap, Directorate of Agriculture, Khmer Republic.
John Mesele, extension specialist, Institute for Agricultural Research, Nigeria.
N. K. Mitra, assistant agronomist, The Fertilizer Corporation of India, Ltd.
N. B. Mursal, inspector of agriculture, Department of Agriculture, Sudan.
Assibi Nahyi, senior agricultural officer, Ministry of Agriculture, Ghana.
Benito Narvaez, training officer, Land Reform Training Center, Bulacan, Philippines.
B. Palarajah, agricultural extension instructor, Department of Agriculture, Ceylon.
A. Perinpanayagam, lecturer, School of Agriculture, Department of Agriculture, Ceylon.
Anand Prasad, field officer (extension), Department of Agriculture, Fiji.
D. U. Pribadi, extension specialist, Ministry of Agriculture, Indonesia.
Vicente Rabe, vocational agriculture teacher, Bicol University, Philippines.
Alipio Rosalinas, teacher, Bureau of Public Schools, Camarines Norte, Philippines.
H. B. Senarath, agricultural instructor, Department of Agriculture, Ceylon.
Udom Simaban, 2nd grade officer, Rangsit Rice Experiment Station, Thailand.
Sinxai Sisuvong, technician, Rice Experiment Station, Department of Agriculture, Laos.
Suroso Sukardjo, extension specialist, Ministry of Agriculture, Indonesia.
T. A. Tampiyappa, agricultural instructor, Department of Agriculture, Ceylon.
Nichai Thaipanichaya, 2nd grade officer, Technical Division, Rice Department, Thailand.
Asep Wachju, extension service worker, Ministry of Agriculture, Indonesia.
Tomoyuki Watanabe, chemist, Mitsubishi Chemical Industries, Ltd., Japan.

MULTIPLE CROPPING TRAINEES

Claro Abay, teacher, Negros Occidental National Agricultural School, Philippines.
G. S. Ekneligoda, agricultural instructor, Department of Agriculture, Ceylon.
Theodore Ferguson, graduate assistant, University of West Indies, Trinidad.
G. Gunasekara, agricultural instructor, Department of Agriculture, Ceylon.
K. B. Khatua, officer-in-charge (agronomy), Orissa University of Agriculture and Technology, India.
Wanna Khowsudhi, agronomist, Land Development Department, Thailand.

Eddie Maape, plant pest control officer, Bureau of Plant Industry, Philippines.
P. S. Mahalle, agronomist, Punjabrao Agricultural University, India.
J. Meedeniya, farm manager, Department of Agriculture, Ceylon.
Roman Mercado, plant pest control officer, Bureau of Plant Industry, Philippines.
B. S. L. Munasinghe, teaching assistant, University of Ceylon.
Pablo Piatos, Jr., agronomist, Bureau of Plant Industry, Philippines.
Jose Quilao, agronomist, Bureau of Plant Industry, Philippines.
M. A. Rasheed, assistant manager, Agricultural Marketing Operations and Research Ltd., Pakistan.
G. R. R. Muktapuram, assistant agronomist, Andhra Pradesh Agricultural University, India.
Vichien Sasiprapa, agriculturist officer, Rice Department, Thailand.
Uttam Sharma, research assistant, Department of Agriculture, Jammu & Kashmir, India.
V. Sivalingam, agricultural instructor, Department of Agriculture, Ceylon.
Sisouphanh, chief agricultural officer, Department of Agriculture, Laos.
Achmad Sjariffudin, assistant corn agronomist, Central Research Institute for Agriculture, Indonesia.
Freddy Tangkuman, agronomist, Central Research Institute for Agriculture, Indonesia.
R. Vadivel, agricultural extension officer, Department of Agriculture, Ceylon.

FIELD EXPERIMENTATION WORKSHOP PARTICIPANTS

Amir Mukelar, plant pathologist, Central Research Institute for Agriculture, Indonesia.
Ernesto Andres, provincial rice specialist, Agricultural Productivity Commission, Philippines.
F. A. Bahar, research officer, Makassar Research Station, Indonesia.
Aniceto Cara, farm management technician, Agricultural Productivity Commission, Philippines.
Abu Dardak, head, soil science department, University of North Sumatra, Indonesia.
A. M. Fagi, research officer, Central Research Institute for Agriculture, Indonesia.
Jose Gamboa, farm management technician, Agricultural Productivity Commission, Philippines.
W. A. I. P. Gedjer, soil analyst, Soil Research Institute, Indonesia.
Omar Hidajat, head, agronomy division, Central Research Institute for Agriculture, Indonesia.
K. Keobouarabath, chief of station, Hat Doi Keo Pilot Project, Laos.
Antonio Napeñas, farm management technician, Agricultural Productivity Commission, Philippines.
Jose Salazar, farm management technician, Agricultural Productivity Commission, Philippines.
Djoko Santoso, research officer, Department of Agriculture, Indonesia.
Samran Sombatpanit, technical advisor, Land Development Department, Thailand.
Sujin Suthdani, supervisor, Soil Fertility Branch, Ministry of Agriculture, Thailand.
Haeruddin Taslim, research officer, Central Research Insti-

tute for Agriculture, Indonesia.

Ramien Thongsodseng, rice technician, Salakham Rice Station, Laos.

Narong Unayavong, supervisor, Supanburi Rice Experiment Station, Thailand.

Wahjudi, statistician, Central Research Institute for Agriculture, Indonesia.

SHORT-TERM VISITORS

M. S. Balal, rice breeder, Ministry of Agriculture, U.A.R., studied and observed the rice breeding program of the Institute for 2 months.

Jean-Marie Bidaux, research engineer, Institut de Recherches Agronomiques Tropicales et des Cultures Vivrieres, France, spent 3 months studying the variability of *Pyricularia oryzae* and varietal resistance to blast.

Seung Yoo Choi, professor, Seoul National University, Korea, familiarized himself with the techniques for screening rice varieties for resistance to leafhoppers and planthoppers during his 1-month stay.

Vuong-Huu Hai, phytopathologist, Malagasy Agricultural Research Institute, spent 3 months learning the methods of testing varietal resistance to blast and to bacterial blight.

Reinhardt H. Howeler, post-doctoral fellow in soils, Centro Internacional de Agricultura Tropical, Colombia, spent 1 month becoming acquainted with the agronomy program of the Institute.

Shin Han Kwon, head, plant protection division, Radiation Research Institute in Agriculture, Korea, familiarized himself with methods of testing for varietal resistance to blast during his 2-week stay.

Mai-Thi-My-Nhung, agricultural specialist, U.S. AID/Vietnam, observed the multiple cropping program and learned the technique of operating the atomic absorption spectrophotometer during her 2-week stay.

Angel Manondo, farm management technician, Agricultural Productivity Commission, Philippines, observed water management experiments for 1 week.

Rae Kyung Park, chief, research department, Yungnam Crops Experiment Station, Korea, spent 2 months observing Korean rice breeding materials and seed multiplication of promising selections.

Leonard Herther, volunteer, Lutheran Council, U.S.A., observed rice production techniques for 1 week.

Soejitno, Central Research Institute for Agriculture, Indonesia, spent 2 weeks observing the entomology program of the Institute.

International activities

The institute's international activities are designed to strengthen national rice programs and to encourage cooperative work to increase rice production. These goals are being accomplished through grants from aid agencies or contractual arrangements with them that enable IRRI to employ scientists to work with national rice programs. The country projects, in addition, include provisions for training of local scientists and short study tours by senior scientists, for consultative work by IRRI staff members, and for the purchase of essential equipment not available in the host country. During 1971, 12 senior scientists on the institute staff were working in Pakistan, Bangla Desh, Ceylon, India and Indonesia.

The institute also cooperates with rice scientists of other countries by distributing plant material and through exchange of information. In 1971, IRRI supplied 2,600 packages of seed from the rice germ plasm collection to various cooperators. In addition, 7,700 packages of seed of IRRI breeding lines were sent for evaluation in different countries.

The institute also held three international conferences during the year.

Cooperative projects

The work done by IRRI scientists in cooperative projects in different countries is an integral part of the national rice programs of those countries and it is not intended to report the results of their research here. The general progress of the rice programs is briefly reviewed however.

Pakistan. The Pakistan project which was supported by the Ford Foundation ended in October. Pakistan offers very favorable conditions for rice production and the technology developed at IRRI has had a great impact in that country. IR8 and another IRRI line, IR6-156-2, named Mehran 69 in Pakistan, were grown on about 60 percent of the total rice area in 1971. Mehran 69 is preferred to IR8 because it has better grain quality. The main interest of Pakistan now is to produce better quality rice for export. Although the project

was terminated IRRI continued to offer advice on specific problems such as stem borer control and breeding for tolerance to cold water. Also, IRRI assisted the Pakistan rice program by providing facilities for growing an extra generation of the breeding material at Los Baños during the winter season.

Bangla Desh. IRRI's project in Bangla Desh is funded by the Ford Foundation. IRRI is helping to develop a semi-autonomous research center at Joydevpur called the Bangla Desh Rice Research Institute (BRRI). The activities during the year were curtailed due to the war. By the end of 1971, two-thirds of the positions at BRRI had been filled and the work is getting off to a good start. Development of experimental fields and construction of irrigation systems and greenhouses showed marked progress. Five scientists from Bangla Desh continued to receive advanced training in U.S.A. and the Philippines.

Of the IRRI varieties, IR20 has been most successful in Bangla Desh. In 1971, about 400,000 hectares were planted to IR20, which is locally called Irrisail. The BRRI released a new variety, Mala, for commercial production. Mala was developed from IR272-4-1 and is resistant to tungro, which is a widespread problem in Bangla Desh.

The BRRI scientists carried out research to standardize management practices for the new varieties. The communication division of BRRI held accelerated training courses to train agricultural officials in the production of IR20 as part of the overall program of rapidly introducing this variety to farmers.

Ceylon. The Ford Foundation supports the IRRI cooperative project in Ceylon. During 1971, major emphasis was placed on strengthening the rice program and building the multiple cropping program. A program to improve rice processing was started.

The IRRI scientist assigned to the Ceylon project was actively involved in developing local programs for training extension workers and for field testing of new varieties and selections. Ceylon made effective use of individuals trained in rice production at IRRI. The gradu-

ates of the IRRI rice production training program conducted a series of local training courses of 1-day to 2-week duration at two centers and trained hundreds of extension officers and village-level workers. Also, the graduates of the IRRI multiple cropping training program trained about 300 extension workers and farmers in 1- or 2-week courses.

The mini-kit technique of disseminating new technology which has proved a powerful extension tool in the Philippines was successfully adapted by the extension service in Ceylon. About 6,300 mini-kits were distributed to farmers during two planting seasons. Each kit contained a few grams of seed of four or five new selections or varieties plus the required fertilizer and insecticides for planting 10 sq m of each variety at each location. In addition, about 110,000 kits each containing about 0.5 kilograms of seed of newly released varieties were distributed. This gave one out of every seven Ceylonese farmers an opportunity to grow the new varieties.

The Ceylon government requested IRRI to assist with the improvement of rice processing to improve the quality of rice distributed to consumers. Beginning in 1972, IRRI will undertake another project on rice processing for which a separate grant has been approved by the Ford Foundation.

India. IRRI is cooperating with the All-India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project through a contract with the U.S. Agency for International Development which supplies five resident scientists to the project. In addition, the joint coordinator of the project is assigned to IRRI by The Rockefeller Foundation. This year AICRIP paid special attention to carrying the results of research to extension workers and farmers. The seed of semi-dwarf varieties identified in the coordinated testing program in the previous year was multiplied and made available to farmers in 2-kilogram mini-kits for tests in the dry season. The seed distribution program was supported by the production of popular literature regarding the culture of new varieties based on research findings of the All-India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project.

Concentrated efforts in breeding for resistance to diseases and insects were fruitful. Selections

carrying resistance to gall midge and tungro virus were multiplied for farm trials. Many breeding lines incorporate resistance to bacterial leaf blight from different sources. Breeding material possessing resistance to stem borers and green leafhoppers was evaluated. Significant progress was made in identifying semidwarf selections with a range of maturity periods.

Scientists in the areas of agronomy and plant physiology continued to develop management practices to maximize production. Evaluation of rice machinery developed at IRRI and elsewhere was started.

Indonesia. A grant made by the Ford Foundation in 1970 enabled IRRI to assign a senior scientist to work with the National Rice Research Program (NRRP) in Indonesia. An Indonesian is the coordinator of NRRP with the IRRI scientist acting as the joint coordinator. The development of a nationwide integrated program has facilitated close coordination of rice research efforts by Indonesian scientists and foreign scientists contributed by Japan and the Netherlands under bilateral agreements.

During the year, NRRP made considerable efforts to obtain and plan assistance from development aid agencies. In Indonesia, IRRI has something of a coordination role in seeking additional foreign assistance, when required, to strengthen aspects of the national program. IRRI received a grant from the Netherlands government to help develop regional rice research stations in Indonesia. The grant is being used to help establish a 150-hectare regional experiment station in South Sulawesi. IRRI also negotiated a contract with the U.S. Agency for International Development that will enable the Institute to employ five scientists to work on rice improvement and multiple cropping systems in Indonesia.

Two teams of IRRI scientists visited Indonesia in March and July to gain first-hand information about the problems of rice production and to share their knowledge with Indonesian research workers. Joint discussions and observation of the breeding material and selections developed by Indonesian scientists led to the release of two rice varieties for commercial cultivation. These varieties are high yielding and possess other desirable character-

istics that will make them highly acceptable to farmers.

Other countries. In 1971, IRRI signed a contract with the U.S. Agency for International Development to strengthen cooperative work in Vietnam. The contract provides for two senior scientists, one in agronomy and the other in plant breeding, to be located in South Vietnam.

IRRI reached an agreement with the Arid Lands Agricultural Development Program of the Ford Foundation to assist in strengthening and expanding rice breeding research in Egypt. Beginning in 1972, the institute will assign a rice breeder to work in Egypt.

Without any formal agreement, IRRI continued to help Korean rice breeders in developing varieties from crosses of Korean japonica types with semidwarf tropical varieties. Institute scientists visited Korea to observe breeding material and scientists from that country came to IRRI for short study and observation tours. As in previous years, an extra generation of the Korean breeding material was grown at IRRI during the winter. This year a variety developed from this material was named Tongil in Korea (IR667-98) and was released for commercial production. Tongil is more responsive to fertilizer than other Korean varieties and yields about 15 percent more.

International conferences

International rice research conference. About 70 scientists from 19 countries participated in the annual international rice research conference. The first day's program included review papers by IRRI scientists on rice breeding, agronomy, plant physiology, plant pathology, chemistry, soil chemistry, and soil microbiology. The rest of the program concentrated on entomology, agricultural engineering, and communications. One day was devoted each subject. In the entomology seminar, the progress of work on insect control and varietal resistance to rice insects was reviewed by scientists from IRRI and from seven countries. In the seminar on agricultural engineering, 12 scientists from different countries discussed problems of rice mechanization and reported on progress in

machinery development in Asia. The communications seminar focused on the role of communication and other factors in agricultural development. The evolution of the IRRI rice production training program and experiences in training in Ceylon, Pakistan, and the Philippines were reviewed in detail.

The conference concluded with reports and discussions on research procedures in entomology, on training procedures, visits to IRRI demonstrations, and field trips to nearby rice drying and milling facilities.

Rice policy conference. The rice policy conference was attended primarily by economists who are engaged in research related to rice policy or who are making policy. Several other social scientists participated, too. Several IRRI staff members from agricultural science disciplines took part in one or more of the conference sessions. The conference was attended by 40 participants from 14 countries.

During the first day of the conference, IRRI staff members reviewed research on rice problems and outlined the current status and potential developments in rice production technology in Asia. On the second day, the participants discussed policy issues related to farm resource use and the distribution of the benefits of new technology. The third day focused on the modernization of rice processing for domestic consumption and for export. The last day of the conference dealt with prices and fiscal incentives for agricultural production and economic development. On the afternoon of the third day, participants toured rice milling facilities, irrigation systems, and rice farms near IRRI.

The format of the conference represented a departure from the usual system of formal papers and discussions. On arrival at Los Baños, each participant received a set of papers on rice policy in various countries, papers related to rice technology, and reports of research on the economics of rice production and marketing and on policy. Each conference session then operated as an open forum under the direction of a discussion leader.

Rice breeding symposium. The institute held a major symposium on rice breeding which was attended by 100 rice scientists from 26 countries.

Most participants were rice breeders, but several plant pathologists, entomologists, agronomists, and plant physiologists also gave papers. A unique feature of the conference was the participation of eminent wheat breeders which broadened the scope of discussions. Sixty-five formal papers were distributed among 10 major subjects: 1) advances in rice breeding in tropical Asia, Taiwan, Japan, and U.S.A., 2) current breeding programs in Asia, Oceania, and South America, 3) breeding for disease resistance, 4) breeding for insect resistance, 5) improvement

of grain quality and nutritional value, 6) outlook for higher yield potentials, 7) special problems in rice breeding, 8) breeding methods in rice and in wheat, 9) upland rice improvement, and 10) training rice breeders for the tropics.

Group discussions outside the formal presentation of papers led to plans related to international cooperative testing of material for resistance to diseases and insects and to a collaborative scheme on conserving rice germ plasm.

Other activities

Library and documentation center

International bibliography. The 1970 Supplement to the *International Bibliography of Rice Research* was published in 1971. It has 259 pages including indexes and contains 2,550 references to scientific rice literature, the bulk of which appeared in journals in 1970. An additional 50 serial titles were scanned and searched in the compilation. The coverage is worldwide and the items of reference are classified according to subject matter. An author and a manually produced keyword index are provided. A list of 28 rice literature translations, mostly from Japanese to English is included.

Reference and circulation. Numerous requests for information and photocopying services were received from outside IRRI. Requests for Japanese literature on genetics and breeding outranked all other aspects of rice culture. Requests came mostly from India and Peru. Assistance in library organization and management, selection and acquisition of agricultural materials, and the processing of special materials such as microfilm, maps, and pamphlets were also sought. A few requests for short bibliographies on specific subjects were also received.

Within IRRI, 27,200 books and journals were borrowed during the year, 6,000 more than in 1970. These figures are exclusive of use in the library.

Library holdings. Over 2,000 monographs (books, pamphlets, and reprints) were added to the library. The monographic collection now totals 27,820. Over 100 serial titles were added during the year. Maps, translations, and microfilms were also added to the collection. Eleven thousand cards were added to the catalog.

Other library activities. To keep the scientists informed of the latest publications on rice, the routing of tables of contents of newly received journals was continued. As in previous years, this service included the rice breeding department of the Centro Internacional de Agricultura Tropical in Colombia and the All-India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project in India. The monthly listing of new acquisitions of

books, serial titles, translations, reprints, and microfilm was more widely distributed.

Copies of English translations of foreign-language literature were sent regularly to the National Agriculture Library of the U.S. Department of Agriculture. Eventually, these translations are listed in the Bibliography of Agriculture to make them readily accessible and available to other rice scientists.

Experimental farm

The experimental farm planted IR5, IR8, and IR24 on 5.6 hectares in the dry season for seed production. In the wet season, it planted 12.5 hectares of IR24 and IR841-67-1 for seed. Most of this area was planted to IR24 which we had hoped to distribute to seed growers. But high winds and a severe outbreak of tungro disease almost wiped out the whole crop.

All experimental plots not being used by the other departments were turned over to us for seed production. We also rented a 2-hectare farm outside the IRRI farm for seed increase and borrowed additional land from the U.P. College of Agriculture for use of the plant pathology department.

We converted certain upland areas in the IRRI farm into lowland rice plots, complete with underground pipes for irrigation, for growing seedlings of the increased number of selections being planted by the different departments, especially varietal improvement.

A trainee from India spent 6 months with the department to learn farm and experiment station management.

The area prepared and planted to rice in the station this year increased from last years' 76 hectares to 79 hectares.

Widespread infestation of brown planthoppers contributed to low yields of varieties and selections intended for distribution to seed growers. We used Dolmix, Sevin, Folidol, DDT, lindane, Azodrin, and Mipcin for insect control.

As in previous years, ammonium sulfate was our chief nitrogen fertilizer. We also used solophos, muriate of potash, and urea.

To keep weeds under control in the experimental and production plots and in the station as a whole, we used Hedonal powder and liquid, Saturn, and Gramoxone.

Seed production during the dry season averaged 5.1 t/ha for IR22, 4.7 t/ha for IR24, 5.5 t/ha for IR661-1-140-3-2, 4.5 t/ha for IR5, and 4.4 t/ha for IR8. The wet season crop, which was badly affected by tungro disease and high winds averaged 2.1 t/ha for IR841-67-1 and 2.2 t/ha for IR24. Only selected spots in the production plots that were not badly affected by the disease were harvested for seed.

For preparing rat bait we used, in place of 1080, zinc phosphide, which is as effective but much cheaper. We continued to dust rat burrows with Cyanogas and to use the electric fence. About 9,000 rats were killed by the electric fence.

Information services

Fifty-five thousand copies of *Field problems of tropical rice* in two languages were in print or on order by the end of the year. This book is a pocket-sized manual that contains short descriptions and 90 color plates of common problems of rice. The 31,000 copies of the English edition in print have been distributed primarily in India and the Philippines. Another 12,000 copies which will be distributed in the Philippines are being printed. In Indonesia, a 12,000 copy run of a Bahasa translation of the book is on the press. A Vietnamese translation is being set in type. Translations into two other Asian languages are planned. The cost of the initial color separations was underwritten by the Ford Foundation/Indonesia. Ford Foundation projects in several countries purchased large quantities of the book.

Duplicate sets of all the transparencies pub-

lished in the book are being made available at cost.

To improve the "recognizability" of the annual report, the cover and spine were re-designed. The total number of pages in the report was kept the same as in the 1969 report through the efforts of the contributors to be concise and by sharply condensing the non-research sections. To help the reader use the report a simple thumb-index was added and the table of contents was expanded.

Technical Bulletin 11, *Resistance of rice varieties to striped rice borers*, was published and distributed.

Editing of the booklet *Rice virus diseases* was completed. The booklet is in page proofs and will be printed next year.

The preliminary draft of the *Training manual in rice production*, published last year, was revised and re-edited and is being set in type.

Two operator's manuals for machines developed by the agricultural engineering department were prepared and printed.

Work on the *Laboratory manual for physiological studies of rice* was completed. The first printing of 1,000 copies was quickly exhausted, so a revised and enlarged second edition was published before the end of the year. The cover is water-resistant to protect it in laboratory use and the pages have extra-wide margins to give the user ample room for notes.

Manuscripts for the rice breeding symposium held in September were given preliminary editing before the meeting and multilithed for distribution to the participants at the meeting. The authors were able to review and correct the papers before they left Los Baños. By the year's end, two-thirds of the papers were at the printer.

Over 1,000 visitors a month took tours of the Institute.

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Seminars

The following topics were the subjects of seminars held at the institute during 1971. Unless otherwise stated the speakers were staff members.

- The future of mankind as a social animal. Dr. G. Ledyard Stebbins, professor of genetics, University of California, Davis.
Pesticide legislation in the U.S.A. Dr. Arthur A. Muka, professor of entomology, Cornell University.
- The flow of sediment-laden waters into recharging wells. Dr. Md. Mozibur Biswas, head, Department of Irrigation and Water Management, East Pakistan Agricultural University, Mymensingh.
- Development of mechanical harvesters at Cornell University. Dr. E. S. Shepardson, visiting scientist, IRRI.
- IRRI accomplishments in rice breeding and future plans. Mr. Beachell.
- Rice breeding in California. Dr. Howard L. Carnahan, director of plant breeding, Rice Experiment Station, Biggs, California.
- The impact of improved varieties and agricultural mechanization on labor-force absorption problems in West Pakistan. Mr. Duff.
- Nitrogen availability in upland soils. Dr. William V. Bartholomew, professor of soil microbiology, North California State University.
- Limiting factors in pineapple yields in Hawaii and in the Philippines. Dr. Donald H. Smith, research manager, Philippine Packing Corporation, Manila.
- Rationalizing Philippine rice statistics. Dr. Leon A. Mears, field chairman, UP-Wisconsin Training Program in Developing Economics, University of the Philippines.
- Breeding rice for resistance to tropical viruses and their vectors. Dr. Khush.
- The use of genetical variation to define nutritional quality in cereals. Dr. Lars Munck, chemist, Institute of Genetics, University of Lund, Sweden.
- Selection for photosynthetic efficiency in corn. Dr. Robert B. Musgrave, visiting scientist, UP-Cornell Graduate Education Program, UPCA.
- Rice production activities in the South Pacific and in Ceylon. Mr. William G. Golden, Jr., project leader, IRRI-Ford Foundation Rice Project, Ceylon.
- The social laboratory idea. Prof. C. W. Chang, visiting professor of agricultural education, Southeast Asian Regional Center for Graduate Study and Research in Agriculture, College, Laguna.
- Training and other developments at CIAT. Dr. Francis C. Byrnes, leader, Training and Communication, Centro Internacional de Agricultura Tropical, Cali, Colombia.
- Genetic resources and adaptation to environment in plants. Dr. Hiko-Ichi-Oka, UNESCO expert, Central Luzon State University, Nueva Ecija.
- A crop physiologist looks at yields in rice. Dr. Graeme L. Wilson, visiting scientist, IRRI.
- The protein bodies of cereal grains and their properties—a review. Dr. Juliano.
- Inactivation of rice tungro virus. Dr. Ling.
- Rural Philippine entrepreneurship. Dr. David L. Szanton, assistant to the Representative, Ford Foundation Office, Makati, Rizal.
- What farmers are doing with multiple cropping. Dr. Bradfield.
- Obstacles to Asian development. Mr. Varinda Tarzie Vittachi, editor-in-chief, Asian News Service, and director, Press Foundation of Asia, Manila and Hong Kong.
- Dry matter production and grain yield of rice. Dr. James Cock, postdoctoral fellow, IRRI.
- Some issues in education for agriculture. Dr. Gelia T. Castillo, associate professor, Department of Agricultural Education, UPCA.
- Rice research in East Pakistan. Mr. Rufus K. Walker, rice advisor, Ford Foundation, East Pakistan.
- Approaches to technical assistance. Mr. John Rawnsley, project manager, United Nations Development Program Special Fund Project—Training of Technicians for Grain Industries, College, Laguna.
- Rats and rice in the Philippines, 1970. Mr. Nelson Swink, station leader, Rodent Research Center, College, Laguna.
- Problems of rice production in Indonesia. Dr. S. Yoshida, Dr. Pathak, Dr. Ou, and Mr. Beachell.
- Contract research on agricultural development in Ethiopia. Dr. Raymond E. Borton, Agricultural Development Council, College, Laguna.
- Some observations on yield in a rice crop. Dr. G. L. Wilson, visiting scientist, IRRI.
- Peasantization of kasama tenants—socioeconomic changes of a Central Luzon village. Dr. Akira Takahashi, associate professor, Institute of Oriental Culture, University of Tokyo.
- Research for agricultural development. Dr. A. H. Moseman, director, Malaysian Agricultural Research and Development Institute, Kuala Lumpur.
- Sugarcane breeding in India. Dr. N. Parthasarathy, formerly regional rice specialist, FAO, Thailand.
- Bacterial wilt of bananas—origin and evolution of a classic bacterial disease. Dr. Ivan Buddenhagen, visiting scientist, IRRI (University of Hawaii).
- Rural family planning. Dr. Juan Flavio, vice president, International Institute of Rural Reconstruction, Silang, Cavite.
- Availability of potassium in the soil and its significance for crop production. Dr. K. Mengel, director, Agricultural Experiment Station, "Bunthof," Buntreveg, Germany.
- Recent advances in the chemistry of rice ageing. Dr. Salvador Barber, head, Cereals Laboratory, Instituto de Agroquímica y Tecnología de Alimentos, Valencia, Spain.
- Physiological aspects of protein in wheat. Dr. G. M. Paulsen, visiting scientist, IRRI (Kansas State University).

Studies on buttoning in cauliflower. Dr. E. Oyer, project leader, UP-Cornell Graduate Education Program, and visiting professor in agronomy, UPCA.

Confronting an ancient culture where orchid leaves are mini-skirts. Mr. John Nance, chief of bureau, Associated Press, Manila.

Industry and economic research in the Philippines. Dr. Bernardo M. Villegas, academic director, Center for Research and Communication, Manila.

High-horsepower machine mechanization of rice and intertilled crops in Sumatra. Dr. B. H. Behrens, managing director, Uniroyal Sumatra Plantations, Sumatra, Indonesia.

Growing tropical mushrooms in the Philippines. Mr. R. V. Alicbusan, assistant professor, Plant Pathology Department, UPCA.

Problems of sorghum production in the Philippines. Dr. Arturo Gomez, chairman, Agronomy Department, UPCA.

Role of chlorine in potassium chloride in increasing nut size and copra yield of coconut palm. Dr. H. R. von Uexkull, president, Potash Research Association, Tokyo.

International agricultural research centers: worldwide objectives. Dr. Lowell Hardin, vice president, International Division, Ford Foundation, New York.

Heart rate as an indicator of caloric needs and labor efficiency. Mr. Weyland Beeghly, graduate assistant in Agricultural Economics, Cornell University.

The influence of ammonium nitrogen on P uptake by corn. Dr. Cesar Mamaril, chairman, Department of Soils, UPCA.

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